

IMPLEMENTING THE UN GUIDING PRINCIPLES ON BUSINESS AND HUMAN RIGHTS:
THE CHALLENGE OF OPERATIONALISING UN GUIDING PRINCIPLE NO. 4 IN THE CON-
TEXT OF STATE EXPORT CREDIT AGENCIES USING THE EXAMPLE OF GERMANY

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Declaration

I certify that this thesis has been written by me and is my own work except where explicitly stated otherwise. I further declare that it has not been submitted for any other degree or professional qualification.

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Date: 27th August 2024 (re-submission 2 March 2026)

Abstract

This doctoral thesis explored how Export Credit Agencies (ECAs) and their clients can fulfil their responsibility to protect and respect human rights pursuant to the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011). Focusing on Guiding Principle 4, it contributes new and original knowledge to a definition of Human Rights Due Diligence (HRDD) in the ECA context, taking Germany as the research subject. A pragmatic research paradigm was adopted and a mixed methods approach to data generation employed, where a literature review and a case survey served as secondary sources of information, and qualitative interviews as sources of primary data.

Apart from the fact that there is a paucity of closely related literature on human rights in export finance, the literature review revealed several allegations *that* human rights are insufficiently considered in the ECA context. At the same time, concrete proposals were not provided on *how* human rights could be better addressed and *how* the UNGPs and especially HRDD could be implemented in the ECA context. This thesis sought to contribute to closing this gap in research.

A case survey followed the literature review, consisting of a meta-analysis of existing cases (Petersen, 2020, p. 67) which report on human rights violations in the context of ECA-related projects. The aim of the survey was to find out whether there are connections and patterns between, for example, a country and an industry sector and concrete human rights violations, and what the most salient risks to human rights in state export finance are.

The final step of data generation involved conducting exploratory research through 18 expert interviews. 20 interview partners were selected, representing a diverse range of ECA stakeholders across the German government, ECA employees and clients, research and science institutions, as well as NGOs. The focus of these interviews was to explore how business-related human rights impacts are addressed and how HRDD is defined and implemented. The interviews were analysed by drawing on Braun and Clarke's six-phase guide to reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2022) in order to identify and interpret common themes provided by the interviewees, as well as to comprehensively present the qualitative data generated. By involving representatives of all relevant ECA stakeholders as experts in the interviews, the research project was situated within new governance theory (Ruggie, 2014), and, more precisely, within polycentric governance (e.g., McCorquodale and Nolan, 2021, p. 469), as all ECA stakeholders were approached, and their respective opinions and experiences considered.

It can be concluded from this exploratory research presented that human rights are already addressed and elements of HRDD are already implemented in Germany's export promotion. At the same time, there is a fundamental lack of knowledge in relation to what human rights are in the ECA context, which is perceived as a complex setting for BHR, characterised for example by diverse players, competing interests, and the political embedding. This complexity also exists regarding to defining and explaining HRDD, which is understood in different ways by ECA stakeholders. Notably, the expert interviews showed a significant gap in awareness regarding the obligation for the German ECA to implement HRDD as a key management concept, including a complete understanding of the HRDD elements and process.

By analysing HRDD in the context of ECAs through the lens of polycentric governance, the thesis contributes to the business and human rights literature by showing how human rights responsibilities and due diligence processes are shaped in practice within a state-supported, multi-actor governance setting. Based on the research taken, a framework for HRDD in the ECA context was developed, comprising of the six elements Human Rights Policy Statement, Risk Identification and Assessment, Remedial Action and Effectiveness Control, Reporting and Transparency, Grievance Mechanism, and Stakeholder Engagement. The proposed framework reflects the specific responsibilities and practical conditions of ECAs and adapts

HRDD to the realities of state-supported export finance. It could be the subject of a Focus Group Discussion (Krueger and Casey, 2009) which is, among other aspects deemed relevant, recommended for future research on implementing HRDD in the ECA context upon closing this thesis.

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Abbreviations

BHR	Business and Human Rights
BHRRRC	Business and Human Rights Resource Centre
BMWK	Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Action
Common Approaches	Recommendations of the Council on Common Approaches for Officially Supported Export Credits and Environmental and Social Due Diligence
CorA	Network for Corporate Accountability
CSOs	Civil Society Organisations
ECAs	Export Credit Agencies
EPs	Equator Principles
ESHR	Environmental, Social, and Human Rights
ESIA	Environmental and Social Impact Assessment
Euler Hermes	Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft
FDI	Foreign Direct Investment
FPIC	Free, Prior and Informed Consent
GP	Guiding Principle
HRD	Human Rights Defender(s)
HRDD	Human Rights Due Diligence
HRIA	Human Rights Impact Assessment
IBHR	International Bill of Human Rights
IFC	International Finance Corporation
IFC PS	IFC Performance Standards
IHRB	Institute for Human Rights and Business
ILO	International Labour Organization
IMC	Interministerial Committee

INEF	Institut für Entwicklung und Frieden / Institute for Development and Peace
NAP	National Action Plan
NCP	National Contact Point
NPG	New Public Governance
NPM	New Public Management
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OECD MNE-Guidelines	OECD Guidelines for Multinational Enterprises on Responsible Business Conduct
OHCHR	Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights
OHS	Occupational Health and Safety
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SOEs	State-owned enterprises
Supply Chain Act	Act on Corporate Due Diligence Obligations in Supply Chains
TPA	Traditional Public Administration
UN Forum	UN Forum on Business and Human Rights
UNGPs	UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights
UN Working Group	UN Working Group on Business and Human Rights
World Bank ESS	World Bank Environmental and Social Standards
World Bank EHS Guidelines	Environmental, Health, and Safety Guidelines

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

This doctoral research explores how the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs) can be operationalised in the context of Export Credit Agencies (ECAs), especially with regard to Human Rights Due Diligence (HRDD). To date, existing studies on ‘human rights and foreign trade promotion’ or even more concretely, on human rights in state export promotion, have been conducted from an external perspective. This doctoral thesis is informed by the authors’ year-long work experience at the German ECA, especially as a Sustainability Adviser responsible for the environmental and social due diligence of foreign projects, including human rights aspects. This experience brings an internal view to the current research undertaking.

Moreover, as the researcher was responsible for the topic of human rights, the relevance and necessity for this research project arose out of her work at that time, when she realised that certain questions regarding the operationalisation of the UNGPs in general and HRDD in specific existed, but that she could not answer them within the framework of her everyday work. The researcher’s previous engagement with the former German Development Service as well as CSR-advisory activities focusing on social standards especially in the textile value and supply chain complete this picture. From both her professional and her personal point of view, two topics are particularly relevant to the researcher: foreign trade promotion and, above all, export promotion, and the protection of those whose rights could potentially be negatively affected by projects associated with ECAs.

This chapter opens with a comprehensive overview of the research background that shaped the aims, questions, and basic assumptions of this doctoral dissertation. Firstly, the topic of human rights in connection with ECAs as public agencies is presented. It is shown that human rights violations repeatedly occur in projects associated with ECAs, even though ECAs have agreed at international level to address human rights in their activities and also reference the UNGPs there. As is briefly mentioned, the UNGPs explicitly refer to the ECA context and call for HRDD of these agencies, among others.

At the same time, however, the following section already indicates that there is no concrete guidance on how exactly the UNGPs should be implemented in the ECA context and what HRDD means in this regard. This fact is addressed by the overarching research question, which is explained after the research subject and geography have been introduced. Subsequently, this chapter addresses the methodological and theoretical frameworks that are adopted and turn to the study’s contribution to knowledge. After providing an outline of the

structure of this thesis including the underlying research questions, this chapter closes with a short conclusion.

1.2 Human Rights and Export Credit Agencies

Projects backed by ECAs are often associated with human rights abuses (Human Rights Council, 2018, pp. 9–10). As “official or quasi-official branches of their governments” (Klasen, 2015, p. 21), ECAs are public agencies that provide government-backed loans or credit guarantees or insurance respectively (McCorquodale, 2024, p. 57). Most of the current 38 member countries within the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) have established an ECA (see list of current ECAs, OECD, 2023c). They support the export of goods and services from producers in their own countries (Raza, Schlögl and Pfaffenbichler, 2023, p. 1; Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date t). Such undertakings range across a wide array of industry sectors (Raza, Schlögl and Pfaffenbichler, 2023, p. 20). ECAs represent the largest source of government financing for private sector industries worldwide (Klasen, 2015, p. 22).

According to an independent UN expert, “numerous reports have documented human rights violations arising from or associated with projects supported by export credit agencies” (United Nations, 2011, p. 2). Adverse human rights impacts mentioned in these reports are, for example, forced displacement of local populations, violation of the rights of indigenous peoples, workplace injuries, paramilitary and police repression, state-sponsored intimidation and censorship, the destruction of cultural sites, the denial of access to basic services, and environmental damage or contamination which can also constitute a severe human rights violation (see for example *ibid*; Keenan, 2008, p. 2). Those negative impacts are attributed to corporate activities of both business enterprises seeking state support as well as their business partners abroad.

In legal terms, according to a paper of the Danish Institute for Human Rights, “business enterprises do not violate human rights, but breach labour law, environmental law or criminal law provisions” (Lagoutte, 2014, p. 13). The reason for this is that in international law, only states are legal entities that can violate human rights (Weidmann, 2014, p. 48). It has therefore long been common sense that states are solely responsible for the respect for and observance of human rights and their protection. By now, however, there is almost uniform agreement that business have and should fulfil their own corporate responsibility to respect human rights when doing business at home or abroad (Ruggie, 2013, pp. 81–102).

The United Nations have developed a set of guidelines for States as well as companies to address negative impacts on human rights by business activities, the UNGPs (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011). Their unanimous adoption in 2011 set the

globally acknowledged standard, clarifying the different roles and responsibilities of both States and business when it comes to preventing and addressing negative impacts on human rights by business activities (UN Working Group on Business and Human Rights, n.d., p. 2). As the language and content of the UNGPs is quite complex, they need to be translated into practical actions at national levels (Methven O'Brien *et al.*, 2014, p. 13) by means of so-called National Action Plans (NAPs, *ibid.*, p. v).

Within the State duty to protect human rights, the UNGPs' first pillar, Guiding Principle (GP) 1 asserts that States have to protect human rights against abuse by third parties, including business, by implementing relevant policies, legislation and regulations (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 3). In this context, GP 4 identifies the State-business nexus as an important area where heightened due diligence is required (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 6–8). This nexus “includes situations in which a State owns or controls a company, or where it contracts or otherwise engages with companies to provide services that may have an impact on the enjoyment of human rights. Finally, it covers States' commercial transactions, notably procurement” (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2014, p. 19).

As service providers to business, ECAs fall under this setting where “governments have direct influence on corporate behaviour” (UN Working Group on Business and Human Rights, 2014, p. 23), and States take a role “as economic actors” (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2017). Against this background, GP 4 stipulates further State efforts to ensure their responsibility to protect human rights: “States should take additional steps to protect against human rights abuses by business enterprises that are owned or controlled by the State, or that receive substantial support and services from State agencies such as export credit agencies” (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 6). States are advised to “encourage and, where appropriate, require human rights due diligence by the agencies themselves and by those business enterprises or projects receiving their support” (*ibid.*).

In mentioning the HRDD of both ECAs and companies or projects supported, GP 4 refers to the second pillar of the UNGPs where this concept is described as “an ongoing management process” (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2014, p. 42) a company needs to undertake in order to meet its corporate responsibility to respect human rights. Yet no further specification is given as to how the UNGPs in general, the GP 4, or the aspects of HRDD respectively should be implemented in an ECA context.

Within the OECD, “the key multilateral negotiating forum where international disciplines for officially supported export credits are agreed, implemented, and monitored” (OECD, no date c), “a level playing field for exporters via a series of financial and good governance rules” has been established (*ibid.*). Minimum standards for the sustainable use of government-backed

export credits have been commonly agreed upon (Klasen, 2015, p. 22), for example the Recommendation of the Council on Common Approaches for Officially Supported Export Credits and Environmental and Social Due Diligence of the OECD (the “Common Approaches”, OECD, 2016), which define the procedural and assessment requirements for environmental, social, and human rights aspects (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 2).

Since 2016, the OECD or ECAs have recognised the UNGPs in the respective version of the Common Approaches which reference the UNGPs in the preamble (ibid., p. 2). Moreover, it is stated that social impacts “encompass relevant adverse project-related human rights impacts” (ibid., p. 5), that all applications covered by the Common Approaches are screened for severe project-related human rights risks (ibid., p. 7), that applications will be further assessed when the screening identifies a high likelihood of such risks (ibid.), and that the environmental and social project review may then be complemented with HRDD (ibid., p. 9). Nevertheless, criticism persists, particularly from civil society organisations (CSOs), regarding the inadequate consideration of human rights aspects by ECAs (Klasen, 2015, p. 22).

Against this background, this doctoral research seeks to elaborate how ECAs and their clients, namely exporting companies and export financing banks, can fulfil their responsibility to address human rights pursuant to the UNGPs, i.e., to contribute to a previously missing definition of HRDD in the ECA context.

1.3 Research Subject and Geography

Germany, with a particular focus on the German ECA, was chosen as the subject of investigation and research on the implementation of the UNGPs and specifically GP 4 for several reasons. Germany is one of the largest export economies worldwide (Statista, no date), and the German ECA has always been amongst the most active OECD ECAs with regard to the number of project assessments related to environmental, social, and human rights aspects (OECD, 2022b, p. 7). Between 2017-2019, Germany provided the largest number of respective project reports to the OECD (72), followed by Denmark (51) and the United Kingdom (28, ibid.). These three ECAs provided 43% of project reports by number in the same period (ibid.). Due to its embedding in the OECD, the results of this research will generally not be bound to the German level. Though certain adjustments might have to take place as ECAs vary in structure and business scope, a high degree of transferability of the results to other OECD ECAs is expected.

Moreover, the German government has devoted a separate section to foreign trade promotion in its NAP, including several measures that the German ECA has to implement in order to comply with the UNGPs (The Federal Government, 2017, pp. 16–18). In addition, the German

foreign trade promotion, of which export promotion is one part, is highlighted as one of the main areas to be monitored in the implementation phase of this plan (ibid., p. 28). Another fact which was not clear at the beginning of this research project but also serves as a reason for taking Germany as a research subject, is the German Act on Corporate Due Diligence in Supply Chains (Supply Chain Act, The Bundestag, 2021). This mandatory human rights and environmental due diligence legislation was enacted in June 2021 and went into force in 2023 for companies with more than 3,000 employees, and in 2024 for companies with 1,000 or more employees (ibid). Even though the Supply Chain Act does not mention foreign trade promotion, it applies directly to some of the companies applying for export credits. Thus, HRDD is an agenda topic for all stakeholders of the German ECA, although the origin is not necessarily export promotion.

Last but not least, the author's work as a sustainability advisor with the German ECA for some ten years as well as her research location as a PhD student and a research assistant at the HAW Hamburg justify Germany as a research subject due to the researcher's knowledge of the topic and the need from practice to deal with it intensively, as well as her existing contacts and proximity to some of the stakeholders that she included in her research.

1.4 Research Question and Aim

This dissertation project aims to research the operationalising of human rights in public export credit guarantee schemes, tackling the following overall research question:

- How are business-related human rights impacts addressed by state ECAs, particularly the German ECA, in order to comply with the UNGPs, especially regarding the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD?

New insights into the elements of HRDD will be gained as a practicable approach for especially ECAs but also their clients to comply with the UNGPs. In doing so, this undertaking provides further clarification of the first and second pillar of the UNGPs, aiming at elaborating concrete implementation options. At the same time, a deeper understanding of the difficulties that exist in implementing human rights in export finance will be generated. The wider setting to which this research belongs is therefore the field of human rights in export finance and, in a broad sense, to Business and Human Rights (BHR, European Commission, no date).

1.5 Basic Research Assumptions

Germany's commitment to complying with the Common Approaches (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018) and to implementing the UNGPs also in the context of foreign trade promotion, as reflected in its NAP, provides the framework for this research undertaking. The need to define HRDD in general is indicated in the German NAP, which advises companies

within a given sector to formulate specific common definitions of due diligence (The Federal Government, 2017, p. 19). As will be shown in the following chapters, the identification of risks to and negative impacts on human rights is paramount for the German ECA, and thus an important element of HRDD is already implemented, though weaknesses might persist in this regard. However, open questions remain, as the requirements for HRDD and its elements still need to be worked out and clearly defined for the ECA context. In contributing to answering these open questions by means of this doctoral study, the research focus will be the German ECA and the client relationships thereof, as well as on the human rights risks associated with the foreign projects linked to these relationships.

The federal government commissioned Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft (Euler Hermes) to manage the export promotion scheme (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date j). As a business enterprise itself, Euler Hermes has its own human rights responsibilities (Ruggie, 2010a, p. 5), i.e. under the second pillar of the UNGPs. Nevertheless, focusing on HRDD at the ECA level is considered a reasonable and relevant starting point by the author due to the fact that human rights issues may arise at the foreign project to which state-supported exports are delivered. Therefore, not all aspects of the corporate responsibility to respect human rights, though relevant, might be addressed by this study, which also applies to the role of the German ECA within the third pillar of the UNGPs (access to remedy). Consequently, this research seeks to contribute to the discussion on further protecting human rights in Germany's export promotion and that of other OECD member states. In doing so, the UNGPs are the approach and benchmark for this doctoral study, rather than any possible legislative interpretations of HRDD.

1.6 Methodology and Theoretical Orientation

A pragmatic research paradigm is adopted, employing a mixed methods approach to data generation from a literature review and a case survey as secondary sources of information, and from 18 qualitative interviews with 20 experts, with two interviews being conducted jointly, as sources of primary data. The latter are analysed by drawing on Braun and Clarke's six-phase guide to reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2022) in order to identify and interpret common themes provided by the interviewees, as well as to comprehensively present the qualitative data generated. By involving representatives of all relevant ECA stakeholders as experts in the interviews, the research project is situated within what the literature refers to as new governance theory (Ruggie, 2014), and, more precisely, within polycentric governance (e.g., McCorquodale and Nolan, 2021, p. 469). The different research methods will be used to develop a conceptual framework for HRDD in public export credit guarantee schemes, aiming at achieving stakeholder consensus when doing so, therefore in a polycentric approach.

1.7 Contribution to Knowledge

This study seeks to elaborate how ECAs and their clients can fulfil their responsibility to address human rights pursuant to the UNGPs, i.e., to contribute to a definition of HRDD in the ECA context. Although the UNGPs demand HRDD in this context, including from the ECAs themselves, and ECAs are repeatedly called upon to take greater account of human rights and implement HRDD, such a definition does not yet exist.

By researching the literature and existing case studies on human rights in state supported export finance as well as by exploratory research via expert interviews, this research project is offering an original contribution to knowledge: as the literature review demonstrates, there is not only little literature dealing with human rights in export finance, but above all there are virtually no academic sources, i.e. peer-reviewed work, in this regard. This study seeks to contribute to closing this research gap by asking the ‘question of how’ as its overall research question:

- How are business-related human rights impacts addressed by state ECAs, particularly the German ECA, in order to comply with the UNGPs, especially regarding the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD?

The findings of this research project show that human rights are already addressed in Germany’s export promotion. At the same time, there is a fundamental lack of knowledge in relation to what human rights are in the ECA context, which is perceived as a complex setting for BHR. This complexity also exists with regard to defining and explaining HRDD, which is understood in different ways by ECA stakeholders. Notably, the interviews show a significant gap in awareness regarding the obligation for the German ECA to implement HRDD as a key management concept, including a complete understanding of the HRDD elements and process. Based on the different research methods applied, however, a framework for HRDD is proposed in the final data chapter, comprising of the six elements Human Rights Policy Statement, Risk Identification and Assessment, Remedial Action and Effectiveness Control, Reporting and Transparency, Grievance Mechanism, and Stakeholder Engagement. This framework reflects the specific context of state-supported export finance and the responsibilities of ECAs in addressing business-related human rights risks and impacts.

This doctoral project is the first of its kind to address the research questions of how business-related human rights impacts are currently addressed and how HRDD may be further operationalised in the ECA context, with Germany taken as the research subject. Apart from this topic-related innovation, this research is characterised by its methodological and theoretical originality: Experts, including those who are typically hard to access, were interviewed on topics that are both politically and commercially sensitive. Additionally,

previously separate bodies of literature – specifically, human rights and legal literature and business-related export finance literature – were integrated to provide a more comprehensive perspective.

In addition, the thesis contributes a theoretically informed perspective by examining how HRDD and human rights responsibilities are shaped within a polycentric governance setting. This adds an empirical dimension to the governance discussion by showing how export promotion mandates, stakeholder diversity, and political considerations influence coordination in practice.

Therefore, this thesis does not only contribute to filling the above-mentioned knowledge gap identified in the literature review, but at the same time represents a new contribution to knowledge.

1.8 Thesis Structure

This thesis is organised into nine chapters, and the following outline provides a detailed structure. Several sub-questions to the overall research question are addressed in the different chapters and pointed out, of applicable.

Chapter 2 establishes a comprehensive understanding of the background to this dissertation, namely state export promotion, the UNGPs and, in particular, their relevance for ECAs. Moreover, it outlines how human rights aspects are considered especially in the German export credit scheme. This chapter therefore draws to the sub-research question:

- What do the UNGPs require of ECAs and of the business businesses involved in ECA-backed transactions?

In Chapter 3, the contribution literature can make regarding how the UNGPs, including the concept of HRDD, can and should be implemented in the ECA context according to its stakeholders, is explored. A short scoping review introduces the wider field of BHR, followed by a structured mapping of literature to ECAs. Even though only a few sources directly relate to the application of the UNGPs to ECAs, the literature review organises the relevant sources into the four categories that appear repeatedly: (1) challenges and difficulties regarding the consideration of human rights in the ECA context, (2) positive statements, (3) negative statements, and (4) relevant demands. After a critical assessment of the sources, a knowledge gap in research is identified. Moreover, Chapter 3 concludes with a summary of the findings, suggesting further research directions within the context of this doctoral thesis.

The research questions guiding the literature review are:

- What are the requirements of the UNGPs with regard to ECAs?

- How are human rights embedded in the ECA context?
- Which implementation mechanisms can be identified?
- How should human rights be embedded according to ECA stakeholders?
- What are the possibilities, difficulties, and limitations regarding the implementation of human rights in the ECA context, including HRDD?
- What is meant by HRDD in the context of state export credit guarantees?
- What are the expectations towards HRDD in the ECA context?

Chapter 4 illustrates the theoretical framework that guides this study. It discusses the underlying research theory, namely new governance theory, and more specifically, polycentric governance, and explains how the research concept relates to this theoretical perspective.

Chapter 5 then outlines the methodological framework adopted for answering the overall research question within the scope of this doctoral study, beginning with the underpinning pragmatic research philosophy which focuses on practical solutions and outcomes for the topic researched. The methods employed by combining both quantitative and qualitative research to gather and analyse data are examined and defended, before outlining potential limitations of the research conducted.

In Chapter 6, existing cases and reports on human rights impacts at projects related to ECA support are analysed in order to find out whether and how adverse human rights impacts are connected to a specific industry, a specific country or a specific project, and what the most salient human rights risks are in the ECA context. Based on the case survey findings, specific human rights issues related to internationally recognised human rights that can be negatively affected in the context of export financing are illustrated. The human rights aspects of resettlement and compensation seem to be the most relevant in ECA projects with the exception of the pulp and paper industry, equally to the aspect of (clean) water, health, and waste management, for example. The case survey therefore addresses three research questions, namely

- What evidence exists for both positive and negative impacts on human rights in projects connected to ECA support?
- Whether and how are adverse human rights impacts connected to a specific industry, a specific country, or a specific project?
- What are the most salient human rights risks in the ECA context?

Chapter 7 and 8 then present the thematic analysis of the expert interviews conducted, by addressing the following research questions:

- Whether and how are adverse human rights impacts connected to a specific industry, a specific country, or a specific project?

- What are the most salient human rights risks in the ECA context?
- How should human rights be implemented in the ECA context according to ECA stakeholders?
- What is the specific meaning of and what are expectations to HRDD in the ECA context?

Chapter 7 addresses the first part of the overall research question that relates to the general consideration of human rights in the ECA context. The data illustrates that human rights are already an established topic in export finance, especially by means of the benchmark standards against which, among other issues, human rights aspects of foreign projects are assessed. Yet there are several complexities and challenges inherent in the ECA context which should be considered in the endeavour of integrating human rights more effectively. On the one hand, a nuanced understanding of the meaning and scope of human rights seems to be lacking among ECA stakeholders. On the other hand, the complexity of the context in which the German ECA operates, characterised for example by diverse players, competing interests, and the political embedding, has so far been given too little consideration in the literature reviewed.

Chapter 8 then addresses the second part of the research question, by analysing the interview data in terms of what the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD are in the ECA context and especially at the level of the German ECA. The interviews show a significant gap in awareness regarding the obligation for the German ECA to implement HRDD as a key management concept, including a complete understanding of the HRDD elements and process. However, a framework for HRDD is proposed in this chapter and based on all findings generated in the course of this doctoral research, intended to contribute to the operationalisation of the UNGPs and GP 4 in particular.

Chapter 9 finally discusses the relevant results and conclusions drawn from the research, highlighting the significance of this study and its original contribution to knowledge, including insights into HRDD in a polycentric governance setting. In closing, this doctoral thesis offers recommendations for future research based on the research findings presented.

1.9 Conclusion

In summary, this chapter has presented a detailed overview of the research context that underpins the aims, questions, and foundational assumptions of this doctoral dissertation, namely on how the UNGPs can be operationalised in the context of ECAs and especially regarding HRDD. The overall research question addressed by this doctoral research is

- How are business-related human rights impacts addressed by state ECAs, particularly the German ECA, in order to comply with the UNGPs, especially regarding the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD?

By laying out the methodological and theoretical frameworks employed, demonstrating the basic research assumptions, and outlining the structure of this thesis including the underlying research questions, it has established the basis for understanding how this study approaches not only these research questions, but also how it originally contributes to the body of knowledge. Building on this, the next chapter provides a comprehensive understanding of the background to this dissertation, namely state export promotion, the UNGPs, and ECAs, with a particular focus on the German ECA as the research subject.

Chapter 2: State Export Promotion, the UNGPs, and the German ECA

2.1 Introduction

This chapter forms the background to this doctoral research project. It provides information on state export promotion and the UNGPs, with a particular focus on the role of ECAs. It outlines how human rights aspects are addressed by OECD ECAs and especially in the German export credit scheme. This chapter begins by introducing the instrument of official export credits, which can be granted by ECAs to exporters or export financing banks to support exports abroad. The UNGPs and their pillars are then briefly presented with a focus on foreign export promotion and HRDD as a legally non-binding human rights due diligence obligation.

In order to gain an understanding of ‘human rights’, the international human rights to which the UNGPs refer are compiled afterwards, and some possible human rights risks in the German ECA business are presented. Subsequently, human rights-related standards and guidelines relevant to the German ECA are illustrated. The business model of the German ECA, the research subject of this thesis, is then discussed, and it is indicated where foreign trade and specifically export promotion are addressed in the UNGPs. Moreover, it is pointed out that HRDD is mentioned in GP 4 but is only described in the second pillar of the UNGPs. This is followed by a detailed explanation of how environmental, social, and human rights aspects are considered by the German ECA, largely based on the Common Approaches, which are consequently referenced repeatedly throughout this doctoral thesis. A short summary concludes this chapter.

2.2 State Export Promotion

Official export credits and ECAs are part of state export finance (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date p) or export financing system (OECD, 2008, p. 1). In 34 of the 38 OECD countries, governments provide officially supported export credits through ECAs as a longstanding instrument employed to support domestic companies in their export activities (OECD, 2023c; Raza, Schlögl and Pfaffenbichler, 2023, p. v; OECD, no date h). Such support can take the form of ‘official financing support’, including direct credits to foreign buyers, refinancing, or interest-rate assistance (OECD, no date c). Alternatively, it can be so-called ‘pure cover support’, namely export credit insurance or guarantees offered to exporters or the export financing banks (OECD, 2008, p. 2; Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date l). The volume of pure cover is about four times greater than that of financing support at least among the largest EU ECAs (Raza, Schlögl and Pfaffenbichler, 2023, p. 9).

If an exporter insures their receivables arising from an export transaction to a foreign buyer, the form of export credit is called 'supplier credit cover' (OECD, 2008, p. 2; Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date r). Figure 1 illustrates this in graphic form.

Figure 1: Supplier credit cover

Source: Johanna Imiela

A 'buyer credit cover' enables a bank to insure their receivables arising from the financing of a single export transaction, i.e. when a bank lends to the foreign buyer or to the buyer's bank (OECD, 2008, p. 2; Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date d). Figure 2 illustrates this in graphic form.

Figure 2: Buyer credit cover

Source: Johanna Imiela

Unlike other possible ECA products, this doctoral project focuses on an exporter's single transaction with a single buyer and the associated export credit guarantees taken on by either the exporter or the export financing bank, and especially in a pure cover context. The widely used term 'ECA cover' also serves as a basis for this doctoral thesis, even though contemporary terms for insurances and guarantees provided by financial institutions are sometimes referred to as 'products' (Salcic, 2014, p. 11). Moreover, ECA cover includes both export credit guarantee or export credit insurance which do not appear to be clearly differentiated and achieve the same economic effect nevertheless (ibid., p. 7). For this reason, no further distinction is made here either.

2.3 The UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights

The UNGPs were developed by the former UN Special Representative on Business and Human Rights, John Ruggie, and unanimously adopted by the UN Human Rights Council in 2011 (UN Working Group on Business and Human Rights, n.d., p. 2). They comprise 31 Guiding Principles, each is accompanied by a commentary and divided into the following three pillars (Figure 3).

Figure 3: The pillars of the UNGPs

Source: Own presentation based on the UNGPs (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011)

State support and services, e.g. foreign export promotion, are explicitly mentioned in the first pillar (GP 2, GP 4, GP 7, GP 8, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011) and the necessity of HRDD is emphasised (ibid., GP 4). As part of its duty to protect, the state should oblige ECAs, supported companies or projects to carry out HRDD (ibid.). The second pillar, which is aimed at the human rights responsibility of companies, also comes into play, as

HRDD is discussed in more detail here (ibid., GP 17-21, pp. 17-24). Furthermore, the second pillar could be relevant in the case of the German ECA insofar as a private company in Germany, Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft (Euler Hermes), has been commissioned to implement export credit guarantee schemes (see 2.6.2 below), and the requirements of the second pillar therefore also apply to them. However, in order to enable a certain transferability of the results of this doctoral research to other ECAs, which may be governmental institutions, Euler Hermes' responsibility to respect human rights will not be discussed in detail below.

The UNGPs identify HRDD as a central management concept (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2014, p. 42) to identify, avoid or mitigate potential or actual negative impacts on human rights through business activities (GP 15, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 16). Companies should fulfil their responsibility to respect internationally recognised human rights (GP 12, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011) by implementing HRDD, among other things (GP 15, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011). The obligation arising from the UNGPs, which is so-called soft law (Macchi and Bernaz, 2021, p. 2), is not legally binding, in contrast to the recent development of mandatory human rights due diligence obligations from national laws, such as the German Supply Chain Act (The Bundestag, 2021) or the European Directive on corporate sustainability due diligence (*Directive (EU) 2024/1760 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 on corporate sustainability due diligence and amending Directive (EU) 2019/1937 and Regulation (EU) 2023/2859, 2024*).

The starting point for this doctoral thesis is the significance of HRDD as a legally non-binding human rights due diligence obligation, which states should demand in the context of their export promotion according to the UNGPs (GP 4, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 6–7). The focus is on potential or actual negative impacts on human rights, which are countered by HRDD; environmental human rights are not considered separately.

2.4 Human Rights in the UNGPs

The UNGPs refer to the human rights that must be protected, specifically highlighting the International Bill of Human Rights (IBHR) and the core conventions of the International Labour Organization (ILO).¹ The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) and two international treaties, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), form the IBHR (Office of the High Commissioner, no date c). The following Table 1 lists human rights under international human rights law and was compiled by the author, using the Guide to Human Rights Impact

¹ Since the adoption of the UNGPs, two health and safety-related conventions have become ILO core conventions (International Labour Organization, 2022).

Assessment (Abrahams and Wyss, 2010), UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) webpages including the UDHR and the relevant conventions (Office of the High Commissioner, no date c, no date b, no date a), as well as the ILO core conventions (International Labour Organization, 2022, 2024).

Table 1: List of human rights

1. Right to life UDHR 3, ICCPR 6	22. Right to freedom of assembly UDHR 20, ICCPR 21
2. Right to Liberty and Security UDHR 3+9, ICCPR 9	23. Right to freedom of association UDHR 20, ICCPR 22, ILO No. 87
3. Right not to be subjected to slavery, servitude or forced labour UDHR 4, ICCPR 8, ILO No. 105	24. Right to participate in public life UDHR 21, ICCPR 25
4. Right not to be subjected to torture, cruel, inhuman and/or degrading treatment or punishment UDHR 5, ICCPR 7	25. Right to social security, including social insurance UDHR 22, ICESCR 9
5. Right to recognition as a person before the law UDHR 6, ICCPR 16	26. Right to work UDHR 23, ICESCR 6
6. Right to equality before the law, equal protection of the law, non-discrimination UDHR 7, ICCPR 14+26	27. Right to enjoy just and favourable conditions of work UDHR 23+24, ICESCR 7, all ILO Core Conventions
7. Right to freedom from war propaganda, and freedom from incitement to racial, religious or national hatred UDHR 7, ICCPR 20	28. Right to form and join trade unions and the right to strike UDHR 23, ICESCR 8, ILO No. 98
8. Right to access to effective remedies UDHR 8, ICCPR 2+9 (compensation)	29. Right to an adequate standard of living UDHR 25, ICESCR 11
9. Right to a fair trial UDHR 10, ICCPR 14	30. Right to health UDHR 25, ICESCR 12
10. Right to be free from retroactive criminal law UDHR 11, ICCPR 15	31. Right to education UDHR 26, ICESCR 13+14
11. Right to privacy UDHR 12, ICCPR 17	32. Right to take part in cultural life, benefit from scientific progress, material and moral rights of authors and inventors UDHR 27, ICESCR 15

12. Right to freedom of movement and choice of residence UDHR 13, ICCPR 12	33. Right to self-determination UDHR 27, ICCPR 1, ICESCR 1
13. Right to seek asylum from persecution in other countries UDHR 14	34. Right of detained persons to humane treatment ICCPR 10
14. Right to have a nationality UDHR 15, ICCPR 24 (child)	35. Right not to be subjected to imprisonment for inability to fulfil a contract ICCPR 11
15. Right of protection for the child ICCPR 24, ICESCR 10, ILO No. 182	36. Right of aliens' due process when facing expulsion ICCPR 13
16. Right to marry and form a family UDHR 16, ICCPR 23, ICESCR 10	37. Rights of minorities ICCPR 27
17. Right to own property UDHR 17	38. Right to Family Life ICCPR 23, ICESCR 10
18. Right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion UDHR 18, ICCPR 18	39. Right to Water and Sanitation UDHR 25, ICESCR 11, UDHR 3, UDHR 23; A/RES/64/292
19. Right to non-discrimination UDHR 2, ICCPR 2+26, ICESCR 2, ILO No. 111	40. Right not to be subject to arbitrary arrest or detention UDHR 9, ICCPR 9
20. Rights of Indigenous Peoples UNDRIP, ICCPR 1+27, ICESCR 1	41. Right to a clean, healthy and sustainable environment A/HRC/RES/48/13
21. Right to freedom of opinion, information and expression UDHR 19, ICCPR 19	

Source: Johanna Imiela

2.5 Human Rights in the ECA Context

According to the commentary to GP 12, companies “can have an impact on virtually the entire spectrum of internationally recognized human rights” (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 13). Ruggie concludes that “any ex ante limited list of rights is bound to be misleading” (Ruggie, 2010c, p. 2). At the same time, he states that “some rights will be more relevant in some activities, sectors, or contexts” (ibid.). Likewise, “in order to identify any key human rights risks and impacts associated with the business activity” (Abrahams and

Wyss, 2010, p. 25), Abrahams and Wyss emphasise the importance of understanding the business activity “in context, in particular (...) (t)he industry sector and its particular human rights risks and challenges” (ibid.).

Aiming at generating a more concrete understanding of the term ‘human rights’ in an ECA context, some relevant sectors of German ECA projects (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022) have been looked at and combined with industry specific human rights examples as provided by Abrahams and Wyss (2010). As a result, the following Table 2 was compiled.

Table 2: Sector-specific human rights risks in the German ECA context

Industry Sector	Possible Critical Human Rights Issues	
Construction and Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Resettlement ▪ Emissions ▪ Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Overtime ▪ Migrant Workers ▪ Child Labour ▪ Workers’ Accommodation
Mining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Resettlement ▪ Land Use ▪ Drinking water/ Groundwater 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ OHS ▪ Public Health ▪ Conflict Minerals
Agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Pesticides ▪ Security Personnel ▪ Deforestation ▪ Resettlement ▪ Migrant Workers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Overtime ▪ Exhaust Emissions ▪ Child Labour ▪ Drinking water/ Groundwater
Food and Beverage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Pesticides ▪ OHS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Child Labour
Textile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Child Labour ▪ Trade Unions ▪ Supply Chain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ OHS ▪ Overtime
Oil and Gas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Effluents ▪ OHS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Resettlement ▪ Migrant Workers
Pulp and Paper	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Effluents ▪ Expropriation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Public Health
Pharmaceutical and Chemical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ OHS ▪ Information of trial participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Environment ▪ Water Management

Source: Johanna Imiela

2.6 Human Rights related Guidelines and Standards in the ECA Context

State export promotion must consider various guidelines and standards with regard to human rights aspects. Referring to the German ECA, these standards are illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Human rights related guidelines and standards

Source: Johanna Imiela

This overview shows the standards and guidelines relevant for the work of the German ECA with regard to human rights. All of these are explained in more detail below. Although the World Bank Group standard shown here are part of the Common Approaches, they have been separated out as an individual source for this illustration. Neither the German Supply Chain Act nor the European Directive on corporate sustainability due diligence explicitly relate to the financial sector and have therefore not been included in this chart.

2.7 German Export Cover

2.7.1 Operating Principles

Export credit guarantees are one instrument of Germany's foreign trade promotion (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate, no date b). Export credit guarantees protect exporters and banks financing the exports against economically or politically induced payment defaults (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date h). An example of an economic risk that can be covered is the insolvency of the foreign customer, while warlike events can be covered as a political risk (*FAQ - Fragen und Antworten. Exportkreditgarantien*, no date).

In return for payment of a premium, the German government assumes most of the risk from the exporter or the financing bank that the German exporter's trade receivables will not be paid (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date h). In contrast to other countries that grant state financing support such as direct loans to foreign buyers, the German government's support is pure cover support (FN 29, Scheper and Feldt, 2010a, p. 68).

In principle, all export transactions of German companies can be covered, regardless of the size and sector of the business or company (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date h). The export transactions to be covered can have short or long-term payment terms, be based on a one-off delivery, involve complex financing from several banks and relate to both the phase before and after shipment of the goods (*FAQ - Fragen und Antworten. Exportkreditgarantien*, no date). The product range of export credit guarantees is correspondingly broad. As mentioned before, the focus of this doctoral thesis is on an exporter's single transaction with a single buyer and the associated export credit guarantees taken on by either the exporter or the export financing bank, i.e. on supplier credit cover and buyer credit cover.

Export credit guarantees are only used when there is no private insurance supply according to the subsidiarity principle (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, 2022, p. 15). Accordingly, transactions are mainly covered in emerging and developing countries (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date h) whose share amounted to 87% in 2023 (Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz, 2024, p. 19). In the last five years, short-term transactions, i.e. loan terms of up to one year, have accounted for the majority of new business (*ibid.*, p. 18). In 2023, however, long-term business predominated at just under 64% (*ibid.*).

2.7.2 Mandatary of the Federal Government

Euler Hermes was commissioned to handle state export credit guarantees by the government of the newly founded Federal Republic of Germany in 1949. Therefore, the German export credit guarantees are known as “Hermes Cover” (Altmann, 2018). As a subsidiary of the Allianz Group with headquarters in Paris, the German ECA, Euler Hermes, is a private-sector company (Euler Hermes, 2018).

2.7.3 Procedure for Granting a Guarantee

The applications for export credit guarantees reviewed and prepared by Euler Hermes are decided upon by a respective Interministerial Committee (IMC), in which the leading Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK), the Federal Ministry of Finance, the Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development, and the Federal Foreign Office are represented (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2019, p. 80; Bundesministerium der Finanzen, no date). In addition to the mandatary, specially appointed experts from industry, trade and banks also advise on the consensual decisions of the IMC (*ibid.*; Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate, no date a).

Within the framework of the so-called mandatary authorisation (Bundesministerium der Finanzen, no date), Euler Hermes may decide on applications for export credit guarantees up to EUR 5 million themselves (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2020, p. 12), i.e. without the

involvement of the IMC, which, however, always decides on fundamental issues and large export transactions (Bundesministerium der Finanzen, no date). These large transactions have a volume of more than EUR 10 million; the Small Interministerial Committee, whose composition is not publicly known, decides on the coverage of transactions between EUR 5 million and EUR 10 million (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2020, p. 12).

The prerequisite for an export credit guarantee is that the transaction for which cover is considered is ‘worthy of support’ and with an ‘acceptable risk level’ (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, no date a). This implies that the goods and services to be exported help secure and create jobs in Germany and open up new sales markets, making the export transaction eligible for cover (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date t, p. 5). Moreover, when the loss-free progress of the export transaction applied for cover is realistic, the risk is justifiable (ibid.).

Examples of important criteria for risk-related justifiability in the context of the application assessment by Euler Hermes are the creditworthiness check of the foreign customer and the country risk, in which financial aspects and the economic development of a country are considered (FAQ - Fragen und Antworten. Exportkreditgarantien, no date). Environmental, social and human rights standards are also central aspects of the application assessment (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date o). Under the eligibility criteria, “environmental impacts in the buyer country, social and development criteria” are mentioned, but not human rights (FAQ - Fragen und Antworten. Exportkreditgarantien, no date).

2.8 State Export Promotion in the UNGPs

Some of the GPs address state foreign trade or concretely state export promotion. Table 3 shows these, and the content related to the export credits, highlighted in bold.

Table 3: State foreign trade promotion in the UNGPs

GP	Content
2	Call for State expectations that businesses respect human rights abroad, especially where the State itself is involved in or supports those businesses (foreign trade promotion)
4 State-Business Nexus	States should take additional steps to protect against human rights abuses by business enterprises that (...) receive substantial support and services from State agencies such as ECAs (...) including, where appropriate, by requiring HRDD

GP	Content
	<i>Commentary: State should encourage, and, where appropriate, require HRDD by the agencies themselves and by those business enterprises or projects receiving their support</i>
7 Supporting Business Respect for Human Rights in Conflict- Affected Areas	Denial of access to public support and services for a business enterprise that is involved with gross human rights abuses and refuses to cooperate in addressing the situation (foreign trade promotion) <i>Commentary: States should attach appropriate consequences to any failure by enterprises to cooperate in these contexts, including by denying or withdrawing existing public support or services, or where that is not possible, denying their future provision</i>
8 Ensuring Policy Coherence	States should ensure that governmental departments, agencies and other State-based institutions that shape business practices are aware of and observe the State's human rights obligations (...) including ECAs

Source: Johanna Imiela based on the UNGPs (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011)

HRDD is only addressed by GP 4 within the first pillar of the UNGPs, the State duty to protect human rights. The nexus between the State and business is seen as an important area for increased due diligence: By engaging in foreign trade promotion, for example, the State becomes an economic actor and, in this context, should ensure the protection of and respect for human rights by encouraging or requiring ECAs and their clients or projects to HRDD.

GP 4 refers to the second pillar of the UNGPs by pointing to the HRDD obligations of ECAs and the supported companies or projects. It is only within the second pillar that HRDD is described as an ongoing management process that a company must implement in order to fulfil its corporate responsibility to respect human rights (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, 2012, p. 6). According to GP 17-21, HRDD consists of the following four elements:

- (1) Identifying risks to and adverse impacts on human rights;
- (2) Establishing measures to minimise or prevent adverse human rights impacts;
- (3) Monitoring the effectiveness of these measures; and
- (4) Reporting on how human rights impacts are addressed (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 17–24).

2.9 Environmental, Social and Human Rights Aspects in Germany's Export Promotion

The mandatory Euler Hermes carries out an assessment of environmental, social, and human rights (ESHR) issues in addition to the assessment of the economic representativeness of the projects, as mentioned above (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date a). Neither the German export nor the German company are the subject of this assessment, but rather the project abroad to which a German exporter delivers (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 2).

2.9.1 Assessment Guidelines: The Common Approaches

The 2016 version of the Common Approaches is relevant for the assessment of the ESHR aspects of projects in the country of the buyer, i.e. the foreign customer of the German exporter (OECD, 2016). The OECD member countries agreed on this common set of rules for the assessment of then purely environmental aspects of officially supported export credit guarantees in 2004 (OECD, no date a). Since then, the Common Approaches have been revised and further developed several times. They now also include social and, subsumed under this, human rights aspects (OECD, 2016, p. 5). As the author's analysis has shown that the 2024 Common Approaches only include an adjustment to the assessment standards (see below), the 2016 version is used for this dissertation unless otherwise stated.

The Common Approaches rely on voluntary compliance and the application of peer pressure and are therefore a "Gentlemen's Agreement" (Raza, Schlögl and Pfaffenbichler, 2023, p. 24). They apply to exports with a credit period of at least two years (OECD, 2016, p. 5). Military and agricultural goods are excluded (ibid.). In addition, the Common Approaches provide for a site-related assessment of projects, meaning that mobile goods such as aircraft and ships do not fall within their scope of application (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 3).

The Common Approaches take a risk-based approach to the assessment. This means that the focus is on possible impacts on environmental and social aspects from the construction or operation of the projects (OECD, 2016, pp. 4–5), and the scope of the assessment depends on these ESHR risks (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2019, p. 6). The Common Approaches include "relevant adverse project-related human rights impacts" under social aspects (OECD, 2016, p. 5), so the project context is emphasised. No reference is made to the above-mentioned internationally recognised frameworks such as the UDHR, the IBHR or the ILO core labour conventions. However, the obligations of member states to protect human rights and the responsibility of companies to respect them are mentioned with a reference to the UNGPs in the preamble (ibid., p. 2).

2.9.2 Assessment Procedure

The ESHR assessment, which is carried out by the employees of the German ECA, consists of the screening, categorisation and actual ESHR review (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018). In the first step, known as screening, a check is carried out in accordance with the Common Approaches to determine whether a project to which a German exporter delivers needs to be classified into a project category followed by an ESHR review (ibid., p. 5). The screening is therefore a kind of preliminary check to determine whether a project falls within the scope of the Common Approaches: Categorisation should take place for all projects in or near sensitive areas (OECD, 2016, p. 7) or whenever the export value to be secured is at least 10 million special drawing rights (ibid.). The German ECA has currently translated this with EUR 15 million (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 2).

The Common Approaches provide for three project categories: Category A for projects with potentially significant adverse impacts on ESHR aspects that are "diverse, irreversible and/or unprecedented" (ibid., p. 6). Annex I of the Common Approaches lists examples of such projects, including crude oil refineries, the construction of airports, motorways and large dams as well as the large-scale development of oil, gas or liquefied natural gas (OECD, 2016, pp. 16–18). Projects that involve the "resettlement of a significant number of affected people" (ibid., p. 18) or that may result in "significant adverse social impacts to local communities or other project affected parties" (ibid.) are categorised as A projects with explicit human rights relevance. However, neither the Common Approaches nor Euler Hermes specify 'significant numbers' or 'significant adverse social impacts'. Projects in sensitive areas are always categorised as category A.

Category B projects have a lower potential impact on ESHR aspects than category A projects (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 7). The impacts are locally limited or more easily reversible or cause less impact beyond the project location (ibid.). Euler Hermes cites wind turbines and plants for the production of medium-density fibreboard as examples (ibid.). Category C projects have no or only minimal ESHR impact (ibid.). In addition to the Common Approaches, Euler Hermes also assigns category E for exports to existing facilities that "do not result in a significant change in performance or function and thus no change in the impact on ESHR aspects of the operation" (ibid., p. 3).

The Common Approaches do not provide any examples for category B and C projects. Consequently, all projects that cannot be classified as category C or E and are not listed as category A projects in Annex I of the Common Approaches should generally be categorised as B projects. The depth of the subsequent ESHR review corresponds to the previously defined category (ibid., p. 5). Category B projects are therefore not checked as thoroughly as category

A projects (*FAQ - Fragen und Antworten. Exportkreditgarantien*, no date). Category C projects do not have to be checked any further (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 7).

The Environmental and Social Review of the Common Approaches (OECD, 2016, pp. 8–11) corresponds to the actual (German) ESHR review (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018). This means that all category A, B and E projects with a German contract value of at least EUR 15 million are initially intended for this. In addition, according to the Common Approaches, projects with deliveries worth less than EUR 15 million but with a credit period of at least two years should also be reviewed if the screening has revealed "a high likelihood of serious project-related human rights impacts" (OECD, 2016, p. 7). These impacts are defined as those that are "particularly grave in nature (e.g. threats to life, child/forced labour and human trafficking), widespread in scope (e.g. large-scale resettlement and working conditions across a sector), cannot be remediated (e.g. torture, loss of health and destruction of indigenous peoples' lands) or are related to the project's operating context (e.g. conflict and post-conflict situations)" (ibid., FN 2, p. 9).

For transactions with a credit period of less than two years and a contract value of more than EUR 15 million, a risk assessment is carried out with regard to ESHR aspects if the projects were classified in category A on long-term payment terms, the transactions relate to a high-risk sector or the German delivery amounts to more than EUR 50 million (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 10). This is the German ECA's so-called "watchful-eye approach" (ibid.). On its website, however, Euler Hermes states that they go beyond the requirements of the Common Approaches if there are indications of serious ESHR risks (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date a). Regardless of the credit period and order value, projects are then subject to a risk assessment (ibid.).

It remains unclear though how such indications are determined or recognised and what exactly is part of the risk assessment. According to Euler Hermes, this focusses on the material risks and there is no complete comparison with international standards (ibid.). For category E projects, only a cursory review of ESHR risks is carried out, which also does not include a comparison with international standards (Fitschen and Osoba, 2018, p. 10). In accordance with the Common Approaches, these international standards are part of the full assessment for category A and B projects and are illustrated in the following.

2.9.3 Assessment Standards

In principle, a project must comply with the national legislation of the buyer's country (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 4). Information on local authorisations such as operating or environmental permits is considered proof (ibid.). In addition, a comparison is made with the standards of the World Bank Group, i.e. with the World Bank Safeguard Operational Policies

(World Bank Safeguard Policies) or the International Finance Corporation's (IFC) Performance Standards (IFC Performance Standards, *ibid.*). As stated in the Common Approaches, project finance and transactions structured in a similar way to project finance are always reviewed in accordance with the IFC Performance Standards (*ibid.*, p. 6; OECD, 2016, p. 10).

In the amended 2024 Common Approaches though, the World Bank Safeguard Policies are no longer mentioned at all, but the succeeding ten World Bank Environmental and Social Standards (World Bank ESS) for projects involving sovereign obligators (OECD, 2024b, p. 10). However, as the World Bank Safeguard Policies were applied by the German ECA during the period in which this doctoral research took place, they are still considered here. The technical sector guidelines of the World Bank Group, the Environmental, Health, and Safety Guidelines (World Bank EHS Guidelines), must also always be consulted (OECD, 2016, p. 10; Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 5), also according to the 2024 Common Approaches (OECD, 2024b, p. 10).

The Common Approaches consider that some of the international standards "contain margins of tolerance in how their overall objectives may be achieved " (OECD, 2016, p. 11). In addition, the Common Approaches allow for exceptional cases in which a project does not fulfil the relevant aspects of the international standards. However, these cases must be justified at OECD level with regard to the choice of standard, the reasons for non-compliance, why the project is nevertheless supported and which monitoring measures are associated with this (*ibid.*).

The World Bank Safeguard Policies were generally used for export credit guarantees, except for project finance (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 5). In the 2019 annual report on export credit guarantees, the new World Bank ESS were mentioned, therefore replacing the former World Bank Safeguard Policies (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2019, p. 34). The World Bank ESS were published in 2018 and are expected to exist alongside the World Bank Safeguard Policies at World Bank level until 2025 (The World Bank, 2017). In the information on covered transactions published on the ECA's website, the World Bank Safeguard Policies are still mentioned as a benchmark standard used (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date s).

The following overview (Table 4) compares the three standards of the World Bank Group that are used as reference standards for the assessment of ESHR risks. For ease of reading, individual standards with overlapping titles have been listed next to each other in one row of the table. The extent to which certain topics can be found in the detailed content of the standards and thus overlap was not checked. In addition, the World Bank EHS Guidelines are not considered further in this report, as they contain sector-specific requirements on

occupational health and safety, but no further references to social or human rights issues (International Finance Corporation, no date).

Table 4: Comparison of benchmark standards

World Bank Safeguard Policies	World Bank ESS	IFC Performance Standards
Environmental Assessment	Assessment and Management of Environmental and Social Risks and Impacts (ESS 1)	Assessment and Management of Environmental and Social Risks and Impacts (Performance Standard 1)
Natural Habitats	-	-
Pest Management	-	-
Forests	-	-
-	Resource Efficiency and Pollution Prevention and Management (ESS 3)	Resource Efficiency and Pollution Prevention (Performance Standard 3)
-	Biodiversity Conservation and Sustainable Management of Living Natural Resources (ESS 6)	Biodiversity Conservation and Sustainable Management of Living Natural Resources (Performance Standard 6)
Indigenous Peoples	Indigenous Peoples/Sub-Saharan African Historically Underserved Traditional Local Communities (ESS 7)	Indigenous Peoples (Performance Standard 7)
Physical Cultural Resources	Cultural Heritage (ESS 8)	Cultural Heritage (Performance Standard 8)
Involuntary Resettlement	Land Acquisition, Restrictions on Land Use and Involuntary Resettlement (ESS 5)	Land Acquisition and Involuntary Resettlement (Performance Standard 5)
-	Labor and Working Conditions (ESS 2)	Labor and Working Conditions (Performance Standard 2)
-	Community Health and Safety (ESS 4)	Community Health, Safety, and Security (Performance Standard 4)
Safety of Dams	-	-
Projects in Disputed Areas	-	-
Projects on International Waterways	-	-
	Financial Intermediaries (ESS 9)	
	Stakeholder Engagement and Information Disclosure (ESS 10)	-

Source: Author's own compilation, based on (International Finance Corporation, 2012; The World Bank, 2017; World Bank Group, no date)

Even though the World Bank's ESS seem more comprehensive than the World Bank Safeguard Policies regarding human rights aspects, human rights are explicitly mentioned only in ESS 7 (Indigenous Peoples) within the World Bank's environmental and social framework,

aside from the 'vision for sustainable development' (World Bank Group, no date, pp. 1–2, 75). The IFC Performance Standards, on the other hand, emphasise human rights more frequently. For example, Performance Standard 1 (Assessment and Management of Environmental and Social Risks and Impacts) states that each of the Performance Standards contains elements that relate to human rights dimensions (Performance Standard 1, International Finance Corporation, 2012, p. 1). Assessment against the Performance Standards enables to consider "many relevant human rights issues" (ibid.) in a project. In addition, Performance Standard 1 mentions HRDD in a footnote which states that in "limited high risk circumstances, it may be appropriate for the client to complement its environmental and social risks and impacts identification process with specific human rights due diligence" (ibid., FN 12, p. 3).

However, there is no further explanation of what these 'limited high-risk cases' are and what 'specific HRDD' means. In addition, the objective of Performance Standard 4 (Community Health, Safety, and Security) is the protection of personnel and property "in accordance with relevant human rights principles" (Performance Standard 4, International Finance Corporation, 2012, p. 1). Finally, the objective of Performance Standard 7 emphasises "full respect for the human rights (...) of Indigenous Peoples" (Performance Standard 7, International Finance Corporation, 2012, p. 1).

A precise analysis of the three benchmark standards and any advantages and disadvantages of their individual or parallel use for the purposes of the ESHR review is beyond the scope of this doctoral thesis. In 2023, Euler Hermes carried out such a review for 60 of the 5,767 new applications, 37 of which were analysed in depth according to category A and B (Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz, 2024, pp. 17, 24).

2.9.4 Information to Be Included

Information provided by the applicant is utilised for the ESHR assessment. Examples of this are predefined questionnaires (a general and sector-specific ones) that were developed by Euler Hermes based on the benchmark standards (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 6, see questionnaires available under no date a). An Environmental and Social Impact Assessment (ESIA) is required for category A projects in accordance with the Common Approaches (OECD, 2016, p. 9) and should be prepared by an independent expert if possible (*FAQ - Fragen und Antworten. Exportkreditgarantien*, no date).

Moreover, the respective ESIA will be published on the ECA's website 30 days prior to the final commitment as required by the Common Approaches (OECD, 2016, p. 12; Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 8). This relates to enabling "a critical public" (Scheper and Feldt, 2010a, p. 47) to gain information about planned projects (ibid.). The typical contents of an ESIA are listed in Annex II of the Common Approaches (OECD, 2016, pp. 19–20). In addition, Euler

Hermes' employees use a provider of ESG risk data, RepRisk, a biodiversity assessment tool, IBAT, as well as NGO and press reports (Fitschen and Osoba, 2018, p. 10). Where necessary, site visits to inspect projects are carried out by Euler Hermes, the German embassy of the country in question is involved, or external consultants are utilised (ibid.).

According to the Common Approaches, statements or reports of the OECD National Contact Point² (NCP) in the ECA country must be considered (OECD, 2016, p. 9), which are published at the end of a complaint procedure within the application of the OECD MNE-Guidelines (ibid.). The German ECA goes beyond this requirement as "complaints already received by the NCP as well as certain incidents and problems related to these" (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date g) are considered in the ESHR review.

2.9.5 Decision and Monitoring

As shown in the previous sections, the German ECA focuses on identifying risks to and negative impacts on human rights when assessing foreign projects to which German exporters aim to deliver. An important element of HRDD, namely the first one (identifying risks to and adverse impacts on human rights), is therefore implemented in export credit guarantees as part of the ESHR review. The results of this review are included in a recommendation for a decision for the IMC (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 5). In accordance with the Common Approaches, the positive IMC decision can be linked to ESHR conditions that must be fulfilled before or after the final cover note (ibid; OECD, 2016, p. 11). For example, "complex category A projects with corresponding ESHR risks or impacts" normally require monitoring after a transaction has been covered (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 7). According to the Common Approaches, all project financing category A projects are subject to monitoring during the term of the loan (OECD, 2016, p. 11), whereas monitoring is not provided for other cases.

Monitoring can be passive, i.e. Euler Hermes is informed by the cover holder in the event of deviations from the ESHR standards, or active, i.e. Euler Hermes receives monitoring reports from the cover holder on the status of the agreed implementation targets, analyses these and coordinates any necessary measures with the cover holder (Fitschen and Osoba, 2018, p. 14). In the event of non-compliance with ESHR conditions, the Common Approaches do not provide for the guarantee agreement to be cancelled: ECAs should then "take actions that they deem appropriate in order to restore compliance, in accordance with the terms of the contract for official support" (OECD, 2016, p. 12). It is important to point out that any conditions to mitigate

² Set up by governments adhering to the OECD Guidelines for Multinational Enterprises on Responsible Business Conduct (OECD MNE-Guidelines, OECD, 2023a).

environmental or social harms are only applicable for the duration of the guarantee contract (Raza, Schlögl and Pfaffenbichler, 2023, p. 7).

2.9.6 Disclosure of Information

Apart from the publication of ESIAAs as mentioned above, the German ECA publicly discloses information on category A and B projects in line with the Common Approaches (OECD, 2016, pp. 12–13; Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date s). These projects are also reported to the OECD (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 10) where they are made available in an aggregated form (Raza, Schlögl and Pfaffenbichler, 2023, p. 9; OECD, no date b).

2.9.7 Summary: ESHR Assessment

The following illustration (Figure 5) is a simplified representation of the ESHR assessment described in the previous sections before concluding this chapter.

Figure 5: ESHR review

Source: Johanna Imiela

2.10 Conclusion

This chapter has established a comprehensive understanding of the background to this dissertation. Starting with state export promotion, the forms of ECA support and export credits were explained, highlighting the focus of this doctoral thesis on an exporter’s individual transaction with a single buyer and the associated export credit guarantees that are provided either to the exporter or the export financing bank and especially in a pure cover context.

Other key foundations were systematically developed in a logical sequence. First, the UNGPs and their pillars were described. Afterwards, the human rights mentioned in the UNGPs were compiled in a list and subsequently brought into the context of the German ECA by highlighting industry specific human rights risks. Being the research subject of this doctoral dissertation, the German ECA was then drawn to in detail by illustrating the human rights related standards and guidelines and, above all, by explaining the Common Approaches. These rules serve as the basis for evaluating environmental, social and human rights aspects, as agreed upon at the OECD level, guiding the content and direction of the respective assessments conducted by the German ECA. The assessment process undertaken by the German ECA was thoroughly analysed and presented afterwards.

Building on this foundation, the following literature review (Chapter 3) examines what contribution the literature makes to understanding how the UNGPs, including the concept of HRDD, are addressed in relation to ECAs. In doing so, this work is set in relation to previous findings in order to identify a possible gap that this research project aims to bridge.

Chapter 3: Critical Review of Literature on the Integration of Human Rights in the Context of State ECAs

3.1 Scoping Review: BHR and State-Supported Economic Activity

Over the past two decades, BHR has developed as a distinct area of academic and policy discussion, particularly in connection with the UNGPs (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011). The UNGPs provide the normative reference point for debates on State duties, corporate responsibility, and HRDD in the business context. Against this background, the following scoping review situates the present study within the broader BHR field and clarifies the relevance of debates on State-supported economic activity for ECAs. The conceptual foundations, structure, and evolution of the UNGPs, including their relationship to the Ruggie Framework and to other relevant governance instruments relevant to State-supported export activity are discussed in detail in Chapter 2 and are therefore not repeated here.

Within the broader BHR field, particular attention has been paid to situations in which States are not only regulators of business conduct but are also involved in economic activity through ownership, control, or the provision of support to business enterprises. Such situations raise specific questions about how State duties to protect human rights operate where public authority is exercised through market-based instruments or State-mandated economic activity. These questions are explicitly reflected in GP 4, which addresses situations in which States provide substantial support to business enterprises, including through institutions such as ECAs, and highlights the relevance of HRDD in this context (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 6–7). While the UNGPs thus clearly identify ECAs as relevant actors under Pillar I, the question of how the expectations articulated in GP 4 translate into concrete practices in the ECA context remains a key issue addressed in this doctoral study.

Scholarly work on the role of the State in markets provides an important conceptual backdrop for understanding GP 4. Backer (2023) emphasises that when States move beyond their traditional role as political and public authorities and participate in economic activity, they “never shed their paramount character as public bodies” (p. 36) but continue to bear responsibilities under the State duty to protect human rights (*ibid.*, pp. 36-37). These additional duties arise at the conceptual intersection where the State duty to protect human rights meets

the corporate responsibility to respect human rights (*ibid.*, p. 37). While Backer's earlier work also focuses primarily on State-owned enterprises (SOEs) and their dual positioning under Pillars I and II of the UNGPs, this analysis presupposes ownership or control by the State and is therefore not directly applicable to ECAs, which do not operate as State-owned or State-controlled enterprises (Backer, 2017, pp. 844–848).

Nevertheless, Backer explicitly situates the State duty with respect to State economic activity within GP 4, noting that the provision applies not only to State-owned or State-controlled enterprises but also to business enterprises that receive substantial support and services from State agencies such as ECAs (Backer, 2017, pp. 859-860,884, 2023, p. 240, FN 116). This distinction underscores that ECAs fall within the scope of GP 4 without being assimilated to the category of SOEs. Backer further notes that while the obligations articulated in GP 4 are discretionary rather than mandatory (Backer, 2023, p. 37), they nonetheless suggest that States should at least encourage, and in appropriate circumstances require, HRDD (*ibid.*, p. 38).

In parallel, case-based research has documented human rights risks associated with internationally supported economic activities, including large-scale infrastructure and energy projects. Such studies illustrate recurring patterns of adverse impacts linked to land-related conflicts, deficiencies in consultation processes, and impacts on Indigenous and local communities. Ramirez's analysis of a wind energy project, for example, documents how conflicts arose in relation to communal land use, consultation practices, and Indigenous rights in a transnational project involving foreign corporate actors (Ramirez and Vester, 2013, pp. 5–7). The case further highlights governance gaps and the limited role assumed by the State in addressing these conflicts (*ibid.*, p. 9). Although this body of work does not focus on ECAs as institutional actors and concerns a project finance context, it nonetheless provides insights into the types of human rights risks that may also be relevant for projects linked to State-supported export activity.

Against this background, the literature reviewed for this chapter indicates that publications directly addressing ECAs and human rights are limited in number and highly heterogeneous in form. The material identified through the literature mapping conducted for this study comprises academic publications, policy-oriented analyses, reports by international organisations, submissions to accountability mechanisms, and publications by CSOs. These sources predominantly engage with concrete practices, institutional arrangements, and specific controversies related to export support.

This observation informs the structure of the present literature review. Given the fragmented and practice-oriented character of the material identified, the review adopts a mapping approach and organises existing contributions around recurring themes identified namely (1)

challenges and difficulties regarding the consideration of human rights in the ECA context, (2) positive statements, (3) negative statements, and (4) relevant demands. This structure enables a transparent and systematic overview of the state of knowledge while remaining closely aligned with the specific research focus of this thesis on the operationalisation of human rights and HRDD in the context of ECAs.

3.2 Introduction

This research undertaking deals with the implementation of the UNGPs in the context of state ECAs, focussing on GP 4 and the corresponding challenges of its operationalisation. Shedding light on concrete steps regarding how human rights are addressed in the ECA business is paramount, with a particular interest in the meaning and practical content of HRDD.

Business activities and their impacts on human rights have been much discussed and researched (Wettstein *et al.*, 2019, p. 54). In the field of economics though, the question of how to integrate human rights into global business is largely unexplored, as Debora Spar is cited on the cover of *Business and Human Rights: From Principles to Practice* (Baumann-Pauly and Nolan, 2016). In the scholarly world in particular, financial institutions such as ECAs, which may support business activities by financing or guaranteeing export undertakings that are too risky for the private insurance sector, have almost completely been ignored.

ECAs must respect human rights under the UNGPs, the first pillar of which the State duty to protect human rights explicitly addresses HRDD in GP 4: As a form of the State-business nexus, the state is called upon to protect against human rights abuses by requiring or obliging ECAs and their clients or projects to engage in HRDD (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 6–8). While some experts acknowledge initial movements towards supporting human rights and, specifically, HRDD (Seck and Chimisso dos Santos, 2018, p. 104; Linder, 2019, pp. 75–77; UN Working Group on Business and Human Rights, 2021), the need for States to align their trade promotion schemes with the UNGPs is consistently emphasised and called for (UN Working Group on Business and Human Rights, 2021, p. 12; Bachelet, 2022; Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2022).

However, neither the UNGPs nor accompanying materials (see e.g. Interpretive Guide, Frequently Asked Questions and An Introduction at Business & Human Rights Resource Centre, no date; United Nations, 2018) suggest how the UNGPs can be concretely embedded in the ECA context. This literature review therefore explores what contribution the existing literature makes to understanding how the UNGPs, including the concept of HRDD, are addressed in relation to ECAs, providing a foundation for examining the German state ECA in this study.

Even though only a few sources are directly related to the application of the UNGPs to ECAs, this review organises the relevant sources into the four categories that appear repeatedly: (1) challenges and difficulties regarding the consideration of human rights in the ECA context, (2) positive statements, (3) negative statements, and (4) relevant demands. After a critical assessment of the sources, the conclusion identifies a knowledge gap in research. As the author is German, this literature review includes both English and German sources and focuses on Germany and the German ECA.

To find the most significant and relevant research on human rights in an ECA context – particularly research on the operationalisation of the UNGPs and GP 4 – and to analyse both, the literature review involves several systematic steps that are described in the following sections. This chapter begins by introducing the methodology, research questions and approach of the literature review as well as the literature search itself. This is followed by presenting the results of the literature reviewed, arranged according to the four categories mentioned above. Finally, this chapter concludes with a summary of the findings, suggesting further research directions within the context of this doctoral thesis.

3.3 Methodology and Research Questions

This doctoral project's research question is how human rights impacts are addressed by state ECAs, particularly the German ECA, in order to comply with the UNGPs, especially with regard to HRDD. To guide the review, several sub-questions were formulated from a more general view on what the UNGPs actually require, encompassing discussions spanning from how stakeholders believe human rights should be implemented to what the specific meaning of and expectations concerning HRDD are. The question of who ECA stakeholders and their standpoints are were dropped for the literature review because this became more or less apparent as a by-product during the search. Nonetheless, the various stakeholders or stakeholder groups, as well as questions directly relating to the envisaged exchange with them, were put on hold for the qualitative part of this research undertaking.³

To guide the review, the following questions were included, from a more general view on human rights in the ECA context to the concept of HRDD, but without relevance weighting:

- What are the requirements of the UNGPs with regard to ECAs?
- How are human rights embedded in the ECA context?
- Which implementation mechanisms can be identified?
- How should human rights be embedded?

³ See Chapter 5 (Methodology) as well as Chapter 7 and 8 (interview data chapters)

- What are the possibilities, difficulties, and limitations regarding the implementation of human rights in the ECA context, including HRDD?
- What is meant by HRDD in the context of state export credit guarantees? and
- What are stakeholder expectations towards HRDD in the ECA context?

3.4 Approach

The main collection and evaluation of material was carried out between January 2018 and May 2019. Thereafter, the ongoing acquisition and analysis of additional information from newsletters, alerts and webinars lasted until August 2024. Several databases were selected to be researched, with a focus on finding literature related to BHR from the fields of social science, economics, and law, and based inter alia on information provided by the HAW Hamburg librarian, matching databases provided by the HAW Hamburg database information system, as well as the UWS library.

These databases were *Cambridge University Press/ Cambridge Core*, *Emerald Insight*, *Ebsco*, *Elsevier/ ScienceDirect*, *Sage Journals*, *Springer Link*, *Web of Science*, *Beluga* (the consortium catalogue for Hamburg libraries), the *World Bank eLibrary*, and *EconBiz*. For unpublished work and other grey literature, *Google Scholar* and *Google* were chosen in addition to international organisations (such as the *OHCHR* and the *United Nations Association of Germany*), CSOs (such as the Business and Human Rights Resource Centre (*BHRRC*) and the Institute for Human Rights and Business (*IHRB*)), non-profit organisations (such as *Shift*), national and international NGOs (such as the German CorA Network for Corporate Accountability (*CorA*), *ECA Watch* and the *International Network for Economic, Social and Cultural Rights*), and university research institutes (such as the Institute for Development and Peace (*INEF*) and the London School of Economics' Laboratory for Advanced Research on the Global Economy - Investment & Human Rights Project).

To complement the database search, five journals dealing with BHR were first selected. While the *Business Ethics Journal Review* and *The International Journal of Human Rights* were searched directly online, searching the *Journal of Business Ethics* was integrated into the Springer Link search. *The Business and Human Rights Journal* and the *Business Ethics Quarterly* were included in researching articles on Cambridge. After the database search revealed that the *German Journal for Human Rights* and the *Global Policy Journal* could be relevant as well, they were also examined, as was the *Nordic Journal of Human Rights*.

In addition to identifying appropriate databases and journals, further search strategies were applied. Apart from searching sources by hand and indexes of sources as well as checking citation information, several supplementary sources of information were deemed relevant, namely, authors searched, authors and experts contacted directly, reference lists, alerts set

up on Google and Google Scholar, newsletters related to BHR, websites of certain institutions in the field of BHR, webinars, and online or live events on BHR.

Above all, citations and source references as well as the targeted search of websites were relevant for finding suitable literature. Alerts, newsletters, contacting authors and experts, and participating in webinars though did not lead to more sources on the research topic, with only a few exceptions. This was no less important, however, as the author could be sure that there was no research project similar to hers. In addition, she always stayed up to date with the big picture of BHR and its wider research context.

Authors were searched in relation to their work on human rights in export finance. At first, John Ruggie (Harvard University) was identified as the relevant author for this research project. During the literature review, other authors, whose articles or contributions were selected for further scrutiny, were also searched. These were, inter alia and in alphabetical order, Nadia Bernaz (Wageningen University), Karin Buhmann (Copenhagen Business School), Marta Bordignon (Temple University Rome), Brigitte Hamm (University of Duisburg-Essen), Robert McCorquodale (University of Nottingham), and Werner Raza (Austrian Foundation for Development Research).

Several authors and experts were contacted directly, for example the UN Working Group on Business and Human Rights (UN Working Group, Anita Ramasastry) and Shift (Rachel Davis), and scholars such as Florian Wettstein (University of St Gallen), Karen Weidmann (New York University), Brigitte Hamm (University of Duisburg-Essen), and Manfred Nowak (University of Vienna). Being part of the Business and Human Rights Young Researchers Summit Network, organised by the University of St. Gallen and the NYU Stern School of Business, as well as the Teaching Business and Human Rights Forum, helped to identify more experts on the research topic and, moreover, exchange on the wider research context. However, the topic of export finance was not on the agenda in these networks.

The following alerts were created on Google Scholar and Google in both English and German based on the selection process for the following search strings and terms:

- “Human rights” AND “trade promotion” / “Außenwirtschaftsförderung“ AND “Menschenrechte“
- “Foreign trade promotion” / “Außenwirtschaftsförderung”
- “Human Rights” / “Menschenrechte”
- “Human rights” AND “export credit agenc*” / “Menschenrechte “AND “Exportkreditagentur”
- “Human rights” AND “export credit” / “Menschenrechte” AND “Exportkredit”
- “Business and human rights” / “Wirtschaft und Menschenrechte”

- “National action plan” AND “human rights” / “Nationaler Aktionsplan”
- “Human rights due diligence” / “Menschenrechtliche Sorgfalt*”
- “Human rights due diligence” AND “export credit” / “Human rights due diligence” AND “Exportkredit”
- “Export credit” and “PhD” / “Exportkredit” AND “Dissertation”
- “Export credit” AND “private enterprise” / Exportkredit AND “private* Unternehmen”
- “State-business nexus”
- “UN Guiding Principles” / “UN Leitprinzipien”
- “OECD guidelines” AND “multinational” / “OECD-Leitsätze” AND “Multinationale* Unternehmen”

Newsletters relating to BHR, ECAs, sustainability or similar were subscribed to and checked for their possible content on human rights in regard to export finance. Among these newsletters were the *Handelsblatt Nachhaltigkeit* (trade journal series on sustainability issues), the *Business Ethics* magazine and *OECD Watch Case Alerts*. Newsletters of organisations included that of the *IHRB*, the *BHRRC*, *ECA Watch*, *INEF*, the NGO *INKOTA-netzwerk e.V.*, *Shift*, the *German Institute for Human Rights*, the *Danish Institute for Human Rights*, and – with a specific focus on ECAs – the *TXF* (Trade and Export Finance).

During the whole time of the research undertaking, various webinars and online or on-site events – usually relating to the wider research context and, for lack of ability, not to ECAs – hosted by CSOs, law firms or consultancies were attended during the material collection period. Most of the time, ECAs were not part of the discussions. In this regard, the Berlin-based consultancy *Löning* offered several webinars on BHR and the UNGPs, for example on what the UNGPs say about “Human Rights Due Diligence” (21 February 2018), while the webinar “Modern Slavery” (25 July 2018) explained what Modern Slavery is, where it occurs and what the UK Modern Slavery Act requires from companies.

On 13 February 2019, *Löning* stated that human rights will be increasingly in the focus of investors, consumers, and legislators when thinking of “Human rights in business practice - what to expect in 2019”. In another webinar, the consultants explained the legal landscape for financial market participants regarding disclosure on human rights under the title “Complying with the EU Sustainability-related Disclosures Regulation?” (8 September 2020). *Euler Hermes* explained the stages and content of the “Environmental, Social, and Human Rights Assessment” (27 November 2018) at the German ECA. Not surprisingly, although not unthinkable, there was no ECA relation when the *Global Compact Network Germany* informed about current and planned legislative initiatives for mandatory HRDD and their meaning for German companies (4 April 2020). Interestingly, ECAs were not even explicitly mentioned at

the launch of the UN Working Group's project "Business and human rights: towards a decade of global implementation" (7 July 2020).

However, it was emphasised that it is not only with regard to public procurement that a state should lead by example when being economically active, which in turn implies ECAs. Together with *SÜDWIND*, *Fair Finance International* hosted the webinar "One for all and all for one: calling for a CSDDD that includes the financial sector" (12 October 2022), but ECAs were not pointed to, as was the case in *FIAN's* and *SÜDWIND's* "Holding financial players to account" (1 June 2023). During the online event "Greener and geo-economically smarter? – The reform of the OECD standards for export credits" which was organised by the *OECD Berlin Centre* (21 June 2023) to inform about the new Arrangement on export credits (see Chapter 2), social aspects or human rights were not mentioned. In addition, ECAs were not a topic in the numerous webinars offered on German and EU supply chain legislation (2021-2024) and the revised OECD MNE-Guidelines (September 2023).

The annual UN Forum on Business and Human Rights (UN Forum), which was attended on site in Geneva or online from 2018 through 2023, discussed ECAs in part. The 2019 UN Forum, which addressed ECAs specifically, concluded that GP 4 and the State-business nexus were areas where little actual implementation of the UNGPs had occurred and were topics that, among others, academics were welcomed to unpack. The usefulness and importance of this research project was therefore emphasised. Three additional points are worth mentioning from the 2019 UN Forum: trade and investment promotion are good levers for BHR, approval of (several) governments' beginning to implement the UNGPs, and the state as an economic actor becoming an issue. As mentioned in the previous paragraph, ECAs are one example of such economic action. On the other hand, in a digital conference in 2022, then UN High Commissioner on Human Rights Michelle Bachelet urged G7 governments to strengthen ECAs' human rights standard (Bachelet, 2022).

3.5 Strings and Terms

3.5.1 Determination of Search Strings

In order to answer the above-mentioned research questions, keywords were chosen, and correlating synonyms listed. This task resulted in the following four search strings which also fed into the alerts set up on Google and Google Scholar:

1. "Human right*" AND ("trade promotion" OR "foreign trade promotion" OR "export credit" OR "export credit agenc*" AND "national action plan")
2. Menschenrecht* AND (Wirtschaftsförderung OR Außenwirtschaftsförderung OR Exportkredit* OR (Exportkreditagentur AND "Nationaler Aktionsplan"))

3. "Business and human rights" OR "Wirtschaft und Menschenrechte" OR "Human Rights Due Diligence" OR ("Human Rights Due Diligence" AND "export credit*") OR ("Human Rights Due Diligence" AND "Exportkredit*") OR "Menschenrechtliche Sorgfalt*" OR "human rights due diligence" OR ("Export Credit*" and "PhD") OR ("Exportkredit*" AND "Dissertation") OR ("Export Credit*" AND "private enterprise*") OR ("Exportkredit*" AND "private* Unternehmen") OR "State-business nexus"
4. "UN Guiding Principle*" OR "UN Leitprinzip*" OR ("OECD guidelines" AND multinational*) OR ("OECD-Leitsätze" AND Multinationale)

3.5.2 Search Terms

As not all databases allowed for search strings or the use of asterisks, the search strategy needed to be adapted and keyword, phrase or subject searching were applied instead. In some databases, predetermined keywords ("tags") could be chosen from upon an initial search term. If databases allowed for joint search terms, "human right*" combined with "export credit*" was at least used because it quickly became clear that the literature review needed to be broader, i.e. exceeding the UNGPs. The reason for this was that there was little closely related literature on the application of the UNGPs to ECAs, including HRDD in trade promotion. In some databases though, it seemed more reasonable to combine the term "Guiding Principles" with keywords like "human rights" or "export credit agencies". The fourth search string ("UN Guiding Principle*" OR "UN Leitprinzip*" OR ("OECD guidelines" AND multinational*) OR ("OECD-Leitsätze" AND Multinationale) was not considered for the database search because it yielded imprecise results, i.e., no reference to foreign trade promotion.

3.5.3 Search Example

The following two tables (Table 5 and Table 6) illustrate the database search.

Table 5: Search example Google Scholar

Search String	Results	Relevant	Not Chosen	Date
"human right*" AND ("trade promotion" OR "export credit*")	773			25.05. 2018
"export credit*" AND "human right*"	380-413	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sikka (s.a.) 2. Nolan/Kinley? 3. Lee (s.a.) 4. de Schutter (partly Case, legal) 5. Bordignon (s.a.) 6. Krajewski (s.a.) 7. Gibb et al (grey) 	<p>IF</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Report on shortcomings of IFC Performance Standards ▪ ECAs only mentioned once or 	25.05. 2018

Search String	Results	Relevant	Not Chosen	Date
		8. Sant'Ana (s.a.) 9. Lagoutte 10. Kirunda (Case) 11. Brynildsen (Cases and critique; NGO) 12. Leader 13. Grabska (Science: Institute for Development Studies, University of Sussex; Case mentioned: Ilisu) 14. Eichert: s.a. 15. Özden (grey, Case: Ilisu et al) 16. Simons 17. Klasen (grey/Science) 18. Buhmann (Legal) 19. Cotula (Case, Legal) 20. Myllylä (Case, Business Science) 21. Fleming. (Case, BTC Pipeline: Cultural Heritage; social sciences) 22. Laasonen (pos. Case on Finnvera, Business?) 23. Debus, Börzel (eds.) 24. Meyerstein	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> only in general terms or ECA-hr-relation not clear ▪ <2008 cited (ECAs lacking access to information) ▪ CHN ECA ▪ Health justice ▪ Curricula/BHR ▪ MA-Thesis (exclusion criteria) ▪ Investment only (DIA; e.g. Jacob/INEF) ▪ Ilisu: nothing new 	

Source: Johanna Imiela

Table 6: Search example Beluga

Search String	Results	Relevant	Not Chosen	Date
"human right*" AND "export credit*" AND "guiding principle*"	0	▪	▪	07.07.2018
"human right*" AND "export credit*"	874(e-articles, peer-reviewed)	1. Bernaz (s.a.) 2. Muchlinski (2009) 3. Mantilla 4. Mares 5. Taylor 6. Keenan (2010) 7. Shemberg 8. Clémant 9. Ploeg/Vanclay 10. Cirlig 11. Davis (s.b.) 12. Rae 13. Rajavuori 14. Cariffo, 15. Gilbert 16. Schöne/Bittner/Waldenfels 17. Eberlein et al. (Case, NGO) 18. Caspary 19. Webb (s.a.) 20. Tan 21. Vanclay 22. Shea/Hutchin	IF <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ilisu ▪ < 2008 ▪ no (clear) ECA-hr-relation ▪ too general ▪ only on resettlement (Vanclay) and no ECA relation from abstract 	17.08.2018 18.08.2018 20.08.2018

Search String	Results	Relevant	Not Chosen	Date
		23. Middtun 24. Dendena/Corsi (s.a.) 25. Orr 26. Caspary (2009) 27. Spagnoletti/O'Callaghan 28. Downey 29. Clausen 30. Campbell 31. Weber/Banks		
"human right*" AND "export credit"	269 (Books)	1. OECD (2011) 2. Scheper/Feldt (2010) 3. Fliesser (Case: Ilisu) 4. Papp 5. Bernaz: s.a. 6. Sant'ana 7. Träger 8. Spiesshofer	IF <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <2008 ▪ FDI/intl. Investment Agreements ▪ If no ECA-hr-relation ▪ Development projects 	07.05.2018
Exportkredit* Menschenrecht*	10 +2 e-articles	1. Scheper/Feldt (s.a.) 2. Zimmer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ No HR-ECA relation ▪ < 2008 	15.08.2018

Source: Johanna Imiela

3.6 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The inclusion and exclusion criteria decided upon are summarised in Table 7:

Table 7: Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Trade promotion ▪ Export credit ▪ Human Rights Due Diligence ▪ Financial institution ▪ Languages: English, German ▪ Guiding Principles ▪ Anything related to the research subject, e.g., German NAP, German foreign trade promotion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Bachelor's thesis* (if standalone publication) ▪ Master's thesis* (if standalone publication) ▪ <2008**, >2019*** ▪ Languages other than English and German ▪ Climate finance/justice/change ▪ Investment risks/rules/law ▪ Human development ▪ Development agency, Official Development Assistance ▪ External debt, national debt-increase ▪ Chinese ECA (not part of the OECD)

Source: Johanna Imiela

* After working through some Bachelor's and Master's theses, it was noticed that these lacked precision with regard to the export credit guarantee as a funding instrument; this was also confirmed after a renewed search explicitly for Bachelor's and Master's theses.

** In 2008, the so-called Ruggie Framework (Human Rights Council, 2008a) was published, and human rights explicitly mentioned in relation with ECAs; in general, the topic of BHR has gained momentum since then.

*** When databases required an end date for the search, 2019 was chosen as the year until the main literature review took place.

3.7 Use of Grey Literature

Apart from the fact that an analysis of grey literature was necessary to identify stakeholder views, little secondary literature related to the research subject was found which contrasts the planned original design of the literature search. Only a few scientifically based sources exist on the human rights dimension of the ECA business. Therefore, most of the findings from the full-text review presented below (around 80%) refer to grey literature sources. Since these (primary) literature sources must also be considered in order to show a complete picture of the state of knowledge, to what extent and under what conditions this may occur must be discussed. However, Adams et al. have observed that little methodological guidance on including grey literature in systematic literature reviews exists (Adams, Smart and Huff, 2017, p. 433). In order to address this shortcoming, prevailing criticism and challenges will briefly be examined and linked to this research project hereinafter.

Concerns that grey (or primary) literature is more difficult to access and locate (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009) cannot be confirmed. Compared with only a few secondary sources, an abundance of grey sources was found during research. The Internet may be the cause as information is made more accessible (Rucinski, 2015, p. 544). Correspondingly, the amount of grey literature and its influence have increased (Adams, Smart and Huff, 2017, p. 434), and so has a more obvious need to include it in systematic literature reviews (*ibid.*). Criticism that grey literature is lacking scientific representation of data or analyses (Soldani, Tamburri and Van Den Heuvel, 2018, p. 2) should apply more to scientific studies than to this research project which deals less with tangible numbers and measurable facts than with qualitative elements, i.e. human rights.

Therefore, the topic of personal opinion and bias (Benzies *et al.*, 2006, p. 55; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009, p. 74) seems much more crucial with regard to the consideration of grey literature, as this – including research published online by academics – is not peer-reviewed or evaluated, unlike journal articles and books (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009, p. 74). Because academic reports can nevertheless be a useful source of information (*ibid.*) and grey literature is by itself said to be “both practical and meaningful” (Rucinski, 2015, p. 544), it seems that the quality of grey literature is important for deciding whether to include it in systematic literature reviews.

In this regard, Adams et al. have suggested that the author of a source and their experience play a crucial role in addition to where a source is publicised (Adams, Smart and Huff, 2017, p. 435). Therefore, the appropriateness of grey literature has to be assessed, and explicit judgements have to be recorded (ibid.), which will take place on a case-by-case basis in this present review, grounded on the above-mentioned assumptions. Against this background, it should be possible to take grey literature into account in this literature review and thus fully show the state of knowledge concerning human rights in the context of ECAs.

3.8 Literature Search

The document search required very detailed and thorough steps and was a time-consuming task as was the critical assessment of the grey literature sources. As indicated above, searching in the selected databases was characterised by little synchronised processes but individual adaptation instead. Sometimes, articles were listed more than once under the same search criteria so that the statistics had to be adjusted even within one specific search. Some databases did not allow for limiting the time period of the search according to the exclusion criteria so that the results were larger and had to be refined by hand. Another challenging feature was that some authors referred to other ones, but when the respective works were checked, the assumed topic did not appear at all.

Occasionally, access to articles was not provided but those articles looked for and found in other databases, or they were sent by acquainted researchers with further access possibilities. When sources were not available online, they were ordered via the state or the economics library of the University of Hamburg, or the HAW Hamburg library. Few articles could not be accessed via the UWS or HAW Hamburg, and due to the prevailing financial lock at the HAW Hamburg, also not be ordered.

Apart from these more technical aspects, it became obvious that several flawed assumptions exist in view of the ECA business on the one hand and also with regard to ECA-related contents of the UNGPs and other international guidelines. Irrespective of an author's background – ranging from being related to the UN, EU, an NGO, a university institute or the German ECA – several factual inaccurate statements were found. These statements often relate to the business model of ECAs when saying that ECAs in general would support or even fund or finance projects abroad. As became clear in Chapter 2, pure cover ECAs support exports to foreign projects but do not have any business relationship with the foreign buyer or project owner.

Other insufficient statements relate to some details of the ECA screening procedure, i.e., the benchmark standards⁴ or the Common Approaches⁵ as such, or to the UNGPs. Sometimes, the policy statement as well as grievance mechanisms are improperly subsumed under HRDD according to the UNGPs, while the latter consider these equivalent to HRDD in order to meet the corporate responsibility to respect human rights (see the UNGPs' second pillar, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 13–21).

Careful attention had to be paid to comments on the Ruggie Framework which in turn are revised by the UNGPs. For example, GP 18 mentions stakeholder consultations as an important element of HRDD (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 19–20) whereas the Ruggie Framework is silent about these. The reason for this is that the UNGPs concretise and operationalise the contents of the framework, i.e. they “address the ‘how’ question” (Harrison, 2013, p. 107) and go further than the Ruggie Framework. Respective criticism or statements might have become invalid over time, which also applies to former versions of the Common Approaches which did not yet explicitly state on human rights.⁶ Therefore, the validity of relating assertions had to be assessed, and several negative ones were not considered on these grounds.

In total, 3,071 articles and books were identified through database searches. Their titles, abstracts (if extant) or both were read and assessed in order to eliminate those that did not fit the research questions. Judgement was based on the above-mentioned exclusion criteria, however. Documents were also excluded when they did not involve a relation between human rights and ECAs or export finance, or when export finance was obviously only a marginal topic. This process led to an elimination of most of the documents, leaving 222 articles for further review. It is therefore obvious that there is only a relatively small body of literature concerned with human rights in export finance.

After removing duplicates amongst these 222 documents, a total of 169 records from the database search were considered eligible for full-text review. These were complemented by 182 records identified through additional sources, i.e., as mentioned above, citations and source references as well as specific websites, and also – although less fruitful – alerts, newsletters, authors and experts, webinars, and (online) events. Once duplicates were removed again, the number of articles chosen for full-text review was 306 (see Appendix A for an overview of the identification of sources). The main reason for excluding 71% of these was the missing relationship between human rights and ECAs. 90 articles, accounting for 29% of the full-text review, were ultimately selected for in-depth analysis and to prove the gap in

⁴ See Chapter 2

⁵ See Chapter 2

⁶ ‘Human rights’ were mentioned for the first time in the 2012 Common Approaches version (see Chapter 2).

research, as will be described in the following. In sum, Figure 6 visualises the process of the literature search and analysis.

Figure 6: Overview of the systematic literature review

Source: Johanna Imiela

The 90 records selected to indicate the state of knowledge and to prove the research gap were analysed based on the following criteria and related to the above-mentioned research questions:

- How are human rights embedded in the ECA context?
→ What are positive/neutral statements? What are critical ones?
- How should human rights be embedded?
→ What do authors claim and consider to be important?
- What challenges, difficulties and limitations are mentioned?

Looking at GP 4 as one main objective of the overall research undertaking, namely a proposal for HRDD in the context of state ECAs, the following questions were also considered during the full-text review:

- What is meant by HRDD in the context of state export credit guarantees?
- What are the expectations (ideas, proposals, wishes, demands) concerning HRDD in this regard?
- What are the essential elements of HRDD according to the sources?
- What difficulties and limitations might exist concerning HRDD in the ECA business?

3.9 Results and Discussion

The literature was analysed based on the research question how ECA stakeholders think that human rights are considered in the ECA context, and the respective sub-questions posed above. During the process of the literature review, these questions were refined in order to analyse the articles chosen for full-text review. Generalisation yielded four categories. The literature that considers human rights in the context of state ECAs has highlighted few related difficulties and several positive views, but the majority of the literature has been critical and raised several claims for strengthening the integration of human rights. Therefore, the following presents the results of the literature search, sorted by the four categories (1) challenges and difficulties, (2) positive points of view, (3) negative points of view and (4) demands.

3.9.1 Challenges and Difficulties

Regarding the challenges and difficulties of the human rights dimension of ECAs, two keywords can be highlighted in Figure 7:

Figure 7: Challenges and difficulties

Source: Johanna Imiela

Leverage, i.e., according to the UNGPs, a business’s influence on the practices of another party that negatively impact human rights (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2014, pp. 29, 43), is described a challenge for both exporters and ECAs in terms of the consideration and enforcement of human rights in foreign projects. Scheper and Feldt have argued that to generate sufficient information to carry out an effective human rights review and for the exporter to positively influence a project overall depends on the exporter’s leverage over the latter (Scheper and Feldt, 2010a, p. 29), which is limited in short-term export credit undertakings or when the exporter’s share in the overall project is only small (ibid.). In the

authors' interviews, exporters stated that timing plays a crucial role because the planning phase of a project has already been completed when they are commissioned (ibid.). From a temporal point of view, the possibility of influencing the project design, which can lead to or even include adverse human rights impacts, no longer seems given. Moreover, the exporters are usually not on site to assess the conditions and consequences of the overall project (ibid.). In this case, due to distance alone, exporters' leverage to comprehensively assess and, as a consequence, positively influence the human rights situation at the project location appears to be lacking.

Regarding an ECA's leverage, Spießhofer has claimed that ECAs have economic and legal leverage (Spießhofer, 2018, p. 284). Although her use of the term 'leverage' differs somewhat from that of the UNGPs because it refers more to the lever used than the influence, the result is the same when she states that the UNGPs, among other guidelines, have identified ECAs as "important leverage in order to exert influence on the related projects through the inclusion of human rights, social and environmental provisions" in ECA contracts (ibid., p. 283). Looking at the form of the ECA cover, Scheper and Feldt have indicated that direct lending ECAs have more influence on the project design than those that do not provide credits but only insurances or guarantees, i.e. pure cover support, such as the German ECA (Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 68, FN 29). Moreover, in pure supplies and services contexts, i.e., where neither the ECA nor a private financial institution provides a credit, a comprehensive consideration of human rights in individual exports hardly seems practical (ibid., p. 76).

As a rule, these contexts comprise a tendering business in which the supplier competes with various competitors and supplies not large capital goods but production (ibid., p. 28, 70-71). Since exporters are virtually interchangeable, they can exercise little influence, and so Scheper and Feldt see a restrictive policy as particularly important for identifying eligible businesses and target countries (ibid., p. 76). The German ECA itself has stated that, depending on the type of transaction, the ECA and the exporter have a different degree of influence on the buyer and on the social and environmental performance of the project (Schöne-Alaluf, Bittner and von Waldenfels, 2011, p. 130). While exports that only amount to a small contribution to an overall project are usually associated with a lower level of influence by an exporter and the ECA, the opposite is true if, for example, the export share represents a larger part of the total volume of the project (ibid.). In the latter constellation, not only can the ECA's ESHR review be positively influenced by better information gathering, but so too can the overall performance of the project with regard to these aspects.

Against this background, leverage seems to be a relevant factor for the assessment of human rights, but also as a challenging one. Yet according to Scheper and Feldt, this conclusion must first be seen as independent of the State duty to protect human rights in the ECA context

(Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 29). This leads to a challenge for practical implementation because the exporter’s influence, as a client of the ECA in the export financing context, cannot be separated from the State duty to protect human rights. Ruggie’s statements on leverage lead in a similar direction when he has explained that ECAs have to assess the potential human rights impacts of projects, regardless of their leverage (Ruggie, 2010c, p. 2), and that leverage only becomes important once necessary measures are decided upon, i.e. after human rights have been assessed (ibid.). According to Harrison and Linder, a difficulty relating to this assessment stems from the *limited options* ECAs have in judging a company’s HRDD (Harrison, 2012; Linder, 2019, p. 75). Harrison has found that ECAs can only determine whether a client has undertaken HRDD, but that they are not in a position to assess its appropriateness and contents, i.e. to verify and evaluate the details of the methods used or the results reported (Harrison, 2012).

In practical terms, these findings are therefore relevant to complying with the UNGPs. At the same time, several – mostly government-related – sources have perceived the consideration of human rights in the ECA context as positive (see the summarising Figure 8).

3.9.2 Positive Points of View

Figure 8: Positive statements

Source: Johanna Imiela

Weidmann has seen an *increasing linkage* between foreign trade promotion and corporate compliance with human rights standards (Weidmann, 2014, p. 144). Similarly, Hamm et al. and Linder have observed that *awareness of human rights* has been raised within the OECD and that the sustainability and environmental assessments of ECAs have incorporated human rights criteria in the meantime (Hamm, Scheper and Drebes, 2014, p. 31; Linder, 2019, pp. 80–83; 86). This has been influenced by the standards established by the World Bank Group (Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 51), i.e., the World Bank Safeguard Policies, World Bank ESS, IFC Performance Standards and World Bank EHS Guidelines, which are used as benchmark criteria (OECD, no date a).

The UN Working Group has praised the OECD as the main organisation to incorporate human rights into its export credit decisions (Human Rights Council, 2018, p. 51). This view is

supported at the EU level by the EU Commission, which has reported that during the project assessment, EU ECAs are increasingly taking human rights risks into account beyond the Common Approaches (EU Commission, 2018, pp. 4–6). When it comes to Germany, Haupt has seen a potential to contribute to compliance with environmental standards and human rights through foreign trade promotion (Haupt, 2024, p. 18), even though her report has focused primarily on negative project impacts on the environment and on human rights in the ECA context.

The federal government and ministries have stressed that human rights have already been an *element of project assessment*, e.g. as part of ESIA⁷ (The Federal Government, 2017, p. 17), and that they place significant emphasis on ESHR consideration in its foreign trade promotion (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date t, p. 24). Relevant human rights implications are considered (Auswärtiges Amt, 2016, pp. 201–202, 2020, p. 240). Projects' human rights impacts are comprehensively reviewed (Auswärtiges Amt, 2019, p. 141), e.g. by means of the assessment standards of the World Bank Group, which cover the human rights relevant in this context (Auswärtiges Amt, 2020, p. 240).

In contrast to previous reports, the German government has also mentioned in its two most recent reports on its human rights policy that ESHR aspects of the relevant projects covered are followed up even after the guarantee has been issued and, if necessary, improvement measures are demanded (ibid, 2022, p. 230). What exactly relevant projects are has not been specified in more detail though. The German ECA itself has underlined that respect for human rights plays an *important role* in foreign trade promotion (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date g), and that the review of aspects such as human rights is obligatory for and integral to the review process (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date b).

According to two more recently uploaded brochures, human rights are now even part of the eligibility criteria (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2022, p. 1, no date t, p. 5), which has not been formulated in this way elsewhere though (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date i; Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, no date b). Human rights aspects have gained in importance in the course of the 2016 revision of the Common Approaches (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 2), and their *visibility and autonomy* have been heightened by implementing the German NAP (ibid.). In case of a violation of “internationally acknowledged” human rights standards through export transactions, cover is not provided (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, 2022, p. 40).

Projects and transactions that fall under the scope of the Common Approaches, namely, transactions with a repayment term of more than two years and a contract value of at least

⁷ See Chapter 2

EUR 15 million are *always reviewed* regarding their human rights impact (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date b). Even those transactions outside the Common Approaches are *assessed for any significant risks*, according to the so-called watchful-eye approach (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2019, p. 41). In order to implement the German NAP, “a *project-related HRDD*” will complement the assessment procedure (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date n).

In sum, the German ECA in particular has emphasised the importance of human rights in its export credit business. At the same time, however, there has been no concrete presentation concerning how human rights are considered. For example, statements on the assessment procedure have remained rather theoretical and vague, and relevant explanations have been lacking. Speaking of “a project-related HRDD” (*ibid.*, emphasis added) seems confusing as the UNGPs do not provide an article for HRDD at all. It is surprising that the ECA has not further clarified HRDD at this point and has apparently used it differently than the UNGPs intended.

This finding is underlined when the ECA has considered HRDD an “in-depth examination” of human rights aspects (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2019, p. 41; see also equations of Human Rights Impact Assessment (HRIA) and HRDD in Die Bundesregierung, 2021, p. 41), which appears to be more of a one-time exercise similar to a HRIA than an ongoing process, comprising not only steps to identify human rights risks but also to prevent, mitigate, and account for adverse human rights impacts (see GP 17, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 17). However, the German ECA does not seem to understand HRDD to be “an ongoing management process” as intended by the UNGPs (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2014, p. 42).

Elsewhere, “ESHR due diligence” has been mentioned (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date b), but not explained. While the most recent annual report on German export credit guarantees 2023⁸ has only shortly, i.e. in two sentences, mentioned that in 2023, 60 ESHR assessments were conducted for projects under the OECD Common Approaches (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, 2023, p. 24), the respective annual reports of 2018-2022 have underlined the importance of human rights. None of the latter have explained though how human rights violations are specifically identified (see e.g. the vague formulations ‘high probability’, ‘serious human rights implications’ and ‘significant risks’ in Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2019, pp. 40–41) in a manner that results in a sustainability check (*ibid.*, p. 40) or ESHR assessment (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2020, p. 33, 2021, p. 34; Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, 2022, pp. 40–41, 2023, p. 36).

⁸ Until August 2024; the annual report for 2023 was not yet available in English.

The annual reports also mention that projects within the scope of the Common Approaches are subject to an ESHR assessment, but do not explain this assessment (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2019, p. 40f., 2020, p. 33f., 2021, p. 34; Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, 2022, p. 40, 2023, p. 55; Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz, 2024, p. 24). Even though the ESHR review has been considered an “integral part of the examination procedure” (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, 2022, p. 40), depending on the order value and term of a transaction to be hedged by the ECA (ibid.), the exact approach to human rights remains rather unclear and obscure. At least with regard to the hitherto non-existent definition of HRDD in literature and practice, especially in implementation, this research project should contribute.

3.9.3 Critical Points of View

Figure 9 summarises some of the critical statements found during the research.

Figure 9: Critical statements

Source: Johanna Imiela

Against the background of the previous section, it does not seem surprising that critical voices have mentioned the *lack of transparency* at ECAs in general (United Nations, 2011, p. 2; Raza, Schlögl and Pfaffenbichler, 2023, p. 27) or at the German ECA in particular (Papp, 2013, p. 329; Heydenreich, Paasch and Kusch, 2014, p. 53). The ambition of the German ECA to give human rights a higher priority is questioned in its implementation – examples of projects that are critical from a human rights perspective, among other perspectives, “give rise to doubts as to whether this priority has an adequate impact in practice” (Heydenreich and Paasch, 2017, p. 52).

Several sources have lamented that human rights are *insufficiently considered*, by ECAs in general (Wiher Fernandez, 2011, p. 185; Scheper, 2013, p. 47; Finance & Trade Watch and CEE Bankwatch Network, 2017, p. 20), the German ECA in particular (Burckhardt, 2013, p. 55; Papp, 2013, p. 168; Hamm, Scheper and Drebes, 2014, pp. 30–31; CorA, 2017, p. 9) and at other individual ECAs (Vessel, 2015, p. 16). Bernaz has formulated this deficiency much more sharply when stating that the provision of export finance is dependent on neither human rights nor environmental criteria (Bernaz, 2013, p. 502). The ICC, on the other hand, has

credited ECAs with initially leading the export finance industry in terms of sustainability trends (ICC, 2021, p. 25). In the meantime, however, ECAs have focused on the issue of climate, i.e. on the environmental sustainability dimension, while neglecting the social one (Acre Impact Capital/ICC/IFCL, 2023, pp. 15, 20). Some sources, such as Scheper and Feldt, have highlighted that *explicit reference* to (Human Rights Council, 2008a, p. 39; Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 52; United Nations, 2011, p. 8) or consideration of (Human Rights Council, 2008a, p. 39; Papp, 2013, p. 168) human rights is lacking. At the OECD level, human rights are not approached systematically according to Scheper (Scheper, 2017, p. 202), and clear guidelines, e.g. for a HRIA, do not exist (Hamm, Scheper and Drebes, 2014, p. 31).

Criticism of the *Common Approaches*, which has been mentioned quite frequently, fits this allegation. The Common Approaches have been regarded as insufficient, amongst other things, because of the threshold for project assessment (Finance & Trade Watch and CEE Bankwatch Network, 2017, p. 20; Kovick, Vermijs and Davis, 2017, p. 10), their non-binding character (United Nations, 2011, p. 13; Papp, 2013, p. 329; Seck and Chimisso dos Santos, 2018, p. 105), and the underlying standards of the World Bank Group, especially the World Bank Safeguard Policies, which do not cover all human rights that can potentially be negatively impacted (Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 52; Papp, 2013, p. 329; Scheper, 2013, p. 47).

As the 2016 review of the World Bank Safeguard Policies has brought them more closely in line with the (social) issues already covered by the IFC Performance Standards, it seems worth mentioning that some authors, such as Kämpf, have explicitly pointed out the insufficiency also of the latter and have questioned whether the new World Bank ESS better account for human rights (on the IFC Performance Standards, see Ruggie, 2010c, p. 2; Hamm, Scheper and Schölmerich, 2011, p. 4; Linder, 2019, p. 94; Heydenreich, Paasch and Kusch, 2014, p. 55; Human Rights Council, 2018, p. 69; on the new World Bank Standards, see Kämpf, 2016; Linder, 2019, pp. 87–89). Again, the fact that companies can impact all human rights has been given as one reason (Ruggie, 2010c, p. 2).

Apart from these criticisms of the reference standards, the Common Approaches have been said to lack clear (Papp, 2013, p. 329), systematic (Scheper, 2013, p. 47) and uniform (Human Rights Council, 2018, p. 58; Raza, Schlögl and Pfaffenbichler, 2023, p. 20) requirements and to leave room for discretion instead (Raza, Schlögl and Pfaffenbichler, 2023, p. 6), specifically with regard to the meaning and implementation of HRDD (Both ENDS, 2016, p. 4; Finance & Trade Watch and CEE Bankwatch Network, 2017, p. 38; Human Rights Council, 2018, p. 58; Seck and Chimisso dos Santos, 2018, p. 95; Linder, 2019, p. 85). Several authors, including Kovick, Vermijs and Davis, have concluded that the Common Approaches therefore do not comply with the UNGPs (Scheper, 2013, p. 47; Kovick, Vermijs and Davis, 2017, pp. 10–12;

Human Rights Council, 2018, pp. 14–15; Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2022, p. 51). This assertion will be explored further in the remainder of this research project.

The above-mentioned may justify the concerns that have been raised and the examples that have been provided about *human rights violations on projects* associated with ECAs (United Nations, 2011, pp. 3–4; Bernaz, 2013, p. 502; Papp, 2013, pp. 171–172; Finance & Trade Watch and CEE Bankwatch Network, 2017, p. 43; McCorquodale, 2024, pp. 57–58), even explicitly with the German ECA (Heydenreich and Paasch, 2017, p. 50f). Scheper has pointed out that HRIAs are not required by the benchmark standards (Scheper, 2013, p. 47), and an independent UN expert has indicated that they are “rarely undertaken” (United Nations, 2011, p. 8).

Some contradictory statements have been made. On the one hand, Spieß has considered the current practice of German export promotion unsatisfactory from a human rights perspective (Spieß, 2009, p. 72) because the German government would continue to support projects with problematic human rights implications, which it would do because of existing gaps in the granting of export credit guarantees (*ibid.*). On the other hand, Germany’s leading business organisations have warned against overloading German foreign trade promotion with social criteria, as this would only favour competitors (CSR Germany, no date).

In conclusion, three UN-level sources have commented specifically on HRDD. Ruggie has reported that ECAs *neither practice nor require HRDD* (Ruggie, 2010b, p. 4). This view has been supported by the UN Working Group, which has observed a lack of focus of ECAs on HRDD (Human Rights Council, 2018, p. 10) and a weak integration of HRDD into ECAs’ practice and requirements (United Nations, 2018, p. 10).

3.9.4 Demands

Almost 60% (namely 53 sources) of the 90 records selected for closer analysis have placed demands on ECAs with regard to their human rights performance. Many of those demands have been accompanied by negative connotations of ECAs’ shortcomings. Therefore, some of the claims pointed out below have already been formulated in a negative critique as described in the previous section. It is striking that many of these demands remain vague or are not formulated specifically and concretely with regard to practical implementation, as will become clear in the following section.

While almost 40% of the sources that listed at least one demand were specifically aimed at the German ECA, three submissions looked at other ECAs, namely, at UK Export Finance and the Austrian Österreichische Kontrollbank. Claims relating more to the policy level than ECAs’ actual business – such as asking for parliamentary scrutiny, the assessment of possibilities to use withdrawal of trade support more actively or demanding laws or stronger ECA regulation

– have not been considered because they exceed the scope of this research undertaking. This could be a topic for further research.

Figure 10 summarises the main demands provided.

Figure 10: Demands

Source: Johanna Imiela

Rather general requirements like *greater consideration of human rights*, which have been required of ECAs, have been requested. While the European Council has encouraged all EU Member States to address their human rights responsibilities as ECAs (Council of the European Union, 2016, p. 11), other sources have claimed that the granting of export credits should be made conditional on corporate respect for human rights (United Nations, 2018, p. 20), including clients' commitments to the UNGPs (Human Rights Council, 2018, p. 4).

Similar demands have been made on the German ECA. In general, it has been claimed that human rights must be given greater account (Fraktion BUENDNIS 90/DIE GRUENEN, 2009, p. 1; Hoppe, 2009; Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, pp. 68–69). The granting of export credits should be *dependent on human rights conformance* (Papp, 2013, p. 316) and should only be provided to companies who make adequate efforts to address human rights risks (Knopf *et al.*, 2013, p. 111) or who are committed to complying with OECD policies (Fraktion BUENDNIS 90/DIE GRUENEN, 2009, p. 1). Guarantee awarding could be subject to proof that human rights are being respected in the whole production chain of a project (Wenisch, 2015), which must meet the highest human rights standards (GegenStroemung *et al.*, 2013, p. 3).

In less strident terms, the OECD has recommended just in 2023 that governments “lead by example and take measure to promote and exemplify responsible business conduct (...) through the integration of environmental, social and governance criteria in the provision and management of (...) loans, guarantees or insurance” (OECD, 2023d, p. 8). As export credit applications are mentioned as one example for doing so (ibid.), this recommendation has apparently not yet been fulfilled and therefore has a demanding character.

Hamm et al. have argued that human rights need to be *systematically integrated* at the German ECA (Hamm, Scheper and Drebes, 2014, p. 30f) and (consistent) human rights criteria, among others, have been considered as crucial (Fraktion BUENDNIS 90/DIE GRUENEN, 2009, p. 1; Hamm and Scheper, 2009, p. 22; Hoppe, 2009; Grabosch and Scheper, 2015, p. 21). Separate from Germany, there have also been calls to link export credits, or foreign trade promotion in general, to human rights criteria (Hamm and Scheper, 2009, p. 22; Danish Institute for Human Rights, French National Consultative Commission on Human Rights and German Institute for Human Rights, 2013, pp. 3–5; Scheper, 2017, p. 202).

More specific requirements like *transparency and disclosure* regarding funding decisions and review processes have been demanded of the German ECA (Spieß, 2009, pp. 74–75; Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 60; Papp, 2013, p. 326; Krajewski, 2017, p. 29; CorA, 2021, p. 6), UK Export Finance (Institute for Human Rights and Business, 2012), and ECAs in general (Danish Institute for Human Rights, French National Consultative Commission on Human Rights and German Institute for Human Rights, 2013, pp. 5–6; Human Rights Council, 2018, p. 71; Seck and Chimisso dos Santos, 2018, p. 102). The need for *monitoring* has been mentioned (concerning ECAs in general (Parker and Howe, 2012, p. 289) or the German (Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 60) and Austrian ECA (Vessel, 2015, p. 16) in particular), as has the establishment of a *grievance mechanism* in the context of German export promotion (Spieß, 2009, p. 76; Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 62; Papp, 2013, p. 326) or similar foreign trade schemes (Danish Institute for Human Rights, French National Consultative Commission on Human Rights and German Institute for Human Rights, 2013, pp. 6–7; Scheper, 2017, p. 202), so that people who are negatively affected by projects can raise their concerns.

Regarding the grievance mechanism, only the National Human Rights Institutions have provided some detail when stating that grievance mechanisms should be in place at both the project and ECA levels (Danish Institute for Human Rights, French National Consultative Commission on Human Rights and German Institute for Human Rights, 2013, p. 7). The UN Working Group has seen the need for grievance mechanisms at the operational level and at ECAs themselves and has urged ECAs to focus more on the issue of enabling access to remedy (Human Rights Council, 2018, pp. 15, 20).

In addition, criticism of the *Common Approaches*, as described above, matches demands to improve them. Relating to the thresholds for the Common Approaches, several sources have instead called for project assessments for all applications, from the German ECA (Spieß, 2009, p. 74; GegenStromung et al., 2013, p. 5; Heydenreich, Paasch and Kusch, 2014, p. 58) and UK ECA (Institute for Human Rights and Business, 2012). In relation to OECD ECAs, this view has been supported by representatives of the Swedish ECA (Apelman and Olming, 2015), whereas the UN Working Group has adopted a broader perspective in pointing out several areas where advancement of the Common Approaches is needed (Human Rights Council, 2018, pp. 14–15), including the threshold topic.

In the same report, the UN Working Group has also made an appeal to *link findings of NCPs to ECA support* (ibid., p. 17), a postulate that has been voiced by other authors as well (Finance & Trade Watch and CEE Bankwatch Network, 2017, p. 36; relating to the German ECA: GegenStromung et al., 2013; Heydenreich and Paasch, 2017, p. 53; Papp, 2013, pp. 310–311). The Common Approaches have already provided for such a connection when asking ECAs to take publicly available NCP statements into account (OECD, 2016, p. 9). Since the German ECA has emphasised that it goes beyond this requirement in its project appraisal by accounting for complaints and the like received by its NCP (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date g), i.e., independent of and prior to any public statement, there nevertheless seems to be potential for improvement, and the claims mentioned continue to apply to ECAs in general.

Relating to NCPs, several NGOs have called for a temporary *exclusion* of companies that violate the OECD MNE-Guidelines from support of the German ECA (GegenStromung et al., 2013, p. 6). Krajewski has suggested that ECA support should be “withheld or withdrawn if (...) recipients abuse human rights” (Krajewski, 2017, p. 29), and Papp, focusing solely on Germany, has pointed out that guarantees must be terminated when critical human rights situations arise (Papp, 2013, p. 329; see Linder’s elaborations on the Ilisu dam for the “first time ever” example of ECA withdrawal: Linder, 2019, p. 74).

Exports of arms should receive no German trade support at all (Spieß, 2009, p. 76; Pilgrim and Drillisch, 2021, p. 4; Wündsche and Windfuhr, 2022, p. 59) and surveillance technology neither (ibid.) which could lead to adverse human rights impacts such as the right to life (McCorquodale, 2024, p. 58). Other authors have looked at the topic of dual use goods and have concluded that taking greater account of potential negative impacts on human rights resulting from these transactions is important when it comes to determining the eligibility for ECA support of specific products and countries targeted for such exports (Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 76; Pilgrim and Drillisch, 2021, p. 4). Some of the literature has turned directly to ECA employees when stating that their *human rights knowledge* (Ruggie, 2010c, p. 6; Hamm, Scheper and Drebes, 2014, p. 67 (addressed to Germany); Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 78

(addressed to Germany)) or *human rights consultancy* (Grabosch and Scheper, 2015, p. 21 (addressed to Germany); Scheper, 2017, p. 202) should be developed and increased.

In contrast to the three previous sections about the challenges and positive and negative views, the keywords HRIA and HRDD have been mentioned quite often in connection with claims made. Interestingly, calls to implement *HRIA* as part of export support have been raised with regard only to the German ECA, with the exceptions of Krajewski and the UN independent expert who have both argued that ECAs should be required to conduct HRIsAs for all projects (United Nations, 2011, p. 8; Krajewski, 2017, p. 29). In the context of German export support, HRIsAs or similar should at least be carried out for category A projects⁹ (CorA, 2017, p. 10), though they may be carried out for all projects (Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, pp. 68, 77-78; Hamm, Scheper and Drebes, 2014, p. 44) or large export projects such as major infrastructure or dam construction, i.e., especially for project finance projects, or for all projects (Spieß, 2009, pp. 75–76; GegenStromung et al., 2013, p. 5; Papp, 2013, p. 326; Heydenreich and Paasch, 2017, p. 53).

While Scheper and Feldt have emphasised that no comprehensive, accepted, and standardised instruments for HRIA exist yet (Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 64), there is no common understanding among German authors as to whether the ECA or its clients must undertake HRIA. CorA as well as Scheper and Feldt do not specify this at all (Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, pp. 68, 77-78; CorA, 2017, p. 10; Heydenreich and Paasch, 2017, p. 53), but both alternatives are conceivable for Hamm et al. (Hamm, Scheper and Drebes, 2014, p. 31). For GegenStromung et al. and Papp, the German ECA must subject projects to HRIA (GegenStromung et al., 2013; Papp, 2013, p. 326), whereas Spieß has advised the ECA to evaluate the HRIA delivered by its client (Spieß, 2009, p. 75).

Finally, several sources have stated that ECAs should require their clients to undertake HRDD, including the Ruggie Framework (Human Rights Council, 2008a, p. 12; Amnesty International UK, 2013, p. 9; Buhmann, 2017, p. 250; Krajewski, 2017, p. 19). Several authors have emphasised that client HRDD should even be a prerequisite for any export support (De Schutter, Eide, *et al.*, 2012, p. 62; with a focus on the German ECA, see CorA. Corporate Accountability – Netzwerk für Unternehmensverantwortung, Forum Menschenrechte and VENRO Verband Entwicklungspolitik und humanitäre Hilfe, 2021; Wüdsch and Windfuhr, 2022, p. 59). Similarly, Scheper has suggested that a client's compliance with HRDD could be one criterion for ECA support (Scheper, 2017, p. 202).

Turning to Germany, this view has been supported by Hamm et al. who have asked for proof of this compliance (Hamm, Scheper and Drebes, 2014, p. 67), though without further

⁹ Projects with a potentially high negative environmental or social impact (see Chapter 2)

explaining what such proof would look like. In addition, Scheper and Feldt have also seen the obligation for HRDD to be the applicant's (Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 18), but they have also indicated that ECAs have an HRDD obligation of their own (ibid., p. 68). According to Heydenreich et al., the German ECA should review a client's HRDD (Heydenreich, Paasch and Kusch, 2014, pp. 7, 58), whereas other authors have demanded HRDD reports for all category A projects (CorA, 2017, p. 10; Heydenreich and Paasch, 2017, p. 53), without clearly explaining who must create or present them. Ruggie however has asked ECAs to practice HRDD and require it from projects or project sponsors (Ruggie, 2010b, pp. 4, 6). The UNGPs, or more concretely, GP 4, have gone one step further, stating that ECAs *and* their clients or projects should be required to HRDD (Office of the High Commissioner, 2011, p. 7, emphasis added).

Against this background, three issues relating to HRDD are striking. Firstly, there seems to be no unanimous opinion on what entities HRDD relates to (ECAs, their clients or foreign projects). Secondly, it is not clear when HRDD should occur. In this regard, the Common Approaches have also remained opaque when stating that in the case of "a high likelihood of severe project-related human rights impacts occurring, the environmental and social review of a project may need to be complemented by specific human rights due diligence" (OECD, 2016, p. 9). Examples of 'severe project-related human rights impacts' have been provided, but there is no explanation of what 'specific HRDD' is and 'high likelihood' mean.

While acknowledging that the revised Common Approaches, opposed their previous versions, require "some form of" HRDD from applicants (Human Rights Council, 2018, p. 19), the UN Working Group has pointed out in 2018 that most ECAs do not seem to be using the UNGPs in their decision-making (ibid., p. 18). Thirdly, a definition of HRDD with concrete instructions has not been provided by the literature reviewed. In this regard, Grabosch and Scheper have noted that in general, the particular meaning and scope of HRDD remains unresolved (Grabosch and Scheper, 2015, p. 8), whereas the Human Rights Council has particularly stated concerning ECAs that "specific methods for [HRDD] are left to the discretion of the individual export credit agencies" (Human Rights Council, 2018, p. 12).

This ambiguity exists for most of the requirements presented here. In sum, several claims have been made about ECAs in order to better address human rights issues. At the same time, only some advice on how human rights could be better integrated into the ECA business has been brought forward, Scheper and Feld and Hamm et al. being two examples of such. While Scheper and Feld have recommended several adjustments to the German ECA, they have not provided any information on the content and process of HRIA or HRDD, though mentioning both. A similar picture emerges from Hamm et al. whose definition of HRDD, including its application to only ECA clients, differs from the UNGPs (Hamm, Scheper and Drebes, 2014,

pp. 14, 67), and whose recommendations remain rather general (ibid., p. 67-68). Therefore, questions that principally remain unanswered are what concretely must or could be done to implement the UNGPs in the ECA context, where this is to be done and, in particular, how. That States and ECAs “should ensure that their practices are aligned with the UNGPs”, as the UN Working Group has stated (Human Rights Council, 2018, p. 19), is a view that seems to be widely shared, but how exactly this should be put into practice remains largely open.

3.10 Conclusion: State of Knowledge

Within the State-business nexus of GP 4, the UNGPs call on States to take “additional steps” to protect against human rights violations (Office of the High Commissioner, 2011, p. 6), but what these steps are about, remains open. Barnes has noticed that “there is nothing in scholarship that explicitly deals with this question” (Barnes, 2018, p. 52), which can be confirmed from this literature review. There is obviously a gap in research, which this research undertaking seeks to close.

Focusing on the ECA context, the key research question examined how business-related human rights impacts are addressed in the context of state ECAs, particularly the German ECA, in order to comply with the UNGPs, especially with regard to the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD. In order to answer this question, a very comprehensive approach was taken by first identifying and then analysing any literature and other sources of information that consider human rights or specifically HRDD implementation in the ECA context, as required by GP 4. Grey literature was deliberately considered in order to identify stakeholder views and to therefore fully show the complete state of knowledge.

After having identified and analysed current contributions to the above-mentioned research questions during the systematic literature review, no other research and methodologies were discovered that have dealt with the operationalisation of the UNGPs, or especially with GP 4, in the ECA context. Even though it was found that few sources directly relate to the application of the UNGPs to ECAs, the present literature review organises the relevant sources into four categories which appear repeatedly, namely, (1) challenges and difficulties regarding the consideration of human rights in the ECA context, (2) positive statements, (3) negative statements and (4) demands. The majority of the literature reviewed has been critical of how human rights are considered by ECAs. Several allegations came to light, including *that* human rights are insufficiently considered in this context, but there were fewer concrete proposals for *how* human rights can be better addressed in export support. Therefore, this final question remains unanswered.

It has been shown in this chapter that there is neither a common understanding among the range of ECA stakeholders across governments, ECA employees and clients, research and

science institutions or NGOs on how human rights are to be addressed, nor a shared agreement on what HRDD can look like in the ECA context. To date, the four questions on HRDD which guided the literature review (see section 3.7: (1) What is meant by HRDD in the context of state export credit guarantees? (2) What are the expectations (ideas, proposals, wishes, demands) towards HRDD in this regard? (3) Which elements of HRDD can be concluded from the sources? (4) What difficulties and limitations might exist concerning HRDD in the ECA business?) remain unanswered. Ruggie himself has admitted, in direct reference to ECAs, that his “suggestions leave important practical questions unanswered” (Ruggie, 2010b, p. 7).

While this gap concerns ECAs in general, this study focuses on the German ECA to examine how GP 4 responsibilities are implemented in practice, providing insights that may also be relevant to other state ECAs. This research undertaking is therefore of great relevance to close the aforementioned gap in research. Chapter 5 (Methodology) explains the envisaged steps which will be taken to explore expectations towards and possible elements of HRDD in export support, with the aim of developing a conceptual framework for HRDD in this regard. First, however, the theoretical framework underpinning this doctoral research is illustrated in the following Chapter 4.

Chapter 4: Theoretical Framework

4.1 Introduction

After critically reviewing the literature on human rights in export finance, a research gap was concluded in the previous Chapter 3. This chapter outlines the theoretical framework for this doctoral study to ensure a structured and systematic approach to investigating the research questions, thereby contributing to closing the identified gap in research. It begins by detailing the research aims and objectives, providing a clear direction for the study.

To understand how ECAs address business-related human rights impacts in line with the UNGPs, particularly regarding HRDD, it is necessary to consider the broader governance structures in which they operate. Governance theory provides the conceptual foundation for this thesis, as it explains how authority, responsibility and accountability are organised and exercised in complex policy environments such as export finance. Examining the evolution of governance helps clarify how the state's role in promoting and protecting human rights has changed as public functions increasingly depend on networks of governmental, private and international actors.

Accordingly, this chapter explains and discusses the theoretical approach underlying the research, commonly referred to as New Governance. It outlines the evolution of governance approaches from Traditional Public Administration (TPA) and New Public Management (NPM) to New Public Governance (NPG), before introducing Polycentric Governance as the framework used to analyse how ECAs address business-related human rights impacts in line with the UNGPs within a transnational, multi-actor governance system. Finally, the chapter presents the research concept in relation to New Governance and its relevance to the field of BHR.

4.2 Research Aims and Objectives

The research gap identified by the current research emphasises the need to answer the overall research question for this dissertation project of how business-related human rights impacts are addressed by state ECAs, particularly the German ECA, in order to comply with the UNGPs, especially regarding the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD. Consequently, the research aim of this thesis is to develop concrete proposals for implementing HRDD in public export credit guarantee schemes. This study therefore seeks to elaborate how ECAs and their clients (exporting companies and financing banks) address their human rights responsibilities pursuant to the UNGPs, i.e., to contribute to a definition of HRDD in the ECA context.

To reach this aim, the first objective was to review the literature on human rights in state foreign trade promotion with a focus on ECA support in order to (1) understand the challenges and difficulties regarding the consideration of human rights in the ECA context, (2) trace positive views by ECA stakeholders on how human rights are addressed, (3) trace negative ones, and (4) comprehend demands placed in this regard. Apart from this Literature Review which has just been presented and discussed in the previous chapter, the following two objectives will be taken:

- Analyse existing cases on human rights impacts at projects related to ECA support to find out whether and how adverse human rights impacts are connected to a specific industry, a specific country or a specific project, whether there are any correlations between these aspects, and what the most salient human rights risks are in the ECA context (Case Survey), and
- Interview ECA stakeholders with respective expertise in sustainability-related aspects of the ECA business (Expert Interviews).

These different research methods will be used to develop a conceptual framework for HRDD in public export credit guarantee schemes.

4.3 The Evolution of Governance

Understanding how ECAs address business-related human rights risks and impacts in line with the UNGPs requires situating them within the broader evolution of governance theory. Bevir (2011) observes that governments today operate in a far more interconnected environment than in the past (pp. 1, 9). They depend increasingly on organisations in civil society and are shaped by international and transnational linkages (ibid., p. 2). The public sector has therefore moved away from purely hierarchical bureaucracy (ibid., p. 1) and now works through markets and networks involving actors from the public, private, and voluntary sectors (ibid., p. 9). These wider developments provide the context for the different models of public governance discussed in the following sections.

4.3.1 Traditional Public Administration

The Traditional Public Administration (TPA) model, referred to by Osborne (2010) simply as Public Administration, represents the classical understanding of how the state governs and delivers public services (pp. 1-10). Dominant from the late nineteenth century through to the late 1970s and early 1980s (Osborne, 2010, p. 1), it embodies what Osborne describes as a “static and bureaucratic tradition” (ibid., p. 2) in which policies formulated at the political level were implemented through hierarchical administrative systems. It was defined by the hegemony of the public sector (ibid., p. 8). Its emphasis lay on policy creation and

implementation, and hierarchy served as the principal mechanism for resource allocation (ibid.).

Although Rhodes (1997) does not use the term Traditional Public Administration either, his description of governance captures features commonly associated with that tradition. He portrays a system in which power lies with the Prime Minister, Cabinet, and civil service (p. 6) and describes a unitary state with a strong executive (p. 13). Within this framework, politics and administration are clearly separated (ibid., p. 17), and authority is organised through formal structures and procedures. As the author explains, the classical institutional approach focuses on the rules, procedures, and formal organisation of government (ibid., p. 23).

While Rhodes' discussion is situated in the context of the British state, these characteristics reflect the hierarchical and rule-bound orientation associated with TPA, a bureaucratic system guided by formal rules and procedures and concerned with accountability through compliance with established processes (Osborne, 2010, pp. 2–3). Osborne (2010) further describes it through the “dominance of the ‘rule of law’” (p. 2), a “focus on administering set rules and guidelines” (ibid.), and the central role of bureaucracy in the delivery of public service (ibid., p. 3).

TPA reached its high point during “the era of the welfare state, when the state was confidently expected to meet all the social and economic needs of the citizenry” (ibid., p. 3). By the late 1970s, the TPA and welfare state model came under pressure as public needs began to outstrip the resources available to meet them (ibid.). Osborne (2010) notes that this tension, together with broader calls for reform, paved the way for the rise of New Public Management (p. 3). Rhodes (1997) likewise describes how the traditional hierarchical system of government faced increasing pressure for reform, opening the way for new managerial approaches (pp. 48-49).

4.3.2 New Public Management

New Public Management (NPM) replaced the TPA model as the dominant approach to public administration until the early twenty-first century (Osborne, 2010, p. 1). NPM introduced market-oriented practices and managerial principles into the public sector (Osborne, 2010, p. 8). Osborne describes this approach as prioritising economy and efficiency in service delivery and promoting the view that “the marketplace (...) provides the most appropriate place for the production of public services” (2010, p. 8). He further explains that NPM focuses on intraorganisational processes and management and that, within this model, the role of the state becomes primarily regulatory (ibid.) rather than directly involved in the provision of public services.

Rhodes (1997) illustrates in detail how these reforms transformed the operation of the public sector (pp. 48-49). He explains that NPM introduced private sector management methods into public administration, including explicit standards and measures of performance, managing by results, and the use of incentive structures (ibid.). NPM also promoted closeness to the customer, greater competition through contracting out, and ideas of consumer choice (ibid.). These elements reflected a broader emphasis on competition, markets, customers and outcomes and contributed to what he terms a transformation of the public sector and a move towards “less government but more governance” (Rhodes, 1997, p. 49). Rhodes (1997) uses the term “hollowing out of the state” (p. 17) to describe the relocation of governmental functions beyond the core executive, upward to the European Union, downward to special purpose bodies, and outward to various agencies (ibid.).

As Bevir (2011) further notes, NPM sought to make the culture of the public sector resemble that of private companies, embracing marketisation and performance incentives (p. 9). In doing so, it contributed to a broader shift from direct state provision to more complex governance arrangements involving markets, networks, and actors from the private and voluntary sectors (ibid.). However, Osborne (2010) emphasises that NPM has been criticised for its intraorganisational focus in an increasingly plural world and for its adherence to private sector techniques that have become outdated in the context of contemporary public services delivery and public policy implementation (p. 4). This criticism highlights the limits of NPM and points to the need for alternative approaches to public governance.

4.3.3 New Public Governance

New Public Governance (NPG) emerged as a response to the way both TPA and NPM miss key features of the complex, plural, and fragmented nature of contemporary public service delivery (Osborne, 2010, p. 7). Osborne describes these conditions in terms of a plural state, involving multiple actors, and a pluralist state, involving multiple processes (ibid.). He explains that NPG “captures the realities of public policy implementation and public service delivery within the plural and pluralist complexities of the state in the twenty-first century” (ibid.).

Osborne argues that NPG repositions this plural and pluralist state by shifting attention away from the intraorganisational processes and management practices under NPM (ibid., p. 8). Instead, NPG focuses on the interorganisational relationships through which public services are developed and delivered (ibid., p. 9). Osborne also notes that public service organisations interact with their wider environment (ibid.). This implies that their work requires engagement across organisational boundaries rather than relying solely on internal management (ibid., pp. 8-9). In these settings, accountability must be negotiated at the interorganisational and interpersonal level within networks (ibid., p. 9). These networks are rarely alliances of equals but are shaped by inequalities of power and by dispersed and sometimes contested value

bases (ibid.). Osborne emphasises that “NPG is both a product of and a response to the increasingly complex, plural and fragmented nature of public policy implementation and service delivery” (ibid.).

Rhodes’ account of governance reinforces this understanding. Although he does not use the term New Public Governance, his account of governance aligns closely with its core features. Rhodes (1997) conceptualises governance as “self-organizing, interorganizational networks characterised by interdependence, resource exchanges, rules of the game and significant autonomy from the state” (Rhodes, 1997, p. 15). He further notes that service delivery involves complex sets of organisations from the public, private, and voluntary sectors, with interorganisational linkages forming a defining feature of how services are provided (ibid., p. 51). Networks therefore consist of several interdependent actors engaged in delivering services across organisational boundaries, raising challenges for steering and accountability that cannot be addressed through hierarchical control or through NPM’s focus on internal organisational management (ibid., pp. 51, 55). This emphasis on interdependence aligns closely with Osborne’s distinction between NPM and NPG: while NPM relied on competitive relationships between independent units (Osborne, 2010, p. 8), NPG centres on interorganisational relationships and the forms of cooperation required among interdependent actors working within complex networks (ibid., p. 9).

Kennett (2010) also draws attention to the wider settings in which contemporary governance takes place. She notes that governance now involves a broad range of public and private actors, including states, international and regional organisations, professional and expert groups, civil society organisations and business actors (Kennett, 2010, p. 31). Kennett further observes that the increasing involvement of non-state actors in shaping norms and rules points to the emergence of what she terms “global public governance” (ibid.). This perspective complements the accounts of Bevir, Rhodes and Osborne by underlining that governance is exercised through interactions across multiple organisations and sectors and is no longer confined to hierarchical state structures.

4.4 Three Approaches within New Public Governance

Within NPG, several approaches have emerged that explain different forms of modern governance involving diverse public and private actors.

4.4.1 Co-Governance

Kooiman (2003) describes co-governance as a mode of governing that involves collaboration, co-operation and co-ordination between interacting parties at different levels of society (pp. 96–97). He links the emergence of this approach to a tendency towards increasing societal

interdependence and what he terms “interpenetration”, referring to the growing permeability of boundaries between state, market, and civil society (2003, p. 111). Co-governance therefore takes a horizontal form in which actors communicate, collaborate, or cooperate without a central or dominating governing actor (ibid., p. 97). It relies on the idea that actors pursue shared concerns and “do things together” (ibid., pp. 96, 112).

These observations are relevant for this research because ECAs operate within networks that include government ministries, financial institutions, exporters, and civil society actors. Such constellations resemble the mixed public-private networks that Kooiman identifies at the boundary between state and society, which have contributed to a shift from hierarchical to horizontal coordination in domestic governance settings (Kooiman, 2003, p. 106). At the same time, Kooiman’s discussion of co-governance is developed using examples drawn from domestic governance settings and national contexts in which actors operate within a shared institutional environment and interact in close organisational proximity (ibid., pp. 96-106, 111). Given the transnational character of export finance and the reliance on soft-law instruments such as the Common Approaches as well as the UNGPs, co-governance only partially reflects the conditions under which ECAs address business-related human rights risks.

4.4.2 Multi-Level Governance

Multi-level governance adds a vertical dimension to the way public authority is understood within NPG. Developed in the context of European integration, it challenges the assumption that national governments act as the exclusive centre of authority (Hooghe and Marks, 2001, p. 28). Instead, multi-level governance highlights that decision-making powers are shared across several territorial levels (ibid., p. 3). In the EU context, this involves subnational, national, and supranational levels (ibid., pp. 27, 3). These levels are interconnected rather than operating in isolation (ibid., p. 4). In this perspective, supranational bodies can shape policy outcomes independently of national governments (ibid., p. 3). As a result, policymaking becomes a coordinated process across overlapping jurisdictions (ibid., pp. 3-4).

This perspective is relevant for ECAs because their mandates and operations are shaped by both national and international expectations. While ECAs are domestic institutions accountable to their respective governments, their practices related to ESHR aspects are influenced by supranational frameworks such as the Common Approaches. They therefore operate within a system in which authority and accountability are shared vertically between national ministries and international rulemaking or standard setting bodies.

At the same time, multi-level governance mainly focuses on interactions between governmental actors at different territorial levels (Hooghe and Marks, 2001, pp. 3–4, 27) and does not address non-state actors such as private banks, exporting companies, and civil

society organisations. These actors play a central role in assessing and managing business-related human rights impacts in export credit practice though. Consequently, while multi-level governance helps explain how ECAs operate between domestic mandates and international frameworks, it does not capture the multi-actor setting in which ECAs are embedded.

4.4.3 Public Value Governance

Public Value Governance incorporates Moore's conception of public value as one of its foundations (Bryson, Crosby and Bloomberg, 2014, pp. 449–450). Bryson, Crosby and Bloomberg (2014) include Moore's public value theory within what they describe as "the emerging approach" (p. 449) to public administration and summarise Moore's strategic triangle which defines public value in terms of substantively valuable, legitimate and operationally feasible public action (Moore, 2013, pp. 102–105; Bryson, Crosby and Bloomberg, 2014, p. 449). In this view, what counts as public value is shaped by societal expectations about the outcomes public institutions should pursue and the standards they are expected to uphold (Bryson, Crosby and Bloomberg, 2014, pp. 446, 449–450).

Public Value Governance is relevant for ECAs because their role extends beyond pure export promotion to the evaluation of ESHR aspects in supported transactions. This reflects broader societal expectations about how public institutions should oversee the activities they support. From this perspective, addressing human rights and implementing HRDD can be understood as part of the public value ECAs are expected to safeguard.

At the same time, Bryson et al.'s discussion is grounded primarily in domestic governance settings where public institutions interact directly with citizens and societal stakeholders (*ibid.*, pp. 446-449). ECAs, by contrast, operate in a transnational context, whereas Public Value Governance is grounded in domestic public management settings. Public Value Governance highlights an important aspect of the public mandate under which ECAs operate, including expectations that they address ESHR aspects. But it only partially reflects the multi-actor, cross-border context in which ESHR decision-making in export finance takes place.

4.4.4 Interim Conclusion

Co-Governance, Multi-level governance, and Public Value Governance illustrate key strands within NPG, but their primarily domestic focus does not reflect the transnational and multi-actor setting in which ECAs operate. The next section therefore turns to Polycentric Governance as a more suitable framework for analysing how ECAs address business-related human rights impacts in line with the UNGPs.

4.5 Polycentric Governance

The limitations of Co-Governance, Multi-level Governance, and Public Value Governance in capturing the transnational, multi-actor and soft law-based environment in which ECAs operate point to the need for a framework suited to such conditions. Polycentric governance, developed most prominently by Elinor Ostrom and further elaborated by McGinnis and others, offers such an approach. It describes governance settings with “many centers of decision making that are formally independent of each other” (Ostrom, 2010, p. 552), which nonetheless “take each other into account” (ibid.), engage in “cooperative undertakings” (ibid.) and develop consistent patterns of interaction (ibid.). Such arrangements allow groups facing shared problems to address them in ways they “best see fit” (McGinnis, 2011, p. 1) and through “self-governance” (ibid.), rather than turning to a central authority (ibid., pp. 1-2). These features make polycentric governance well suited to analysing policy areas that extend beyond national borders and involve a wide range of actors and institutions.

4.5.1 Key Characteristics, Strengths, and Limitations

Polycentric governance involves multiple, formally independent centres of decision making that nonetheless interact through cooperation and stable patterns of coordination (Ostrom, 2010, p. 552). Such systems support innovation, learning, adaptation and cooperation across different scales, and enable actors to address shared problems through self-governance rather than immediate reliance on central authority (McGinnis, 2011, pp. 1–2). These features provide the basis for assessing the strengths and limitations of polycentric governance.

Research identifies several strengths of polycentric governance that build on its core characteristics. Carlisle and Gruby (2019) emphasise that systems with multiple decision-making centres can facilitate parallel experimentation and learning (p. 936), enabling actors to test approaches and adapt institutions to changing conditions (ibid.). Such arrangements can also create opportunities to correct imbalances of authority and limit the influence of opportunistic actors (ibid., p. 940). Network-based interactions further support cooperation, trust-building and stakeholder participation, as communication and deliberative exchange help develop shared understandings of problems and the social capital needed for coordinated action (Berardo and Lubell, 2016, pp. 738–740). Morrison et al. (2023) add that polycentric systems allow specialisation, tailoring interventions to local circumstances, and coordinating action across scales without relying on hierarchy (pp. 477-479). These strengths align with Ostrom’s (2010) emphasis on innovation, learning and cooperation across different levels of decision-making (p. 552), illustrating the potential of polycentric governance to address complex policy challenges.

At the same time, several limitations are identified in the literature. Carlisle and Gruby (2019) point out that traditional accountability mechanisms may be inadequate when authority is dispersed among many actors (p. 940), and that local actors may lack the capacity or authority to address transboundary problems (p. 934). McGinnis (2011) similarly highlights that coordination often involves high transaction costs (pp. 11, 14), that groups differ in their ability to mobilise and organise collective responses (p. 11), and that increasing institutional diversity can add complexity and cause confusion unless information is made accessible (pp. 11, 17-18). He also notes that self-governance is not automatic and requires sustained effort (p. 2, 4), and that structural biases may place certain groups at a disadvantage within polycentric systems (p. 9). Morrison et al. (2023) point to additional challenges, including fragmentation and inconsistent practices (p. 477), and emphasise that decentralisation and collaboration are “not a panacea” (p. 477) for contemporary governance problems (ibid.). Together, these limitations indicate that while polycentric arrangements offer flexibility, they also generate challenges for accountability, capacity and policy coherence, i.e. the alignment of policies and practices across different decision-making centres so that they support rather than contradict each other.

4.5.2 Interim Assessment

Taken together, these strengths and limitations indicate that polycentric governance does not operate in the absence of public authority but continues to involve the state alongside other actors. Public authorities remain one centre of decision-making among many rather than disappearing from governance altogether (Ostrom, 2010, p. 552). Scholarship highlights the ongoing need for coordination and coherence across interacting governance arrangements (Morrison et al., 2023, pp. 447–479).

Translated to the ECA context, national governments can be understood as occupying multiple functional roles within a polycentric governance system. They may act as gatekeepers by determining whether export credit support is granted and thereby linking access to public financial risk mitigation instruments to compliance with ESHR standards. Governments may also function as network managers by coordinating with other states at the OECD level, facilitating policy coherence, mutual learning and the diffusion of governance practices. In addition, states can assume an entrepreneurial role by contributing to the development and evolution of governance frameworks, for example by integrating emerging HRDD expectations into national ECA procedures. These roles illustrate that within polycentric governance systems, the state is not displaced but remains an important actor that shapes, coordinates and stabilises governance arrangements across institutional levels.

Polycentric governance provides a useful framework for analysing the governance environment in which ECAs operate. It captures the involvement of multiple actors, forms of

stakeholder engagement, the reliance on soft law instruments and the role of learning and cooperation across jurisdictions. These are all features that are central to understanding how ECAs address business-related human rights risks. At the same time, polycentric governance also highlights challenges such as accountability, coordination and uneven capacities, which are also known challenges in the context of BHR. The next section builds on these insights to examine how the UNGPs reflect this polycentric form of governance and what this means for ECAs in the field of BHR.

4.6 New, Global, Polycentric, and Transnational Governance

This research project is related to the so-called new governance theory, and, more precisely, to polycentric governance. The latter, the polycentric governance approach, is envisaged by the UNGPs (Augenstein, Dawson and Thielbörger, 2018, p. 1), aiming at better aligning the three different governance systems that shape corporate behaviour at the global level (Wolfsteller and Li, 2022, p. 8). According to Ruggie, (global) business conduct is in fact influenced by three different governance systems: a public governance system with domestic and international law, a civil governance system with stakeholders and related social compliance mechanisms, and a corporate governance system with elements of the two aforementioned governance systems (Ruggie, 2014, p. 9), but which predominantly consists of entrepreneurial self-regulation (Wolfsteller and Li, 2022, p. 8).

Moreover, Ruggie has claimed so-called “governance gaps” (Human Rights Council, 2008a, p. 3) stemming from globalisation as being responsible for the dilemma of negative business-related human rights impacts. These gaps “between the scope and impact of economic forces and actors, and the capacity of societies to manage their adverse consequences, (...) provide the permissive environment for wrongful acts by companies of all kinds without adequate sanctioning or reparation” (ibid.). Precisely a polycentric approach with various actors would be important to close these governance gaps (Hamm, 2022, p. 106). In order to “deal with global problems that can no longer be dealt with adequately at the national level” (ibid.), i.e. human rights impacts of multinational business activity that are not subject to international law; the absence of a government at the global level (Ruggie, 2014, p. 5); and only domestic law which does not cover misconduct by foreign subsidiaries (ibid., p. 9), the UNGPs “do not merely advocate a theory of polycentric governance; in part, they were produced through such means” (Ruggie, 2014, p. 10).

Hamm goes one step further and states that from Ruggie’s point of view, the UNGPs would not only relate to polycentric governance, but be “a prime example of successful polycentric *global* governance” (Hamm, 2022, p. 107, emphasis added). For the governance of the world economy with transnational companies’ global value and supply chains and networks, “new

forms of global governance, especially polycentric governance, are coming to the fore” (Hamm, 2016, p. 483). Ruggie and Sherman, on the other hand, note that the UNGPs “were conceived on the basis of a polycentric transnational governance mode” (Ruggie and Sherman, 2017, p. 925, emphasis added). But as Ruggie is purely referring to global governance in his article on his mandate as UN Special Representative of the Secretary-General and the eventual outcome of this task, the UNGPs (Ruggie, 2014), this will not be further distinguished here. The same applies to multi-level governance (see for example Methven O’Brien and Ford, 2019) whose further consideration and discussion would exceed the scope of this dissertation.

What all approaches have in common is that BHR governance goes beyond national borders. Ruggie, as a “prominent advocate of global governance” (Hamm, 2022, p. 114), refers to global governance as “an instance of governance in the absence of government” (Ruggie, 2014, p. 5). At the same time, he points out to its “weak system” (ibid.) and “serious problems” (ibid., p. 6), as described in the previous paragraph, and refers to the current (BHR) global governance research as “new governance theory” (ibid., p. 5). He explains that he uses new governance theory “broadly to encompass analyses premised on the relative absence of global legal and institutional hierarchy, coupled with understanding the governance roles played by nonstate actors as well as by normative and ideational factors” (ibid., FN 4, p.16). Although it is not clear from Ruggie himself whether he sees himself as a representative from new governance theory (Melish and Meidinger, 2012, p. 2), he relates the UNGPs to his understanding of new governance theory (Ruggie, 2014) and stresses that these can improve the functioning of the new governance (ibid., p. 8).

As Alexander states, new governance is described by scholars as “a variety of alternative approaches to regulation that eschew government mandated rules, norms and directives that are issued from the top down and are implemented primarily by governmental actors” (Alexander, 2009, p. 120). It evolved during the 1990s (Peters and Pierre, 2006, p. 6; Ruggie, 2014, p. 16) to provide domestic public services in coordination with social and market actors (Peters and Pierre, 2006, p. 5). According to Abbott and Snidal who relate new governance research to the international level and thereby adapt it to “transnational new governance” (Abbott and Snidal, 2009), new governance is difficult to define due to diverse practices (ibid., 508, see also various references to and examples of new governance instruments and approaches in e.g. public policy or as ecolabels in FN 31).

Therefore, there is also not one or the only new governance (Eberlein and Kerwer, 2004, p. 136). Often, new governance is characterised by its opposition to traditional forms of regulation, i.e. old governance, with a top-down and state-centric authority, and mandatory rules (Abbott and Snidal, 2009). The authors name four main features of new governance: State orchestration (i.e., although remaining a significant player, the State “authorizes,

empowers, and orchestrates the public and private actors and institutions to which it assigns regulatory responsibilities” (ibid., p. 544)); decentralised regulatory authority “with regulatory responsibilities shared among private actors as well as state agencies” (ibid., p. 524); dispersed expertise among different stakeholders (ibid., p. 234); and soft law rules (ibid.).

Especially from Abbott’s and Snidal’s elaborations on new governance, a clear link to the UNGPs can be seen. The UNGPs take different governance roles into account, namely that of states, but also of non-state actors. This is reflected in the UNGPs’ polycentric approach, which is equated with a co-governance one (McCorquodale and Nolan, 2021, p. 469), therefore aiming at achieving a more holistic governance picture (Voß and Schroth, 2018, p. 99) by engaging different actors and governance systems apart from local governments. Indeed, the UNGPs take the regulatory contributions of companies, (other) market and social actors explicitly into account (Ford and Nolan, 2020, p. 32). According to Ruggie, new governance theory “rests on the premise that the state by itself cannot do all the heavy lifting required to meet most pressing societal challenges” (Ruggie, 2014, p. 8), e.g. addressing negative business-related human rights impacts. Therefore, the State “needs to engage other actors to leverage its capacities” (ibid., p. 9).

The UNGPs precisely reflect this, emphasising not only the human rights responsibility of states but also the role of companies as well as of civil society – in other words, the actors who exercise power in the respective governance systems mentioned above. Involving all these actors both in the process of developing the UNGPs and in their function as “a new regulatory dynamic under which these [three] governance systems become better aligned in relation to business and human rights” (ibid.) can also be seen as counteracting the fact that individual state or company action would be “too constrained” (Human Rights Council, 2008a, p. 6) to reduce the governance gaps. “Recognizing that some business and human rights challenges require multi-stakeholder responses” (Human Rights Council, 2007, p. 16), Ruggie involved all relevant actors in the business and human rights debate when creating both the Ruggie Framework and the UNGPs and was thus able to achieve “thick stakeholder consensus” (Ruggie, 2014, p. 10). In doing so, new governance theory opposes the top-down and hierarchical old governance model (ibid., p. 8), and accordingly pluralistic regulatory systems in contrast to traditional state-centred ones (Melish and Meidinger, 2012, p. 15).

The pluralistic character of BHR governance already hinted at here several times is also taken up by Methven O’Brien and Ford (2019). BHR involves “new government and market actors into domestic human rights implementation” (Methven O’Brien and Ford, 2019, p. 216), i.e. “into the human rights dialogue, policy-making, and accountability frameworks” (ibid., p. 223). ECAs are highlighted as one example of new government actors that are involved in the discourse and practice of implementing human rights domestically, namely through BHR

(ibid.). By implementing and following the UNGPs, especially of course GP 4, at e.g. OECD or national state level, ECAs are thus integrated into the national human rights system (ibid.), which also contributes to its reorganisation (ibid., p. 230). Buhmann also points out that the duty to protect in BHR terms does not only concern the core organs of a State, but also, for example, ECAs, therefore “agencies that differ from those normally associated with human rights” (Buhmann, 2017, p. 236). In another article, she emphasises that involving key stakeholders and taking their interests into account is a way to effectively implement international policy and law on BHR challenges (Buhmann, 2013, p. 27).

4.7 Research Concept

This research project is placed precisely within the new governance framework presented here. It aims at achieving stakeholder consensus for a HRDD model in a polycentric approach, i.e., by involving the key stakeholders of Germany’s ECA in the process for its development. This approach therefore acknowledges the holistic governance structure of BHR in an area where BHR involves new government actors in the national human rights system, namely in state export promotion. In addition to the government (German ministries) or government-related agency (Euler Hermes), market (exporters and banks) and social actors (e.g. CSOs) are also involved as key stakeholders in the research undertaking. The procedure is therefore similar to that for policy formulation in new governance (Eberlein and Kerwer, 2004, p. 123), by participating private actors and by relying on broad consultation and substantive input of the stakeholders engaged. This is guided by Ruggie’s approach and aim of achieving “the broadest possible consensus among stakeholders” (Wolfsteller and Li, 2022, p. 7).

The (justified) criticism or expressed limitations of Ruggie’s theoretical thinking, the UNGPs or polycentric governance theory (Melish and Meidinger, 2012; Deva, 2021; McDonnell and Curphey, 2022; Wolfsteller and Li, 2022) do not oppose this research project because Germany or the German ECA (at the German level, e.g. through the NAP, but also within the OECD) is explicitly committed to implementing the UNGPs. Moreover, this research project can be distinguished from experimentalist governance theory, as it is about stakeholder participation, agreement on a broad problem definition and local contextualisation (Methven O’Brien, Ferguson and McVey, 2022, p. 71), but not about monitoring and peer review as well as periodic revision and learning (ibid.) as would be the case in experimentalist governance theory, in order to, for example, effectively adopt NAPs on implementing the UNGPs.

The epistemological and ontological points of view correspond to a pragmatic research paradigm (see Chapter 5): practical solutions are sought for, as the UNGPs and accompanying documents do not provide concrete recommendations for actions. After all, and as mentioned before, Ruggie himself told the OECD ECAs that his suggestions “leave important practical

questions unanswered” (Ruggie, 2010b, p. 7). This research undertaking is therefore of great relevance to close the aforementioned gap in research.

4.8 Conclusion

The theoretical framework presented here provides the foundation for understanding the key assumptions and constructs relevant to this research project. Its aims and objectives were highlighted: to develop concrete proposals for implementing HRDD in public export credit guarantee schemes by taking three objectives, namely a literature review on human rights in state foreign trade promotion, a case survey on human rights impacts at projects related to ECA support, and expert interviews with ECA stakeholders. In doing so, this doctoral thesis seeks to elaborate how ECAs and their clients can fulfil their responsibility to address business-related human rights pursuant to the UNGPs. The current research therefore aims at contributing to a definition of HRDD in the ECA context and thereby at closing the research gap identified in the literature review.

This chapter has demonstrated and critically examined the evolution of governance theory as the conceptual foundation for this study. It traced the shift from TPA through NPM to NPG and its core approaches co-governance, multi-level governance, and public value governance before extending these ideas to polycentric and transnational governance. These developments illustrate how the role of the state has shifted from a predominantly hierarchical authority to one that works within and alongside networks of public, private, and civil society actors.

New governance theory underlying this doctoral research was demonstrated and critically examined. As shown, the UNGPs are related to new governance thinking and, at the same time, reflect a polycentric approach by moving away from traditional top-down governance models and instead involving the various actors within the three governance systems that shape business conduct. States, companies, and civil society are all considered relevant to closing the governance gaps that enable negative business-related human rights impacts to occur. The discussion also showed that polycentric governance provides a suitable analytical framework for understanding how authority is distributed, how responsibility and accountability are allocated and exercised across actors, and how coordination is achieved in the governance environment in which ECAs address business-related human rights risks.

This chapter has illustrated that the current doctoral research is placed precisely within the new governance framework as it aims at achieving stakeholder consensus for a HRDD model in a polycentric approach, by involving the key stakeholders of Germany’s ECA in the process for its development. These stakeholders can be categorized according to the actors in the

three governance systems mentioned above. Depicted here, the research concept is therefore consistent with the pluralistic character of BHR.

In summary, this chapter established the conceptual and theoretical foundation for the thesis. It also clarified the role of governance theory in shaping the approach taken in this research. The theoretical framework outlined thus guides the research methodology, including its design and strategy, which is the subject of the following chapter. This Chapter 5 (Methodology) explains the envisaged steps which will be taken to explore expectations towards and possible elements of HRDD in export support, with the aim of developing a conceptual framework for HRDD in this regard.

Chapter 5: Methodology

5.1 Introduction

This doctoral study explored how human rights are addressed in the ECA context in order to implement the UNGPs and especially HRDD. As State agencies, ECAs provide substantial support for export projects and are explicitly mentioned in GP 4: the HRDD of both ECAs and their clients (exporting companies and financing banks) or foreign projects receiving ECA support is emphasised and identified as important (GP 4, Office of the High Commissioner, 2011, pp. 6–7). At the same time, however, the literature review has shown that the UNGPs and accompanying documents do not further specify how HRDD and the UNGPs in general are to be implemented in the context of foreign trade promotion. There is neither a uniform definition of HRDD nor are there clearly defined requirements for HRDD and its elements in that framework.

It is therefore relevant to address this gap in knowledge, which this doctoral project aimed to contribute to filling. Taking Germany as an example (see reasons listed under 1.3), the research setting was government-supported international business activity, focusing on export credit guarantee schemes delivered by ECAs. The aim was to elaborate how ECAs can fulfil their responsibility to respect human rights pursuant to the UNGPs, i.e., to contribute to a definition of HRDD and to elaborate concrete proposals for realising HRDD in the ECA context.

Within the framework of implementing the UNGPs in the context of state ECAs, the overall research question for this research project was:

- How are business-related human rights impacts addressed by state ECAs, particularly the German ECA, in order to comply with the UNGPs, especially regarding the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD?

To answer the said research question, several sub-questions were formulated, from a more general view on what the UNGPs actually require, through how stakeholders believe human rights should be implemented, to the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD. Several objectives were taken to address the research questions, namely a literature review, a case survey, and expert interviews.

This chapter covers the research assumptions and paradigm, theoretical framework, and methods used in order to answer the above-mentioned research questions. It explains the steps taken to investigate these questions by outlining the methodological approach, research design, and research strategy, following the so-called "Research Onion" (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 130) and the aspects the authors deem necessary to be considered in the

methodology section (ibid., p. 717). The methodological limitations, including potential biases and the role of the researcher, are also addressed. A final conclusion summarises this chapter.

5.2 Research Design

This section outlines the overall strategy for answering the research question stated above.

5.2.1 Research Philosophy

The research philosophy underpinning this research project or “worldview”, as Creswell and Creswell have pointed out (Creswell and Creswell, 2018, p. 5), was a pragmatic one. Pragmatism, as a research paradigm, focuses on practical solutions and outcomes for the topic and problem researched (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019, p. 17; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 151). In pragmatist research, the primary factors shaping the research design and strategy are the research problem that the researcher aims to address, and the research question which emphasises a pragmatic focus on practical outcomes (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 151). This research project followed precisely this pragmatic approach. It aimed at tackling real-world issues (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019, p. 4), such as the need to (better) address human rights in export finance. At the same time, the overall research question focused on delivering actionable outcomes, namely the development of a conceptual framework for HRDD in this context.

All research paradigms have philosophical assumptions in common (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019, p. 1). These will be looked at in relation to this research project and from the perspective of the pragmatic research philosophy, by following Saunders et al.’s and Creswell and Plano Clark’s discussions (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p. 42; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, pp. 144–145, 150–151).

5.2.1.1 *Ontology*

Ontology refers to the nature of reality (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 133). In a pragmatic approach, research stresses the practical consequences (ibid., p. 151) where reality is shaped by the practical outcomes of ideas (ibid.). Reality is seen as both singular and multiple (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p. 42) and therefore opposed to being a fixed entity. Research aims to find practical solutions in order to change and improve the situation being studied (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019, p. 5). In the setting of this PhD project, these elaborations mean to take human rights aspects into account in export finance and thereby to improve the way human rights are addressed, but also to improve the human rights situation at projects in destination countries for German exports. The research undertaking aimed at practical implications where knowledge should be examined by using the best suited tools (see 5.2.1.2

(Epistemology); Creswell and Creswell, 2018, p. 10) to suggest how human rights could and should be addressed in the ECA context to comply with the UNGPs.

5.2.1.2 Epistemology

Epistemology concerns the fundamental foundations of knowledge (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p. 5), the way through which knowledge can be acquired (ibid; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 134), and the relationship between the researcher and what is being researched (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p. 42). A key principle of pragmatic epistemology is that knowledge is invariably derived from experience (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019, p. 4). From a pragmatic perspective, knowledge should be examined using the tools best suited to solve the research issue (Creswell and Creswell, 2018, p. 10), while targeting practical meaning, problems, practices and relevance (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 145).

Data collection is characterised by practicality, i.e. in a "what works" approach (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, pp. 42–43). Both the case survey and the expert interviews supported this research goal and approach, by directly engaging with real-world contexts, practical insights, and expertise to enhance the credibility and practicality of the research findings. Together with the literature research, the research question was addressed in a way that worked best, by employing diverse approaches and both objective and subjective knowledge (ibid., p. 43) in order to generate a practical and useful solution for understanding and implementing HRDD in the ECA context.

5.2.1.3 Methodology

The methodology refers to the process of research (ibid., p. 42) and methods applied to answer the research question, including the theoretical and philosophical assumptions (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 808). Pragmatism is linked to mixed methods as it allows for a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, pp. 42–43), guided by the research problem and research question (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 144). The objective is to choose the method that best advances the research (ibid., p. 151) and leads to practical results (ibid., 145). Mixed methods research combines quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques and analysis within a single research undertaking (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 181).

In seeking to find methods which fit to the above-mentioned research topic, and which made the most sense to answer the overall research question in a practical and applied way (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p. 44), data was gathered from the literature review and the case survey as secondary sources of information. Conversely, primary data was generated through exploratory qualitative research conducted via expert interviews. Therefore, data

generation took place mainly from qualitative research but also included quantitative elements from the case survey analysis, i.e. a mixed methods approach was applied (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p. 2; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 181).

Consisting of a meta-analysis of existing cases (Peterson, 2020, p. 67) which report on human rights violations in the context of ECA-related projects, the aim of the case survey was to find out whether there are connections and patterns between, for example, a country and an industry sector in concrete human rights violations. The purpose of this approach was to gain a broad understanding of the research problem (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p. 104), i.e., the consideration of human rights in state export finance, through quantitative data and its subsequent analysis (ibid.). The succeeding qualitative data collection, through expert interviews, was informed by the literature review and the case survey analysis, allowing for an in-depth exploration of participants' perspectives on the findings (ibid.). The data generation methods are discussed in more detail below (see 5.3.3).

5.2.1.4 Axiology

Axiology concerns the role of values in the research process (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p. 42; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 145). In a pragmatic approach, the researcher's own values and experiences play a crucial role (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019, p. 5; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 145). This allows for a reflexive approach (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 145), where the researcher incorporates both unbiased and biased perspectives (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p. 42). Reflexivity is a core characteristic of qualitative research (Creswell and Creswell, 2018, p. 200) which formed a significant part of primary data generation and analysis.

The researcher's own values, experiences, doubts and beliefs (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 145) played a crucial role: as a former sustainability advisor at the German ECA, she was responsible for the topic of human rights. The relevance and necessity for her research undertaking arose out of her work at that time, when she realised that certain questions regarding the operationalisation of the UNGPs in general and HRDD in specific existed, but that she could not answer them within the framework of her everyday work. The author's prior work and working relationships have therefore informed the research process as well as the research agenda, as have active consultations with some of the people working in the field of BHR and especially in sustainability and, more concretely, human rights in export finance.

Hence, the researcher recognised that she had an impact on her research and that the research had an impact on her. At the same time, it must be stressed that the author was aware of possibly being an insider researcher (Fleming, 2018) to some degree. She already had a solid knowledge of state promotion with its internal and external processes and knew

some of the stakeholders and their positions – although not always personally – who she planned to approach during the qualitative research. This prior experience informed her initial understanding of which actors might be relevant, while the final identification of stakeholder groups was based on the literature review. It also meant that some roles and institutional structures were familiar from previous cooperation in the field. However, some of these aspects were part of the ethics application for this doctoral study, which was approved by the UWS ESS Ethics Committee, as pointed out in section 5.3.1. Throughout the research process, the researcher sought to mitigate possible biases arising from this positionality by ensuring that all stakeholder groups identified through the literature review were included in the study, by reflecting on her own assumptions when interpreting the data, and by discussing methodological choices with her supervisory team.

5.2.2 Research Type and Underlying Theory

As the research aimed at exploring expectations towards and possible elements of HRDD in export support with the aim of developing a conceptual framework for HRDD, an inductive approach was utilised. Themes were worked out from three data sources, namely the literature review, the case survey, and the expert interviews. Creswell and Creswell describe the latter approach as the “inductive logic of research in a qualitative study” (Creswell and Creswell, 2018, pp. 63–64). Information was mainly gathered directly from the subject (Creswell and Creswell, 2018, p. 4) by the researcher herself via one qualitative research method, namely the expert interviews. On the other hand, the qualitative research method was preceded by two secondary research methods, i.e. the literature review and the case study analysis. Both the primary and the secondary data generation can be attributed to exploratory research (ibid., p. 104).

The research project was based on the so-called new governance theory, and, more precisely, on polycentric governance (see Chapter 4). According to Ruggie, (global) business conduct is influenced by three different governance systems: a public governance system with domestic and international law, a civil governance system with stakeholders and related social compliance mechanisms, and a corporate governance system with elements of the two aforementioned governance systems (Ruggie, 2014, p. 9). Moreover, Ruggie has claimed so-called “governance gaps” (Human Rights Council, 2008a, p. 3) stemming from globalisation as being responsible for the dilemma of negative business-related human rights impacts.

These gaps “between the scope and impact of economic forces and actors, and the capacity of societies to manage their adverse consequences, (...) provide the permissive environment for wrongful acts by companies of all kinds without adequate sanctioning or reparation” (ibid.). Precisely a polycentric approach with various actors would be important to close these governance gaps (Hamm, 2022, p. 106). In order to “deal with global problems that can no

longer be dealt with adequately at the national level” (ibid.), i.e., human rights impacts of multinational business activity on the one hand that are not subject to international law; the absence of a government at the global level (Ruggie, 2014, p. 5); and only domestic law which does not cover misconduct by foreign subsidiaries (ibid., p. 9), the UNGPs “do not merely advocate a theory of polycentric governance; in part, they were produced through such means” (Ruggie, 2014, p. 10).

Guided by Ruggie’s thinking of new governance theory, the UNGPs take different governance roles into account, namely that of states, but also of non-state actors, which is reflected in the UNGPs’ polycentric approach. According to Ruggie, new governance theory “rests on the premise that the state by itself cannot do all the heavy lifting required to meet most pressing societal challenges” (Ruggie, 2014, p. 8), e.g. addressing negative business-related human rights impacts. Therefore, the state “needs to engage other actors to leverage its capacities” (ibid., p. 9).

The UNGPs reflect precisely this, emphasising not only the human rights responsibility of states but also the role of companies as well as of civil society – in other words, the actors who exercise power in the respective governance systems mentioned above. Involving all these actors both in the process of developing the UNGPs and in their function as “a new regulatory dynamic under which (...) [the three] governance systems become better aligned in relation to business and human rights” (ibid.) can also be seen as counteracting the fact that individual state or company action would be “too constrained” (Human Rights Council, 2008a, p. 6) to reduce the governance gaps.

“Recognizing that some business and human rights challenges require multi-stakeholder responses” (Human Rights Council, 2007, p. 16), Ruggie involved all relevant actors in the business and human rights debate when creating both the Ruggie Framework and the UNGPs and was thus able to achieve “thick stakeholder consensus” (Ruggie, 2014, p. 10). In doing so, new governance theory opposes the top-down and hierarchical old governance model (ibid., p. 8). This research project was situated precisely within his new governance framework and aimed to achieve stakeholder consensus for a HRDD model in a polycentric approach, by involving all ECA stakeholders in the process for its development.

5.3 Research Strategy

To develop a conceptual framework for HRDD in the ECA context to which the above-mentioned different stakeholders have agreed upon, a sequential explanatory design according to Creswell and Creswell’s mixed method research approach (Creswell and Creswell, 2018) was chosen, as shown in the following Figure 11. The contents of this design are described below.

Figure 11: Research strategy and design

Source: Johanna Imiela

After reviewing the literature on human rights, the UNGPs, and HRDD in the context of state foreign trade promotion and especially export finance (Literature Review), it was clear that there was a gap in research on how human rights could be (better) addressed in the ECA context. At the same time, the need to explore expectations towards and possible elements of HRDD in export support was scientifically proven. In order to collect data in a narrower sense, i.e. beyond literature research and analysis, existing cases studies and reports on human rights impacts at projects related to ECA support were researched and analysed in a subsequent step (Case Survey) – on negative impacts only as no positive examples were found.

Through the explorative approach that followed as the next research step, namely Expert Interviews (the participants of which were representatives of the different stakeholder groups of the German ECA), the difficulties in the implementation of the UNGPs were better understood and the necessary HRDD of an ECA developed and defined. Since the Case Survey, with its quantitative research about patterns across the different cases reported (Petersen, 2020, p. 78), preceded the qualitative research, and its results flowed into the latter, a sequential explanatory design was applied which is summarised in the following Figure 12.

Figure 12: Sequential explanatory design

Source: Johanna Imiela, inspired by Creswell and Cresswell (2018, pp. 15, 218, 238)

Consequently, for a deeper understanding of the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD in the ECA context and therefore to achieve the research objective of elaborating concrete proposals for implementing HRDD, different methods were used. While the case survey employed quantitative data collection and analysis, the expert interviews formed the qualitative data collection (Creswell and Creswell, 2018, p. 188). This mixed methods design of the research undertaking served to triangulate data from several sources, aiming at generating a deeper and more multi-layered understanding of the research context (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 218).

Triangulation refers to the use of both multiple data sources and multiple data collection methods in order to ensure the validity, credibility and authenticity of research findings (ibid; Green, 2008b, p. 157). In this study, the conceptual framework for HRDD was developed from three data sources which also formed the data collection methods (i.e., literature review, case survey, and the ECA stakeholders who were interviewed as experts where a proposal for HRDD developed up to that point and refined through the interviews was agreed to). The choice of the research methods applied as well as the sampling of the participants at the qualitative stages (see below) were guided by this multi-perspective approach of triangulation to validate all data gathered (Green, 2008a, p. 157; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p. 62).

Since the start of her PhD project, the researcher has, as already mentioned, actively exchanged ideas with experts in the field, some of whom she contacted quite deliberately. Several of these experts also came from the academic field, so that the exchange was not only of a substantive nature but also concerned the scientific approach. The researcher also utilised HAW Hamburg colloquia for review and quality control of her research methods and methodological approach, then with PhD candidates from outside the BHR discipline.

5.3.1 Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for the qualitative part of this study at hand was granted on 28 February 2022 by the two Co-Chairs of the ESS Ethics Committee, provided by few conditions to be met when

planning and undertaking the expert interviews (see Appendix B). With regard to the questionnaire, for example, the researcher was advised to give only a general time direction for the overall interview duration instead of defining time frames for the individual interview topics. Moreover, the importance of achieving unbiased, authentic responses from the interviewees instead of providing leading questions or statements was emphasised and kept in mind by the researcher.

The topics of access and recruitment of the intended sample size, including the respective documentation, were also pointed out. The researcher discussed these conditions with her supervisors. She slightly adapted the interview questionnaire according to the requirements and presented a plan with possible alternatives in terms of the number and distribution of the intended interview participants to the supervisory team. An Excel spreadsheet was used to manage the recruitment of interview participants and, if needed, to identify additional candidates. The spreadsheet also tracked scheduled interview dates and recorded when each interview was completed. Against this background, the HAW Hamburg waived an own ethics application by the researcher on 6 April 2022.

5.3.2 Time Horizon and Language

Data was generated at one point in time or over a short period of time respectively, and the time horizon was therefore cross-sectional (Creswell and Creswell, 2018, p. 149). The fact that the literature review extended over several months, starting in 2018 and continuing until the end of the doctoral project, does not contradict this. New literature on the research topic was continually sought, and relevant events on BHR were attended throughout this period. The timeline did not include a developmental component, as seen in longitudinal research (*ibid.*, p. 12). Instead, it reflected the extensive scope of the literature review and analysis, which required considerable time. This duration was further extended due to the one-year interruption by parental leave in 2019/2020.

The same cross-sectional time horizon applied to the case study analysis, which took mainly place within a short period of time in 2021. Subsequently, the search for cases of human rights violations in the ECA context was maintained through the existing alerts on Google and Google Scholar for the ongoing literature review and, for example, the continuous reading of subscribed newsletters. By the end of this doctoral project, however, only one additional case was identified and subsequently included in the case survey. The generation of primary data justifies the cross-sectional research approach more clearly: the expert interviews were conducted consecutively over a period of 16 weeks between March and July 2023.

All quotes mentioned in this study were translated into English by the researcher independently and with AI support (DeepL, Google Translate).

5.3.3 Data Generation Methods

As already pointed out above, data was initially gathered through secondary research, followed by the generation of primary data via a qualitative research method.

5.3.3.1 Literature Review

The first method of secondary data generation was the literature search and analysis, i.e., the Literature Review. Based on previously defined inclusion and exclusion criteria, sources on how human rights are considered in state-promoted export finance were reviewed, looking at e.g. legal literature, business sources, the United Nations, the OECD, academia, NGOs, and the German government and ECA. The results of the literature review were presented and discussed on the basis of four categories derived from the research, namely challenges and difficulties, positive points of view, negative points of view, and demands raised.

As shown in Chapter 3, the findings of the systematic literature review are presented and discussed in detail there. The review revealed a clear research gap on how human rights and HRDD are addressed in the ECA context, and it also helped to identify the different ECA stakeholder groups and their respective perspectives.

5.3.3.2 Case Survey

After the literature review had revealed a large majority of critical literature on human rights in export finance, an analysis of existing cases on human rights impacts at projects related to ECA support was conducted. The results of this case survey should contribute to answering how human rights can be better considered in the ECA context, by understanding and pointing out central human rights risks and impacts in this framework (Abrahams and Wyss, 2010, p. 25). On the one hand, certain constellations that lead to concrete human rights violations in export finance were to be identified, for example, related to a specific country and an industry sector. On the other hand, the survey also aimed to identify positive examples that favour the protection of human rights, i.e. where ECAs positively impacted the mitigation or prevention of such violations, as this could also feed into the proposal for HRDD. The aim of this approach was to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the research problem, i.e. the consideration of human rights in state export finance, by collecting and analysing quantitative data (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p. 104).

This case survey followed as the second step of secondary data generation in order to find out whether and how adverse human rights impacts are connected to a specific industry, a specific country or a specific project (Chapter 6). Additionally, the case analysis aimed to identify the most salient human rights risks in the ECA context, which could help in prioritising action for preventing and mitigating adverse human rights impacts as part of HRDD in accordance with

GP 24 (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 26). These findings could be incorporated into the envisaged proposal for HRDD of ECAs and their clients,

The source for this survey were existing case studies and reports on human rights impacts at projects related to ECA support. Similar to the literature review, these cases were found via a broad search and selected on the basis of predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria, whereby the criteria for including cases were significantly less than exclusion criteria. In this context, for example, at least one ECA had to be mentioned by name, while the place or time of publication was irrelevant because the case survey looked at human rights violations in the context of ECA projects, i.e. independent of e.g. international agreements or the UNGPs. It was therefore important that the cases included precisely ECA-related projects and not state support for foreign direct investment projects.

The analysis was done both in a quantitative and qualitative way: statements on human rights violations were assigned to the IBHR (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, no date b) and the core conventions of the ILO (International Labour Organization, no date), and all findings (including the project industry and country as well as the people affected) were recorded in an Excel table and empirically analysed. Both the frequency and variability were measured, not any tendencies. Therefore, a descriptive statistic method was applied (Creswell and Creswell, 2018, p. 173). In the end, a graphic evaluation according to various aspects, such as concrete human rights topics related to different industry sectors, summarised the findings.

The results of the case study were considered important topics for the interviews and therefore incorporated into the development of the respective questionnaire (see below): On the one hand, related to prioritised action to prevent or mitigate negative human rights impacts in the ECA context. On the other hand, the case survey highlighted that international human rights can be broad and encompass multiple human rights issues. It was consequently concluded to ask the interview participants whether specifying detailed human rights aspects would enhance understanding and improve the approach to addressing human rights in export finance.

Therefore, the human rights issues identified in the case survey contributed to answering how human rights are addressed in the ECA context and where there is a need for improvement. Moreover, it helped filling the proposal for HRDD with concrete content, even though a matrix representing critical constellations of a project country and sector leading to a concrete human rights violation did not result from the case survey for lack of reported cases.

5.3.3.3 Expert Interviews

As this doctoral study specifically sought to understand the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD, the range of ECA stakeholders across governments, ECA employees

and clients, research and science institutions as well as CSOs was finally approached as experts, by means of semi-structured interviews. These interviews were the main qualitative method of primary data generation and took place in the form of expert interviews. This interview form was chosen over elite interviews not only because the researcher is part of the European and particularly German-speaking research community where expert interviewing is commonly utilised (Bogner, Littig and Menz, 2014, p. 5; Petintseva, Faria and Eski, 2020, p. 9).

In the interviews conducted, the emphasis was placed less on power, authority, social position, and status, which are typical focal points of elite interviews (Petintseva, Faria and Eski, 2020, pp. 10–11). Instead, the primary focus was on the interviewees’ knowledge (Bogner, Littig and Menz, 2014, p. 9; Petintseva, Faria and Eski, 2020, p. 9) about the ECA context. The goal was to gather insights from individuals with expertise in specific societal contexts and who have privileged access to particular information (ibid.), i.e., on the one hand, related to the federal government’s export credit guarantee funding scheme, but of course also to sustainability and specifically human rights aspects in this regard.

Since the expert interviews constitute the primary data collection and the core of this work, especially with regard to the original contribution to knowledge, they will be discussed in more detail below.

5.4 Expert Interviews: In-Depth Exploration

20 ECA stakeholders were interviewed as experts, categorised in Table 8.

Table 8: Interview participants

Stakeholder Group	Number of Representatives
German ECA	2
Exporters	4
Banks	3
The Government Level	3
Business Associations and Networks	2
Science and Research Institutions	3
Trade Unions	1
NGOs	2

Source: Johanna Imiela

The following sub-sections discuss the expert interviews in more detail, including their structure, the selection of participants, and how the interviews were conducted and analysed.

5.4.1 Structure and Questionnaire

The form of the interviews was semi-structured. This means that an interview guide with set questions was used to ensure that similar data could be collected from all participants (Green, 2008a, pp. 53–54; Bogner, Littig and Menz, 2014, pp. 27–29). However, the researcher had the flexibility to enquire about further information (*ibid.*) and therefore to explore relevant topics in greater depth based on the interviewees' responses. The key themes and general issues of both the literature review and the case survey were taken when developing the set of questions which guided the planned interviews (see interview questionnaire (Appendix C) and preceded mind map (Appendix D)).

The construction of the questionnaire followed the recommendations developed by Bogner, Littig and Menz and Gläser and Laudel (Gläser and Laudel, 2010, pp. 144–149; Bogner, Littig and Menz, 2014, p. 61). For example, a warm-up entry question and an exit question framed the interviews. After conducting three mock interviews to test the feasibility of the questionnaire (Bogner, Littig and Menz, 2014, p. 34) and having the questionnaire cross-checked by another doctoral student experienced in qualitative research and familiar with the topic of BHR, the researcher made slight adaptations based on the feedback received (*ibid.*). The original time frame proved too long, and the interview framework seemed very complex and extensive, so it was decided to omit sections on basic assumptions and previous research results. Instead, key aspects derived from prior research were provided, allowing more room for interviewees to explore and discuss these points.

As part of the interviews, the researcher presented the interviewees with a draft graphic proposal for possible elements of HRDD at the level of the German ECA (see interview questionnaire, Appendix C). The interviewees were asked to comment on as a kind of brainstorming exercise in order to find out what could be included in the individual elements, which were considered particularly important, and which required further consideration. The draft framework was based on an adapted version of the OECD Due Diligence Guidance for Responsible Business Conduct (OECD, 2018a, p. 21) and served as an anchor to structure the interviews and explore whether and how these elements would need to be refined in the ECA context. The interview questions were designed to elicit feedback on the draft model and thereby informed subsequent adjustments to the proposed framework.

This was followed by a discussion of individual topics that the researcher had identified based on her previous research, such as the much-disputed issue of transparency, the topic of ECAs and Remedy as well as the complaint mechanism specifically defined by the German NAP for foreign trade promotion projects.

5.4.2 The Sampling Strategy and Process

As a first step in the sampling process, a map of the German ECA's stakeholder groups was created (see Figure 13), which became apparent during the Literature Review (Bogner, Littig and Menz, 2014, p. 35).

Figure 13: Stakeholder groups I

Source: Johanna Imiela

The government level included the four ministries that make up the IIMC which decides on the cover policy and the acceptance of an application for export credit guarantees for export transactions,¹⁰ and the OECD, of which Germany is a member. Not all IMC ministries had to be included in the study as there were enough participants representing the government level. Further data collection in the ministerial sphere would have been redundant, a phenomenon that is referred to as “data saturation” (Hennink, Kaiser and Marconi, 2017). A discussion of the challenges in applying data saturation in qualitative studies, i.e. not founded in a grounded theory approach where it originates from (ibid.), can, for example, be found in Hennink et al. and Hennink and Kaiser (Hennink, Kaiser and Marconi, 2017; Hennink and Kaiser, 2022).

¹⁰ See Chapter 2

From the ranks of the opposition parties in the national parliament of the Federal Republic of Germany, the Bundestag, minor or major interpellations are repeatedly put to the federal government, and, in the context of foreign trade promotion, target the consideration of ESHR aspects in this regard (e.g., Dörr-Voß, 2020). These interpellations are an instrument of control and scrutiny of the Bundestag against the German government (*German Bundestag - Instruments of scrutiny*, no date); accordingly, they contain critical questions or a critical point of view of the questioner. As CSOs also approach the federal government from such a standpoint, for example by means of publications, statements and case studies, it was considered sufficient to see the group of CSOs as the more important one due to reasons of data saturation as described above, and thus the Bundestag was dropped as an important stakeholder for this research project.

In addition, against the background of the topic of access to the field (see below), it was assumed that NGOs act as proxies of those affected on the ground, i.e. the Rights Holders in the countries hosting the projects to which German exporters deliver. An example of this assumption can be derived directly from the German ECA context: in connection with their critical reporting on export credit guarantees for the Colombian dam project Hidrosogamoso, some German NGOs invited representatives of a Colombian environmental movement to Berlin and supported them in speaking, among other things, at today's BMWK on human rights violations at the dam project (Seufert, 2015; 'Hermesbürgschaft für kolumbianischen Staudamm in der Kritik', no date; 'VerDAMMT zur Entwicklung? Veranstaltung am 4.11.2015 mit kolumbianischem Aktivisten', no date). Moreover, the German Supply Chain Act includes representative (e.g. NGO) action on behalf of affected people (Division 3, Section 11, The Bundestag, 2021). It was therefore decided to also drop the Rights Holders in project countries as stakeholders, and the following overview (Figure 14, Stakeholder Groups II) was drawn.

Figure 14: Stakeholder groups II

Source: Johanna Imiela

In a next step, the ECA clients were divided into the different stakeholder groups exporters and banks, and NGOs were distinguished from trade unions. Together with the ECA and its staff itself, eight stakeholder groups were finally identified as important stakeholders for this research undertaking, namely

- (1) The German ECA
- (2) Exporters
- (3) Banks
- (4) The Government Level
- (5) Business Associations and Networks
- (6) Science and Research Institutions
- (7) Trade Unions and
- (8) NGOs.

These stakeholder groups (Stakeholder Groups III), which ultimately emerged as relevant for this research project, are shown in the following Figure 15.

Figure 15: Stakeholder groups III

Source: Johanna Imiela

The individual representatives of these eight stakeholder groups were selected with purpose (Creswell and Creswell, 2018, p. 185), based on their respective expertise in sustainability-related aspects of the ECA business. The findings of the literature research were helpful in obtaining specific institutions and personal names (see Chapter 3). In addition, documentation that was compiled as part of the German NAP was also used, for example (Arbeitsstab Wirtschaft und Menschenrechte im Auswärtigen Amt, 2015). Therefore, non-probability sampling took place (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 315). The researcher's prior professional experience at the German ECA informed her understanding of the institutional landscape and supported the identification of relevant stakeholder groups. This positionality may have shaped the initial sense of which actors appeared relevant to the study. However, the final sample was based on the full range of stakeholder groups identified in the literature review rather than on existing professional contacts.

In order to ultimately achieve results from the interviews that are suitable for decision-making and to achieve an equal distribution of participants, the original aim was to interview three participants of each group, hence 24 experts in total. With the aim of offering a complete and

comprehensive picture, it was ensured that both Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) and large ones were represented among the exporters (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p. 174). However, this originally planned division was slightly adapted.

For example, as it turned out during the recruitment of NGO representatives, the topic of funding played a decisive role. The researcher was told that due to lacking resources, there was not enough capacity to deal with the topic of foreign trade promotion at present; instead, one focus of the respective NGO activities was on evolving legal HRDD regulation. Opportunities for social research are therefore not a given, and NGO recruiting for research undertakings could represent a barrier to access (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 796). Other interviewees had a dual role and found it appropriate to represent a company rather than, for example, a particular business network. In addition, only one trade union that dealt with human rights in export finance could be selected for the lack of alternatives. With regard to the German ECA itself, no added value was seen in interviewing more than two employees, as it was decided that expertise on the topic was the decisive factor, and that data saturation should not occur here either.

Access to the field (Bogner, Littig and Menz, 2014, p. 37) was favoured by the researcher's professional background. As a former employee of the German ECA, the researcher already knew some of the stakeholders who she wanted to include in her qualitative research. This in turn would not mean that these people knew the researcher herself. If they did, personal contacts were employed. In other cases, the researcher had an idea of which, for example, particular NGO or which unit or position in one of the respective institutions was to be addressed. Through analysing concrete job descriptions found on the internet, the researcher was able to identify the experts along with their respective institutions. Frequently, the researcher also located the corresponding email addresses online; however, on occasion, additional research was required to obtain this information.

In all cases, the researcher did not find any hurdles in contacting the experts with a concrete idea about her research project while at the same time highlighting their possible part due to their role and experience. All experts were contacted via email, including a short explanation of the doctoral project, based on the Participant Information Sheet (see Appendix E). In this email, having a short phone call or online meeting with the researcher was suggested to introduce herself and her research project in person, and to answer any existing questions. None of those contacted required a preliminary discussion at this point. If someone did not respond after being contacted via email three times, no further attempts were made. In some cases, a more detailed letter was requested in order to obtain internal approval for participation in the interviews (see Appendix F).

Occasionally, the interview questionnaire was sent in advance. This was done for two reasons: to get the experts' approval to participate in the interviews, which is connected with trust (Bogner, Littig and Menz, 2014, p. 31), or when interviewees wished to prepare for the interviews. At this point, i.e. after having received their approval to participate in the interviews, interviewees asked for telephone calls or pre-online meetings. In one case, consent to participate was given after a previous interviewee had encouraged or requested another expert to do so. Furthermore, all experts were asked about other possible contact persons at the end of the interviews (Bogner, Littig and Menz, 2014, p. 35; Petintseva, Faria and Eski, 2020, p. 63). In return, the researcher asked if she could explicitly use the experts' name when approaching these possible contacts. This was perceived by the researcher as trust-building and therefore helpful in relation to getting additional contacts' approval to take part in an interview. If persons suggested fit the research sample, they were approached as well, using the procedure just described.

The process outlined here showed the researcher both how sensitive and important the research topic seemed to be for an interviewee; at the same time, preliminary contact contributed to increased trust and helped to gain participants' agreement to be interviewed. The researcher greatly appreciates the fact that she had access to official bodies such as ministries, and that high-ranking representatives of e.g. companies, banks, and CSOs took time to participate in and support this study, often with a great deal of preparation.

Against the background highlighted, the intended sample size was 20 experts, as illustrated in Table 8 above. For the data chapters to be compiled, these experts were summarised (see Table 9) in order to guarantee the anonymity of the interviewees and to avoid drawing conclusions about their respective institutions. The government level, German ECA, and one science and research institution related to a public university were assigned to *Public Institutions*, while the sustainability-related business association and network, the two other science and research institutions, the trade union, and both NGOs were combined under *NGOs* according to the Cambridge definition of NGO as "an organization that tries to achieve social or political aims but is not controlled by a government" (Cambridge University Press & Assessment, 2024).

Table 9: Anonymised interview participants

Exporters	Banks	Public Institutions	NGOs
E1	B1	P1	N1
E2	B2	P2	N2
E3	B3	P3	N3
E4		P4	N4
		P5	N5
		P6	N6
			N7

Source: Johanna Imiela

5.4.3 Interview Process

Prior to the interviews, the Participant Information Sheet (see Appendix E) and the Consent Form (see Appendix G) were sent to the interview participants to be signed and sent back upon the interview. At the beginning of each interview, a preliminary discussion took place in which the researcher introduced herself, summarised the background of the research project, explained the time frame of the interview and obtained consent to audio recording (Bogner, Littig and Menz, 2014, pp. 40, 60). In many cases, an informal discussion (ibid., p. 61) took place after the interviewees had been thanked and the recording equipment had been switched off. If relevant to the research topic, the contents of these were written down in the notes taken after each interview (ibid.).

The interviews were conducted in person in the premises of the respective interview partner or online and lasted between around 30 minutes and 1.5 hours. While three interviews took place in English, all others were conducted in German. Two interviews were joint ones with two colleagues as the interview partners. In both cases, it was ensured that each interviewee answered all questions or said something about all topics. An audio recording device was used for all interviews and completely transcribed by a writing service office recommended by a HAW Hamburg colleague. The recordings were sent via end-to-end encryption technology. All transcripts and audio-recordings were stored as encrypted files in line with General Data Protection Regulation (*Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)*, 2016) and ethical approval conditions made by the UWS ESS Ethics Committee (see 5.3.3).

Each transcription was thoroughly read and corrected and, if parts appeared unclear, improved using the original audio recordings. This showed that the researcher's deep knowledge was

helpful in correctly transcribing some interrelationships or technical terms used by the interviewees. Moreover, in order to maintain anonymity, names of people or institutions were anonymised if this could lead to conclusions about the interview partners themselves. Two interviewees asked for the transcript to be sent and only afterwards gave their approval for further use, so that the analysis described below could take place.

5.4.4 Interview Data Analysis

The data analysis used thematic criteria instead of formal ones (Schreier, 2012, p. 136) and therefore took place in an inductive approach, as concepts and categories emerged from the data (ibid., p. 25). Reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2022) was employed in line with the above-mentioned axiological research assumption where researcher subjectivity functions not merely as the main tool (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p. 8). Within qualitative research, knowledge creation is fundamentally influenced by personal perspectives and specific contexts (ibid.), and reflexive thematic analysis values this subjectivity along with a context-aware, insightful, and probing researcher (ibid., p. 5). This means that researcher bias is not particularly relevant (ibid., p. 8) if researcher subjectivity is utilised as a tool for conducting analysis (ibid.). In reflexive thematic analysis, the researcher is proactively involved in knowledge creation (Byrne, 2022, p. 1393).

Braun and Clark see the reflexive researcher who critically reflects on their role, research practises and processes, i.e., “what we do, how and why we do it, and the impacts and influences of this on our research” (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p. 5). In this context, the researcher of this study has consciously addressed the issue of bias and subjectivity. She has reflected on her role and experience, and what was made possible as a result of both. Bias existed first and foremost through the researcher’s many years of professional activity at the German ECA, but also through her own attitude to the topic of BHR. This attitude was not only shaped by her work as a sustainability adviser at the German ECA, but also by her previous professional experience in a sustainability consultancy, and by her interest in (social) sustainability topics, which runs like a red thread through her life thus far.

Therefore, from both her professional and her personal point of view, a positive bias for two topics could be seen: first, the promotion of foreign trade, and second, the protection of those whose rights could possibly be negatively affected by projects associated with foreign trade promotion. The underlying and both positions unifying belief for this research project was that state foreign trade and especially state export promotion is able to strengthen project-related human rights.

Regarding her role as a researcher, the author was aware of the issue of bias throughout the research process, starting with the choice of the research topic and questions, and the mainly

explorative research design, the generation of the interview guide, the selection of experts as interviewees, as well as the conduct of the interviews, and especially, of course, up to the evaluation of these. At the same time, it seems appropriate to reiterate that some of these aspects were part of the approved ethics application. Moreover, in qualitative research, reflexivity does not only relate to the researcher, but also to the participants of a study (Schreier, 2012, p. 23). These were seen as partners (ibid.) which is also shown by the fact that the term 'interview partner' was used in the respective data chapters, but also as the experts to the research question (ibid.). Objectivity therefore is not applicable in the context of this qualitative research part (ibid.).

The researcher did not try to be an "invisible, neutral survey instrument" (Bogner, Littig and Menz, 2014, p. 55). In both the data collection and data analysis, the researcher made her own contribution as a co-producer (Schreier, 2012, p. 23). She interacted with the interview participants in a committed way (Bogner, Littig and Menz, 2014, p. 55) and obviously showed here competencies in the research topic, as she was sometimes referred to as an expert herself by the interviewees (ibid.). Against the background of valued subjectivity in the frame of reflexive thematic analysis, both on the part of the interview participants and the researcher, there should be no expectation that the codes or themes interpreted by one researcher can be exactly replicated by another (Byrne, 2022, p. 1393). Reflexive thematic analysis is an accessible and theoretically adaptable interpretive method for qualitative data analysis that enables the identification and examination of patterns or themes within a data set (ibid., p. 1392).

The interview data was analysed according to Braun and Clarke's (2022, pp. 35-36) six-phase approach to conducting reflexive thematic analysis as described in the following, using the qualitative data analysis software NVivo. To this end and after several failed attempts due to lacking know-how and experience, three projects were created in succession, each containing two phases of the reflexive thematic analysis: the first project for phases 1 and 2, the second for phases 3 and 4, and the third for the last two phases 5 and 6.

Phase 1: Familiarising yourself with the dataset

After having created clean versions of the transcripts, so to speak, using the audio recordings to validate or correct data (see above), the researcher read through each transcript one after the other, sometimes re-listened to the audio recordings once again. Important passages or statements were marked and summarised, using so-called annotations. Since most of the interviews were in German, a time-consuming step, namely translating, was included at this stage. As translating is always related to interpretation, an additional interpretation step was therefore established even before the actual interpretative data analysis (Schreier, 2012, p. 47).

Phase 2: Coding

In this phase, the researcher read through all marked passages and annotations and coded the data in a systematic and thorough way. The researcher focused on data segments that seemed interesting, relevant or meaningful to answer the overall research question and the relating sub-questions. So-called nodes were created, capturing “pithy, analytically-meaningful descriptions” (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p. 35). To collate all data, folders were created, guided but not prescribed by the interview questionnaire, as this seemed to provide a useful framework. All codes were then related to and compiled under these following folders, as depicted in Table 10.

Table 10: Folders encompassing the nodes/codes

▪ Benchmark standards	▪ Meaning of HRDD
▪ Biggest challenges	▪ Miscellaneous
▪ Closer look necessary	▪ Overview for enhanced HRDD
▪ ECA and remedy	▪ Positive aspects of ECA business
▪ ECA business and techniques	▪ Positive aspects of German ECA
▪ Exclusion list	▪ Prioritisation
▪ Granular human rights aspects	▪ Scope of ECA HRDD
▪ HRDD framework	▪ Leverage

Source: Johanna Imiela

The code and folder creation formed the foundation for developing themes in the following Phase 3.

Phase 3: Generating initial themes

Within each folder, codes that seem to share the same idea or concept were assigned to overarching themes, which were named as such in this process. The creating of initial themes took place outside NVivo. The researcher exported all files successively into Excel files and clustered the exported codes in separate Word documents. After the subsequent clustering, summarising headings were assigned to the respective groups of codes. These headings were transferred back into NVivo as initial themes, and the codes related to and compiled under these. An example for the topic “Benchmark standards” is summarised in Table 11:

Table 11: Initial themes

Cluster 1: Human rights relevance of benchmark standards	Cluster 2: IFC Performance Standards compliance
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Address relevant human rights topics ▪ Benchmark standards concretise human rights ▪ Benchmark standards improve human rights situation on the ground 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ IFC Performance Standards address human rights ▪ IFC Performance Standards address stakeholder engagement ▪ IFC Performance Standards address grievance mechanism ▪ IFC Performance Standards address ILO core labour standards ▪ IFC Performance Standards will be THE benchmark standard for most ECA transactions

Source: Johanna Imiela

During this phase and based on the interviewees' statements, another folder had to be created for codes related to the theme "HRDD laws", therefore going back to the previous Phase 2. This shows that reflexive thematic analysis is a recursive process instead of a linear one (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p. 36).

Phase 4: Developing and reviewing themes

After all the data was brought back to NVivo and sorted according to the initial themes, these were reviewed and refined. Codes with data related to them were shifted to other themes, by looking at the full data set again. Sub-folders containing codes assessed as not relevant for answering the research question were created within the main folders. Moreover, when reviewing the themes, it was decided to drop three main topics, namely "ECA and remedy", "Positive aspects of ECA business" and "Positive aspects of the German ECA" due to their missing relation to the research question. Some initial themes were discarded as well, for example "Exclusion lists are needed" with several codes and data related to it under the overall topic "Exclusion list", as the theme "Alternative view: tackle the disadvantages" was highlighted as much more meaningful and bringing in a new perspective. The above-mentioned folders were therefore reduced to the following 14 ones (Table 12):

Table 12: Reviewed folders encompassing themes and nodes/codes

▪ Benchmark standards	▪ Meaning of HRDD
▪ Biggest challenges	▪ Miscellaneous
▪ Closer look necessary	▪ Overview for enhanced HRDD
▪ ECA business and techniques	▪ Prioritisation
▪ Exclusion list	▪ Scope of ECA HRDD
▪ Granular human rights aspects	▪ Leverage
▪ HRDD framework	▪ HRDD Laws

Source: Johanna Imiela

Phase 5: Refining, defining and naming themes

In this phase, the data analysis so far was fine-tuned. Outside NVivo, but in parallel, all folder names with the containing themes were written down. Some themes were further dropped, and others renamed. Sometimes, the codes and data sources were looked at in more detail once again, copied or moved to what seemed to be more appropriate themes. A 1.5 pages Word document resulted (see Appendix J). The researcher asked the two questions guiding this phase, namely “what story does this theme tell” and especially “how does this theme fit into my overall story about the data” (ibid.), while looking at the Word document and at all data stored and organised in NVivo. As a final step in and result of Phase 5, a one pager emerged, consisting of three headings and several “concise, punchy and informative” (ibid.) names for each themes underneath (see Appendix K).

At a later stage during the actual writing in Phase 6, another recursive step took place where it was decided to drop the third heading. Even though regarded as highly interesting, the researcher had to realise that the topics listed therein were exciting but were too specific at this point to contribute to answering the research question. The framework of refined themes created in Phase 5 formed the basis for the subsequent writing up (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Final themes from interviews

- HR in the ECA context
 - Hr are already addressed
 - Standards
 - IFC PS to become main reference standard in GER → deficiencies though (see Lit Review-chapter), but good start (ibid.)?
 - Exclusion lists
 - Meaning of hr
 - Diverse and lacking knowledge of all players involved (incl. SMEs)
 - mainstreaming and promotion needed
 - granular hr aspects could help mainstreaming and reduce resistance
 - Complex BHR setting
 - Many players involved incl. role of politics
 - Streamlining processes asked for by all
 - Scale and scope of hr risks as a trade intermediary vs. company-own supply chain (incl. transaction approach vs. general one)
 - Economic interests meet hr
 - Original aim
 - Role of \$
 - Hr risks are inherent in state export finance
- ▲ HRDD in the ECA context
 - Diverse understanding of HRDD
 - Important elements of HRDD in the ECA context
 - Some elements are already existing – HRDD is not new!
 - What is most important? (s. xls)
 - Some elements need to be further looked at
 - Stakeholder Engagement
 - Transparency and Reporting
 - HR Policy
 - German NCP as grievance mechanism for export credit context
 - Agreement to my proposal (pictorial presentation)
 - What about...
 - Beyond CA
 - enhanced HRDD
 - Prioritisation
 - Operationalizing GP 4: Scope of ECA HRDD

Source: Johanna Imiela

Phase 6: Writing up

Taking this framework of final themes as a basis, it immediately became clear that both headings chosen to organise these themes formed two parts of the research question, namely (1) how to address human rights in export finance and (2) how to operationalise HRDD. A circle was thus completed. After some seven months of data analysis inside and outside NVivo in Phases 1-5, the researcher quickly realised that writing the two data chapters according to the above-mentioned division of the research question was an analytic process as well (ibid., p. 118), as further analysis took place in writing the two chapters.

Illustrative examples in the form of citations from the interviews were used and analysed in relation to the literature and research question, followed by a lot of editing (ibid., p. 36) and

refinement (ibid.), such as described in the previous phase concerning the deletion of the third heading and related topics therein. This integral phase of reflexive thematic analysis (ibid., p. 36) continued for another 3.5 months. During these months, the researcher reviewed previous data analyses and parts of the original data set, translating some of these if still necessary, thereby further interpreting and analysing the data in writing. Therefore, not only was this phase about “refining analytic work” (ibid., p. 118), but also “to tell [the] whole analytic story” (ibid.), including the source of the envisaged dissemination, aiming at proving the quality and validity of the qualitative research and its analysis (ibid.).

5.5 Evaluation of Methodological Choices

The final step in the methodology chapter is to address the reliability, validity, credibility and transferability of the research findings in accordance with Saunders, Luis and Thornhill (2019, p. 717). As the focus in qualitative research is less on reliability (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p. 211), the analysis procedure is the origin for qualitative validity (ibid.). Even though the researcher has not approached the interviewees with summaries of her research findings (so-called member-checking, ibid.), initial results were partly discussed with subsequent interview partners. Moreover, some of the research findings were conferred with several interview partners or colleagues representing respective stakeholder groups, in a loose and less formal setting and, as the data analysis was still progressing, at a rather abstract level.

Not only when approaching the experts, but also in an online meeting with various OECD ECAs that had asked the researcher at the beginning of conducting the interview phase for her opinion on human rights and HRDD in the ECA context, first outcomes from the literature review and the case survey were indicated and the overall strategy including its methods explained. As a result, a certain amount of credibility has already been gained then. In addition to employing data triangulation for validity (ibid.), the researcher received valuable feedback from her supervisors, who also served as external reviewers (ibid.) for all data generated through the research methods employed. This significantly enhanced the validity of the data.

The transferability of findings might be limited both in terms of the case survey and the expert interviews. While the data analysis of the case survey has concluded that no valid and general applicable assumptions can be drawn from the cases due to the limited data available, the idea of the qualitative interviews was not to generalise from the sample which was less large compared to quantitative studies (ibid., p. 174). As is the case in semi-structured interviews, the exact same questions were not asked in all interviews (Bogner, Littig and Menz, 2014, p. 29), but comparability between the interviews was nevertheless established and similar data collected (Green, 2008c, p. 54). The aim was to gain in-depth information from the interviewees (Green, 2008c, p. 54; Bogner, Littig and Menz, 2014, p. 28).

Not many details about the experts were given though, and some statements (though even surprising ones) were not included in the analysis in order to preserve the experts' anonymity. After all, the researcher had promised each expert that it would never be possible to draw conclusions about them as a person or their institution on the basis of their statements. This has led to trust (Green, 2008c, p. 54), which also contributes to the credibility of the research findings (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 217). Nevertheless, the reader of this doctoral thesis can judge the transferability of the study as the researcher has provided a comprehensive description of e.g. the research question, design, and findings (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 217).

Finally, even though one limitation of the mixed methods approach of this research undertaking might be seen in the fact that quite an amount of time and resources was required (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p. 14) and contributed to the study's overall duration, the researcher is convinced that the impacts of possible limitations have been addressed and therefore mitigated. This doctoral project still provides value as it is the first of its kind to address the research questions of how human rights can be addressed and how HRDD can be implemented in the ECA context. Therefore, this thesis does not only contribute to filling the knowledge gap identified in the literature review, but at the same time represents a new contribution to knowledge. The weaknesses outlined here should therefore be outweighed.

5.6 Conclusion

Only few literature sources directly refer to the application of the UNGPs to ECAs, and the question of how human rights can be better considered in export promotion remains unanswered. Therefore, this thesis aimed to elaborate how ECAs can fulfil their responsibility to respect human rights pursuant to the UNGPs, i.e., to contribute to a definition of HRDD and to elaborate concrete proposals for realising HRDD in the ECA context. In order to reach this research aim, the researcher sought to answer the overall research question of how business-related human rights are addressed in order to comply with the UNGPs, especially with regard to the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD.

This chapter has outlined the methodological framework adopted for answering the research question within the scope of this doctoral study. The research philosophy underpinning this work is pragmatism, which focuses on practical solutions and outcomes for the topic researched. Aligned with this philosophy, a mixed methods approach was employed by combining both quantitative research in the course of a case survey and qualitative research by means of comprehensive expert interviews. Therefore, multiple data generation methods were utilised, while the research design was predominantly qualitative though. 20 representatives of the relevant stakeholders identified in the literature review were interviewed

as experts in the research topic of human rights in export finance. These semi-structured interviews in particular demonstrated the inductive research approach, but also the literature review and case survey, as themes were derived directly from the data (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p. 10). The researcher elaborated upon the interviews in more detail due to their central role in generating primary data collection and in the study, especially with regard to the original contribution to knowledge.

Interview data analysis drew on Braun and Clarke's (2022, pp. 35-36) six-phase approach to conducting reflexive thematic analysis. After reading through the transcripts and coding relevant information, final themes were developed in a reflexive way. As both data chapters showed, the two headings chosen to organise the themes formed two parts of the research question, namely (1) how to address human rights in export finance and (2) how to operationalise HRDD.

The theoretical framework guiding this study was informed by so-called new governance theory, and, more precisely, on polycentric governance, aiming at achieving stakeholder consensus for a HRDD model by involving all ECA stakeholders in the process for its development. In evaluating the methods chosen, the reliability, validity, credibility and transferability of the research findings were assessed. Though acknowledging potential limitations of the research conducted, it was concluded that this thesis does not only contribute to filling the knowledge gap identified in the literature review but also represents a new contribution to knowledge. The weaknesses outlined should therefore be considered less significant, as the methodology adopted for this study provided a comprehensive framework for exploring and answering the research question of how business-related human rights are addressed in order to comply with the UNGPs, especially with regard to the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD.

Against this background, the following three chapters are devoted to two of the data generation methods presented here: the case survey in the following Chapter 6, and the two chapters in which the analysis of the expert interviews is presented (Chapter 7 and Chapter 8).

Chapter 6: Case Survey on Human Rights Violations in ECA-Related Projects

6.1 Introduction

The Literature Review (Chapter 3) has revealed that most of the literature on human rights in export finance has been critical of how human rights are addressed in that context. Several sources have provided examples of human rights violations at projects associated with ECAs, such as violations of the rights of Indigenous Peoples, forced displacement of local populations, paramilitary and police repression or workplace injuries (United Nations, 2011, p. 3ff; Bernaz, 2013, p. 502). However, to make concrete proposals within the scope of this research project on how human rights can be better considered in export support, and to develop a conceptual framework for HRDD, it is essential to address the three aspects which form the research questions on which the case survey is based.

First, it is necessary to understand the central human rights risks and impacts in the ECA context; second, to find out whether and how these adverse human rights impacts are connected to a specific industry, a specific country or a specific project; and third, which correlations and conclusions can be drawn from this approach. On the one hand, the results are intended to directly inform a proposal for HRDD that the researcher plans to discuss with the interviewees in the next step. On the other hand, the aim is to identify any gaps and topics that need to be addressed in the expert interviews in order to fill the identified research gap and answer the overall research question of how human rights can and should be addressed in the context of state ECAs in order to comply with the UNGPs, especially with regard to the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD.

Following Petersen's guidelines for case survey research (Petersen, 2020), the case survey was chosen as a method for answering the above-mentioned research questions, consisting of a meta-analysis (*ibid.*, p. 67) of existing cases which report on human rights violations in the context of ECA-related projects. The aim of the survey was to find out whether there are connections and patterns between, for example, a country and an industry sector in concrete human rights violations, i.e. with regard to a specific human right and its violation, such as child labour. The purpose of this approach was to gain a broad understanding of the research problem, i.e. the consideration of human rights in state export finance, through quantitative data and its subsequent analysis (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p. 104). These findings could be incorporated into the envisaged proposal for HRDD of ECAs and their clients, as well as the most salient risks to human rights, which could help in prioritising action for preventing

and mitigating adverse human rights impacts as part of HRDD in accordance with GP 24 (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 26).

6.2 Approach

Similar to the approach used in the literature review, reported cases of human rights violations in projects associated with ECA support were examined. An Excel sheet was deemed sufficient for recording and evaluating these cases (as opposed to a computer-based analysis tool). In this table, 21 categories were determined for the case analysis (see Appendix H). Inspired by the survey of alleged corporate-related human rights abuses which fed into the Ruggie Framework (Human Rights Council, 2008b), the merits of the allegations were not verified. This case survey is not intended to assign blame or responsibility. Instead, its primary goal is to gain insights into the conditions and factors that can lead to human rights violations at projects related to export credits.

In line with the above-mentioned survey and the methodology applied therein (Human Rights Council, 2008b, pp. 10–11), but adapted to the ECA context by the researcher, allegations of abuse were reviewed for the human right or rights impacted, using the human rights expressed in the IBHR and the ILO core conventions¹¹ as well as applicable additional UN instruments which have been elaborated further on the rights of specific groups, as all such rights should be respected by business enterprises according to the UNGPs (Guiding Principle 12, Office of the High Commissioner, 2011).

Not all concerns which were raised in the reports always related to human rights terms though. It was therefore independently assessed whether the international recognised human rights were impacted and if so, which of these, while bearing in mind that a clear attribution of a concern to a single specific human right was not always possible. In these cases, one of the possible human rights that were violated was chosen by trying to infer from the context of the case what human rights violation might be meant. As an example, "polluted drinking water" can serve as an allegation. If in a report the health impairment caused by contaminated water is primarily addressed, the "right to health" was chosen; however, in another case it could be the "right to clean water".

Environmental impacts were considered when they were mentioned in direct relation to a negative human rights claim. Although environmental and human rights are obviously interdependent, and the *Right to a clean, healthy and sustainable environment* was declared a human right in 2021 (Human Rights Council, 2021), it was deemed necessary in the context of this survey to clearly assign environmental impacts to a specific human rights violation.

¹¹ See the human rights provided in the list "Human Rights under International Human Rights Law" (Chapter 2).

Allegations of corruption were recorded against the background that corruption can lead to human rights violations (McCorquodale and Nolan, 2021, p. 470). However, it was determined that potential human rights violations resulting from corruption were described too broadly in the analysed cases to be included in the quantitative evaluation of the case studies.

Due to the unique nature of each reported case, some predefined parameters had to be excluded from detailed analysis, as information on these aspects was often unavailable. These parameters were the cover holding exporter and/or bank, the guarantee volume as well as the project volume, the severity of impact – i.e., the scope, scale and potential for remediation of impacts (Guiding Principle 14, Office of the High Commissioner, 2011) –, the form of ECA involvement and that of its clients (direct or indirect), as well as the type of ECA cover (pure cover or direct lending). The case evaluation excel sheet therefore mainly contains information on

- The project name
- The country
- The project sector to which the projects were inductively assigned to
- The alleged human rights violations
- The affected persons whose rights were violated
- The author of the report
- The literature source
- The year of publication
- The ECA named and
- Whether the report should be used for the case analysis.

If the latter was not the case, the reason for this was also included by referring to the exclusion criteria which are presented below. To record additional valuable information for the further course of this doctoral research, concrete points of criticism by the case study authors and possible requirements that an ECA should fulfil were also noted even though it was not intended that these should be part of the quantitative case analysis. However, this information could be helpful and therefore important for the development of a proposal for HRDD.

The case analysis should first and foremost bring to light concrete human rights violations that occur in the context of ECA support. Certain points of criticism or suggestions for improvement in dealing with human rights in this regard are in turn part of the qualitative research of this dissertation project (Chapter 7 and Chapter 8), which will also draw on the results of the case study analysis. Apart from analysing examples of human rights violations in export finance, another aim of the case survey was to identify and examine instances where ECAs positively impacted the mitigation or prevention of such violations, as this could also feed into the proposal for HRDD.

Yet no such positive examples were found during the case research and survey. Only the example of the Ilisu Dam involves the withdrawal of export credit guarantees also due to human rights aspects (Human Rights Council, 2018, p. 10; Linder, 2019, pp. 67–71, 74). However, the authors of the cases in question have attributed this to pressure from NGOs against the involvement of several ECAs and not to the proactive behaviour of the respective ECAs (e.g. Eberlein et al., 2010; Eichert, 2014). Therefore, the results presented in the following refer solely on negative human rights impacts reported upon in the context of projects related to ECA support.

6.3 Selection of Relevant Cases

The three research questions for the selection and subsequent analysis of the cases were

- What evidence exists for both positive and negative impacts on human rights in projects connected to ECA support?
- Whether and how are adverse human rights impacts connected to a specific industry, a specific country, or a specific project?
- What are the most salient human rights risks in the ECA context?

While the Literature Review (Chapter 3) included any statements on human rights in the context of export finance, the focus of this case analysis was on the connection to concrete ECA-related projects. Table 13 shows that the criteria for including cases were significantly fewer than the criteria for excluding them:

Table 13: Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ At least one ECA must be named specifically ▪ Reference to a specific project, site, or region ▪ Any author or publisher ▪ Any form and place of publication ▪ Any year of publication ▪ Connection to a concrete human rights violation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ No ECA named specifically ▪ No project name or at least region provided ▪ Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) cover only (investment guarantee) ▪ General criticism of countries and their respective human rights situation/country risk only ▪ Case related to debt burden instead of concrete human rights violation ▪ General human rights violations without concrete examples ▪ Repetition of cases already analysed instead of additional information to a case ▪ Cases referenced from other authors only

Source: Johanna Imiela

Restricting the time period to, for example, the adoption of the first Common Approaches, was considered but dropped, since potential project risks exist regardless of how they are addressed in the context of export financing by means of an agreement between ECA governments. This is of course contrary to the time constraint purposely selected within the literature review, for which the publication of the Ruggie Framework was deliberately chosen as a start.

During the search for cases on human rights violations at ECA-related projects, it quickly became clear that searching with search strings, both in English and in German, brought little success: The cases were not necessarily named as such or as case studies but rather presented reports of human rights violations in a totally inconsistent format. As stated by Papp, the “search for precisely identified facts for cases of Foreign Trade Promotion with human rights violations is difficult” (Papp, 2013, p. 35). Papp has justified this by pointing out that a state lacks comprehensive transparency awareness, and these cases are not taken to courts; so that “one has to rely solely on the reporting of journalists, (...) NGOs, and some statements of the federal authorities” (ibid.).

This not only indicates that this case survey is also mainly based on grey literature, as was the literature review, but that it was also necessary to collect cases via other ways of information. The collection and analysis of material for the literature review were instrumental, revealing several emerging cases. In addition, the pages of the NGO ECA Watch were explicitly searched for so-called “dodgy deals” (*Dodgy deals* | www.eca-watch.org, no date), and these were analysed according to the above-mentioned inclusion and exclusion criteria.

6.4 Empirical Analysis

After identifying and reading 86 different sources relating to 54 cases in sum, a total of 21 cases met the inclusion criteria. These cases were not compared with each other, even if they related to the same project. Rather, the aim was to understand and highlight which specific human rights violations occur in which project context. This information could be incorporated into the corresponding ESHR review of the (German) ECA and therefore contribute to a definition of HRDD, e.g. by concretising human rights risks as part of the risk identification (Abrahams and Wyss, 2010, p. 25; GP 18, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 19). The following Table 14 lists the 21 cases on which this analysis was based.

Table 14: Reported cases on human rights violations in export finance

Project name	Country	Author of case and year of publication
Hydropower plant Hidrosogamoso	Columbia	Keenan, Hamilton (2015) Kim et al. (2015)
Power station Medupi	South Africa	Germanwatch, Misereor (2017)
Three Gorges Dam	China	The Corner House et al. (2005)
BTC Pipeline		Amnesty International (2013) Germanwatch, Misereor (2017) Hildyard (2007)
Lesotho Highlands Water Project	Lesotho, South Africa	The Corner House et al. (2005) Amnesty International
Sakhalin II	Russia	Ong (2011)
Vinnytsia poultry complex	Ukraine	Kolomiets, McGrath (2015)
Sasan coal power plant and mine	India	Bengali (2014)
Chad-Cameroon Pipeline	Chad, Cameroon	ESCR-net (2005)
Suez Canal Expansion Project	Egypt	Hazekamp et al. (2016)
Seaport Suape	Brazil	Dutch NCP (2016) Keenan, Hamilton (2015)
Carajás project expansion	Brazil	Keenan, Hamilton (2015)
Bisha Copper Mine	Eritrea	Garcia (2017)
Katanga mines	Democratic Republic of the Congo	Garcia (2017)
Ocensa Pipeline	Columbia	Berne Declaration et al. (1999)
Manantali Project	Mali, Mauritius, Senegal	Berne Declaration et al. (1999)
Indah Kiat	India	Berne Declaration et al. (1999)
San Roque Dam Project	Philippines	Norlen et al. (2002) The Corner House et al. (2005) Papp (2013) Russau (2016)
The Birecik Hydroelectric Project	Turkey	The Corner House et al. (2005)
Nickel mining projects	India	Papp (2013)
Oyu Tolgoi copper mine	Mongolia	Seck, dos Santos (2016) Spohr (2016)

Source: Johanna Imiela

Contrary to what was envisaged in advance, no valid and general applicable conclusions can be drawn from the analysis of these cases though due to the limited data available. As has already been concluded in the literature review, it applies to this case survey as well that there is simply not much closely related literature on human rights violations related to ECA-related projects. Despite a catch-all approach used, which involved researching and evaluating all reports of human rights violations related to ECA projects, the conclusions presented below have at best an indicative effect, since there are hardly any cases and, moreover, these are almost exclusively, with one exception, taken from grey literature sources.

While it is therefore not possible to create, for example, a matrix that represents particularly critical constellations of a project country and sector leading to a concrete human rights violation, which could in turn directly feed into an ECA's HRDD, e.g. in the risk identification, the findings of the case survey will nevertheless be summarised in the following. For this purpose, the data of the analysis table mentioned above were segmented according to certain aspects: the *sectors* from which the reported case projects stem; the *countries* in which the projects are located; and which *human rights are alleged to be violated* in the reported cases. The findings were then *correlated*, as far as possible, by linking the alleged human rights violations to the project sectors. To be able to show results that are as tangible as possible, the issues behind the internationally recognised human rights were recorded and quantified in a further step of the analysis. Here, too, these *concrete human rights issues* were then compared with the project sectors as a final step. In doing so, qualitative information is transformed into quantitative information (Petersen, 2020, p. 65).

In total, the projects mentioned in the 21 cases relate to seven different sectors (Figure 17).

Figure 17: Number of cases per project sector

Source: Johanna Imiela

Most human rights violations are linked to hydropower projects (i.e. sector Energy/Water), namely six, followed by five projects related to mining projects and four to the oil sector. Looking at countries where projects with human rights violations are situated (Figure 18), the so-called host countries, the case survey included three projects in India and two projects each in Brazil, Columbia, Turkey, and South Africa. Seven countries were documented as hosting one project each. As projects sometimes related to more than one country, for example in connection with oil pipelines, the case-country quantity amounts to 27 countries.

Figure 18: Countries with documented human rights violations in export finance

Source: Johanna Imiela

As shown in Figure 18, critical projects were hosted exclusively in emerging and developing countries. These countries are primarily targeted for ECA financing because they are considered too risky for financing by the private capital market (ICC, 2021, p. 7). In the context of the German ECA, export credit guarantees are only allowed if there is no private sector offer according to the principle of subsidiarity (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, 2022, p. 15), and therefore, transactions in emerging and developing countries are mainly covered. Against this backdrop, it is not surprising that the cases reported do not refer to projects in European countries, the USA, Canada, Japan, Australia, or New Zealand. On the contrary, however, precisely the ECAs from these countries are predominantly referenced in the reports (see Appendix I).

14 times, and thus most frequently, the violation of the *Right to an adequate standard of living* was mentioned in the reports, which always related to issues of resettlement and/or compensation. In second place was the *Right to health* (ten times) which was mostly related to environmental impacts of the projects concerned, such as polluted water and air, but also to inadequate waste management. Together with the *Right to water*, the *Right to participate in public life* was stated third most often. It referred entirely to lack of information and consultation of those affected by the project. In the analytical process, the principle of so-called Free, Prior and Informed Consent (FPIC) was distinguished from this human right, and it was assigned to the *Rights of Indigenous Peoples*. The human rights violations mentioned in the analysed cases are depicted in the following Figure 19.

Figure 19: Alleged human rights violations

HR Violation	Quantity
Right to an adequate standard of living	14
Right to health	10
Right to participate in public life	9
Right to water	9
Rights of Indigenous Peoples	7
Right to freedom of opinion, expression, information	6
Right to enjoy just and favourable conditions of work	4
Right to own property	2
Right to culture	1
Right to freedom of assembly	1
Right to life	1
Right not to be subjected to slavery or forced labour	1
Right not to be subjected to torture	1
Right not to be subjected to arbitrary arrest, alleged torture	1

Source: Author's own compilation

The following Figure 20 illustrates the correlation between specific human rights violations and the corresponding project sectors.

Figure 20: Alleged human rights violations in the different project sectors

Source: Johanna Imiela

As demonstrated in Figure 20, the most frequently mentioned human rights violation was the *Right to an adequate standard of living*. In the cases analysed, this right always related to aspects of resettlement or compensation. Resettlement and compensation, in turn, do not appear to be a (human right) risk in the pulp and paper industry, as this sector is the only one where these did not occur. This is also supported by the fact that these topics are not covered in the respective sector-specific questionnaire provided by the German ECA; instead, the questionnaire’s focus is on purely environmental topics such as wastewater, sustainable timber cultivation, and water and energy consumption (‘Questionnaire (Pulp and Paper Production)’, 2018).

Other questionnaires such as the sector-specific one for mining, oil and gas deal with the topic of resettlement, for example (‘Questionnaire for mining, oil and gas (sector-related questions)’, 2021, pp. 2, 8–10). The typical land use practices in the pulp and paper industry generally involves managed forestry operations (WWF International, 2010, p. 4), which is opposed to community displacement scenarios. For the other sectors, it appears to be relevant to address the *Right to an adequate standard of living* and especially resettlement and compensation in the ECA assessment and support. This finding could inform the proposed HRDD framework.

The previous section has already shown that there are specific issues behind the respective human rights which were alleged to be violated. In a second last step, it was quantitatively evaluated how often these specific human rights issues were mentioned in the case studies (Figure 21).

Figure 21: Human rights topics

Source: Johanna Imiela

As can be seen from Figure 21, the most frequently mentioned human rights issues related to compensation for resettlement undertakings and to compensation in general, and to the issues of water, health, and waste management, which were named in the cases as belonging together. In second place, the involvement of the affected community (information and consultation) followed. Alleged violations of the *Rights of Indigenous Peoples* were mostly about FPIC and mentioned third most often. Also in third place is the topic of repression, which refers to the suppression of protesters. These could possibly be Human Rights Defenders (HRDs) who often face severe repression and attacks due to their work in promoting and protecting human rights (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2004), and pressure in general. Workplace injuries were referred to here as OHS issues and ranked fifth.

As a final step of the case analysis, these human rights topics were correlated with the different project sectors (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Human rights topics in the different project sectors

Source: Johanna Imiela

Lastly, Figure 22 could be used to quickly capture concrete issues involving the violation of an internationally recognised human right in an industry context. For example, at least on the basis of the case survey findings, the issue of resettlement and compensation seems to be the most relevant aspect in ECA projects from a human rights point of view, with the exception of the pulp and paper industry. Equally relevant is the aspect (clean) water, health, and waste management. However, the other eleven topics or topic blocks depicted are not less salient, at least for some sectors. Finally, Figure 22 summarises which specific human rights issues can be negatively affected in the context of export financing. Referring to the overall research question of this doctoral research, namely how human rights are to be addressed in the context of state ECAs in order to comply with the UNGPs, the author of this doctoral dissertation deems it worthwhile to recognise specific relevant human rights issues in this context in order to be able to address them.

6.5 Conclusion

While, as mentioned above, it is not possible to create a meaningful matrix from the cases analysed that illustrates the relationship and interaction between the project industry, the host country, and a concrete human rights violation in the context of ECA projects, the human rights issues highlighted here could help to fill the envisaged HRDD with concrete content. Without disregarding Ruggie's findings that a company can negatively influence all human rights (Ruggie, 2010c, p. 2), the next step of the qualitative study – the expert interviews – could, derived from this case analysis and evaluation, explore whether it is helpful to name and deal

with concrete human rights issues in the context of export credit guarantees, in addition to the international human rights that are sometimes more general and that might cover several human rights topics within.

A substitute for a matrix to be discussed with the experts could be to ask the interview partners which components they deem relevant for such an overview, and which project and country constellations are particularly critical from their point of view with regard to human rights violations (in general or even concrete ones). This could help in prioritising action for preventing and mitigating adverse human rights impacts in accordance with GP 24 (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 26).

Accordingly, the case survey results highlighted were incorporated into the development of the interview questionnaire under the topic block "Prioritisation" (see Annex C), which emerged from the case survey analysis. The following chapters 7 and 8 present the thematic analysis of the expert interviews conducted. While Chapter 7 focuses on the general consideration of human rights in the ECA context, Chapter 8 presents the interview data relating to the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD in this regard.

Chapter 7: Human Rights in the Export Credit Agency Context

7.1 Introduction

In this chapter, three main topics which derived from the thematic analysis of the expert interviews are highlighted. The data illuminates that human rights are already an established topic in export finance, especially by means of the benchmark standards against which, among other issues, human rights aspects of foreign projects are assessed. Yet there are several complexities and challenges inherent in the ECA context which should be considered in the endeavour of integrating human rights more effectively.

On the one hand, a nuanced understanding of the meaning and scope of human rights seems to be lacking among ECA stakeholders. On the other hand, the complexity of the context in which the German ECA operates, characterised for example by diverse players, competing interests, and the political embedding, has so far been given too little consideration in the literature reviewed. However, this complexity has emerged as a pertinent topic in the interviews conducted, underscoring its significance. The following chapter therefore addresses the part of the overall research question of this doctoral thesis that relates to the general consideration of human rights in the ECA context, regardless of HRDD requirements as laid down in the UNGPs, which will be touched upon in the next chapter.

7.2 Human Rights Are Already Addressed in the ECA Context

7.2.1 Benchmark Standards

The literature review revealed the inadequate consideration of human rights especially in the World Bank Safeguard Policies as opposed to the Performance Standards of the IFC. Despite their revision into new standards (the World Bank ESS¹²), the World Bank Safeguard Policies are still used in the project appraisal, for example in December 2023 (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date s). As the comparative rough analysis of the benchmark standards¹³ used by OECD ECAs concluded that even the new World Bank ESS mention human rights less frequently than the IFC Performance Standards, the recently finalised amendment of the Common Approaches could bring an improvement for human rights.

With the 2024 version of the Common Approaches, the IFC Performance Standards will be the primary standard for benchmarking projects (OECD, 2024b, p. 10). Only in case of sovereign

¹² See Chapter 2

¹³ See Chapter 2

obligators, i.e. public buyers, the World Bank ESS may be used instead (ibid.). The IFC Performance Standards will therefore at least be applied for assessing private buyers' projects. As private buyers generally account for the larger share of Germany's ECA clients according to the most recent annual report 2023, namely 65 % of single transaction cover volume in contrast to 35 % (Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz, 2024, p. 17), this can be seen as an improvement for the protection of human rights.

In this context, one of the three bank representatives interviewed – which were anonymised accordingly with participant B1, participant B2 and participant B3 (see Table 9 in Chapter 5) – referred to the IFC Performance Standards as the “*golden standard*” (participant B1). The six interview partners from the government level, the German ECA, and one science and research institution related to a public university, were assigned to ‘Public Institutions’ and therefore anonymised with participant P1-P6. One of these interview partners, the public institution representative P3, stated that

“I believe that the issue will then be fully or finally fully anchored and then you will no longer have this loophole, if you want to call it that, via the Safeguard Policies.”
(participant P3)

Both interviewees cited here seem to agree that the IFC Performance Standards cover human rights aspects more thoroughly and especially compared to the former, but still used, World Bank Safeguard Policies. Moreover, interview partner P3, who was allocated to the public sector, appears to approve the IFC Performance Standards as the sole or at least primary benchmark standard, by emphasising that applying these cannot be circumvented in the future. According to the previous Common Approaches version, ECAs were able to choose whether they evaluate projects against the World Bank Safeguard Policies or the IFC Performance Standards (OECD, 2016, p. 10). In the amended 2024 version, the World Bank Safeguard Policies are no longer mentioned at all. This concretisation with regard to a uniform benchmark standard could put an end to the criticised variable ECA benchmark practice amongst OECD ECAs (Human Rights Council, 2018, p. 58) and could at the same time reduce the lacking systematisation of the Common Approaches which came to light in the literature review (e.g. Scheper, 2013, p. 47, 2017, p. 202).

Several interviewees emphasised that the IFC Performance Standards address relevant human rights aspects such as *stakeholder engagement* (mentioned by one of the four exporter representatives, namely participant E1, as well as by two interview partners assigned to public institutions, participant P2 and participant P4), and a *grievance mechanism* (mentioned by the above cited interviewee P3). Moreover, one of the seven interview partners who were combined under ‘NGO’ and accordingly anonymised as participant N1-N7, stressed that the IFC Performance Standards address the *ILO core labour standards* (participant N4). To ensure

the fulfilment of these aspects, the foreign projects reviewed against the IFC Performance Standards must of course be compliant with the relevant aspects comprising them (Raza, Schlögl and Pfaffenbichler, 2023, p. 5), or compliance must be sought through action plans, as described in Chapter 2. In this way, compliance with the IFC Performance Standards thus supports human rights. Irrespective of the criticised insufficiency also of the IFC Performance Standards (e.g. Hamm, Scheper and Schölmerich, 2011, p. 4; Human Rights Council, 2018, p. 69), the human rights or even UNGPs relevance of the benchmark standards pointed out by several interviewees are worth mentioning here, as the following two quotes show.

“But I think the topics are still seen through the standards.” (P4)

“I mean, I guess I would assume that like the IFC Performance Standards or whatever, even the World Bank ESS would be taking the Guiding Principles each and every one of them and making them more concrete in the sense of the context of the project and what to look at.” (B1)

Both the public sector representative P4 and the bank representative B1 therefore agree that human rights topics are considered and concretised through the benchmark standards against which foreign projects are assessed.

7.2.2 Exclusion Lists

In addition to the consideration of human rights through the benchmark standards, the existence of an exclusion list was also discussed during the expert interviews. While some literature on the German ECA has criticised that the definition of companies, sectors, and target countries eligible for ECA support is inadequate (e.g. Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 76), several interview experts pointed out that exclusion lists already exist for both countries and certain sectors. The country level for exclusion is not only agreed upon at the OECD level (OECD, 2024a) and therefore applying to all OECD ECAs, but also known by potential German guarantee applicants, as the following public sector representative P6 stated.

“With these OECD country risk things, categorisation, where you can look at the different corners of the world three times a year and just know which countries are – there’s nothing there. As a rule, there are no enquiries.” (P6)

According to participant P6, guarantee applicants would know if a country was not eligible for export support and therefore not apply for an export credit related to such a country. The following exporter (E4) confirmed that these exclusions exist and are well known, so there do not seem to be any guarantee applications about exports to certain excluded countries:

“Because the exclusion list that we already have at Hermes for various products and countries is, from my point of view, I thought to myself during the preparations, it has

been around for a long time. So, Sudan, Myanmar, North Korea, war zones in general. Well, Ukraine is perhaps now a very strange grey area, but also Iraq and Syria". (E4)

Neither the OECD country risk classification (OECD, 2024a) nor the German ECA (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date f) explicitly states that, for example, Iraq is excluded from (German) export credit guarantees though. Iraq is classified in the highest country category 7 from 7, and the German ECA declares that "cover facilities are available on a case-by-case basis" (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date q). Apparently, however, this is understood and put into practice as if cover were not possible, as mentioned by interviewee E4.

In addition to countries, there might also be exclusion criteria for the sector or product level decided upon by the federal government, according to expert P3:

"No more cover for nuclear, i.e. for nuclear power generation projects; with exceptions. This is a purely national regulation." (P3)

As information on country or sector exclusion is available by the OECD (for example, the ban of official financing support for unabated coal fired power plants, OECD, 2021) or German ECA, it was more interesting that interviewees suggested that improvements could be sought at project level by realising export support, as an alternative to a predefined exclusion list. One reason for this might be that many target countries for German exports would not pass exclusion criteria based on human rights and environmental aspects, meaning that the possibility of state-supported exports would no longer exist at all or only to a very limited extent.

"Yes, there should be exclusions for countries, but I mean, the way the world is developing right now, you can't export much anymore." (N7)

From a human rights perspective, it seems impossible for NGO representative N7 to do business with a lot of countries because the human rights situation there would be too critical. This would leave hardly any target countries for German exports. On the contrary, bank representative B1 suggested that it might be possible and sensible to tackle the disadvantages of an exclusion list which could even hinder positive outcomes:

"(...) it's possible to do those projects in a sustainable way and they have such impacts that it's better to do them with a European partner or an OECD partner than with just China or whatever for example, right now." (B1)

Expert B1 seems to be alluding to the fact that Chinese exporters receive export support from their own government but, unlike OECD ECAs, do not have to adhere to strict environmental and human rights requirements (Scheumann, 2010, p. 2). Consequently, higher standards in favour of human rights, among other things, would apply and be implemented in projects with

an OECD ECA connection. Moreover, positive projects could also be realised in what is assumed to be a negative surrounding, as bank representative B3 put it:

“And I personally don't like these exclusion lists in this respect, because what happens if I have a project in the Uyghur region, China, etc., which (...) is perhaps against human rights, i.e. actually does something positive, creates jobs, etc., and has nothing to do with it? So why shouldn't I support such a project just because it's there?” (B3)

There are many critical reports on investors, companies and even the World Bank in the Uyghur region, including the institutions' ethical role and legal complicity regarding human rights violations and business responsibilities (Kriebitz and Max, 2020; Abdul, 2022; Wright, 2022; Burger, 2024; 'U.K.'s largest bank accused of profiting from Uyghur forced labor', no date). However, this was not discussed in this specific interview because interviewee B3 seemed to be more concerned with the fact that projects which can improve people's situation should also be possible in critical project environments. According to interviewee B3, providing ECA support for such projects would thus be the right thing to do rather than categorically ruling something out. What expert P3 from the public sector said fits in with this:

“Because it is simply very project-specific what the human rights impacts are. So, there can certainly be a coal mine or a [single] coal mine that has few human rights impacts. There can also be, I don't know, a completely uncomplex or unproblematic sector that becomes highly problematic in a specific project.” (P3)

The reverse therefore also seems conceivable: that a seemingly uncritical project becomes critical from a human rights perspective, and vice versa. An exclusion list would neither cover both alternatives. Moreover, false conclusions or decisions could be drawn when not looking beyond excluded countries or sectors in the guarantee awarding process, as the public sector affiliated expert P1 and the NGO representative N6 pointed out.

“And above all, isn't there perhaps an ominous reverse effect? So, if it's not ruled out, it's more or less allowed, yes?” (P1)

“But yes, you know, exclusions are important. But my point is, I think they shouldn't be mistaken as the sum total of due diligence. By having an exclusion policy and then letting everything else in, that's not due diligence.” (N6)

In this way, these interviewees also addressed the importance of the respective project reviews with regard to human rights, which go beyond purely predefined exclusion lists. Moreover, and opposed to predefined exclusion lists, some experts prefer that exporters and banks are accompanied by the German ECA to improve human rights at the project site and therefore mitigate negative human rights impacts.

“(...) to accompany things favourably, to perhaps roll out implementation plans even more strongly through complementary measures, instead of categorically saying that we no longer support this.” (B2)

The fulfilment of human rights at the project level does not yet appear to be complete in this example, as the bank representative B2 spoke of complementary measures, i.e. action plans, to reach compliance with the benchmark standards applied. With the help of ECA cover and ECA monitoring, the human rights situation on the ground could therefore be improved, which would not be the case if there was an exclusion list and therefore no involvement of an ECA backed exporter or bank. On the one hand, the statement on improved human rights protection through OECD ECAs mentioned by interviewee B 1 above fits this interpretation. On the other hand, it could also be deduced that projects are realised independently of ECA involvement, which was also stated by this very bank representative:

“Try more attention to human rights issues, really holding it is a very serious thing that needs to be considered in these projects while also acknowledging that the projects are going to happen; kind of with or without us.” (B1)

However, this would mean that the (poor) human rights situation would continue to exist without ECA financing, while ECA support could therefore lead to an improvement in human rights. Against the backdrop of weak regulation and critical large-scale projects in the destination countries of German exports, foreign trade promotion including ECA support can contribute to compliance with environmental standards and human rights (Haupt, 2024). This attitude, which is more focussed on improvement through ECA promotion, is in stark contrast to statements that projects backed by ECAs are often associated with human rights abuses (Keenan, 2008, p. 2; United Nations, 2011, p. 2). The interviewees, on the other hand, emphasised that export companies supported by the ECA could have a positive impact on the human rights situation locally when using their leverage to enhance e.g. human rights standards as the project sponsor’s foreign trade partner. NGO representative N2 was one of these advocates.

“Empowerment before withdrawal. Companies have the opportunity to exert pressure, especially when it comes to money or loans. And withdrawing completely can have much more serious consequences for the people who are ultimately at stake than staying and taking action.” (N2)

This approach of ending a business relationship only as the last resort, risking possible adverse human rights impacts of doing so, is addressed in GP 19 and also in the official guidance on the German Supply Chain Act (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 22; Federal Office for Economic Affairs and Export Control, 2023, p. 25). The interview experts cited here would therefore rather seek to improve human rights on the ground, and specifically

in the context of export credits, instead of avoiding these positive outcomes due to exclusion lists. Nevertheless, it should not be assumed that human rights are respected simply because projects are supplied with ECA support. On the contrary: If a country's human rights situation is critical, attempts need to be made to protect human rights on the ground at the project site, while supporting exports with the help of an ECA. This was stated by interviewee P5, affiliated with a public institution, as follows:

"(...) human rights are not adequate in Saudi Arabia. Does that mean we shouldn't do any business there? (...) I think we should ensure that the project respects to the extent possible the human rights of the rights holders in a project in Saudi Arabia." (P5)

The focus of expert P5 therefore seems to be on facilitating export businesses, including to countries that are questionable from a human rights perspective (and therefore opposed to a policy of exclusion), while making the greatest possible efforts to ensure that human rights are respected.

7.2.3 Summary

The existence of exclusion criteria as well as the benchmark standards used during the assessment of projects, especially the IFC Performance Standards which have become the primary benchmark standard, illustrate that human rights are already an established topic in Germany's export finance. This shows an improvement on the criticism levelled by Papp in 2013, namely that human rights aspects play a role in Germany's foreign trade promotion "only to a very limited extent" (Papp, 2013, p. 168), in favour of statements by the German government and ECA that compliance with human rights is important in the ECA context (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date a; Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, no date b). However, the following section points out that there is no fundamental understanding of what human rights really are in the ECA context.

7.3 Lacking Nuanced Understanding of the Meaning and Scope of Human Rights

7.3.1 Lack of Clarity

The interviews uncovered that there is a frequent lack of clarity regarding the precise interpretation of human rights, even though all interview partners acknowledged and positively pointed out that human rights have become an essential aspect in export finance. As bank representative B1 put it,

“I think the biggest challenge is that it's poorly understood, like – here, people know that human rights are important, but they don't know exactly what they are. Are they the social things or the thing“. (B1)

According to interviewee B1, the bank's employees do not know exactly what human rights are. This lack of knowledge and understanding might lead to the fact that the qualitative aspects of human rights, as opposed to e.g. emissions, make people feel “scary” (B1) when it comes to measuring or monitoring if human rights are being implemented.

“And when you get to these social things, people are kind of like - they get really scared because there's no way of - there's no framework for assessment, right?” (B1)

B1: *“Or like keep your eyes around human rights. Like that's really challenging because it's so much like of your own subjective kind of - interpretation of like, what's going on? “*

Johanna: *“It's a qualitative aspect, human rights, not emissions.”*

B1: *“Exactly. It's really hard, yeah.”*

It is also not clear to this interviewee themselves what exactly human rights are and mean, and how their fulfilment can be measured and assessed. Bank expert B1 mentioned that human rights might be ‘social aspects’. To interpret this statement, the development of the Common Approaches and the assessment of project impacts on the environment and on people can be used. As the OECD states, social aspects are only recently considered in ECA support, in contrast to the ecological impact of projects (OECD, no date a). The term ‘human rights’ is not mentioned at all in the section on ECAs’ ‘environmental and social due diligence’ (ibid.) though, which is also, perhaps just as incomplete, part of the title of the Common Approaches.

Nevertheless, the Common Approaches explain that social impacts “encompass relevant adverse project-related human rights impacts” (OECD, 2016, p. 5). The German ECA seems to have picked up on this as it refers to “environmental, social and human rights issues”, e.g. on its Website (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date a). The bank representative B1 above did not seem to know the difference between social and human rights aspects though, and the German ECA's website does not provide any explanations in this regard either. Furthermore, interviewee B1 seemed to feel more comfortable with quantitative indicators such as those relating to emissions and related human rights to something that is subjective and linked to interpretation.

This attitude has also been noted in the literature. Most of the existing human rights guidelines are of a qualitative nature (econsense, 2020, p. 3), but human rights must become measurable for companies as they are often recognised as “abstract” as well as “complex” (ibid., p. 5). The

interviewee's mentioned fear seems to be well-known. As human rights are recognised as abstract, there is a possibility of a human rights-related risk arising that was previously not anticipated by a business (Plüss, 2020). That is why companies are concerned (ibid.) or even afraid, particularly against the background of potential legal liabilities (ibid.) which are currently being discussed in the course of supply chain legislation.

This lack of understanding what human rights mean in export finance does not seem to be eliminated by the Common Approaches, but maybe even intensified. On the one hand, it seems that having only one standard for governing export finance would be helpful for different parties involved in Germany's export finance:

"(...) one standard that people look to. Common Approaches, UN, World Bank, EPs¹⁴ etc. It would be great if we could agree on a standard. It's scary. We always have this discussion, especially on the environmental side: how do I deal with project risks? And in my opinion, this can also be applied one-to-one to human rights". (B3)

According to bank representative B3, these various existing standards tend to make discussions, e.g. regarding human rights, more difficult and therefore more complicated. The fright mentioned is therefore more of an annoyance and could be solved by a single standard according to interviewee B3. Moreover, the abstract nature of human rights may be exacerbated by the vagueness of the Common Approaches, which expert B3 criticised for not being specific enough to address a project's human rights risks. However, these risks are considered project- or sector-specific according to interviewee B3, necessitating a more tailored approach.

"For me, the Common Approaches are like a half-empty, half-full or half-empty watering can, depending on how you look at it. Too vague, I think, too superficial. Precisely because sector differences are enormous in projects, and you need a sector-specific view." (B3)

Bank representative B1 mentioned above that unspecific human rights need to be interpreted, and this expert also associated the perceived vagueness of the Common Approaches with interpretation, as stated in the following.

"The Common Approaches leave a lot of things up to interpretation." (B1)

This criticism of the Common Approaches with regard to interpretation and discretion is also reflected in the literature, particularly relating to compliance with human rights standards (Raza, Schlögl and Pfaffenbichler, 2023, pp. 5, 23–24).

¹⁴ (Equator Principles)

7.3.2 Promoting Human Rights

Perhaps especially since human rights do not appear to be clearly measurable, some ECA stakeholders might be concerned of these aspects in the context of state export finance, because human rights seem vague, intangible and subject to interpretation. As concretisation on the part of the Common Approaches is obviously lacking, it seems sensible and important to explain human rights and the importance that they are addressed in the ECA context. Interviewee P5 who was assigned to the public sector formulated this necessity very clearly, especially regarding human rights, as awareness of environmental aspects would already be recognised by the applicants.

“(...) to mainstream this whole issue of a risk-based approach by ECAs in general, but also the exporting community, that their awareness of these issues is raised. I think, you know, you can't just say I'm exporting goods, I'm creating a positive input to the country's GDP. Therefore, you know, why do I need to consider all of these fluffy good governance issues? I'm afraid you do in the environment. So, the whole issue of human rights, climate change, biodiversity, gender, and other issues needs to be more mainstreamed within the business community. There needs to be more promotion out there.” (P5)

Maybe due to the prevailing lack of understanding and fear among applicants regarding the difficulty to measure human rights aspects, guarantee applicants seem not yet convinced enough about the importance of human rights aspects, but expert P5 regards it as significant to soften a possibly defensive stance. To meet opposing attitudes, there should be more human rights understanding and support on the part of the applicants through knowledge building and advocacy according to interviewee P5. In this context, another interview partner from the public sector, expert P6, emphasised that special attention should be given to applicants from SMEs:

“But when you hear that again and again from SMEs, that they really have difficulties with these issues and then say, why do I have to do this at all? (...) But you could perhaps say that you offer a little more comfort, pick them up somewhere and say that we will learn from our dealings with colleagues in the field and give you something to work with. And if you have that and somehow get it agreed with your partners on the other side, you've already gained something with these topics.” (P6)

SMEs seem to be struggling with human rights requirements and might therefore not only be reluctant but also frustrated. SMEs would need more support to ensure that they also meet human rights requirements.

7.3.3 Granular Human Rights Aspects

One means of translating human rights into the ECA business could be to name specific, i.e. granular, human rights aspects which are important in the ECA context. Of course, not in a “‘tick box’ approach” (McCorquodale and Nolan, 2021, p. 470), i.e. limiting human rights to only a few aspects – as some interview partners rightly put it:

“But in such an example context, so as not to give the impression that these are the five topics I have to consider.” (N3)

“I believe that the headline must remain the same, we respect universal human rights.” (B3)

Use and rely on tick the box approaches would, on the contrary, be only cosmetic compliance (Landau, 2019, p. 234) and formulaic (United Nations, 2018, p. 23), which falls short of protecting all possible project-related risks to human rights. As business activity can negatively impact the entire spectrum of all international human rights (GP 12, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 13), all these human rights might be relevant in the ECA context. That is why any predetermined list of human rights which might be checked item after item by ticking boxes leads to false or at least incomplete assessment of the projects abroad (Ruggie, 2010c, p. 2).

Keeping this important limitation in mind, naming concrete human rights aspects could help mainstreaming them in the business world (i.e. above all with the applicants) and reduce possible resistance due to fears arising from a lack of knowledge about human rights, as the NGO representative N4 stated in the following.

“In order to allay companies’ fears that they will somehow be overwhelmed with something, I believe that any kind of assistance or guidance is relevant (...) then break it down again and look at it and make it more concrete. It’s probably just such a huge word that hopefully somehow leaves you in awe”. (N4)

It seems as if the term ‘human rights’ goes hand in hand with complexity and difficult understanding for companies. Not limited to the export finance sector, many companies are indeed grappling with comprehending the meaning of human rights and discerning how these rights intersect with their operations (Castan Centre for Human Rights Law Monash University, Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights and UN Global Compact, 2016, p. ix). The approach of explaining “the meaning of universally recognised human rights in a way that makes sense to business” (ibid.) was also taken up as a result of the case survey (Chapter 6). Based on the case survey finding that the international human rights are sometimes more general and might cover several human rights topics within, it was concluded

that the expert interviews should explore whether naming granular human rights aspects would be helpful in the context of export credit guarantees.

Abrahams and Wyss have emphasised that understanding the industry sector and its specific human rights risks and challenges, among other things, would be important in order to identify central human rights risks and impacts related to a business activity (Abrahams and Wyss, 2010, p. 25). And although companies “can have an impact on virtually the entire spectrum of internationally recognised human rights” (GP 12, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 13), Ruggie has pointed out that certain rights may hold greater relevance within specific activities, sectors or contexts, which will be the focus of attention in each respective scenario (Ruggie, 2010c, p. 2). He therefore himself has suggested that certain human rights should be concentrated upon in the ECA context, yet without selecting only a subset of rights.

In the case survey, the violation of the *Right to an adequate standard of living* was mentioned most often in the cases analysed. Moreover, this human right always related to issues of resettlement, and frequently in combination with compensation. The general questionnaire which applicants of the German ECA are asked to complete during the application process specifically addresses whether resettlement activities relate to the project (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date k, p. 4). The currently applicable benchmark standards also refer to ‘Land Acquisition and Involuntary Resettlement’ (Performance Standard 5, International Finance Corporation, 2012, p. 4) or ‘Land Acquisition, Restrictions on Land Use and Involuntary Resettlement’ (ESS 5, The World Bank, 2017, p. 53).

At the same time, there are a number of different human rights involved in resettlement actions apart from the *Right to an adequate standard of living*. Other human rights potentially affected include the *Right to culture*, the *Right to food*, or the *Right to education* (Box 1., Van Der Ploeg and Vanclay, 2017, p. 35). Yet these rights seem to contribute to the above-mentioned feeling or even fear of overwhelming (human rights) requirements for German exporters and financing banks according to NGO representative N7.

“I think it might be helpful to formulate this once, because otherwise it's like, my God, we're supposed to somehow - preferably the right to education. Like this. (...) And it's all far too much. But just to break it down”. (N7)

The *Right to education* not only appears irrelevant to businesses according to this NGO expert but also seems to be overly demanding for them. Naming concrete human rights aspects instead of addressing the whole and general list of international recognised human rights, including those that might not be relevant in a certain project context such as the *Right to education*, could counter the struggle of companies to understand the meaning of universally

recognised human rights (Castan Centre for Human Rights Law Monash University, Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights and UN Global Compact, 2016, p. ix). All in all, resettlement could therefore be a relevant and concrete aspect of human rights in ECA support, which was one of the central findings of the case survey (see Chapter 6).

Hence, the term 'human rights' could be concretised, making it more tangible for guarantee applicants and all other stakeholders, helping them better understand how human rights apply in the ECA context, as stated by experts N1 and B1 in the following.

"I think making it tangible is really good (...) that the topic is made concrete." (N1)

"(...) as concrete as possible this human rights sort of thing (...) and that's all like making this sort of nebulous thing very, very analytical and concrete. And that's probably exactly what needs to happen on this, too." (B1)

Concretising specific human rights aspects seems to bring advantages to several ECA stakeholders. On the one hand, as NGO representative N7 put it,

"for the exporters, to make it clear why this is happening at all - I can imagine that this is helpful to simply make it clear that this is not about the good, the true and the beautiful, but that this project may also have a total impact on something." (N7)

According to expert N7, this concretisation explains to exporters why human rights are being addressed as a project's real impacts, to help them understand its tangible consequences e.g. on human rights, opposed to just abstract ideals. On the other hand, specifying human rights can benefit the ESHR assessment of the German ECA, as stated by two further interviewees.

"I believe that this is the right way to come down deductively from a general version and then check everything below." (E4)

"I've heard ECAs describe these as focus areas". (N6)

According to both exporter representative E4 and NGO representative N6, this approach allows for focusing on specific human rights within the context of a particular project and is reflected in Ruggie's suggestions as well (Ruggie, 2010c, p. 2).

7.3.4 Summary

The idea of proposing granular human rights aspects that might be especially relevant in the ECA context, i.e., *"which have the potential to have impacts on local people"* (P5), was received as very positive, important, and helpful. Bank representative E3 even expressed it as follows:

"I am in favour of the specific human rights issues." (E3)

The definition of focus areas seems to be valuable for external stakeholders, i.e., especially the applicants, but also for the internal ECA processes. It could help explain what human rights mean and are in the ECA context, and which ones are especially important. Greater sensitisation could also reduce the negative attitude of some experts, which might be related to fear of human rights based on a lack of knowledge about the meaning of human rights in business activities. By concretising specific human rights issues, criticism of overloaded human rights requirements could be met, and clarification provided. Due to the complexity of the ECA business, the topic of clarification appears to be a fundamentally important one for operationalising the UNGPs with regard to ECAs. This is illustrated in the following sub-chapter.

7.4 Complex Setting for Business and Human Rights

7.4.1 Various Actors and Role of Politics

The interviews conducted emphasised the complex environment in which the German ECA operates as a challenge for the realisation and protection of human rights. This environment is, as indicated in Chapter 2, defined by various stakeholders, conflicting interests, and political involvement. The German state export finance involves multiple parties, including the German government and in particular the four ministries that make up the IMC,¹⁵ the mandatory Euler Hermes, exporters, financing banks, but also local communities and NGOs – i.e. of many who were identified as stakeholders for the expert interviews. All these groups have their vested interests in the ECA business, depending on their role or affiliation as well as use and impact of export credit guarantees, some of which already came to light during the literature review.

As the federal government is the provider of export credit guarantees through the German ECA (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date h; OECD, no date d), the proximity to the German federal government is inherently natural. However, it also became clear in the expert interviews that political decisions and current interest can influence the design and implementation of export finance policies. One example for this has already been mentioned above, namely that German export credit guarantees will not be granted for nuclear power generation plants (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date e).

Moreover, especially when it comes to human rights issues, the complexity of the environment in state export finance stems from the fact that as a financial institution,

“you are connected to a great number of impacts, actual and potential. And pursuant to the international standards, you are involved with impacts that are caused or

¹⁵ See Chapter 2

contributed to by companies in your portfolio. So, that is an extreme challenge of scale.”
(N6)

NGO representative N6's statement is emphasising that as a financial institution, the German ECA might be involved in many human rights impacts and risks through its clients and their respective relationships. According to Shift, an ECA's challenge of scale is the result of the infinite number of actual or potential effects on people (Shift Project Ltd., no date a). ECAs are connected to both the customers' business activities and their operating context (Commentary to GP 4, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 7), which also includes the foreign project. ECAs should therefore address the actual and potential human rights impacts of the companies they support, especially if the client's business activity or the business environment is associated with significant risks to human rights (ibid.).

At the same time, GP 4 states that ECAs should meet this challenge of scale due to the direct interaction between the private and the public sector, particularly when the government functions as an active participant in the economy (Scheper, 2020), in the State-business nexus (GP 4, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011). The political or governmental level hence plays an important role in the German export credit guarantee scheme, and it is at the same time also part of its complex environment. Exploring the precise distinction between the German ECA and the German government may further compound the intricacies of the scenario, as mentioned by expert P1 from the public sector:

“The ECA is actually the interaction between the government and the service provider at Hermes.” (P1)

It would go beyond the scope of this dissertation to analyse this point in more detail. In addition, as became clear both in the literature research and in the interviews, Euler Hermes appears to be perceived as not only the mandatary of the federal government to manage the export credit guarantee scheme, but at the same time as the German ECA. The OECD also cites Euler Hermes as the ECA for Germany (OECD, 2023b). Likewise, in its 'ESHR impact assessment example of a category A project', Euler Hermes itself relates tasks which are obviously carried out by Euler Hermes employees to the “staff of the export credit agency” (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 9). For the sake of simplicity, Euler Hermes represents the German ECA for this dissertation project, although other obviously prevailing opinions confirm the multifaceted environment in which the ECA operates.

As indicated, not only plays the respective political orientation of the German government a role with regard to specific requirements and regulations for German export promotion, but also the political proximity of the instrument and its integration into the wider context of German politics. Foreign policy and political relations seem to be particularly relevant. This came to

light during the interviews, e.g. regarding the exclusion of target countries for German exports, a topic which was raised by two experts from the public sector, namely interviewee P4 and interviewee P3:

“(...) the country issue is also simply extremely political for me.” (P4)

Diplomatic relations in particular seem to be important to maintain:

“In some cases, sensitive information comes into play, which may well be problematic in diplomatic relations”. (P3)

Country exclusions seem to be highly political and sensitive to both interview partner P4 and P3 as these could cause difficulties or tensions in diplomatic relationships between countries. The maintenance of diplomatic relations was also mentioned elsewhere in the interviews, but no academic or non-academic source could be found in this regard. However, one source has indicated that in connection with the granting of an export credit guarantee, this could possibly have a negative impact on diplomatic relations with third countries (Saito, 1988, p. 55).

Moreover, current political foci could also influence the ECA business, e.g. in terms of human rights aspects, as highlighted in the following two statements of the two public sector representatives P4 and P6:

“Where does political attention perhaps lie?” (P4)

“Sometimes it's also the case that perhaps - this is nothing new, the political pressure, so to speak, and then certain projects have somehow been initiated by the government coalition or delegation through a trip abroad, then these issues have to be regulated in some form afterwards.” (P6)

Expert P6's statement would even mean that a project does not undergo the regular project assessment, but that the guarantee is granted due to political influence and without the ECA's involvement. Human rights aspects, among others, would only be addressed afterwards. Of course, this thwarts the standard processes as a basis for guarantee applications and poses a challenge for the consideration of human rights. Nevertheless, both these interview statements also stress that political influence obviously cannot be ignored in the ECA context. This in turn relates to calls for stricter human rights standards to be applied by the ECA because it has a special responsibility with regard to upholding human rights as a government agency, which is obviously reflected in the UNGPs (Krajewski, 2017, pp. 18–19).

Under the State duty to protect human rights, as laid down in their first pillar, the UNGPs anticipate that States uphold the protection and respect of human rights when functioning as economic entities (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2017, p. 3). In the State-

business nexus which GP 4, 5 and 6 refer to (Barnes, 2018, p. 44), especially GP 4 calls for “additional steps” a State should take to ensure that human rights are not impacted by supported businesses (GP 4, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011; Barnes, 2018, p. 52). This was also reflected in the interviews, as the following two examples from the two NGO representatives N6 and N1 show.

“(..) being that voice of higher standards is a really important role to play.” (N6)

“The fact that they are state service providers means that they also have a special responsibility”. (N1)

Interview partner N1 emphasised that ECAs must adhere to strict human rights standards due to their responsibility as state agencies. Consequently, and as interview partner N6 pointed out, these higher standards would be applied to the ECA applicants. As already pointed out in the literature review, the OECD encourages governments to set an example by incorporating environmental, social, and governance criteria into the management and provision of loans, guarantees, and insurance to promote responsible business practices (OECD, 2023d, p. 8).

In terms of allocation of responsibilities in addressing human rights though, the multitude of players involved appears to entail some ambiguities when it comes to e.g. risk assessment or reporting requirements.

“We now have a large number of parties involved, which is also a weakness of the ECA construct, should the ECA now identify the risks, or should the applicant do this?” (N3)

“Who reports at all, who is responsible for transparency?” (P4)

Both these statements point out that responsibilities might not necessarily be clearly defined and delineated among all parties involved, e.g. regarding the identification of human rights risks at the project site, as stated by interviewee N3, or regarding reporting and transparency requirements, which was mentioned by interviewee P4. Another interview partner from the public sector, namely P1, asked for a stronger focus on the respective roles and responsibilities of the different players when they said that

“always really look at who is responsible for what here (...) a stronger focus, that would be absolutely desirable.” (P1)

According to this expert P1, the specific tasks of the ECA should also be considered when it comes to the allocation of responsibilities.

“(..) it would be desirable to ask more questions about who can achieve what and where. In other words, to focus more on what an ECA does, what it is called to do, what

its mandate is; and what its opportunities for knowledge and influence are, so to speak; and what its primary responsibilities are.” (P1)

Moreover, it is implied by interviewee P1 that there could also be limited possibilities for the ECA as far as addressing and upholding human rights is concerned, meaning that the ECA could not know and influence all human rights issues. At the same time, interviewee P1 also emphasised the respective responsibilities of the applicant or cover holder.

“And I think it's also really important in this whole complex to always really look at who is responsible for what. And I mean, if a company exports and delivers to a project, that is their responsibility and nobody can release them from it or relieve them of it or whatever, so that they also fulfil the requirements that they are subject to.” (P1)

P1 underlined that exporters themselves have human rights responsibilities, and not only the ECA. Sorting out all the players involved and assigning respective responsibilities seems to be closely linked to the issue of efficiency according to another expert from the public sector, participant P4:

“To create clarity is, firstly, to sort out these players a bit, who does what (...) which players are actually still involved and where are we not looking at, where is something perhaps already there? To bring a bit of clarity into this in order to organise it efficiently. And on the other hand, perhaps also to encourage that it is already being done elsewhere anyway and then not always this, yes, we'll check everything in the end”.
(P4)

P4 showed a preference for avoiding duplicate efforts, such as in the identification of human rights risks. However, this would require an exchange of information among the parties involved that does not appear to be easy due to limited transparency, for example, as NGO representative N4 pointed out:

“(...) if someone has already checked it according to the same criteria, then you don't have to check it again yourself, but you could say, yes, okay, we have. Someone has already done the check, and this is the result. So of course, the question of transparency is probably the problem again, to what extent information is exchanged, at least between the credit agencies, I don't know, but that would certainly make sense in order to save so many steps and somehow make it a bit easier for all sides”. (N4)

N4's statement that there should at least be an exchange of information between the ECAs might already be taken up by the general questionnaire (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date k). This explicitly asks, for example, which other ECA is involved in the transaction or project (ibid., p. 2), maybe to allow exactly this exchange to take place.

7.4.2 Streamlining Parallel Processes

Precisely this aforementioned transparency could help to gain and maintain clarity among the various actors involved and thus streamline parallel activities that seem to exist.

“Everyone checks everything, and in my view that's not only inefficient, but it also leads to poor results, because ultimately no one really does it properly. So, the longer I think about it, I would say that such a stronger focus would be absolutely desirable. (...) I think that would actually create considerable added value.” (P1)

Interviewee P1 refers to the previously mentioned sorting of the actors with specific tasks and responsibilities so that redundant processes do not occur. Alluding to assessment tasks within the project review, expert P1 seems to have especially the ECA staff, exporters, and bank representatives in mind. In this regard, the NGO representative N4 mentioned that creating transparency about respective actors and their specific tasks could prevent parallel processes.

“How can things also be linked? (...) And I think it's important to have transparency between the different processes, between the different organisations involved. So, we have the OECD, the National Contact Point, which also prepares reports on country risks etc., there are various OECD manuals that provide some kind of support on how I actually implement my due diligence, what that means, how I can do it. So, I think there are already resources available to companies to help them do this.” (N4)

According to expert N4, there could therefore be an increase in efficiency by utilising already existing information and linking processes and players with one another, on the basis of previously created transparency. Moreover, this undertaking could also extend beyond the narrow circle of participants as the previous expert P1 seemed to refer to. Interview partner N4 mentioned the broader OECD sphere as opposed to the subject of export credits only under the OECD topic trade (OECD, no date g), but referred to the NCP and due diligence guidance, both of which are allocated to the topic investment (OECD, no date g, no date e). The transparency to be created in this respect therefore seems to be more about clarity as to what information is already available that could be used, for example, in the context of project evaluation.

In addition, expert N4 suggested to streamlining responsible business conduct processes in general, e.g. on the EU level, with the ECA context.

“I think the biggest challenge is that there are so many parallel processes running that shouldn't contradict each other. So we've already had this at one point or another - I think it's good that this paradigm shift from voluntary to binding is now taking place, so to speak, but that this - because otherwise the argument that it's too overwhelming and

somehow a bureaucratic monster, etc. - will be fuelled if it's not thought through consistently. - If it's not thought through in a consistent way, then of course you're feeding the argument. So, I think there is still a lot to be done at EU level, because the various initiatives come from different Directorates-General that don't talk to each other - or I don't want to imply it, but it feels like they could talk to each other more and they all need to be better thought through together. And then, of course, to break that down to the national level. And, yes, I don't think that's something we can know right now, but I think it's a fundamental challenge. (...) And we no longer need to talk about whether this is relevant and right now, because we've already done that somewhere else. So that's what I've never been able to understand, why we even have to talk about implementing the ILO core labour standards, because we've already said that within the ILO, we've ratified them, or we've agreed to them. (...) We are all committed to human rights. (...) And then of course to say, okay, we want these standards, and we are also prepared to support compliance with them. Because of course that's also a trade policy issue, that the partners say, yes, we can't do it, we don't want to do it, then we won't do it because the standards are so high that we can't apply them or something... Then we won't do it with you. So, let's see how it turns out, but then it has to be sold as, yes, that's not protectionism, but we want to take you with us and the big picture, so to speak.” (N4)

Interviewee N4 seems to have seen a possible impact of evolving legal regulation concerning BHR at the EU level on the ECA context, e.g. on the cover holders, when they talked about overwhelming and bureaucratic requirements companies might face. At the same time, this expert stressed the relevance of human rights standards that need to be complied with at all levels in Germany, and therefore including in export finance. It was also pointed out by participant N4 that addressing human rights on the side of the government should no longer be questioned due to Germany's ILO membership. Upon this membership, Germany is required to respecting and promoting the ILO principles and rights at work (International Labour Organization, 2020), which includes the so-called core labour standards (Federal Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs, 2020).

According to the experts stated until here, parallel processes relating to human rights are therefore taking place at several levels, within the narrow framework of the parties involved in the guarantee application, somewhat further at OECD level, and between the German and European level. All of these processes should be made transparent in order to be harmonised, with the aim of avoiding redundancy and increasing efficiency, for the benefit of human rights.

7.4.3 Scale and Scope

Apart from the multitude of actors, the construct of the ECA as an insurance company or intermediary, as opposed to a merchandising enterprise, for example, was given as a reason by expert P6 for intensifying the complex setting.

“And those who at some point led to the federal government giving a guarantee for this, i.e. taking a guarantee on the books, are simply intermediaries, initiators, whatever.”
(P6)

It is precisely this position that leads to the fact that the ECA is linked to many possible human rights risks, through its connection to exporters, banks, and even foreign projects – as is the case for all financial institutions (Shift Project Ltd., no date a). The various business relationships and transactions which characterise the financial sector indeed poses a challenge to addressing human rights (OECD, 2022a, p. 14, no date f). This challenge was also reflected by the three interview partners N4, N2, and P4.

“And of course, you know, as financial institutions, we're looking at the key challenge of scale. It's different to a retail apparel company, even with the complexity of retail supply chains.” (N6)

“And that it is simply a little more difficult to grasp when it comes to service matters or platform matters or financing matters, even if the responsibility is the same.” (N2)

“I think that's where (...) the ECA - it's just more difficult (...) than for a company itself in its own supply chain.” (P4)

The UNGPs do not refer to the supply chain, but to the value chain, and thus also to the downstream aspects of business conduct (Smit *et al.*, 2020, p. 159f.). Should exporters be required to evaluate and mitigate human rights risks irrespective of their position within the value chain of their customers or even their customers in export finance (Apelman and Olming, 2015), the German ECA will face increased complexity and challenges in scope, as reflected in the three statements of N6, N2, and P6 cited above.

Moreover, and in contrast to companies, there are two levels of the ECA business that are relevant for considering human rights. One level is the identification of those transactions that need to undergo detailed human rights assessment, while the other level relates to the specific human rights risks or impacts that should be addressed within a given transaction (Kovick, Vermijs and Davis, 2017, p. 12). In this context, the German ECA explains the important role human rights play in Germany's export finance in general (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date g) and how the screening and classification identify transactions for ESHR assessment and determine its scope (*ibid.*).

On the other hand, there is the level of individual transactions, i.e. exports to foreign projects. It is in this context that the majority of human rights assessments takes place, addressed at the project to which German exporters deliver (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date c). In previous research studied by the author of this doctoral thesis, this differentiation between these two levels has not been made, but it seems to contribute to the complexity of implementing the UNGPs at ECA level, as pointed out by the exporter representative E3 in the following.

“So, I noticed that - I see the ECA, which also refers back to the fact that it is transaction-related and not exporter-related. And for me, this is too much – it’s a kind of basis, so to speak, (...) you can’t do it again in every single transaction – (...) a Hermes driving licence, so to speak, not everyone can play along.” (E3)

Instead of evaluating projects on an individual basis, expert E3 would like to see exporters being held more accountable in general. This contradicts the argument that instead of individual ECA project assessments, ECA clients should carry out those, which are then in turn reviewed by the ECAs (Apelman and Olming, 2015). Exporter representative E3, on the other hand, stressed that responsibility for human rights should also be borne by the exporter, but independent of the respective transaction in question.

“And I simply believe that the exporter must be included, regardless of the individual project business. For the individual project business – what does that lead to? It means that we have less and less overall responsibility.” (E3)

At the same time, however, the ECA context also includes not only shedding light on ECA customers, but also on the ECA itself. Corresponding to the complexity outlined so far, interview partner P3 from the public sector pointed out that ECA support would constitute

“(...) a really complex instrument that is very difficult to understand (...).” (P3)

It seems necessary to take a closer look at the specific responsibilities of the ECA itself when it comes to considering human rights, but also at possible limitations that might exist in this regard, as emphasised by expert P3 from the public sector:

“(...) that it is clear - or should be even clearer - what the possibilities and limitations of ECAs actually are (...) And I believe that even in the internal ECA discussion, but of course even more so in the external discussion, the role of the respective ECA is being confused.” (P3)

According to interviewee P3, there seem to be limitations but also a misunderstanding or misinterpretation about the functions and responsibilities of ECAs in addressing human rights

issues at foreign projects, especially among stakeholders outside the ECA itself such as NGOs. This is discussed in the following sub-section.

7.4.4 Economic Interests Meet Human Rights

Looking at the “*complexity of contexts in which the solution isn't necessarily clear*”, as NGO representative N6 outlined the ECA framework presented so far, the question arises what an ECA's role and task are in trade finance, and how this might have changed and developed over time. Or, as interview partner P1 from the public sector stated,

“And what ECAs are responsible for, they are not made for the entire breadth of all economic development and - or all economic activity. And that's why it's okay. That is simply the criterion, the characteristic of focussing, that some things remain out of focus.” (P1)

Expert P1 referred to the focus of ECAs on their respective business, namely providing export credit guarantees. The original aim of the German ECA as an instrument for foreign trade promotion has been to protect exporters and banks from the risk of payment defaults on commercial and political grounds (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date h). Economic interests persist as a significant factor in export finance due to the inherent nature of trade promotion, as ECAs are established to bridge market deficiencies that hinder private sector involvement in financing exports and cross-border transactions (ICC, 2021, p. 14). When these interests meet human rights, this brings with it some complexity, demonstrated in the following two statements from the experts N4 and E2.

“At the same time, I can of course understand the argument that the hurdles shouldn't be super high in order for you to be able to operate economically.” (N4)

“(...) we still have to do business with it.” (E2)

Both the NGO representative N4 and the exporter representative E2 mention that economic viability of export undertakings, for which ECA support is sought, is important. It seems as if the requirements to get ECA support, especially regarding ESHR aspects, could contradict this though. Overloading German foreign trade promotion with social criteria has been one point of criticism which came to light during the literature review (CSR Germany, no date). However, it is interesting to note that the ‘hurdles’ cited above were not raised by an exporter, but that it was an NGO representative (N4) who highlighted the need for economic viability.

In contrast, the public sector expert P2 below would like to see high standards or thresholds to receive ECA support, e.g. connected to specific transparency requirements on the part of ECA clients, as they receive government support in return.

“And I would actually expect a German ECA to ask itself much more strongly from the outset what business activities are actually worthy of promotion? And then to a certain extent - in other words, to set the threshold high, so to speak, for foreign trade promotion in political terms and then, in connection with this, also impose higher requirements, for example with regard to the disclosure of certain business practices or strategies that have so far been largely untouchable. So, I would not be in favour of making this an instrument that can no longer be used, so to speak. But I would, yes, argue in favour of setting state objectives and human rights protection and environmental protection etc. a little more strongly as standards from the outset, which would then help determine what is worthy of support from the outset.” (P2)

Even though this expert stressed that ECA support needs to stay feasible in contrast to preventing export business due to, for example, excessive publication requirements, it was stressed that human rights, among other aspects, should play a much larger role in contrast to seemingly predominant economic criteria. There therefore seems to be a conflict between the original aim of pure export support and especially social and human rights criteria that have evolved at the OECD level in the meantime (Hickie, 2009, p. 603).

“Basically, it is a funding instrument that was originally structured quite simply.” (E1)

“(…) well, I can also understand that our mission is to promote exports and then the other thing is what comes along with it.” (N7)

This development was mentioned by exporter representative E1 and NGO representative N7. As there were no common ESHR standards before 2000 (ibid.), the adoption of the first Common Approaches and its respective reviews and amendments (History of agreements on environment and social due diligence, OECD, no date a) has brought with it new requirements (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 2). As part of the 2016 revision of the Common Approaches, greater priority has been placed on human rights aspects (ibid.). It is therefore logical that the structure of ECA funding has changed. At the same time, however, the German government seems to be emphasising or even tolerating economic interest over e.g. human rights aspects, as was formulated quite sharply by public sector expert P2:

“With the ECAs it is still a somewhat, I always say, sacred area, where it is somehow about promoting the German economy and where you somehow have human rights and sustainability as an add-on.” (P2)

According to this expert, human rights and sustainability aspects are only secondary in export finance, while the German ECA is said to primarily serve economic interests. The tension between economic and sustainability aspects mentioned before appears to be tolerated by the authorising federal government, as the ECA business is seen as something untouchable.

Economic interests would therefore not only exist on part of the exporters, but also at the ECA itself, which was confirmed by the bank representative B1.

“But clearly there's also a lot of economical stuff going around in the background.” (B1)

This statement could be related to the fact that the ECA business contributes to the Federal budget (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, 2023, p. 10), and the German government therefore has an economic interest in issuing export credit guarantees, as stated by expert N5.

“I also assume that the staff, which now exists at Euler Hermes, are really endeavouring to discover human rights risks and to work on them. But I think that decisions are of course made differently, especially for large projects. And, yes, basically, I would say that institutionally, the Ministry of Economic Affairs is somehow naturally interested in approving as much as possible.” (N5)

Dealing with human rights aspects, which have to be checked and answered upon by the applicant in advance, could be seen as a competitive disadvantage to exporters or banks that are not faced with these requirements from their governments (CSR Germany, no date). It has already been mentioned (see section 7.2.2) that Chinese exporters do not have to adhere to strict environmental and human rights requirements when receiving their government's export support (Scheumann, 2010, p. 2). Exporter representative E2 expressed exactly this:

“While the other countries that don't answer the questions, the exporters like the Chinese, say, we're done, when will you finally place that order? And we say we need more time because we still have to answer the questions.” (E2)

Not related to the ECA context, sources such as Rogge have pointed out that there can be tensions between economic interests on the one hand and the protection of human rights on the other in the business world (Rogge, 2022, p. 4). The pursuit of economic gain may clash with the protection of human rights, presenting difficult choices where sacrificing one for the other may seem unavoidable. This conflict or tension is referred to as “odious tradeoffs” [sic] (ibid.).

As an alternative to only require higher standards which must be fulfilled by guarantee applicants in return for state support, as stated by expert P2 above, a suggestion could be to “show the areas of tension and the thematic interfaces” (E4) on the one hand and try balancing out both economic interests and human rights or sustainability aspects. By this, according to exporter representative E4, it might be possible to find

“this balance between export promotion, project implementation and the other topics from the ESHR assessment”. (E4)

In contrast to some stakeholders' apparent defensive attitude towards ESHR standards, which came to light during the literature research and in part up to this point in the interviews, expert E4 is in favour of balancing both economic and human rights aspects. At this point, the author would like to cite some of her own reflections of the overall impressions of the interviews. After taking and analysing all interviews, she concluded that 'pragmatic views exist on all sides', i.e., different stakeholder groups, and that even those who might be seen as 'bad players', namely exporters and financing banks, see room for improvement and even provide concrete ideas for doing so. NGOs would 'not deny and criticise everything', as it is perhaps perceived by some exporters, and that in general, views and opinions among interview partners were 'very differentiated', while everyone would know that efforts for more human rights protection are 'difficult to implement and realise' in the ECA context.

The different interests of the various stakeholders involved came to light in the interviews, but at the same time the common desire on all sides to take a pragmatic, i.e., realistic, approach to the issue of human rights in export promotion. The literature review has highlighted that especially CSOs are critical of the German ECA and place several demands on it. However, it became clear in the interviews that NGOs do not require that all (human rights) criteria are fulfilled at all costs, but that it must be feasible to implement such needs. When asked when stakeholders should be involved, for example, NGO representative N5 stated that

"Well, in principle, of course, in every project. But at the same time, I'm realistic and pragmatic and I know that Euler Hermes also has a limited number of people. (...) Yes, and I think that with, yes, manageable projects, the effort probably must be lower somehow." (N5)

This expert N5, for pragmatic reasons, would therefore deviate from the actual idea that local stakeholders should be involved in every project in favour of feasibility.

The last aspect which contributes to the complex setting of the ECA business for addressing and realising human rights is the fact that human rights risks are inherent in state export finance, which emerged during the interviews. Due to the principle of subsidiarity, the German ECA may only insure transactions for which there is no private insurance (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date m). Accordingly, export transactions are mainly secured in emerging and developing countries (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date h) – therefore in vulnerable socio-economic and political contexts especially in terms of environmental and human rights aspects (Hickie, 2009, p. 590).

Another risk associated with these inherent risks could be the time lapse between project assessment or guarantee decision and the project course, as stated by public sector expert P6 and NGO representative N3.

"It's difficult to then somehow say that you should have known earlier or made a different decision at time X. That's always the case - sometimes you're always smarter afterwards." (P6)

"But I think that would be an issue that would also have to be looked at. Because it's one thing for me to say, okay, I won't be working with you in the future, but it's something completely different if the project continues to be funded for the time being". (N3)

Moreover, the projects to which ECA supported exports are delivered are often realised in difficult circumstances, e.g. from a human rights perspective. This may be due to lack of alternatives according to exporter representative E2:

"And as a practical company, you can clearly say that as long as the market is good, you won't have any difficulty at all in realising such projects." (E2)

But in general, as the principle of subsidiarity prescribes, the target countries for German exports are critical in terms of human rights, as the bank representative B2 pointed out.

"This primary instrument is actually there to make sales in difficult countries. You must not forget that. By the very nature of the product, we are on the road in difficult countries. And that's where we have these issues." (B2)

These host countries seem difficult because law implementation and compliance might not be monitored, as expert E2 noted rather disparagingly or frustratedly:

"No pig has adhered to it." (E2)

In addition, this exporter representative brought up the difficulty in connection with corruption, which is always associated with negative human rights impacts (McCorquodale and Nolan, 2021, p. 470).

"So, there is always corruption (...) Well, in certain countries it is, you know that. And then, if you've said you won't do it anymore, it's really difficult when others do it." (E2)

Once again, reference is made to the topic of competing on the ground of different ethical standards. In case of a public buyer, it might get difficult for a German exporter to address human rights issues right from the outset in a public tender, as expert E2 continued.

"And that's my problem, that I don't get kicked out during that time because the state doesn't want to answer that." (E2)

If an exporter has only little leverage, access to ESHR information of the project might be limited or not possible when the foreign buyer is unwilling to disclose environmental or social project information (Schöne-Alaluf, Bittner and von Waldenfels, 2011, p. 31). Before submitting

their bids in a public tender, they typically lack the authority to challenge the terms of the bidding process before placing their bids (ibid). At worst, from the exporter's viewpoint, the buyer might choose a seller who does not request information on environmental or social aspects (ibid.), a dilemma to which interviewee E2 related.

According to expert P6, specific assessment criteria would then have to be imposed.

"For some countries, I don't know whether this is the case - for example, in some countries where we have noticed that they are harsh, even towards their own population, the opposition, etc., there is sometimes the possibility of imposing additional review criteria (...) in exceptional cases; but if, of course, such exceptional cases were to become the rule, I wouldn't know to what extent Euler Hermes would be prepared to actually process them in this way." (P6)

Not only some host countries' contexts though, but also the temporal and spatial distance (Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 29) as well as understanding (or better: not understanding) cultural differences seem to enhance human rights risks in export finance, which the following two statements of exporter representative E2 show.

"(...) it is sometimes difficult to find a suitable contact person who can also answer this at the time, who doesn't then say, I'll do it later; and you say, but I need it now". (E2)

"And I have to admit, you can - you sit there and say, why is the religious purity of the Ganges affected by this? You have no idea, you need cooling water. And then it's just not that easy to understand. And if you're an environmental lawyer by training, you're aware of the problem and you say, yes, but it's obvious. And as a technical company, you're really out of your depth, because you stand there and think, what's this all about?" (E2)

7.4.5 Summary

The ECA context is a complex one for realising BHR aspects. A wide range of stakeholders is involved who seek to pursue and realise their specific interests. The influence of German politics and German political affairs on the ECA also became clear from the interviews. Among the experts, there is a desire to streamline seemingly parallel processes, e.g. as part of the project appraisal, for which transparency between the actors would first have to be created.

Moreover, as a financial institution, the ECA is associated with many potential human rights risks via its clients and their foreign project partners, which means that there is a fundamental challenge of scale and scope regarding negative human rights impacts and risks. Finally, the interviews outlined that economic aspects have always played an important role in export promotion, especially on the part of the applicants. These partly seem to contradict with human

rights requirements which have developed in the course of time. The balancing of both strands could obviously not yet be achieved, at least according to the interview data.

7.5 Conclusion

Human rights are, as shown in this chapter, already an issue in German export promotion. They are addressed in the benchmark standards on which the project assessments are based. In this regard, the protection and realisation of human rights at project sites could improve from the recent upgrading of the IFC Performance Standards as the primary benchmark standard. Moreover, human rights also play a role regarding any existing exclusion list. In contrast to such lists, several interviewees suggested to make the greatest possible efforts to ensure that human rights are respected and even enable that human rights improve by export support, especially in critical circumstances from a human rights perspective.

At the same time, the interviews revealed a lack of fundamental understanding of what human rights are in the ECA context. Human rights knowledge is diverse among the ECA stakeholders, and the Common Approaches do not seem to provide the necessary clarity in this regard. Because of their intangible nature, some experts might have a rather defensive attitude to human rights. Translating human rights in the ECA context into granular aspects could contribute to a better understanding and goodwill towards human rights, especially on the part of the guarantee applicants.

The interviews also showed that the ECA context is a complex setting for BHR. According to the interviewees, there are several reasons for this complexity, first and foremost the large number of stakeholders and interests, including the political sphere and involvement. In addition, there seem to be parallel processes that could be organised more efficiently through networking, yet limited transparency among the different actors appears to make this difficult. Moreover, as a financial institution, the German ECA is connected to a multitude of potential or actual human rights risks which are said to be at the same time more difficult to grasp than in the context of corporate supply chains. Finally, it has been worked out that there is a conflict between the ECA's original task of facilitating exports and the human rights requirements that have become necessary in the course of time. Nevertheless, it must be emphasised that there is much more respect and mutual understanding within the stakeholder community than some might assume, e.g. from the findings of the literature review.

In any case, ECAs hold a distinctive position in the global economic framework as entities of sovereign nations (Hickie, 2009, p. 588). Looking at Germany, one exporter representative labelled the German ECA as “*the world’s most puzzling institution*” (E3). Based on the above, the second part of the overall research question – concerning the HRDD requirements pertaining to the ECA business, as outlined in the UNGPs – requires examination. The

following Chapter 8 will deal with precisely this, by analysing the interview data in terms of what the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD are in the ECA context, and especially at the level of this puzzling institution.

Chapter 8: Human Rights Due Diligence in the Export Credit Agency Context

8.1 Introduction

The previous chapter showed that human rights are already addressed in the context of the German ECA. There are certain challenges though that make it difficult to consider human rights more comprehensively. This chapter will now shed light on the topic of HRDD in this very context. The questions on HRDD which guided the literature review – the question of the meaning of HRDD in the context of state export credit guarantees; of expectations towards HRDD in this regard; of the various elements of HRDD; and of difficulties and limitations which might exist concerning HRDD in the ECA business – also guided the expert interviews. While turning directly to ECAs, Ruggie admitted that his recommendations “leave important practical questions unanswered” (Ruggie, 2010b, p. 7). The interviews should specifically target these questions that are pertinent to the implementation of HRDD.

Against this background, it will be illustrated in this chapter what experts understand by HRDD, which elements of HRDD are already existing in the ECA business, and which are still to be clarified. In addition, it is also proposed how the scope of ECA HRDD as defined in the UNGPs could be concretised, especially for practical use. Moreover, this chapter also attempts to identify what could be useful for a common understanding of HRDD among the interview experts, i.e. stakeholder groups, of the German ECA. In doing so, this chapter therefore addresses the part of the research question that relates to the HRDD requirements of state ECAs as laid down in the UNGPs, especially with regard to the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD in the ECA context. This is intended to contribute to the operationalisation of GP 4 in particular.

8.2 Diverse Understanding of HRDD

The literature review pointed out that the precise meaning and scope of HRDD have remained unresolved up until today (Grabosch and Scheper, 2015, p. 8). The UNGPs themselves only give vague replies (*ibid.*). Moreover, due to lack of specifications by the Common Approaches, the UN Human Rights Council has confirmed that ECAs have to decide on particular approaches and methods for HRDD on their own and individually (Human Rights Council, 2018, p. 8). It is precisely this picture that is reflected in the interviews, which revealed that a different understanding of HRDD prevails among the experts.

8.2.1 HRDD Is Not Easy to Explain but It Is About Addressing Human Rights in Export Finance

The interviewees were asked what HRDD means to them, especially in the ECA context.

“I would say that it's basically a procedure for due diligence, as it's so nicely put. So it's actually a procedure that - I have to expand a bit, it's difficult in one sentence. So it's actually - it's a somewhat ambivalent concept, I would say. On the one hand, it certainly means a clear standard, i.e. that companies should not violate human rights. On the other hand, it also means a kind of, how do you say it (...), a standard of conduct, so basically a process that is intended to provide normative guidance, which is intended to ensure that human rights are not violated through relationships with others or through business practices at other partner companies, subsidiaries, etc. And the whole thing is actually essentially risk based. In other words, companies must identify risks and, if they recognise risks, take measures to minimise or eliminate them that somehow affect human rights. Of course, these also affect environmental issues. But in my field, it's primarily human rights.” (P2)

Apart from the fact that the expert P2, affiliated with a public institution, did not find it easy to define HRDD, HRDD seems to be understood as a systematic process guided by standards and norms, with a primary focus on preventing human rights violations through risk identification and mitigation measures, as presented in GP 18 and GP 19 (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 19–22). At the same time, interviewee P2 suggested that HRDD is somewhat ambiguous in the sense that there are two levels: On the one hand, the expectation towards companies to respect human rights, as the expert referred to a behavioural norm. On the other hand, HRDD would be a guideline that provides orientation to fulfil this expectation.

The challenge of defining HRDD also becomes apparent in the following example, provided by exporter representative E1.

“Yes, this is actually not a very simple question, but I would like to reduce it to the formal aspects, so to speak, because these are also the points of contact that we as an export company now have with this topic. You are no doubt familiar with these questionnaires that play a role in the ESHR assessment (...) I mean, they list the things that need to be checked. Yes, I'll start with these fundamental and serious interventions such as resettlement, expropriation of land, how are minorities affected by the project or perhaps even particularly affected, were there, are there grievance mechanisms - not just grievance mechanisms, but was there participation by the civilian population in the run-up to the project and has a grievance mechanism been set up? So these are - okay,

good, and then of course there are still the issues of labour standards and occupational health and safety.” (E1)

From the perspective of this exporter, HRDD means that potential human rights risks and impacts of foreign projects are examined as part of the ECA’s ESHR due diligence (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date a), and certain – or granular, as stated in the previous chapter – human rights aspects which need to be looked at are mentioned. This very stage of the guarantee application, i.e. the project assessment, seems to be the sole connection of an export company with the ECA’s HRDD.

Bank representative B3 stressed that HRDD corresponds to a requirement for ECAs to protect human rights at the project site.

“So ECAs in the context of their projects should certainly - must for me ensure, just like the financing banks (...) that there are no human rights violations in the projects.” (B3)

The German translation of due diligence as a duty of care could explain why this expert sees a connection between HRDD and an obligation on part of the ECA, independent of legal nuances of “due diligence as a legal standard or duty of care” (Smit *et al.*, 2020, p. 260). This obligation would also apply to their institution, namely to a bank that finances an export.

Another expert from the public sector, P5, indicated that the scope of an ECA’s HRDD is not clear from the outset (see below 8.4.2) when stating that

“it’s about looking at the transactions you are being asked to support to identify what the risks and potential impacts are to human rights associated with that transaction or the export or the project, assess how serious those might be, prioritise them and look at responsibilities.” (P5)

In contrast to the previous two examples, interviewee P5 stressed that the ECA’s HRDD does not only refer to the foreign project. Moreover, it seems that the differentiation between the transaction, export or project need to be made. However, this is not apparent between export and transaction. According to the German ECA, both terms mean the same. Usually, it is referred to *exports* as *transactions* or even *export transactions* (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018). According to expert P5, the ECA’s HRDD would therefore relate to both the foreign project but also to the export itself which might include the respective supply chain of a specific export good. However, as this doctoral thesis is about human rights violations at the foreign project, this was not probed any further.

The above-mentioned risk identification does not only seem to be an important element of HRDD but also to depend on the nature of the project abroad. SMEs in particular are said to be more likely involved in projects that have less impacts on human rights. Accordingly, the

extent of the risk assessment as part of HRDD would need to differentiate, as expert P6 from the public sector pointed out.

“And, yes, I think you have to differentiate somehow in terms of the depth of the respective assessments, because of course it makes a difference whether I now have an SME that produces some equipment, assembles some machines and then delivers them here and there, or whether I have a large project financing that creates infrastructure on site, and then perhaps the previous work of the people, whether that is fishing, whether that is agriculture or anything else, is affected or changed in some way or negatively affected in particular, that is then already a difference.” (P6)

Even though not representing an exporter, interview partner P6 considered that SMEs tend to be involved in smaller projects, while larger projects such as project financing would not be carried out by SMEs and would also entail more serious human rights violations. Without going into more detail about the “special case of export credit guarantees” (Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 30), it can be stated that project financing relates to major projects (*Project financing | Federal Export Credit Guarantees*, no date) which can have considerable negative human rights consequences (Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 30) and therefore require a greater need to monitor human rights compliance (ibid.).

Interview partner E4, representing an export company, also related HRDD to the ECA’s ESHR assessment and emphasised the importance of its results regarding access to finance, i.e. obtaining an export credit guarantee, and stressed the significance of HRDD.

“Yes, (...) very important (...), because I think it is one of the issues in, let's say, this triad between eligibility for funding, justifiability of the risk and the issues of sustainability and human rights, which can play a role in determining whether we can really - do we have project realisation opportunities, good project realisation opportunities and do we also have the opportunity to gain access to these financial markets or to these insurance products? Yes? But it doesn't play a separate role, it is often mentioned separately. ESHR, I think it's called, environmental, social and human rights standards at Hermes. For me, this is a complex issue in this sustainability topic and also in the justifiability of the risk.” (E4)

This exporter representative E4 referred to the criteria for provision of cover, namely eligibility for funding and justifiability of the risk,¹⁶ both of which are stated as “key criteria” (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date h). According to interviewee E4, human rights are also part of these criteria and in deciding whether cover will be granted, as foreign projects are required to fulfil human rights aspects (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date g). An explanation of HRDD

¹⁶ See Chapter 2

was not provided for though by this participant, which confirms the perceived difficulty in this regard among the interviewees. Nevertheless, HRDD is considered important by the experts cited here, especially against the background of the already mentioned vulnerable socio-economic and political contexts in which the ECA operates, as the NGO representative N5 stated (see 7.4.4):

“And that is precisely the reality, which is why there should be the UNGPs with the whole due diligence process, so that human rights are nevertheless respected in countries with weak governance, yes.” (N5)

8.2.2 HRDD Is Important in Export Finance

As the previous quote shows, HRDD is thus seen as important in the ECA context, which is stressed by the following representative from a public institution, P3.

“I think it's important that, from my point of view, HRDD is always part of an overarching due diligence process, meaning that environmental and other social issues play just as important a role and that the whole thing takes place as part of a holistic process. And depending on the risks of the specific project, the focus is sometimes more on environmental issues, sometimes more on human rights issues. Sometimes they merge into one another, depending on how the project is organised.” (P3)

Interviewee P3 therefore considers HRDD to be an important part of the general due diligence process taking place at the German ECA, i.e. when the eligibility of funding and the justifiability of the risks are determined. This mirrors the statement of the exporter representative E4 above, while interview partner N5, affiliated with an NGO, provided the following meaning of HRDD:

“At the beginning, the topic of human rights was still taboo. And even environmental and social aspects were dismissed as irrelevant. And I think it's a huge advantage that this concept was created via the UNGPs and that it was somehow clarified what is state responsibility or duty and what is corporate responsibility? And in this respect, for me the HRDD concept primarily means that I look at human rights issues more comprehensively, not necessarily limited to a specific guideline such as the World Bank standards or IFC Performance Standards or something like that. And, exactly, that is the responsibility of the companies, but of course also a state export credit agency, so that they do their own thing, but especially of course with regard to what they support.” (N5)

According to expert N5, HRDD has given greater importance to human rights in the ECA context. Human rights would have been upgraded by the UNGPs and would no longer be considered an unthinkable subject ('taboo'), which this expert welcomed. At the same time, the previous situation was indirectly criticised, maybe based on their NGO affiliation. The

development of social and human rights aspects in particular for the granting of export credit guarantees was discussed in the previous chapter. Due to HRDD, which was introduced by the UNGPs (Barnes, 2018, p. 56), human rights would be more extensively addressed by the German ECA, particularly with regard to human rights aspects of the project abroad, which interviewee N5 appreciates.

8.2.3 HRDD Is for Companies Only

In the commentary to GP 4, States are advised to “encourage and, where appropriate, require human rights due diligence by the agencies themselves and by those business enterprises or projects receiving their support” (GP 4, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 7). Yet, by mentioning HRDD, GP 4 refers to the second pillar of the UNGPs, i.e. the corporate responsibility to respect human rights, as HRDD is only defined in more detail there. By means of GP 4, the 1st pillar of the UNGPs – the State duty to protect – meets the corporate responsibility to respect (Backer, 2017, p. 37). Perhaps the localisation of HRDD in the 2nd pillar of the UNGPs, as its “heart” (Backer, 2017, p. 38; Augenstein, Dawson and Thielbörger, 2018, p. 10), explains why HRDD is seen by some of the experts interviewed as relating first and for most or even solely to companies, as opposed to ECAs. This was indicated by the two experts N1 and N4.

“So, yes, what does HRDD mean, that you take your human rights due diligence seriously and that you adhere to the international framework, but also that you proactively look beyond that, perhaps to see where there is still no regulatory framework and that you integrate at least the core elements of human rights due diligence into the company.”
(N1)

“For me, I would say that this means that companies that operate globally are not only aware of the risks but also avoid them.” (N4)

Interview partner N4, which was assigned to the NGO sector as was interview participant N1, referred to the foundational principles of the corporate responsibility to respect human rights, including the key component of avoiding violating others’ human rights (GP 11 and GP 13, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 13–15) which can be met by exercising HRDD (GP 15, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 15–16; Sherman, 2021, p. 23). The first interviewee N1 did not define HRDD, but mentioned its ‘core elements’, which could link to those stated in the German NAP (The Federal Government, 2017, p. 8). Although all interviews related especially to the ECA and its respective human rights or even HRDD responsibilities, this was not taken up by these two interviewees. The following example from interviewee P2 shows even more clearly that some experts see the focus of HRDD on companies:

“Well, the expectation of the companies is that they should, of course, comply with the applicable international law, but also with the local, national regulations that exist in this area.” (P6)

Like interview partner P2 cited above who was related to the public sphere as well, the expectation aspect raised towards companies was emphasised here by expert P6. This could also be seen in connection with the German NAP, as HRDD and its core elements are set out under the heading ‘Federal government expectations regarding corporate due diligence in respecting human rights’ (The Federal Government, 2017, pp. 7–10). Moreover, interviewee P2 also explicitly aimed at companies:

“In other words, companies must identify risks accordingly and, if they recognise risks, take measures to minimise or eliminate them that somehow affect human rights.” (P2)

The relation of HRDD to companies and not to the German ECA becomes even clearer in the last example:

“Well, HRDD is a bit of a difficult term for me, to be honest, because - as I understand it - it's actually a term that refers to companies that have to ensure in their activities that they don't commit human rights violations in what they do or promote them elsewhere.” (P1)

Public sector representative P1 stressed that HRDD would rather relate to companies instead of to the German ECA. Therefore, none of the interviewees cited here, and regardless of whether they were assigned to the NGO or public sector, stated that GP 4 also explicitly directs to the ECA's HRDD. Interestingly, ECA applicants, i.e. exporters and banks, did not provide this distinction at all.

8.2.4 HRDD Is Approached with an Incomplete Perspective

The literature review has already shown that there is a different or incomplete understanding of HRDD with regard to the UNGPs, at least on the part of the German ECA who thinks of HRDD as a rather one-time exercise in form of an “in-depth examination” (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2019, p. 41) of human rights aspects. In line with this, interviewee B1 pointed out that HRDD is understood as a report:

“And I mean, one thing that could be done to increase transparency is to always require HRDD and then put that on the website with ESIA, right? Because the ESIA touches on sustainability, I mean social topics, but that doesn't go in depth.” (B1)

Bank representative B1 assumed that HRDD is something similar to an ESIA report which needs to be prepared and published for projects of the risk category A (Euler Hermes

Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, pp. 4–6). Social aspects, which include human rights according to the Common Approaches (OECD, 2016, p. 5), would not be covered as comprehensively by an ESIA report. The German NAP also mentions that HRDD reports should be introduced for the assessment of projects that are critical from a human rights perspective (The Federal Government, 2017, p. 17). It is exactly the project assessment where HRDD seems to play the most important role, also in connection with its possible meaning, which was referred to by the public sector expert P4.

“So, I see [human rights] due diligence primarily in the context of project assessments, i.e. (...) risk analyses, assessments also by independent consultants, then the mitigation measures that [are developed] for the individual projects, the follow-up of these measures.” (P4)

Chapter 2 already pointed out that the German ECA’s focus is on risk identification and assessment as part of its ESHR due diligence, as confirmed by the previous interviewee P4. When asked for the meaning of HRDD in their cooperation with the German ECA, bank representative B1 reflected exactly this.

“So, I guess it would mean for me examining the impacts to people and their rights in the context of these transactions.” (B1)

Expert B1 emphasised once again that HRDD is understood first and foremost as identification and assessment of human rights risks, which is the core element of HRDD (Koalick, Utlu and Bleckmann, 2016, p. 10). At the same time, interviewee B1 did not have a clear definition of HRDD and used HRDD interchangeably with terms equivalent to assessment:

“I think it's really difficult to do HRDD or assessment or like whatever you want to call it, like dealing with human rights stuff.” (B1)

The focus on risk identification and assessment as a starting point was also mentioned by another bank representative, namely B2.

B2: *“We have a sustainability mission statement, which can be broken down into a sustainability guideline. This guideline sets out the standards we apply and how projects are to be categorised. In principle, we follow the Equator Principles, which in turn are based on the IFC Performance Standards and the UNGPs. As a result, we assess projects according to these criteria, i.e. inclusion of vulnerable communities and the like. Of course, we also look at the labour standards on the construction site, so of course we also track special incidents and then try to address these aspects in our credit relationships (...) On the one hand, of course, it's*

clearly about first understanding where there are risks; on the other hand, avoiding them, and where they are unavoidable, mitigating them where possible (...) This is part of the credit assessment process, it is part of the credit approval and ultimately also at the back end in the portfolio management.”

Johanna: *“And is that also your - so that means HRDD for you, do I understand correctly?”*

B2: *“Yes, exactly, in relation to the lending [ECA-related] business.”*

Drawing to the bank’s own review processes in an export financing undertaking, the bank representative B2 stressed the HRDD focus on risk identification and assessment. It was also explained though that the sustainability mission statement and the sustainability guideline deriving from it would set the rules as to which standards should be applied when doing so. This interviewee therefore maybe provided a hint to another element of HRDD, namely the human rights policy commitment of GP 16 (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 16), which will be discussed below.

According to the NGO expert N7 below, HRDD in the context of ECA funding means to consider the overall human rights situation of the host country, which, according to critical comments, has not been adequately taken place so far (GegenStroemung et al., 2013, p. 4; CorA. Corporate Accountability – Netzwerk für Unternehmensverantwortung, Forum Menschenrechte and VENRO Verband Entwicklungspolitik und humanitäre Hilfe, 2021, p. 13).

N7: *“Yes, in principle simply - so from our point of view that definitely means looking at the overall situation. I mean, what is the actual situation in a country, so to speak. And I mean, in recent years, with the shrinking space of civil society, I think it's also very important to look at that and - in other words, to look at the persecution of human rights defenders.”*

Especially HRDs, who are key actors of civil society (European Parliament, 2022, p. 6) and were mentioned in the case survey (Chapter 6), should be addressed according to interviewee N7. In case of ‘shrinking space’, CSOs face administrative or legal barriers created by governments (Ayvazyan, 2019, p. 6) or even attacks (European Parliament, 2022, p. 20), to increase the difficulty for them to operate (Ayvazyan, 2019, p. 6). This is why interviewee N7 emphasises that HRDD should consider HRDs.

For two further NGO experts N1 and N2, HRDD would primarily mean to comply with international and national guidelines on responsible business conduct.

“So, yes, what does HRDD mean, that you take your duty of care for human rights seriously and that you adhere to the international frameworks, but also that you proactively look beyond that, perhaps to see where there is not yet a regulatory framework and that you at least integrate the core elements of human rights due diligence into the company.” (N1)

“In other words, to fulfil all the responsibilities that have just been defined within the context of international frameworks, but also national regulations, but for me actually also industry standards, and to fulfil them to the best of our knowledge and belief and, if possible, to exceed them.” (N2)

These guidelines are often referred to as “the global frameworks” (Federal Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs, no date). According to the German government, the global frameworks comprise of e.g. the UNGPs, the OECD MNE-Guidelines, the ILO’s Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work, and the UN Global Compact (ibid.). Independent of these guidelines, HRDD would also mean to comply with voluntary sustainability standards of the respective industries (e.g. Aachener Stiftung Kathy Beys, 2015; Weiss, Hajduk and Knopf, 2017; United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, 2021), as interviewee N2 stated.

Both experts N1 and N2 refer not only to industry standards, but also to recently enacted laws in the context of HRDD. In the German translation of HRDD, the generic term of human rights due diligence must be distinguished from its legally binding standardisation and the associated concretisation into individual due diligence obligations through the German Supply Chain Act (Section 3, The Bundestag, 2021). Expert N2 might have therefore related to HRDD as a means of complying with a law such as the German Supply Chain Act. At the same time, however, the UNGPs emphasise that the responsibility to respect exists “over and above compliance with national laws and regulations protecting human rights” (Commentary to GP 11, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 13).

8.2.5 HRDD Is Something with Leverage

One exporters’ representative, E2, showed more of a blocking and even patronising attitude towards HRDD, as they replied that HRDD would mean

“(a) lot of work. Because there are a lot of people out there who want to save the world. And we have to argue with factual arguments. And that’s often difficult when they simply claim that it works, full stop.” (E2)

It appears that the exporter anticipated challenges in improving a project’s human rights situation, recognising limitations in their ability to exert influence, especially when dealing with

short-term export credit arrangements or when their stake in the project is only minimal (Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 29). The topic of leverage was also mentioned by other interview partners with regard to the meaning of HRDD, but in two very different directions. The following statement provided by public sector expert P5 relates to the fact that the exporter or the ECA must have influence on the foreign project to improve the human rights situation there, i.e. leverage on the practices of another party that negatively impact human rights (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2014, pp. 29, 43).

“Again, it’s a leverage issue whether the exporter actually has any leverage to effect changes or not, whether you can have a link with the project sponsor, whether you have a link to other ECAs, perhaps to a direct lender who’s got influence”. (P5)

This necessary leverage can therefore also come about indirectly, e.g. in interaction with other ECAs and above all with a direct lender (in contrast to the German pure cover ECA).

Another NGO expert, N3, sees HRDD in connection with export credit guarantees primarily as an opportunity for the state to exert particular influence on the guarantee recipients to demand and promote compliance with human rights standards, for example.

“The way I look at it, it is an important topic because it falls under the first pillar of the UNGPs, i.e. an area in which states have more influence than on the average economy, I would say, which is because the state either gives money, loans or at least provides security. In other words, the state can access individual economic projects in a different way. And in my opinion, this additional leverage should also be used to realise the expectations that the federal government has expressed for the economy, namely the UNGPs, which then actually also provide support where they have a special power to do so” (N3)

In the ECA context, according to interviewee N3, the German state can push for responsible business conduct, as companies need state support in order to realise their export transactions, and this support could be linked to certain requirements. The German government’s expectation that companies implement the UNGPs is mentioned as one of these requirements, which is reflected in the German NAP (The Federal Government, 2017, pp. 7–9) and especially in the context of export credit guarantees (ibid., p. 17; Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date g). Moreover, the state should use their leverage when they provide export support, i.e. by requiring HRDD (Backer, 2017, p. 41).

8.2.6 Summary

Among the experts interviewed, there is no standardised definition of HRDD with reference to ECAs. Rather, the examples cited here show that the experts consider HRDD to be important,

and that HRDD aims at improving the protection of human rights at the level of projects abroad. Beyond this, however, there is only a vague understanding of HRDD in the context of the German ECA. The UNGPs identify HRDD as a key ongoing management concept (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2012, p. 6) for avoiding, preventing, mitigating and accounting for potential or actual negative impacts on human rights caused by business activities (GP 17, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 17). The experts interviewed seem to have an incomplete understanding of HRDD compared to the requirements of the UNGPs. While the central element of HRDD, risk identification and assessment, was often mentioned, there was, for example, no reference to the need to account for how companies and the German ECA address human rights risks. Therefore, the following section discusses which elements of HRDD exist in the ECA context, and which elements may require greater attention or clarification.

8.3 Important Elements of HRDD in the ECA Context

The previous section has shown that there is no uniform definition of the meaning of HRDD among the interviewees. As mentioned though, several important elements are already established in the ECA context, above all the element of identification and assessment of human rights risks at the project abroad. In the following, it will be discussed in more detail what exactly HRDD means for the ECA against the background that states should promote HRDD including from the ECAs themselves (Commentary to GP 4, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 7).

8.3.1 HRDD Is Not New in the ECA Context

Risk identification and assessment is seen by the interviewees as the most important element of HRDD without which further HRDD steps would not make any sense.

“I first have to see and recognise what the problems are, because if I don't get that, the whole circle won't work for me. And that's also more important than a policy statement. I first need to have the issue on my radar and be able to identify the problems in a project (...) for me, recognising it in the first place is the basis of everything”. (B3)

Bank representative B3 considered risk assessment and identification as both the initial step but also as the basic prerequisite for the entire HRDD process. This is also reflected in the UNGPs (Commentary to GP 18, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 19), and also in the following two quotes provided by the NGO expert N1 as well as the public sector expert P4.

“(T)hat risk analysis should actually be the starting point, I think - makes perfect sense.”
(N1)

“So, [it] is somehow the basis for everything that comes afterwards. If you have poor identification processes and overlook things, then the others after that make less sense.”
(P4)

Interviewee P4 did not only emphasise the importance of a robust identification process at the beginning. They suggested that if this initial process is weak, subsequent steps become less meaningful or effective, as they build upon the previous ones. Chapter 2 has outlined that the ECA's focus is on identifying risks to and negative impacts on human rights. The experts interviewed confirmed that the core element of HRDD is therefore implemented in the ECA context as part of the ESHR review. As previously discussed, there are several shortcomings of this review, e.g. regarding the benchmark standards or the threshold for the application of the Common Approaches though. Nevertheless, the fact that an ECA as a financial institution might be associated with numerous potential human rights risks (OECD, no date f; Shift Project Ltd., no date b) was again cited by the NGO representative N6 as a challenge for risk identification and assessment:

“So that - even that first step of risk identification has to be done in a, you know, at a degree of - at a fairly high level.” (N6)

Without explaining how the risk identification and assessment exactly could be done, expert N6 might have referred to the extensive client portfolio of ECAs (Shift Project Ltd., no date a) and broader business links (OECD, no date f), therefore the challenge of scale (Owens, 2021, p. 2), which would require such a high level risk identification and assessment exercise.

Remedial action and effectiveness control were also seen as important elements of HRDD which are already implemented by the ECA. Dealing with identified risks or even impacts would be particularly relevant for local stakeholders at the project level, as the public sector expert P3 stated:

“But of course this is probably the most important point for those affected on the ground, because the first priority is of course to avoid possible impacts, but then also to compensate for them or at least to minimise them and then to balance them out. So of course this is important in this respect.” (P3)

The sequence specified by the UNGPs – avoidance of human rights risks and impacts as set out in the Foundational Principles (GP 11, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 13) through HRDD, and prevention and mitigation in accordance with GP 19 (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 19–22) – is reflected in participant P3's statement. In accordance with the Common Approaches, the positive guarantee decision by the IMC may be linked to ESHR conditions that must be fulfilled before or after the final cover note is issued (OECD, 2016, p. 11; Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 5). Accordingly,

it is also important to follow up on these requirements in the form of monitoring (ibid.), which the following exporter representative E1 stated.

“This is followed, of course, by the definition of remedial measures, i.e. the problem areas that have been identified and assessed as such, where it is stated what can be done to eliminate these problems or, if not eliminate them, then at least reduce them to a tolerable level. Effectiveness checks, monitoring, yes, okay, that is of course the review of whether the identified problems have been remedied in the course of the implementation and operation of a project.” (E1)

The ECA monitoring is therefore equivalent to the tracking or effectiveness control according to GP 20 (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 20–21), and as explained by expert P3 pertaining to the public domain:

“And then, of course, the effectiveness checks to see whether the measures that have been agreed are then also implemented.” (P3)

Therefore, monitoring is closely linked to the remedial actions that take place in the ECA context, so that both could be regarded as one element of HRDD. The German ECA is seen as the necessary independent monitoring body (United Nations, 2011, p. 8) ensuring the implementation of remedial measures, as the following NGO expert N4 stated.

“Exactly, remedial measures, effectiveness monitoring, also in cooperation with everyone, but of course an independent body, in this case Euler Hermes, has to monitor whether this is being complied with. And monitoring is definitely very important with regard to this - I think it's important in the course of the process, they are also supported over several years, that you don't just get the blank slate at the beginning, so to speak, and then you can do what you want. I think that's also a question of man and woman power. And of course, independence, but I would like to assume that this all happens independently.” (N4)

Apart from stressing the need for independent monitoring, expert N4 mentioned the time component between the project assessment on the one hand and potential adverse environmental and social impacts that may materialise after granting of cover and which therefore gives reason for monitoring requirements (OECD, 2016, p. 11; Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 5). This was taken up by interviewee P4 from the public sector as well.

“Monitoring is, I believe, a point that has become increasingly important over the years, also in the context of ECA business, because of course the [project] assessment itself takes place at a certain point in time and the [human rights] impacts then certainly arise

over the years, especially in the area of occupational safety or similar topics. And even with larger issues such as resettlement, these are processes that sometimes run for 5, 6, 10, 20 years.” (P3)

The time aspect highlights the need for monitoring once again, which, contrary to expert P3’s statement, should therefore have always been important. The following remark from an exporter (E4) also explains its importance and at the same time shows that the topic of monitoring is considered important regardless of the respective institutional background of the interviewees (i.e., public, NGO, or export company).

“Yes, but remedial measures, mitigation, so that’s what has to happen. This is also a personal concern for me. If we identify gaps at the beginning or over the time of a project that do not meet international or even local standards and that we feel uncomfortable with when identifying it, and we see as a risk here, then clear remedial measures must be taken to prevent, end or... be initiated to mitigate. And of course this has to be, let’s say, monitored and checked sustainably so that it doesn’t get to that point.” (E4)

Expert E4 thus addressed some of the objectives of HRDD, namely that risks must be prevented and mitigated (GP 17, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 17–19), and that effective mitigation must be monitored or tracked according to the UNGPs (GP 20, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 22–23). At the same time, some of the difficulties associated with remedial actions and monitoring were addressed in the interviews. In this regard, the exporter representative E3 fundamentally questioned the concept of compensation.

“So, if I think now, compensation, it’s not good to do. It is - what price should be put on losing your home?” (E3)

Compensation, which is one aspect of remedy (GP 25, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 27) in the form of financial compensation, cannot be achieved in every case according to expert E3, so that a negative human rights risk may therefore be irreparable. Other experts saw the entire topic of this HRDD element as still insufficiently analysed due to several associated challenges.

“Where I believe there is no really satisfactory solution so far is in the area of remedial measures and monitoring. The options here are limited, i.e. legally limited and also partly limited by the resources the ECA has.” (P1)

According to interviewee P1, an ECA does not necessarily appear to have the influence to bring about changes at the project level. This was also taken up by the following bank representative B3.

“Effectiveness control, i.e. the remedial measures, how do you get the problems solved once you have recognised the problems? And I personally find that many people pull out of this or bury their heads in the sand. Also on the ECA and bank side. They want to get out of the problem. Maybe they threaten to withdraw cover or other things because the way to solve the problem is simply difficult or complex or they can't do it within a year because things simply take longer. But then you're actually missing the point. You actually want it to get better and not cover up the whole thing, I don't want to say cover up, but the bottom line is - say I don't want to deal with it - or I can't solve it, so I leave.”
(B3)

However, if an identified risk or negative impact, referred to by interviewee B3 as a ‘problem’, is seen as unsolvable for the ECA, too little would be done to improve the situation. The ECA would then not provide cover or impend to withdraw – as ECAs have rarely withdrawn cover (De Schutter, Ramasastry, *et al.*, 2012, p. 35). This contradicts the approach mentioned in the previous Chapter 7 of seeking to improve the human rights situation in a project by state export promotion (Haupt, 2024, p. 18). From the bank representative B3’s experience, the ECA would miss to openly reflect what the difficulties are in order to be able to cope with them. Nevertheless, the possibility of denial or ending an export credit guarantee cover was brought up by the subsequent interviewee P5 precisely in connection with remedial actions that may not be feasible.

“Well, I mean, the whole - you know, remedial action. You haven't - I suppose there's issues of prioritisation, perhaps it hasn't - that is an element to bring in as well as to - you know, where you can bring your leverage to bear. That's an element for the due diligence. And then equally, there has to be a - at some point, if you go down that line of prioritisation and leverage and looking at what you can do with remedial action, for instance, you almost need an arrow coming off, which is the go / no go decision. Because at some point, you know, you may be faced with transactions where you discover that there are things - that there are impacts or potential impacts or risks with the particular transaction or particular project. And you either have no leverage or it's not effective leverage. And then you are faced with a go / no go decision.” (P5)

Interview partner P5 stressed that if human rights risks or impacts cannot be sufficiently addressed by remedial measures due to lacking ECA leverage, the ECA should decide whether to support the export transaction or not. Though this decision-making step seems to be important, a sense of uncertainty about their suggestion to set up such a step is conveyed. Also, with regard to remedial action and effectiveness control, it might be challenging for the German ECA as a pure cover one to exert the necessary influence on the project in order to bring about change in its human rights situation (Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 68, FN 29).

However, if difficulties were identified as part of the risk identification and assessment, they need to be addressed as part of the remedial action and effectiveness control according to the interviewees.

8.3.2 Most Important HRDD Elements

In the course of the interviews, most interviewees pointed out those HRDD elements which they considered most important for the German ECA. This was sometimes explicitly stated, while it became evident through the focus of the interviewees' remarks at other times. The following table weights the HRDD elements mentioned according to the explicit statements or those interpreted by the researcher according to the Reflexive Thematic Analysis (see Chapter 4). It shows which HRDD element experts saw as most important (1), which as second important (2), and which was named as third most important (3). If no clear statement could be determined, a question mark (?) was set. The zero (0) indicates that this element was not considered particularly important. Even if an expert named only one HRDD element and emphasised its importance repeatedly, this was rated as their respective most important HRDD element.

Table 15: Ranking of HRDD elements

Interview Partner	HRDD elements					
	Policy Statement	Risk Identification & Assessment	Remedial Action and Effectiveness Control	Reporting & Transparency	Grievance Mechanism	Stakeholder Engagement
E1	0	0	0	0	1	0
E2	?	?	?	?	?	?
E3	0	1	1	0	0	0
E4	0	1	1	0	0	0
B1	1	0	0	0	0	2
B2	?	?	?	?	?	?
B3	0	1	0	0	0	0
P1	0	0	1	0	0	0
P2	0	1	0	0	2	0
P3	0	1	2	3	0	0
P4	0	1	2	0	0	0
P5	?	?	?	?	?	?
P6	0	0	0	0	0	1
N1	0	0	0	1	0	0
N2	0	1	0	0	0	0
N3	1	0	0	2	0	2
N4	0	0	2	1	0	0
N5	0	0	2	1	0	0
N6	?	?	?	?	?	?
N7	0	0	0	0	1	0
1	2	7	3	3	2	1
2	0	0	4	1	1	2
3	0	0	0	1	0	0
Points	6	21	17	12	8	7
Rank		I	II	III		

Source: Author's own compilation

To determine the most important HRDD element, three points were awarded for each “1”, two points for each “2”, and one point for each “3” (totalled in the ‘Points’ line). As a result, it can be stated that the HRDD element “Risk Identification and Assessment” is seen as most important. This is followed by “Remedial Action and Effectiveness Control”, then by “Reporting and Transparency”. The first two elements (Risk Identification and Assessment and Remedial Action and Effectiveness Control) have already been noted as existing in the ECA context.

According to the interview partners, however, the following section 8.3.3 shows that the third most important element, "Reporting and Transparency", has not yet been sufficiently implemented, though the experts considered this aspect important. It is reflected in the UNGPs as formal reporting and communication to ensure a level of transparency and accountability towards stakeholders (GP 19 and its commentary, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 32–33), and the German NAP also points out that enterprises should publicly report how they address human rights impacts (The Federal Government, 2017, p. 9). Irrespective of this, the interviews also revealed that the topic of transparency is also considered important in other HRDD elements, e.g. in risk identification and assessment, and not as a standalone element only:

"What I also understood (...) is that this selection of projects that are then funded is not designed to be transparent for all sides. A lack of transparency automatically means that only relatively few pairs of eyes, so to speak, with relatively similar perspectives are likely to look at it from the outside. And I wouldn't be surprised if the perspective of HRDD or, for that matter, human rights and environmental due diligence is underrepresented. But you can only identify and assess risks properly if you have a trained eye for them. And in this respect, if we take this seriously, it would be important to open up these processes and share them with people who have specific expert knowledge in this area so that we can then say afterwards, yes, we believe we have identified the risks properly and we can now prioritise them sensibly." (N3)

What becomes clear from NGO representative N3's statement is, on the one hand, external stakeholders' desire for more transparency in the application process, i.e. about what happens within the ECA. At the same time, the relevance of the ECA ESHR due diligence in the overall assessment of funding applications does not seem to be clear. In the following section, the HRDD elements mentioned here, which appear to be important yet not sufficiently implemented, will be discussed in detail. Beginning with "Reporting and Transparency", which was considered the third most important element by the experts interviewed, it will be demonstrated that this aspect requires a more detailed analysis in the ECA context, as is the case with regard to the ECA Human Rights Policy Statement, the Grievance Mechanism, and Stakeholder Engagement.

8.3.3 Some HRDD Elements Need to Be Further Looked at

The interviews showed that more attention needs to be paid to the HRDD element **transparency and reporting**. While ranked as the third most important HRDD element by the interviewees (see Table 15 above), the literature review has revealed the criticism of lacking transparency at ECAs in general and the German one in specific (e.g., United Nations, 2011, p. 2; Papp, 2013, p. 329; Heydenreich, Paasch and Kusch, 2014, p. 53; Krajewski, 2017, p.

29; Human Rights Council, 2018, p. 71). In addition, the researcher herself concluded that the German ECA's approach towards human rights remains rather ambiguous and opaque (see Chapter 3). Although this has not satisfied all interviewees, it was emphasised that there have already been some improvements in terms of transparency, as the public sector expert P3 stressed.

"So here, too, I would have said that the NAP has already moved a bit in the right direction." (P3)

The German ECA has stated that through the NAP implementation, human rights considerations were accorded greater importance during the ECA review process. In addition, the autonomy and prominence of human rights considerations in the assessment process were strengthened (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 2). However, according to the author of this doctoral research, it is unclear to what extent the review process has been harmonised and revised, especially with regard to the implementation of the core HRDD elements stated in the NAP, and whether HRDD reports have been introduced into the ECA review process (The Federal Government, 2017, p. 17). On the other hand, the two assessment examples mentioned on the ECA website ('Construction and operation of a fertiliser plant and a phosphoric acid plant'; 'Construction of a plant for the production of MDF boards') can be named as a positive example, which show, at least in German, that project-specific human rights aspects are dealt with and included in the (sample) assessment report (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date b).

"In the meantime, sometimes even publishing takes place. The little information that is published about projects sometimes also states the basis on which something is being looked at. And sometimes it also states that there have been some conditions. That's more than 20 years ago. Is it enough? No." (N7)

While there would be more transparency and reporting compared to many years ago, NGO expert N7 regarded these as not sufficient. From the perspective of bank representative B2, it was indicated that further improvements in terms of transparency were possible.

"I do believe that it is possible to report in such a way that confidential data is not disclosed. It always depends on how much of the names you then disclose, but you can, for example, how many deaths, what forced labour was found, perhaps again, if you can somehow cluster this without drawing conclusions about individual projects, clustered together by region. So, I - if you wanted to, I think you could manage that, yes. At the end of the day, I would say that this might not fulfil the information requirements of NGOs - yes, that's the case. But more can be done. You can certainly do more." (B2)

Although expert B2 implied that the information needs of external stakeholders such as NGOs

would always be too high and could therefore never be met, transparency could definitely improve. However, contradictory statements were made about this in particular. On the one hand, another bank representative (B1) mentioned that reporting and transparency would be the easiest HRDD element to fulfil.

“Reporting and transparency are possibly, in my opinion, the easiest thing here. I think it's easy, the probably easiest thing to just like write about what's going on. Talk to people, write about what they're saying. Right? And to publish that, right? That's probably the easiest step of this wheel.” (B1)

B1's statement shows a relaxed attitude to communication. Detached from the content that is reported on, the bank representative encourages a straightforward approach to directly engaging with others, maybe even highlighting critical voices, on projects related to ECA support. Moreover, the expert calls for simplicity in reporting about those viewpoints. On the other hand, though, transparency would be a very difficult HRDD element according to expert P3 from the public sector.

“Wow, I find the topic of transparency really difficult, to be honest (...) Of course you can always do more out of the interest in transparency, but you have to look at the limitations somehow, trade and business secrets and similar topics. Then some useful information comes into play, which can perhaps be problematic diplomatically or which can also be problematic for those affected on site. This is actually not an easy topic, I think.” (P3)

Even if interview partner P3 recognised that transparency could increase, the expert emphasised that there are difficulties in doing so and named some limitations. The topic of diplomatic relations has already been explained in the previous Chapter 7, and expert B2 above stated that confidential data should not be published. Regarding Shift's recommendation that ECAs should publish more on their use of leverage (Kovick, Vermijs and Davis, 2017, p. 15), another interviewee from the public sector (P4) pointed out that certain difficulties would exist in this regard.

“Use of leverage (...) is often not something that can be published in a standardised way in a process. This is really project specific. That always happens - it's new for every project, depending on which actors are involved, how early or how late [ECAs] join a project, and how big the order values are. So that depends on so many factors and sometimes just the counterpart you have in the ordering country. And I would find it difficult to publish more about it because it is also a sensitive topic in negotiations or in discussions about what can be achieved.” (P4)

Again, the protection of sensitive information which cannot be published was stated by interviewee P4, who therefore rejected Shift's aforementioned proposal. Leverage would

depend on specific project factors and not in a standardised way. It could therefore not be reported about because, for example, it could damage business negotiations if the exporter's specific foreign customer were known.

It can be concluded that the issue of reporting and transparency has not yet been properly clarified among ECA stakeholders, especially not in regard to its practical implementation. Most of the experts interviewed mentioned some limitations and difficulties; at the same time, however, there was also a great deal of agreement that the current status quo should and could be improved. This is relevant, as transparency and reporting are considered together as an important HRDD element which serves to provide accountability (GP 19, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 23–24).

Developing a **human rights policy statement** does not seem to be easy according to the experts interviewed. However, such a statement could help clarify the role of human rights, as mentioned below by some of the interviewees. In contrast to the UNGPs, the German NAP subordinates the human rights policy statement to HRDD (The Federal Government, 2017, p. 8). The German Supply Chain Act also regards the policy statement as part of the due diligence obligations (Section 3; Section 6 (4), The Bundestag, 2021), whereas both the policy commitment and processes to enable remediation forms the corporate responsibility to respect together with HRDD according to the UNGPs (GP 15 Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 15–16).

Although the UNGPs therefore do not assign the human rights policy statement (and also not the grievance mechanism as discussed below) to HRDD, they include these elements (Scherf, Gailhofer and Hilbert, 2019, p. 38). Moreover, subsequent standards based on the UNGPs, such as NAPs, the OECD MNE-Guidelines and the OECD Due Diligence Guidance for Responsible Business Conduct, explicitly allocate these aspects to HRDD (ibid., pp. 26, 38). Since the UN Working Group has agreed to the OECD's Due Diligence Guidance with the six core elements of HRDD (Working Group on Business and Human Rights, 2018), it can be concluded that the concept of HRDD has developed further. This is why HRDD is discussed either in its narrower sense according to the UNGPs (Scherf, Gailhofer and Hilbert, 2019, p. 38), or in its broader sense (ibid.) according to e.g. the "supplementary actions" defined by the OECD's Due Diligence Guidance (OECD, 2018a, p. 21).

The German ECA provides some information on the important role of human rights in foreign trade promotion in a section 'background information' (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date g). Maybe this is what the exporter representative E2 had in mind when stating that the ECA's policy statement would already exist:

"Okay, the human rights policy statement, that's actually largely already done." (E2)

Yet this does not seem to be understood as a human rights policy statement by other interviewees such as the expert from the public sector P6 who mentioned that they were not aware of such a statement.

"I don't think I've ever seen this point about the human rights policy statement before."

(P6)

Another interviewee from the NGO sector, N3, confirmed this:

"So, what I have learnt (...) is that there is probably no real human rights policy [statement] published on the federal government's website, i.e. the AGA portal, i.e. no specific reference to the central importance that human rights have and should have in foreign trade promotion. And that is, so to speak, one point that comes to mind in relation to the first - to the core element of the policy statement. So, if you expect the companies that you support with the help of these instruments to implement due diligence processes, then as an overarching unit you have to place this expectation very clearly at the centre." (N3)

Expert N3 not only criticised that a human right policy statement was not provided for any of Germany's foreign trade promotion instruments but also suggested its respective content. On the one hand, such a statement should clarify the important role of human rights in foreign trade promotion, which relates to the above-mentioned analysis of expert E2. On the other hand, the human rights policy statement should stress the expectation that supported companies implement HRDD. This in turn is reflected in the German NAP (The Federal Government, 2017, p. 18). According to interview partner N3, the website of the Foreign Trade and Investment Promotion Scheme under the Agaportal domain (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date j) should therefore include a human rights policy statement. Another NGO expert (N4) stated that the German government should provide for the human rights policy statement, which confirmed that there has not been any yet.

"As a state-owned company or organisation, Hermes should actually be given a human rights policy statement by the state actors, I would say. And to say, okay, these are the principles you must adhere to. After all, you have state money that you are distributing."

(N4)

Even if it must be clarified that Euler Hermes is not a state-owned enterprise but manages the export promotion scheme based on a federal mandate (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date u), interviewee N4's remark stresses that the German government should provide for a human rights policy statement directed to Euler Hermes. This should prescribe the rules the mandatory has to adhere to when managing the federal government's export promotion scheme. At the same time and according to the NGO representative N3 who has already been

cited, a human rights policy statement could provide guidance and orientation for applicant companies and banks with regard to the concrete anchoring of human rights in the application process.

“I would like to see a human rights policy [statement] that includes which topics are to be prioritised or which process steps are important and how they could be or something like that. So, a policy should be more than three sentences: human rights are important to us and should please be respected. This can be made more detailed and can provide companies with guidance (...) That you simply outline typical cases so that companies that may not have had this on their radar are made aware of it.” (N3)

Once again, expert N3 confirmed that the German ECA does not have a human rights policy statement but that there should be one. The human rights policy statement should include more than the aforementioned emphasised role of human rights and the associated expectation that guarantee applicants respect human rights. In an exemplary manner, it should elaborate on concrete human rights topics and how they are addressed to guide companies and raise their human rights awareness. Expert N4 therefore expects a human rights policy statement to explain the concrete handling of human rights. Interview partner P3 from the public sector agreed that a human rights policy statement should be more than only an expression and emphasized the explanatory aspect of such a statement.

“Human rights policy statement is actually a topic that I always struggle with a bit, because for me these are statements that are not relevant enough for me in practice. I understand that they seem to be important. For me in my practical work, they are often not. But I think that's a personal issue. So, of course, the policy statement should include – the processes should be explained, the background should be explained, perhaps the limits should also be explained, I think that's also important, which I sometimes find a little lacking in the discussion.” (P3)

Interviewee P3 does not seem to be able to do much with a human rights policy if it only contains pure statements instead of looking at the practical implementation of these. Therefore, in their view, it would be important to e.g. highlight possible limitations of ECA coverage regarding human rights in such a statement. The ECA's possibilities and limitations for addressing human rights as a financial institution was already brought forward by this interviewee (see Chapter 7). Colleague P4 picked up on this and explained it further, confirming once again that a human rights policy statement does not yet exist.

“I think it's an exciting topic. I think the only thing that needs to be considered for it to really make sense is that it's not just a statement that's written somewhere so that stakeholders are somehow satisfied, but that it has to be a statement that integrates the

entire processes and everything internally, so that it has practical relevance. And I think it's often the case that a human rights policy statement like this - you might commit to it somewhere, it's written somewhere, but in order for it to really have an impact, as it was probably meant to, it has to be able to do a bit more.” (P4)

Both previously cited experts P3 and P4 emphasised that a human rights policy statement should not exist merely to soothe stakeholders, but that its practical relevance is of utmost importance. At the same time, however, these interview partners do not seem to consider such a statement to be extremely important when they are mere statements and therefore lack practical relevance. This practical significance should already be unfolding within Euler Hermes, according to the following quote by another public sector expert, interview participant P2.

“So, with regard to the human rights policy statement, I would say that it must of course be appropriately comprehensive and unambiguous in terms of standards and therefore also clearly refer to international standards or, ideally, international rights. And it must be communicated seriously, I would say appropriately comprehensively, within the company and to the relevant levels. So, I think that first of all. It may be banal, but I've actually often noticed with large companies that it's not actually that clear what is formulated in the policy statement, or that what has been formulated as a policy statement somewhere by the 'heads of' is not necessarily relevant at all levels, but that things are then broken down to certain areas of work that actually no longer correspond to the policy statement, to put it that way. So those would be two points that I would emphasise.” (P2)

Interviewee P2 therefore stressed that a human rights policy statement should at least refer to international standards, e.g. the UNGPs, the OECD MNE-Guidelines, or the ILO's Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work (see the 'global frameworks' in section 8.2.4), or rather to the international human rights (see Chapter 2). Moreover, it should be known throughout the German ECA, specifically at all levels of Euler Hermes. Developing a human rights policy statement for the German ECA though would be challenging according to several interviewees, for example to bank representative B1.

“I think the human rights policy statement is the most important thing and probably also the most challenging thing. I think it's really difficult to do HRDD (...) if you don't know exactly what you're trying to achieve (...) maybe somebody's idea of a human right is a fair wage and a place to work and a good employer; and somebody else's from the same community idea is like, you know, the absence of this entity having their jungle remain pristine, etc. So, it's balancing people's expectations around what's important and what rights they sort of want to invoke. And I think that all comes into the policy that's sort of getting everybody on the same page.” (B1)

Expert B1 saw the policy statement as the basis for addressing human rights in the ECA context and enabling all stakeholders involved to have the same understanding of human rights. However, this was regarded as difficult, as human rights would not be understood in the same way by everyone who would bring with them different needs. Once again, interviewee B1 pointed out that 'human rights' need to be translated to concrete rights, including within the ECA human rights policy statement, as discussed in the previous Chapter 7.

According to interviewee partner P1 from the public sector, the main challenge would be to draw up a human rights policy statement specifically for foreign trade promotion, which they at the same time also did not seem to consider important.

"Well, with the human rights policy statement, we basically have nothing that corresponds to these statements that the companies have to make. This is perhaps also a little difficult (...) because the federal government has issued so many declarations. And it's difficult to somehow summarise or distil them. I wouldn't say it's impossible, but [Germany has] signed so many agreements and voluntary commitments that I think it's a challenge to make a human rights policy statement for [the] very specific area [of export credits]." (P1)

In contrast to NGO representative N3 who asked for a human rights policy statement for all of Germany's foreign trade promotion schemes, interviewee P1 doubts that such a distinct statement can be developed for the export credit context only. The expert pointed out that it was difficult to filter out one declaration relating to human rights and adapt it to the ECA from the many declarations that Germany had already issued. It therefore appears that a human rights policy statement is less suited to the ECA than to a company from this expert's point of view.

As a result, it remains unclear at what level a human rights policy statement should actually be formulated and published. On the one hand, this could come from Euler Hermes as a private company mandated by the German government as ECA, as stated by the NGO expert N4 above. On the other hand, it does not seem to be immediately apparent that the German government can communicate a policy statement solely for its ECA business according to the elaborations of the public sector expert P1. However, looking at the Dutch ECA, Shift has advised that Atradius Dutch State Business should have such a policy commitment to respect human rights, and which is embedded throughout the organisation (Kovick, Vermijs and Davis, 2017, pp. 4f; 10). This could perhaps also be applied to the German ECA. Nonetheless, as the following bank representative B3 stated, the origin of a human rights policy statement might not even be relevant.

"I don't know whether [Euler] Hermes itself needs a human rights policy statement or whether that doesn't go through the federal government, and there has probably already been a statement; I honestly don't know, but that's because it's one and the same in the end, of course - I would also think - I wouldn't give so much weight to the policy statement itself, to be honest." (B3)

Expert B3 views the ECA and the government as a unified entity from an applicant's point of view, making it ultimately irrelevant who of both issues the human rights policy statement. Above all, interviewee B3 emphasised that they do not consider such a statement to be important.

From the perspective of the interviewees quoted here, a human rights policy statement does not yet exist at the German ECA. It does not appear to be a simple endeavour to develop and communicate such a statement. At the same time, the practical relevance of a human rights policy statement is not clear to the experts, which can be seen from the fact that this HRDD element was considered least important (see Table 18).

With regard to the **grievance mechanism** as a further element of HRDD, the experts' opinions varied widely. Before discussing this, it makes sense to categorise the terms 'grievances' and 'complaints, as both terms are often used interchangeably in the literature and are translated with the same term in German ('Beschwerden'). Complaints are defined as informal claims and objections to management acts brought forward orally or in writing by the unrepresented employee (*Difference Between Complaint and Grievance*, 2020), i.e. one that is not represented by a labour organisation (Law Insider Inc., no date). Grievances on the other hand are formal written complaints submitted by a represented employee for resolution (*Difference Between Complaint and Grievance*, 2020).

While the BHR management consultancy twentyfifty mentions "mechanisms for human rights-related grievances and complaints" (Schüle *et al.*, no date, p. 40), they do not provide for an explanation of respective differences. In another guidance, the term "complaint mechanism" is also used several times under the heading "grievance mechanism" (AIM-Progress and twentyfifty, 2022, p. 27). In line with this, the NGO SOMO states that grievance mechanisms "are sometimes also called 'complaints', 'redress', or 'accountability' mechanisms" (SOMO, no date), whereas the UN Working Group asserts that ECAs could have a "grievance or complaint mechanism" themselves (Human Rights Council, 2018, p. 16) or require clients to have "an effective grievance mechanism" (*ibid.*).

Even at the level of the OECD NCPs, which serve as a non-judicial grievance mechanism (OECD, 2023a, p. 59), the term grievances and complaints are used as the same one. The peer review report quotes from the German NAP that "the NCP will become the central

complaints mechanism for foreign trade and investment promotion projects” (OECD, 2018b, p. 4), though the NAP states that the NCP “will be upgraded to become the central grievance mechanism” in this regard (The Federal Government, 2017, p. 17). Also, the OHCHR explains that the UNGPs and their commentary use grievance mechanism “as a term of art to cover a whole range of mechanisms that address complaints and disputes involving enterprises and their stakeholders” (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2012, p. 69), and that such mechanism might also be called differently (ibid.). Therefore, at least with regard to this dissertation, no further distinction between grievances and complaints seems to be necessary.

The UNGPs see the grievance mechanism as one important means to enable access to remedy, which forms the third pillar of the UNGPs (GP 29, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 31–32), but also to track the effectiveness of addressing human rights and of a business’s HRDD itself (GP 17 and GP 20 incl. commentary, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 17, 22–23). While the OECD sees the grievance mechanism as part of the supportive measures (OECD, 2018a, pp. 21, 34–35), it is a core element of HRDD according to the German NAP (The Federal Government, 2017, pp. 8–9). The German Supply Chain Act also defines the complaints procedure as a single duty of care through which business-related risks of and impacts on human rights and the environment can be reported (Section 8, Complaints Procedure, The Bundestag, 2021).

Because the German NAP has upgraded the German NCP to be the central grievance mechanism for all external trade promotion projects (The Federal Government, 2017, p. 17), the question arises as to whether this is sufficient from the experts’ point of view. However, the initial query that seems to arise is the optimal location of the necessary grievance mechanism, which the following expert P5 has not answered.

“This is a biggy. Should it be an ECA grievance mechanism? Should it be the project grievance mechanism.” (P5)

The question of localisation appears to be anything but trivial according to the NGO representative N6.

“I think it is context specific. One of my former colleagues now, but he was doing a great deal of thinking about this point because you have had some in civil society saying, you know, every financial institution needs its own grievance mechanism. Certainly, they need a grievance mechanism for their own operations. If, you know, for workers who are being discriminated against, etc., own operations stuff (...) And we don’t need to say, you know, blanket statement, every ECA should have a grievance mechanism that client – that, you know, stakeholders affected by client activities should be able to contact. But what we can say for certain is that they should have access to remedy.” (N6)

Apart from the fact that expert N6 briefly emphasised that a grievance mechanism must be in place for internal matters, this interview partner believes that not every ECA must necessarily have one for project-related grievances. N6 emphasised that it is not possible to say from the outset where this grievance mechanism should be located, i.e., at ECA or project level. It would be more important that those affected by business activity have access to remedy, which would depend on the context and could therefore be provided at either level. Moreover, the NGO representative N4 stated that it would be important that the grievances are processed by a competent body with knowledge of the ECA business.

“(W)e always say that yes, if there are any cases - complaints - then you also need people who are familiar with labour law, environmental law, etc. to decide these cases. And that would be the same prerequisite for saying, okay, but now I need someone who is familiar with the whole export credit business to decide on this.” (N4)

In addition, the independence of such a grievance mechanism was stressed as important by the following bank representative B3.

“I always find the grievance mechanism (...) I imagine that – it feels like not enough attention is paid to having a neutral place. So really a place where people can actually go.” (B3)

Expert B3 seemed to point out that the grievance mechanism must be accessible precisely for reasons of independence, i.e. neutrality. If reprisals are feared, this independence, which prevents the grievance mechanism from being used, does not exist. In this context, the UNGPs refer to ‘barriers to access’ in the form of fears of reprisal (Commentary to GP 31 Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 34). Consequently, attention must be paid to the risk of reprisals against those affected or complainants (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2022, p. 43), which, according to interviewee B3, has not happened enough so far.

Apart from the question of localisation, the interviewees also did not paint a uniform picture with regard to the sufficiency of the German NCP as the grievance mechanism for projects in the ECA context. On the one hand, NGO representative N3 stressed the advantage of using the already existing structure of the German NCP.

“It’s not just a bad thing to use an instrument that already exists and is somehow established.” (N3)

Nevertheless, this expert N3 continued to elaborate that the German NCP needs to be improved in order to serve as a sufficient grievance mechanism.

“At the same time, very, very few mediation cases end up before the NCP, which could be partly due to the fact that it is relatively unknown and therefore very inaccessible. It is part of a ministry as a department, so to speak. So, as a citizen, especially if you are further away, so to speak, you wouldn't necessarily think that you could go there. And in addition, of course, it is also a mediation mechanism, which is based on cooperation and which, well, in the end probably has relatively little chance of those affected by legal violations actually receiving an effective remedy. I'm not saying that it can't work, but something has to change at the NCP.” (N3)

Interview partner N3 pointed out several weaknesses of the German NCP that exist in their view. Too little would be known about its existence and how it could be utilised, so that the NCP would receive only very few complaints. Moreover, there would hardly be any prospect of remedy for those effected, as the NCP lacks the power to order any remedial actions (OECD, no date). Some of this criticism and call for improvement has also been reflected in the literature, especially from the side of CSOs (Hamm, 2005, pp. 22–23; Heydenreich, 2006; CorA. Corporate Accountability – Netzwerk für Unternehmensverantwortung, Forum Menschenrechte and VENRO Verband Entwicklungspolitik und humanitäre Hilfe, 2021, pp. 28–29).

The public sector expert P3 acknowledged the need for enhancing the German NCP and recognized the ongoing criticism directed at it but also said that existing structures such as the NCP should be utilised.

“So, you could also simply try to optimise the one you have, so to speak, if there is still a lot of criticism behind it, which does come through from time to time.” (P3)

As the NCP is attached to the BMWK, it seems to be given a certain weight for hierarchical reasons in particular according to another public sector expert, interviewee P4, who believes that the NCP is better placed there than at the ECA itself.

“I also wonder to what extent it would really be an improvement if the grievance mechanism were to be located directly [at the ECA]. Because in my opinion, it's actually higher up in a ministry somehow. So, if a direct complaint is received, I would say that this is actually a higher authority that knows about it”. (P4)

The previously noted necessity for expertise in the ECA business is also evident from the following quote of expert P6, in addition to the aspect of hierarchy.

“So, I - in terms of perception – I don't know exactly what the frequency actually is, but the fact that it has actually been available as an option is definitely an added value

compared to the past, when there was no such thing. And I believe that this is also very well positioned in the form of the lead organisation.” (P6)

Expert P6 suggested that especially the fact that the BMWK, having a lead function within the IMC (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2019, p. 12), would be an advantage for the NCP as the ECA grievance mechanism. It would also be beneficial that the NCP could now be utilised in the field of export credits. On the other hand, several experts, not just those affiliate with the NGO sector, regarded the NCP as inadequate to serve as the ECA grievance mechanism.

“Somehow, I had the feeling that [the NCP] was a sleepy empty space (...) And it is unclear who is actually working there - people who have never really had anything to do with human rights and who actually have nothing to do with them. This would definitely need to be expanded institutionally into an advice centre”. (E3)

The exporter representative E3 claimed that the NCP was insufficient. It would be inactive and the human rights knowledge of the NCP staff questionable. A solution would be to transform the NCP into a more active entity that can provide human rights guidance and support. Further criticism of the German NCP related to *lacking independence* exactly because of its location within the BMWK (participant N7), *lacking awareness of its existence* (B1, N3), or that it is *not accessible especially for stakeholders abroad* (B3, N2, N3). These aspects are also reflected in the literature (Hamm, 2005), especially regarding the effectiveness criteria which the UNGPs require for grievance mechanisms to be sufficient (GP 31, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 33–34; Sanabria, 2021).

The clearest statement that the NCP is not sufficient as the grievance mechanism for the German ECA is comprised in the following quote, once again not by an NGO representative but a public sector expert (P1).

“Yes, I would say that this is a complex issue. So, the NCP is not enough, I would say, because - well, let's put it this way, the question is always, what should the NCP look at? As far as the companies are concerned, that's enough, of course. But the NCP is not responsible for what the ECA does. So, you can't lodge a complaint against Euler Hermes (...) with the NCP.” (P1)

According to interviewee P1, the NCP can only process complaints against companies and not against the ECA. If accurate, this statement would undermine the NCP upgrade established by the German NAP insofar as it concerns the ECA's own grievance mechanism, i.e. complaints against Euler Hermes in its function as the ECA. In summary, the interviewees find that the NCP, in its current form, is inadequate to serve as the ECA's own grievance mechanism.

As the underlying element for HRDD (Remmert, Koalick and Wilde, 2014, pp. 8–10; Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, no date a), the importance of engaging with people who might be or even are affected by the foreign project, has been highlighted in relation to individual HRDD elements discussed here. The UNGPs also stress that involving stakeholders is crucial for HRDD (GP 16, GP 18, GP 20, GP 21, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 17–24). **Stakeholder engagement** plays a significant role in shaping or guiding the process of HRDD, as HRDD is informed by it (OECD, 2018a, pp. 18–19). This implies that the insights, perspectives, and information gained from engaging with individuals or groups who may be affected by corporate conduct is key to HRDD (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2012, p. 33), and effective implementation of the UNGPs therefore relies on stakeholder engagement (Shift Project Ltd., 2013, p. 3). However, the interviews revealed that the topic has not yet been fully or for all ECA stakeholders satisfactorily implemented by the German ECA.

Exporter representative E3 considered stakeholder engagement particularly relevant during the ECA's core HRDD element, namely when human rights risks are identified and assessed.

“It has to be done. Yes? And I also think it is undisputed that it must become the standard in many subject areas. But in my perception, when we had new projects here, it was always part of the review process. And I also know ESAPs where this has to be verified, tested and reported on.” (E4)

According to expert E4, it would always be checked in the case of new project applications whether stakeholders have been involved. It is also clear from this expert's comments that stakeholder engagement must be made up for and proven if the risk identification and assessment has shown that this has not yet been done satisfactorily, by means of fulfilling the ESAP subsequent to the guarantee awarding (Deutscher Bundestag, 2014, p. 11). The following quote from interviewee P4 also emphasises that stakeholder engagement is an important part of the ECA risk identification and assessment process.

“And it is also, according to the IFC performance standards, a very important part of the [ECA project] review. The smaller the reviews become and the more risk-based they become, it is of course a question of what kind of review focus we have here. But, yes, I would say that this is one of the more important aspects of [the ECA] reviews.” (P4)

Interviewee P4 pointed out that the topic of stakeholder engagement has specifically been upgraded by designating the IFC Performance Standards as the primary benchmark standard according to the amended Common Approaches. For projects that fall under the Common Approaches, PS 1 – *Assessment and Management of Environmental and Social Risks and Impacts* – stipulates that engaging stakeholders must be addressed (International Finance

Corporation, 2012, pp. 7–9). The ECA does not carry out this engagement itself, but relies on its clients, who in turn must ensure and prove that consultations take place (Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 47). Therefore, ECAs have to ensure that their project reviews are based on the perspective of affected stakeholders (Kovick, Vermijs and Davis, 2017, p. 16), and they have to assess the credibility and effectiveness of the stakeholder engagement processes of clients and their project partners (ibid.). The ECA is not the active party here but must assess the extent to which stakeholder engagement processes are reliable (ibid.).

If stakeholders cannot be engaged, bank representative B3 suggested that this should lead to the rejection of a guarantee application.

“In some other countries, it probably works well to create a transparent position. But in a country that is, I don't know, so corrupt or something... And then the question is, do you want to do something like that? Yes, and I would like to see a bit more honesty from the ECAs, for example (...) So to say faster, for example, is not possible? You can't involve the local people (...) So get a report, take a look at it and then make the decision (...) There may be grey areas, but I either respect human rights or I don't respect them. There's really no in-between for me.” (B3)

On the hand, the importance of involving stakeholders and allowing them to express their opinions freely, by attaching stakeholder engagement to an independent body, was emphasised by expert B3. The results of stakeholder consultations – here referred to as a report – should be included in the project review done by the ECA (Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 45; OECD, 2016, pp. 9–10). The interview partner B3 stressed that stakeholder engagement is a human right, as set out, for example, in the Right to Participate in Public Life (Erfurt Global Justice Clinic, Deutsches Institut für Menschenrechte and Université du Luxembourg, 2023, pp. 5–7; Art. 25, United Nations, 1967). If stakeholder engagement is not possible, this should therefore result in a denial for state export support according to expert B3, based on a human rights violation. This conclusion fits with the statement of the German ECA that foreign projects are required to meet e.g. human rights standards (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date g).

Against this background, stakeholder engagement is already a topic in the context of the German ECA. At the same time however, the difficulty in realising stakeholder engagement in what is assumed to be a proper manner came to light during the interviews.

“I mean, so technically it exists, right? Technically, on these projects you're supposed - I mean stakeholder engagement is a required thing to do, right? But there's no real framework for doing that right.” (B1)

Engaging with stakeholders seems a challenging undertaking due to lacking guidance or

structure, as bank representative B1 put it. From the perspective of a project reviewer on the side of the ECA or a bank, assessing the quality of stakeholder engagement that took place and is checked upon by means of the respective report is almost impossible, as this expert continued to elaborate.

“And so, you’ll see in a report pictures of people sitting in a room, and somebody is telling them something at the front of the room. But beyond that, how can you really assess what’s going on in terms of stakeholder engagement, how effective it is, what’s being discussed? I feel like that’s really poorly understood. And definitely at Euler Hermes people are basically assessing yes or no on stakeholder engagement. Is it getting done somehow or not? Is something in this report addressing a stakeholder engagement or not? They’re not looking at the quality of that at all. And so, it would be really helpful, I think, to have a framework for stakeholder engagement or best practices around stakeholder engagement, what needs to be done, what needs to be documented around that in order to - for an assessor to be able to tell is it good or not?” (B1)

The framework which expert B1 said to be missing should address some of the difficulties identified here. It would enable to evaluate the significance and effectiveness of the stakeholder engagement, i.e. not only that consultations took place, which might be proven by a photograph, but also how they were organised and whether they were effective. This effectiveness includes two aspects. First, it means the selection of suitable stakeholders such as vulnerable ones, who could face substantial impacts yet wield minimal influence over the business activity (Shift Project Ltd., 2013, p. 6). In the example provided by expert B1 however, the people invited for the engagement session did not seem to be either the relevant stakeholders or were not informed about the potential negative project impacts on their lives, which are necessary aspects though (ibid., 6-9).

Second, the effectiveness of stakeholder engagement is demonstrated by the fact that stakeholder concerns could be heard, understood, and responded to (ibid., p. 10). This effectiveness is depending on the context in which stakeholder engagement takes place. The interviewees mentioned various aspects in this regard, some of which have already been addressed here. From identifying and selecting the ‘right’ stakeholders as described by Shift above, to those who can speak freely and do not have to fear reprisals, to the influence of being able to demand stakeholder engagement as the ECA or guarantee applicant in the first place, and not the project owner, as the following quote from exporter representative E4 shows.

“And it’s also the case that, because we operate in foreign territories, we sometimes need leverage, and the national authorities very, very often have to play along. I don’t know of many project countries where you simply, let’s say, travel across the country as an external party and just, and I don’t mean this in a disrespectful way, but just chatter

away, yes? Or otherwise obtain a decision. And I'm not saying that in that way, because, yes, it's all too difficult for the industry and all that". (E4)

From expert's E4 perspective, further difficulties for successful stakeholder engagement lie in the willingness of national authorities to cooperate, in geographical and legal distance, and in access to stakeholders and their information. Foreign exporters would not be able to travel to a country and conduct interviews with people, due to a lack of leverage in that context. Another expert (P3), this time from the public sector, also stressed the importance of leverage in this regard.

"Apart from that, of course, ECAs don't have the influence in certain constellations or in the vast majority of cases, again the distinction between direct lending / pure cover, but even direct lending ECAs don't always have the influence to somehow set up a complete stakeholder engagement and somehow involve all local players. Not the knowledge, nor can they have it in every local situation; but also, not at all the means." (P3)

Especially pure cover ECAs would not only lack the necessary leverage to establish stakeholder engagement but also be deficient in specific knowledge and resources.

The interviews therefore made clear that the involvement of local stakeholders in particular is considered important and prescribed by the benchmark standards. Yet there is still a great deal of uncertainty with regard to the implementation of stakeholder engagement and the evaluation of its effectiveness.

8.3.4 Summary

As presented in this section, HRDD is not new in the context of the German ECA. The experts stressed that its core element, risk identification and assessment, would also be the most important one in state-based export finance. Remedial action and effectiveness control is considered as second relevant and, in the view of the interviewees, corresponds to ECA monitoring before or after the guarantee is granted. Although reporting and transparency is seen as the third most important element of the ECA HRDD, there still seems to be a lot of uncertainty in this regard.

Contradictory statements came to light in the interviews, showing on the one hand an improvement in terms of transparency, which would not go far enough though. On the other hand, transparency was seen as very difficult in the context of sensitive (business) data, among other things, while other interviewees saw it as the easiest HRDD element to implement. This shows that the transparency aspect still requires further analysis, also against the background that reporting and transparency enable the German ECA to be accountable for how human rights risks and impacts are dealt with (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights,

2012, p. 57).

While a human rights policy statement does not yet appear to be in place, the main questions relating to the ECA's grievance mechanism concerned whether the German NCP would serve as a sufficient means for receiving and processing complaints. Moreover, there is still a high level of uncertainty when it comes to evaluating the effectiveness of the stakeholder engagement process for which the ECA customers are responsible, but who often encounter obstacles themselves.

Although some aspects require further clarification, and consensus on the best approach to implementation has yet to be reached, the following Figure 23 can be summarised as HRDD elements for the ECA context and especially the ECA-own HRDD, distilled from the author's previous research and, after discussion during the interviews, slightly adapted.

Figure 23: Proposal for a HRDD framework

Source: Author's own representation based on the OECD Due Diligence Guidance for Responsible Business Conduct (OECD, 2018a, p. 21) and the German NAP (The Federal Government, 2017, pp. 8–10)

The experts interviewed widely agreed to the elements of an ECA's HRDD as summarised in Figure 23. This conceptual framework was developed on the basis of the research questions underlying this dissertation and their answers through the research steps carried out in accordance with the sequential explanatory design (see Chapter 5). As a result, six measures and process steps can be stated for an ECA's HRDD which the UNGPs provide for (GP 4,

Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 7), including several related sub-items.

- (1) In the human rights policy statement, the ECA should state that and how it addresses and respects human rights in its export credit guarantee schemes (GP 16, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 16; The Federal Government, 2017, p. 8).
- (2) The identification and assessment of human rights risks or impacts is the first element in the ECA's HRDD cycle and refers to two levels: the general transaction level to identify transactions for enhanced due diligence, and the specific human rights risks or impacts that could arise and need to be addressed within a given transaction (Kovick, Vermijs and Davis, 2017, p. 12).
- (3) If risks or impacts have been identified in the foreign project, the ECA must ensure that appropriate remedial actions are agreed to prevent, cease or mitigate impacts on human rights. Moreover, the ECA must monitor the implementation of those remedial actions as part of the effectiveness control, either before or after a guarantee is issued (GP 20, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 22; OECD, 2016, pp. 11–12).
- (4) In order to account for how the German ECA addresses human rights risks and impacts (GP 21, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 23–24), and to publicly communicate about the HRDD process (Kovick, Vermijs and Davis, 2017, p. 9), reporting and transparency are crucial (*ibid.*, pp. 15-16).
- (5) The grievance mechanism is another important HRDD element. However, it is not clear where this should be set up – at the ECA itself or at the foreign project. In any case, the German NCP does not appear to be the effective ECA own grievance mechanism without further ado. At the same time, the German ECA could, as part of its HRDD, take greater account of the existence of an effective project-level grievance mechanism (Kovick, Vermijs and Davis, 2017, p. 18).
- (6) Finally, as an underlying element of HRDD, stakeholder engagement is a key component throughout the ECA's HRDD process (OECD, 2018a, p. 50). In the context of ECA financing, this means that stakeholders directly affected by a foreign project need to be engaged (Kovick, Vermijs and Davis, 2017, p. 16), with the outcomes informing the ECA's HRDD. As part of its HRDD, the ECA should therefore ensure the existence of stakeholder engagement (*ibid.*). All experts agreed on this point, but it became clear that significant challenges remain in evaluating the effectiveness of the stakeholder engagement process.

8.4 Implementation of HRDD in the ECA Context

In addition to the HRDD elements that have not yet been fully defined, the interviews revealed that some aspects relating to HRDD are still unclear but seem relevant for implementing HRDD. On the one hand, these aspects refer to the scope of the Common Approaches. On the other hand, several interviews emphasised that the distribution of responsibilities among the parties involved in HRDD remained unclear. Both these issues will now be addressed.

8.4.1 HRDD beyond the Common Approaches

It became evident that human rights might not be addressed for projects outside the Common Approaches.

“And this is perhaps also linked to the problem that many areas in which the ECAs are active are not really - well, for example, if there are many small - well, there are also a lot of, I'll say, mass export areas where you somehow have smaller projects that don't actually fall under the Common Approaches, and where you would perhaps always say in individual cases, yes, that's not so relevant now because it's not so big, I think you have a relatively large area overall that is totally relevant in terms of sustainability, which is somehow not really captured”. (P2)

Expert P2 assigned to the public sector emphasised that smaller export transactions, i.e. below an order value of EUR 15 million, might negatively impact human rights (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date b). For these transactions, a project assessment according to the Common Approaches does not have to take place unless the screening has determined “a high likelihood of severe project-related human rights impacts occurring (OECD, 2016, p. 7). Yet according to interviewee P2, export transactions outside the scope of the Common Approaches should be looked at as well. The literature review has pointed out that the Common Approaches do not comply with the UNGPs (e.g., Scheper, 2013, p. 47; Human Rights Council, 2018, pp. 14–15).

Another interviewee (N6), affiliated with an NGO, criticised that many export transactions supported by ECAs are not looked at in terms of ESHR aspects, as they do not fall in the scope of the Common Approaches, when stating that

“there's so much that ECAs do that doesn't come under the Common Approaches”. (N6)

As already pointed out e.g. in the literature review, the German ECA has implemented a watchful-eye approach in this regard (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 10, no date b), which is referred to by the following bank representative B3.

“There is also this watchful-eye approach even in areas that are not specifically subject to a complete review. This means that appropriate tools are always used to check whether there are any negative reports and the like. I think that's already quite well organised. And then you could also investigate this point again, selectively, even below this threshold.” (B3)

Expert B3 seemed to contradict the above-mentioned NGO representative N6 when stating that the watchful-eye approach would cover critical (human rights) issues. Though with an acknowledgement that there could be further enhancements, this expert's statement conveys a favourable view of the watchful-eye approach. Expert P5 from the public sector saw possible weaknesses in this regard, however.

“The other is, of course, that what you capture in the ordinary transactions, in spite of the watchful eye, that you miss something. And that is a potential risk. Euler Hermes I would hope has, you know, in place its own internal red flags for those things.” (P5)

According to interviewee P5, human rights risks might not be identified via the watchful-eye approach, so that specific determinants or alarm signals would be required to address those risks.

Projects beyond the Common Approaches do not necessarily fall under the ECA's project review and are therefore not covered by the ECA's HRDD elements risk identification and assessment, and also not by remedial action and effectiveness control. As the German ECA itself has stated, the vast majority of guarantee applications are not subject to any further ESHR review (Fitschen and Osoba, 2018, p. 6). In 2017, out of 9.400 guarantee applications, only 85 (equalling 0.9%) related to the scope of the Common Approaches and were therefore fully reviewed (ibid.). 120 applications (equalling 1.3%) were identified for a risk-orientated review according to the watchful-eye approach (ibid.). In 2023, an ESHR assessment was carried out for 60 projects out of 5,767 guarantee applications, amounting to 1% of all applications (Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz, 2024, pp. 17, 24). The number of watchful-eye reviews was not provided. It can therefore be concluded that an ESHR review is not planned and carried out for the majority of guarantee applications.

Against this background, it could therefore be appropriate to define areas that are selected for enhanced HRDD independent of the Common Approaches (Kovick, Vermijs and Davis, 2017, p. 11). In this regard, certain areas that would receive less HRDD could also be pointed out (ibid.). However, the opinions among the interviewees differed. While some experts pointed out that something like this already existed and referred to the watchful-eye approach, for example, others thought that such a definition would be particularly helpful for external

stakeholders. However, the following two statements of interview partners P2 and N6 underline that an overview of projects for enhanced HRDD should at least exist for internal reasons.

“So, I would actually hope that they already have something like this internally. So, then I would say they should definitely do it.” (P2)

“And I think, for an ECA, I think it's really important that they are regularly looking at what is salient in their portfolio and being cognisant of changes to that. If there's a coup in a given country and the political context changes, that changes their salience assessment. (...) But they will have a proactive salience assessment, prioritisation, and being able to justify that (...) So absolutely, [ECAs] should be looking across the portfolio.” (N6)

The NGO expert N6 even emphasised that ECAs need to repeatedly look at their entire portfolio of guarantee instruments for enhanced HRDD because there may be changes of the (human rights) situation in the project countries. Maybe as an alternative, the following expert P5 pointed out that there should be so-called alarm signals, which could then apply to this entire portfolio.

“You know, those sort of red flag indicators, you know, I would hope that all ECAs should have those in place as to what becomes a high-risk transaction.” (P5)

The prioritisation mentioned by interviewee N6 was also taken up in the interviews. The UNGPs allow for prioritisation if not all human rights impacts can be addressed at the same time (GP 24, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 26). HRDD should then address those impacts first that are or could develop to be most severe (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2012, p. 82). As demonstrated by the case survey (Chapter 6) and confirmed by the interviews, it became evident that it is not feasible to establish a universally applicable rule in advance to determine which projects, sectors or export target countries of German exports are particularly risky and thus require prioritised attention. In this regard, some experts referred to the category A projects of the Common Approaches for which an in-depth assessment of ESHR aspects will take place (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 6), for example, while others mentioned different human rights aspects which would demand prioritisation of action, and still others mentioned sectors which differed from each other. In this respect, opinions were very mixed.

To summarise, the interviews revealed that there are some unresolved issues relating to the ECA HRDD that may require further consideration. One of these concerned projects which do not fall under the Common Approaches. For these projects, the ESHR due diligence will not take place, but a risk-based assessment according to the watchful-eye approach, yet without a comprehensive comparison against the benchmark standards (Euler Hermes

Aktiengesellschaft, no date b). The handling of these projects is therefore not in line with the UNGPs and especially their HRDD requirements. Moreover, areas that demand an enhanced HRDD or allow a prioritisation of the ECA HRDD could not be determined uniformly on the basis of the interview statements.

8.4.2 Operationalising Guiding Principle 4: Scope of ECA HRDD

The UNGPs state that HRDD should be required “by the agencies themselves *and* by those business enterprises *or* projects receiving their support (Commentary to GP 4, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 7, emphasis added). In addition to the ECA, HRDD should be carried out either by the customer or at project level. Because the ECA acts as a review body in the processing of applications (e.g. Raza, Schlögl and Pfaffenbichler, 2023, pp. 4–5), the question therefore arises to which extent the ECA should check, as part of its own HRDD, where the respective HRDD elements as defined in the previous section 8.3 are present. In some cases, the interviewees named one possibility per HRDD element; sometimes, they also found that both the ECA client and the project level have to provide evidence of an HRDD element. In other cases, the interviewees were not able to decide, as the following example of expert P2 shows.

“And that’s why I would say, yes, basically you would have to say that it has to be covered at all these levels and, yes, if it is now of course ensured that there are certain steps and measures, for example by the main project manager, that affect the entire project, then an ‘and’ would of course be superfluous. So, in this case it would be an ‘or’, but it must be ensured that these processes take place and that there are no business areas or activities at the end where the risk identification, assessment, remedial measures etc. simply do not apply.” (P2)

It would therefore be important that all HRDD elements are covered, and not by whom. The following NGO expert N2 took a similar line.

“And if, for example, the applicant has a grievance mechanism that works well and that can also be used for the project, then in my opinion it is not necessary for the project to have or demonstrate its own. But then the applicant would have to prove, so to speak, that [the grievance mechanism] is also sufficient for the project. If this is not the case, then another point would certainly be whether the project has something of its own.” (N2)

Expert P5 from a public institution also emphasised that no general statement could be made here, as it would always depend on the project constellation which HRDD element would need to be checked by the ECA and whether such an element existed.

“I think it's a two-step issue. If we're talking about a large deal where Euler Hermes and other financial institutions have direct access to the project, then I think that they should need to check that the project has all of these in place. The client is perhaps less. But I want to make sure still that the client has a human rights policy (...) But I don't think we would expect - if you've already got access to the project sponsor, you don't need to know that - whether the client has already looked at these issues. On other types of deal, I think, you're going to need to check whether the client has these in place and whether – as part of their policies, they have been checking the project. It's what I said at the beginning, there's no one size fits all (...) So there needs to be some flexibility on that.”
(P5)

P5's statement shows that generating the necessary information for this review depends on access to information, which in turn is defined by the size of the project and the players involved. While at least in the German ECA context the applicant usually collects ESHR information (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 3), it might be the case that the ECA has direct linkage with access to the project according to the expert.

Against this background, the following Figure 24 demonstrates that it is possible to assign responsibilities for individual HRDD elements to either the client or the project (shaded in grey). At the same time, the numerical distances between the statements are sometimes small, which in turn confirms that the one size fits all-approach mentioned above by expert P5 does not exist.

Figure 24: Relevant HRDD elements at client or project level

	Client level	Project level
Human Rights Policy Statement	12	9
Risk Identification and Assessment	7	9
Remedial Action and Effectiveness Control	7	10
Reporting and Transparency	8	7
Grievance Mechanism	7	12
Stakeholder Engagement	7	12

Source: Author's own compilation

Three elements stand out, namely those identified as relevant by 12 experts (Human Rights Policy Statement, Grievance Mechanism, and Stakeholder Engagement). On the one hand, the interviewees acknowledged that ECA clients should have a human rights policy statement, the existence of which has to be checked by the ECA. This point is not yet part of the ECA assessment, which relates to the project abroad (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2018, p. 3). Accordingly, this client-related aspect is not included in the general questionnaire (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date k).

On the other hand, it does not seem surprising that the interviewees assigned both the grievance mechanism and the stakeholder engagement primarily to the project level, as this is where human rights might be impacted and where the ECA ESHR due diligence focuses on (OECD, 2016, pp. 5, 7). The UNGPs stipulate that those actors who cause a harm are responsible for providing remedy, including the provision of a grievance mechanism (GP 22, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 24). The experts therefore seem to see this responsibility and causal relationship at the project level or with the project owner. As far as stakeholder engagement is concerned, it has already been explained above that the ECA checks whether this has taken place at project level. While the ECA client should ensure and prove that consultations take place (Scheper and Feldt, 2010b, p. 47; Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, no date k, p. 4), the responsibility for stakeholder engagement lies with the project.

8.5 Conclusion

As this chapter concludes, it is evident that operationalising the UNGPs in the ECA context, especially with regard to HRDD, poses both challenges and opportunities. The chapter has delved into the diverse understandings of HRDD among experts, emphasising its importance despite the complexities in defining and explaining it comprehensively. Notably, the chapter has highlighted a significant gap in awareness regarding the obligation for the German ECA to implement HRDD as a key management concept, including a complete understanding of the HRDD elements and process.

While the core HRDD element Risk Identification and Assessment is acknowledged at the ECA level, challenges remain in implementing Reporting and Transparency as well as Stakeholder Engagement, both of which were identified as two further most crucial aspects of HRDD. Moreover, this chapter underscores the necessity of exploring the establishment of a Human Rights Policy Statement and considering the implementation of a sufficient ECA Grievance Mechanisms in compliance with the UNGPs. A structured framework for assessing the efficiency of Stakeholder Engagement at the project level is lacking, while extending the ESHR due diligence to projects beyond the Common Approaches necessitates further exploration.

Complying with GP 4 underscores the importance of encouraging HRDD at both the ECA client or the foreign project, with emphasis on the presence and effectiveness of HRDD elements rather than their specific location. Yet the German ECA should ascertain the presence of a human rights policy statement among its clients and ensure both a grievance mechanisms and stakeholder engagement at the project level. Leveraging on the project level is paramount within the ECA's HRDD, enabling access to information and fostering improvements in the project's human rights situation. Yet exactly this leverage is sometimes limited for both the

German ECA as a pure cover one, but also for the ECA client, especially the exporter. This leads to a contradiction with the statement by Ruggie mentioned in the literature research (Chapter 3), who emphasised that ECAs have to assess the potential human rights impacts of projects, regardless of their leverage (Ruggie, 2010c, p. 2), and that leverage only becomes important once necessary measures are decided upon, i.e. after human rights have been assessed (ibid.). The issue of leverage appears to require further attention.

Building upon these insights, the chapter has presented a framework for HRDD tailored to the ECA context, comprising of six essential elements: (1) a Human Rights Policy Statement, (2) Risk Identification and Assessment, (3) Remedial Action and Effectiveness Control, (4) Reporting and Transparency, (5) a Grievance Mechanism, and (6) Stakeholder Engagement.

As the final chapter of this dissertation, the following Chapter 9 presents the concluding discussion of this doctoral research. It will delve into the implications of the main findings, examining their significance within the context of BHR. Additionally, it will address the limitations encountered during the doctoral project and offer recommendations for future research directions.

Chapter 9: Concluding Discussion

9.1 Introduction

This doctoral research has explored how the UNGPs can be operationalised in export finance, focusing on GP 4 and the required HRDD of particularly ECAs, but also of ECA clients and projects. The overall research question explored by this doctoral research was

- How are business-related human rights impacts addressed by state ECAs, particularly the German ECA, in order to comply with the UNGPs, especially regarding the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD?

Choosing the German ECA as the research subject, the research aim was to elaborate concrete proposals for implementing HRDD in public export credit guarantee schemes, by taking the following objectives:

- Review the literature on human rights in state foreign trade promotion with a focus on ECA support to (1) understand the challenges and difficulties regarding the consideration of human rights in the ECA context, (2) trace positive views by ECA stakeholders on how human rights are addressed, (3) trace negative ones, and (4) comprehend demands placed in this regard (Literature Review).
- Analyse existing cases on human rights impacts at projects related to ECA support to find out whether and how adverse human rights impacts are connected to a specific industry, a specific country or a specific project, and what the most salient human rights risks are in the ECA context (Case Survey).
- Interview 20 ECA stakeholder representatives with respective expertise in human rights-related aspects of the ECA business to explore how business-related human rights impacts are addressed and how HRDD is defined and implemented (Expert Interviews).

This thesis has demonstrated that human rights are already addressed in Germany's export promotion scheme and that important HRDD elements are already established in the German ECA context. However, the data illustrates a lack of fundamental understanding of what human rights are and what HRDD means in the ECA context. Based on the research conducted within this study, a framework for HRDD tailored to the ECA context has been presented, comprising of six essential elements: (1) a Human Rights Policy Statement, (2) Risk Identification and Assessment, (3) Remedial Action and Effectiveness Control, (4) Reporting and Transparency, (5) a Grievance Mechanism, and (6) Stakeholder Engagement.

This chapter reflects on and summarises the key findings of this doctoral research. It also discusses personal reflections and highlights the original contribution to knowledge. In addition, the chapter includes a discussion of the insights the findings provide for broader debates on polycentric governance. It then critically assesses the potential limitations of this doctoral project and offers recommendations for future research, before concluding this thesis with a final statement.

9.2 Reflections

At the conclusion of a research project, it is essential for a researcher to reflect on their work (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 12, Figure 1.2). Following Kolb's (1984) cycle of reflective practice, the author of this doctoral study will now present the insights gained from her research on the implementation of the UNGPs and specifically GP 4 in the ECA context. This may provide valuable guidance for her future research endeavours, while also offering insights that could benefit other researchers exploring human rights in export finance.

The author began this doctoral research project aiming at contributing to answering existing ECA-related questions regarding the operationalisation of the UNGPs in general and HRDD in specific, which she was not able to turn to within the framework of her everyday work as a Sustainability Adviser of the German ECA. As this doctoral study progressed, the author came to recognise two key aspects whose significant influence on answering the overall research question had previously been underestimated in the literature reviewed.

On the one hand, it is important to highlight the complex setting of the ECA business within the context of BHR. This setting is characterised not only by diverse players involved with their distinct interests and tasks, but also by the influence of (current) German politics and political affairs and interest on the design and implementation of export finance policies, including the consideration of human rights. Additionally, and contributing to this complexity, there is a fundamental challenge of scale and scope for an ECA regarding negative human rights risk and impacts, as has become clear from the interviews, but is also echoed in the literature (Owens, 2021, p. 2). Given their role as a financial institution, these risks and impacts are said to be more difficult to grasp than in the context of corporate supply chains.

Moreover, and in contrast to companies, there are two levels of the ECA business that are relevant for considering human rights, namely the general transaction level to identify transactions for enhanced ESHR due diligence, and the specific human rights risks or impacts that could arise and need to be addressed within a given transaction. Finally, there is potential for conflict between the ECA's original task as an instrument of foreign trade promotion and the necessary human rights requirements that have evolved over the course of time, requiring that economic interests must be balanced with human rights.

On the other hand, the author has illustrated that there is a considerable level of respect and mutual understanding among the different ECA stakeholder groups. Contrary to what one might expect based, for example, on the findings from the literature review, the various stakeholders maintain their respective opinions and interests, yet share a common desire to adopt a pragmatic, i.e., realistic, approach to addressing human rights issues in export promotion. All interview partners consider human rights to be important in the ECA context and recognise the potential for improvement in how they are addressed and accounted for. At the same time, the experts interviewed acknowledged that making excessive demands to address human rights are unproductive; instead, the focus should be on ensuring that these needs are realistically attainable.

9.3 Human Rights in the Export Credit Agency Context

The topic of human rights in state export finance was important to explore in greater detail to contribute to the existing body of knowledge and address gaps in understanding. Projects related to ECA support are often associated with negative impacts on human rights (United Nations, 2011, p. 2). This may be exacerbated by the fact that, as the data show, human rights risks are inherent in the ECA context. The UNGPs also respond to this. Within the State-business nexus of GP 4, the UNGPs call on States to take “additional steps” to protect against human rights violations (Office of the High Commissioner, 2011, p. 6). Yet what these steps are about, remains open. The literature review undertaken by the researcher revealed several allegations *that* human rights are insufficiently considered in the ECA context and at the same time concluded that there are only few concrete proposals on *how* human rights can be better addressed. Moreover, there is no common understanding among the range of ECA stakeholders across governments, ECA employees and clients, research and science institutions or NGOs on the proper approach to addressing human rights. The aim of this doctoral work was to contribute to closing this gap in research.

The data illustrates that human rights are addressed and considered important in Germany’s export promotion scheme. Yet there is a fundamental lack of knowledge in relation to what human rights are in the ECA context, and a lack of clarity regarding the precise interpretation of human rights. This could be the reason for the partly defensive attitude to human rights which came to light from both the literature review and the expert interviews. However, it also explains that it is difficult to take better account of human rights when their meaning – in terms of its concrete definition and handling, as well as their importance – has yet to be clarified.

9.4 Human Rights Due Diligence in the Export Credit Agency

Context

Apart from the fact that the particular meaning and scope of HRDD remains unresolved (Grabosch and Scheper, 2015, p. 8), and “specific methods for [HRDD] are left to the discretion of the individual export credit agencies” (Human Rights Council, 2018, p. 12), the literature review has highlighted a lack of consensus among the ECA stakeholders on what HRDD should entail. This research has demonstrated that there is not only a diverse understanding of HRDD, but also no standardised definition of it. While the German ECA focuses on the central HRDD element Risk Identification and Assessment and has implemented respective Remedial Action and Effectiveness Control as part of the ECA monitoring before or after the guarantee is granted, a complete understanding of the HRDD elements in total and its process does not exist.

Although Reporting and Transparency is seen as the third most important element of the ECA HRDD, there still seems to be a lot of uncertainty in this regard, often related to commercially sensitive information that cannot be shared. As the ECA should account for how human rights risks and impacts are dealt with (GP 21, Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, pp. 23–24), further analysis is required. Other HRDD elements that need additional clarification relate to the Human Rights Policy Statement and the implementation of a sufficient ECA-own Grievance Mechanism in compliance with the UNGPs. Finally, it has been demonstrated that a structured framework for assessing the efficiency of Stakeholder Engagement at the project level is lacking.

Complying with GP 4 underscores the importance of also encouraging HRDD at both the ECA client or the foreign project. The data emphasises the presence and effectiveness of the distinctive HRDD elements rather than their specific location. Yet the German ECA should ascertain the existence of a human rights policy statement among its clients and ensure both a grievance mechanisms and stakeholder engagement at the project level. Extending the ESHR due diligence to projects beyond the Common Approaches necessitates further exploration, as the current approach of the German ECA does not comply with the UNGPs.

Leveraging on the project level is paramount within the ECA’s HRDD, enabling access to information and fostering improvements in the project’s human rights situation. Yet exactly this leverage is sometimes limited for both the German ECA as a pure cover one, but also for the ECA client, especially the exporter. Ruggie (2010c) has emphasized that ECAs are required to assess the potential human rights impacts of projects independently of their leverage as part of their HRDD, with leverage becoming significant only after appropriate measures have been identified. This conflict highlights the need for further attention to the topic of leverage.

While HRDD is not seen as a management concept in Germany's export promotion scheme, this research has contributed to a common understanding of HRDD and its elements among the ECA stakeholders. In this way, this doctoral thesis has advanced the groundwork for reaching the necessary consensus on the most effective approach to HRDD, providing a solid foundation for future discussions and decision-making in the operationalisation of especially GP 4 in the ECA context.

9.5 Insights for Polycentric Governance

The findings of this research show how human rights responsibilities are shaped within a polycentric governance setting. The German ECA environment reflects many of the features described in Chapter 4, such as a structure involving public authorities, private actors, and civil society organisations; reliance on soft law standards such as the Common Approaches and the UNGPs; and decision making that takes place across several levels and institutions.

The interview data confirms that this distribution of roles can create coordination challenges, especially when actors have different mandates, interests, or levels of knowledge. This supports observations in the literature that dispersed authority can make alignment and accountability more difficult, as discussed in Chapter 4. At the same time, the interview findings show that polycentric arrangements can also offer practical advantages. Although the stakeholders interviewed represent different roles and perspectives, they expressed a shared willingness to address human rights risks in a pragmatic way. This indicates that cooperation and mutual learning are possible when actors recognise their interdependence. The interviews also showed that communication between actors can be an important factor in enabling such cooperation, even though this aspect is not highlighted in the polycentric governance literature.

The interview data also points to several constraints within polycentric governance settings. Interviewees highlighted uneven capacities, limited leverage at the project level, and uncertainty about how HRDD should be understood in the ECA context. The interviews further showed that stakeholders often understand human rights differently, which can make cooperation more difficult in a setting where no single actor has the authority to decide how these issues should be managed.

The findings also demonstrate that the state plays an important, but at times contested, role in shaping HRDD expectations for ECAs and its clients and for how human rights are addressed at the project level, for example through decisions on priorities, coordination, and the overall strategic direction. Several interviewees pointed out that these decisions are often influenced by political and economic considerations, which can create tensions when human rights have to be balanced against other policy goals. This indicates that the role of the state in such

governance arrangements is more complex in practice than theoretical descriptions might suggest.

Overall, the findings illustrate how a polycentric governance setting influences both the possibilities and the challenges of addressing business-related human rights risks in export finance, particularly in relation to HRDD and the role of the state-mandated ECA. They illustrate opportunities for cooperation, while also drawing attention to the practical challenges that arise when responsibilities are distributed and enforcement relies mainly on soft law. The results also show how political priorities and the export promotion mandate of the ECA influence coordination between actors. This practical dimension receives relatively little attention in the wider governance literature but is central in the context of export finance.

Finally, the differing understandings of HRDD identified in this research underline the importance of developing a shared understanding of what HRDD entails in this setting. This thesis therefore contributes an empirically grounded perspective on how polycentric governance operates in the field of export finance. Taken together, the findings also help to show how export promotion mandates, differing understandings of HRDD, and politically shaped decisions influence coordination among the actors involved. These aspects are touched upon only indirectly in the broader governance literature, and the study therefore offers a useful empirical perspective on these issues.

9.6 Original Contribution to Knowledge

Taking the German ECA as the research subject, this doctoral research is the first of its kind that explored how ECAs address business-related human rights impacts in order to comply with the UNGPs, particularly with regard to defining the meaning of and expectations to HRDD. The wider context to which this research belongs is therefore the field of human rights in export finance and, in a broad sense, to BHR. By researching the literature and existing case studies on human rights in state supported export finance as well as by exploratory research via expert interviews, this research project has offered an original contribution to knowledge: As the literature review has demonstrated, there is a paucity of literature dealing with human rights in export finance, but above all there are virtually no academic sources, i.e. peer-reviewed work, in this regard.

Moreover, the literature review has revealed several allegations, including that human rights are insufficiently considered in the ECA context, but only few concrete proposals for how human rights can be better addressed in export support. This study sought to contribute to closing this research gap by examining these issues empirically and by generating insights into how human rights and HRDD are currently understood, the challenges that arise, and the expectations associated with them. By involving all relevant ECA stakeholders, the aim was to

achieve stakeholder consensus when doing so; therefore, a polycentric approach to research was taken based on the new governance theory underlying this doctoral project. Drawing from the different research methods applied, a framework for HRDD has been proposed by the author, which has never existed in this form before and is a significant and much needed contribution to the field.

While the OECD Due Diligence Guidance provides the general six-step due diligence process for responsible business conduct (OECD, 2018, p. 21), the framework proposed in this thesis adapts these steps to the specific context of state-backed export finance. The OECD has acknowledged in its sector-specific guidance that the general due diligence process may require contextualisation for particular sectors, including financial actors (OECD, 2019, pp. 3, 14). The adaptation responds directly to insights from the literature review, case survey and expert interviews, which showed that several elements of HRDD require a different operational focus in the ECA setting.

The adapted framework retains the OECD Due Diligence Guidance steps but specifies how they apply to ECAs. ECAs operate differently from companies because, for example, their assessments are project-based. The adapted framework places the human rights policy statement at the centre of the process, reflecting the need for a clear point of reference for applicants and a consistent interpretation of HRDD. It aligns identification, assessment, mitigation and monitoring with the screening and follow-up procedures used in export credit guarantees, and it incorporates transparency as a distinct element, acknowledging its importance (even though confidentiality constraints exist).

The framework also includes the grievance mechanism as a separate element, consistent with the HRDD understanding of the OECD Due Diligence Guidance and the German NAP, while reflecting the relevance of this topic in the interview findings. Stakeholder engagement is also explicitly highlighted in the proposed framework, reflecting its particular importance in the ECA context and the emphasis placed on it by the interviewees. These refinements do not replace the OECD model but contextualise it for ECAs and make it more applicable to export finance, drawing directly on insights from this doctoral research.

Apart from this topic-related innovation, this research is characterised by its methodological and theoretical originality: Experts, including those who are typically hard to access, were interviewed on matters that are both politically and commercially sensitive. Additionally, previously separate bodies of literature – specifically, human rights and legal literature and business-related export finance literature – were integrated to provide a more comprehensive perspective. Moreover, while this study was geographically focused on Germany, the findings could certainly be applicable to other countries. When considering the transferability of findings to other ECAs though, some adjustments may be necessary, as ECAs differ in structure and

business scope. Nevertheless, the research results are generally not bound to the German context. Therefore, this thesis does not only contribute to filling the aforementioned knowledge gap identified in the literature review, but at the same time represents a new contribution to knowledge. In addition, the findings offer an empirical insight into how coordination between multiple actors shapes the way human rights impacts are addressed and how HRDD is understood and operationalised in the ECA context, complementing the polycentric governance perspective outlined in the theoretical framework of this thesis (Chapter 4).

9.7 Implications for Policy and Practice

The research findings suggest that both human rights in general and HRDD in specific need to be further analysed in the ECA context. As the data illustrates, translating human rights in the ECA context into granular aspects could contribute to a better understanding and goodwill towards human rights, especially on the part of the guarantee applicants. Overall, the interviews showed that clearer guidance on what human rights and HRDD mean in this context would help address existing uncertainties and support a more consistent approach among the different actors involved.

In terms of the ECA HRDD and its practical implementation, four elements require further consideration and clarity. It should be analysed how Transparency and Reporting could be enhanced while rules of confidentiality are complied with. Several interviewees highlighted uncertainties about how human rights risks are assessed, suggesting that greater clarity would be helpful for exporters, financing institutions, and other stakeholders. Exploring how transparency can be improved while respecting confidentiality requirements could help address these uncertainties and support more consistent practice within the export promotion system.

Moreover, the German ECA should develop and implement a Human Rights Policy Statement as an overarching guidance on how human rights are addressed in export promotion. The data showed that the absence of such a policy contributes to differing interpretations of HRDD, making it difficult for applicants to understand what is expected. A clear policy statement would help establish a shared understanding and provide a consistent point of reference.

Other HRDD elements that need additional clarification relate to the implementation of a sufficient ECA-own Grievance Mechanism, as it is evident that the current setup of the German NCP does not meet the requirements of the UNGPs in this regard. One interviewee also noted that the German NCP's mandate is limited to handling complaints against companies and therefore does not extend to concerns relating to the ECA itself. While this aspect was not examined in detail in this research, it points to a possible limitation of the current mechanism. Establishing a dedicated mechanism within the ECA would make it possible to address

concerns more directly to the institution responsible and help improve access to remedy in line with the expectations of the UNGPs.

Finally, it is crucial and highly beneficial for the ECA and its clients to develop a structured framework for assessing the effectiveness of Stakeholder Engagement at the project level. Although all interviewees agreed that stakeholder engagement should form part of HRDD, the findings show that evaluating its effectiveness remains difficult. Developing clearer criteria would support a more consistent approach.

Taken together, these steps could help strengthen the overall approach to human rights in state-backed export finance. The findings indicate that coordinated action by the federal government, the ECA, exporters, financing institutions and civil society will be important. The six-element HRDD framework developed in this thesis offers practical support for guiding this process and provides a basis for clarifying expectations in line with the UNGPs.

9.8 Limitations Encountered

The methodology adopted for this study provided a comprehensive framework for exploring and answering the research question of how business-related human rights impacts are addressed by state ECAs, particularly the German ECA, in order to comply with the UNGPs, especially regarding the specific meaning of and expectations to HRDD. Nevertheless, it is important to observe the limitations of the current doctoral research.

The transferability of findings might be limited both in terms of the case survey and the expert interviews. While the data analysis of the case survey has concluded that no valid and general applicable assumptions can be drawn from the cases due to the limited data available (N=21), the idea of the qualitative interviews was not to generalise from the sample which was less large compared to quantitative studies (N=20). Despite the limited sample size of expert interviews, the access gained provided invaluable insights into how human rights aspects are addressed and what these stakeholders understand by, and expect of, HRDD in the ECA context. Additionally, the associated challenges to addressing human rights in general and implementing HRDD in specific were revealed, offering a significant foundation for not only further research, but also for operationalising the UNGPs in practice, and underscoring the relevance of the findings.

Verification of data generated from the expert interviews in the form of member-checking did not take place, yet other means of enhancing data validation were utilised. Moreover, in order to preserve the experts' anonymity and that of their institution, not many details about them were provided, and some statements were not included in the analysis for the same reason. Due to the mutual trust generated, the researcher was able to gather original contribution to

knowledge, as views of those experts who are typically hard to access, were interviewed on topics that are both politically and commercially sensitive. In addition, quite an amount of time and resources was required for the mixed methods approach of this research undertaking (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p. 14), which contributed to the study's overall duration. However, the potential impacts of the mentioned limitations have been acknowledged and taken into account. As a result, they should therefore be regarded as less significant.

Despite these limitations, the study provides a welcome addition to the literature since it provides a better understanding of the challenges in operationalising GP 4 in the context of state ECAs using the example of Germary.

9.9 Recommendations for Future Research

There are several possibilities for future research, some of which are already apparent from the implications mentioned above. Especially the qualitative part of the research, the expert interviews, have shown that certain topics such as transparency, leverage (in terms of access to information and the ability to influence situations), and understanding and improving social issues at the project level are undeniably important, but extend beyond the scope of this research project. Additionally, the need for human rights guidance, the different abilities between SMEs and large companies to address human rights, and the necessity for discussions among stakeholders regarding the application of the Common Approaches and human rights in general are also significant. However, these issues require a depth of focus that goes beyond what this research project can accommodate.

In addressing the topics just mentioned, which appear particularly relevant with regard to the concrete implementation of HRDD in the ECA context and especially at the ECA level, future research should focus on bringing together the various stakeholder groups. As shown by the interview analysis, the positions between the stakeholder groups interviewed were not always as far apart as the results of the literature research would suggest. Therefore, involving stakeholders e.g. in form of a Focus Group Discussion comprising of representatives of each stakeholder group could enable to discuss and clarify what export promotion stands for and how human rights could be (better) addressed, but also point out what the underlying challenges and limitations are. It could help in understanding and clarifying stakeholders' views, guided by a facilitator to ensure that all relevant topics are covered (Krueger and Casey, 2009, pp. 20–21).

This approach might be a research-led way to reach stakeholder consensus in line with the new governance theory (Ruggie, 2014, p. 10; Wolfsteller and Li, 2022, p. 7) which underlies this research project (see Chapter 4). The participatory research tool was not possible to realise within the framework of this PhD thesis, but there are two reasons why the researcher

believes that it could be a useful approach, as it might reduce the different stakeholder positions and ultimately benefit the realisation of human rights in export promotion. Firstly, the level of knowledge about the German export promotion procedure varies among ECA stakeholders, especially outside of Euler Hermes' employees. This may be related to the lack of transparency about the ECA business that became apparent in the literature review and was repeated in the expert interviews, but its extent surprised the researcher in the course of the interviews.

For example, the content of the UNGPs especially related to export promotion did not seem to be known by all interview experts, but also not, for example, the specifications of pure cover support, what exactly is being supported (namely, the German export vs. the foreign project), or the underlying respective business relationships within the ECA cover. Talking to ECA stakeholders who identified themselves based on e.g. their publications, it was anticipated that there would be a higher degree of alignment in knowledge levels prior to the interviews. However, some factual inaccuracies were already noted during the literature review.

Secondly, it might be possible to increase a mutual understanding when representatives of all stakeholder groups identified for the expert interviews could exchange in order to work together constructively to better embed human rights protection in state export promotion. Official meetings with different ECA stakeholders have been organised especially on human rights issues (e.g. Deutsches Institut für Menschenrechte, 2014; Arbeitsstab Wirtschaft und Menschenrechte im Auswärtigen Amt, 2015), and stakeholder dialogue was initiated for the development of the ECA climate strategy (Euler Hermes Aktiengesellschaft, 2020, 2021, p. 36). A Focus Group Discussion on HRDD could follow on from these events, as the personal notes quoted in Chapter 7 demonstrated that the interviews revealed a greater degree of respect and similar goals within the stakeholder community than might have been initially assumed.

Moreover, further research could address claims identified during the literature research which relate more to the policy level than to the ECAs' actual business. These claims, for examples, address parliamentary scrutiny, assessing possibilities to use withdrawal of trade support more actively, or demanding laws or stronger ECA regulation. These aspects were not considered any further because this would have exceeded this doctoral research undertaking.

9.10 Concluding Statement

This doctoral project has targeted the additional steps States should take “to protect against human rights abuses by business enterprises that are owned or controlled by the State, or that receive substantial support and services from State agencies such as export credit agencies” (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2011, p. 6). At the same time, it has

addressed Ruggie's recommendations to ECAs on respecting human rights, which, as noted previously, he has admitted to "leave important practical questions unanswered" (Ruggie, 2010b, p. 7).

At the outset of this research project, there was no concrete information available on how human rights were addressed in the context of state ECAs in order to comply with the UNGPs, especially with regard to the specific meaning of and expectations for HRDD. This doctoral study has highlighted challenges associated with the operationalisation of GP 4 and has proposed actionable steps and directions for implementing the UNGPs and especially HRDD in the ECA context. Is the potential of state foreign trade promotion being utilised to contribute to compliance with environmental standards and human rights (Haupt, 2024, p. 18)? At the end of this work and based on the research findings, the author compellingly concludes that, with some effort, export finance is able to strengthen project-related human rights.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Overview of the Identification of Sources

Database	Results ENG	relevant for f-t screening ENG	Results GER	relevant for f-t screening GER	relevant for f-t screening in total	after deleting duplicates	duplicates	to be read
Cambridge Core	286	3	0	0	3	no. of duplicates: 54 or 53	0	3
Emerald	50	2	0	0	2		0	2
Ebsco	3	0	0	0	0		0	0
UWS	0	0	0	0	0		0	0
Science Direct	39	10	0	0	10		0	10
Sage	3	0	0	0	0		0	0
Springer Link	144	15	17	3	18		2	16
Web of Science	3	1	0	0	1		1	0
Business Ethics Journal Review	0	0	0	0	0		0	0
The International Journal of Human Rights	8	1	0	0	1		0	1
beluga	1.090	39	12	2	41		6	35
econbiz	21	5	5	3	8		7	1
Business and Human Rights Resource Center	70	19	1	0	19		0	19
Google Scholar	632	28	191	18	46		14	32
Google	297	47	162	15	62		23	39
ESCR-Net	30	4	0	0	4		0	4
World Bank eLibrary	7	7	0	0	7	0	7	
Sum	2.683	181	388	41	222	169	53	169

Appendix B: Ethical Approval

28/02/2022

Dear Johanna Imiela,

Your application 17501: Ethics Application Johanna Imiela, submission reference 14925, has been approved, with conditions, by the Education and Social Sciences SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below:**

Title	Comment
Please explain/justify your intended sample size:	You should advise your supervisor on the actual mechanics of how you will negotiate access and what your plan will be if you can't recruit your original sample.
Please upload a copy of the Questionnaire or Interview Schedule	This is incredibly comprehensive and structured. Take care to ensure that the perspectives you share as part of the interview process are not leading (e.g. do not bias what the participant might respond). Additionally, it is hard to stick to such a tight time frame, so it is important to acknowledge to participants that this interview might take longer than one hour.
Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:	Will you keep a schedule of who you contacted and what the outcome was?
Please upload a copy of your Consent Form(s)	Remove the paragraph about the data controller

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Julie Clark & Dr Lucy Troup
Co-Chairs, ESS Ethics Committee

Appendix C: Interview Questionnaire

Aim, background for and envisaged course of the interview

I am interested in contributing to a definition of **HRDD in the ECA context**, i.e. relating to **project-related human rights risks**. So far, I have done a Literature Review on how human rights are considered in state-promoted export finance, and I have researched several cases on negative human rights impacts at projects related to export credit guarantees. Many allegations came to light THAT human rights are insufficiently considered, but less, however, concrete proposals for HOW human rights can be better addressed. I contacted you as (*XXX job description, stakeholder position*), because your experiences of and ideas for HRDD and the consideration of human rights as such in Germany's export credit guarantee scheme seems to be extremely valuable and necessary. Moreover, I think it is imperative to involve all stakeholders of the German ECA in my research project, as I believe that this is the best way to achieve a common understanding.

In the next hour, I would like to ask you a few questions on human rights and HRDD in order to help develop a common understanding of HRDD among German ECA stakeholders. All data will be anonymised so that any publication resulting from my work will not identify you personally. Do you agree with the recording of the interview?

Participant's introduction

1. What is your relation to EH/the German ECA?
2. Could you please briefly state on your involvement with human rights issues, especially in the ECA context, and what your experience with HRDD is, at the German ECA and in general?
3. What does HRDD mean in (your) cooperation with ECAs?
4. What do you appreciate about the German ECA when it comes to addressing human rights?

Key considerations and interview questions: How could and should HRDD look like in the ECA context?

Proposal for a HRDD framework

From my research, there are several elements and topics that seem to be relevant for HRDD, including supporting measures in the ECA context. Here are my concluding findings for a HRDD framework, which you are kindly requested to complete or comment on afterwards. From my point of view, HRDD in the ECA context should comprise of:

Assessment and appraisal (brainstorming)

5. In your opinion, what is the content behind each of the points?
6. What should be included in HRRD and why, what should be omitted and why?
7. What is most important?
8. Which aspects are still insufficient and need to be looked at more closely?
9. Where might be the greatest difficulties and for whom?
10. Regarding **transparency and communication**, do you think that reporting and transparency should and could be improved according to the *Common Approaches* within the boundaries of commercially sensitive information? ¹⁷ How specifically could transparency be increased?
11. Where should a **grievance mechanism** be located? Is the German NCP sufficient as a grievance mechanism?
12. Should the German ECA be more involved with the topic of **remedy**? Or is it mostly only linked to human rights violations (so there is no need to engage in remedy)?
13. Should there be an **exclusion list** for certain products, countries, etc.?

Scope of ECA HRDD

The UNGPs require HRDD by both the ECA and its clients or projects.

14. To what extent should EH check whether the HRDD elements below exist at client and/or project level?

	Client	Project
Human Rights Policy		
Identification & Assessment		
Cessation, Prevention & Mitigation, Tracking & Monitoring		
Reporting & Transparency		
Grievance Mechanism		
Local Stakeholder Involvement		

¹⁷ This is what Shift has said for Atradius (2017) and suggested more transparency on screening criteria, use of leverage, rejected/withdrawn transactions.

15. Should other aspects be considered when operationalising HRDD? If so, which ones?

Stakeholder engagement/ involvement of local stakeholders

The UNGPs note the importance of engaging (potentially) affected stakeholders in HRDD.

16. Should the current mode of involving local stakeholders be further developed and if so, by whom (ECA or client)?

17. When is it particularly relevant to involve local stakeholders?

Prioritisation

The UNGPs allow for a focus on areas where the risk of adverse human rights impacts is most significant.

18. What are these against the background of EH's product portfolio? What are high risk constellations/ contexts?

19. Should EH prepare a general overview of transactions that will require enhanced HRDD (high risk constellations)?

20. Would it be helpful to name and deal with concrete human rights issues in the context of export credit guarantees, in addition to the international human rights that are sometimes more general and that might cover several human rights topics within?

Conclusion

21. The interview is coming to an end. Is there anything about human rights in export finance we have not talked about and that you consider relevant?

22. What do you see as the biggest challenge and what as the most important thing that still needs to be done in regard to addressing human rights in export finance?

23. Do you have any comments?

24. Who else can you recommend as an interview partner for this research undertaking?

25. May I contact you in case of further questions that might arise during my analysis?

Wrapping up

Thanks so much for your time, I am very grateful for and really appreciate your input!

Appendix D: Mind Map

Appendix E: Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Study Title: Implementing the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights: The Challenge of Operationalising UN Guiding Principle No. 4 in the Context of State Export Credit Agencies

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

This project examines the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs) with regard to export promotion/ export credit guarantee schemes delivered by state Export Credit Agencies (ECAs). Specifically, it is concerned with the operationalisation of Human Rights Due Diligence in that context, which the UNGPs emphasise and identify as important for both ECAs and their clients or projects (Guiding Principle 4). As there is neither a uniform definition of HRDD nor are there clearly defined requirements for HRDD and its elements within the framework of foreign trade promotion, the purpose of my study is to contribute to how ECAs and their clients (exporting companies and financing banks) can fulfil their responsibility to respect human rights pursuant to the UNGPs. Through the explorative approach based on expert interviews (the participants are representatives of the different stakeholder groups of the German ECA) as well as one Focus Group Discussion at a later stage, the difficulties in the implementation of the UNGPs are to be better understood and the necessary HRDD of both an ECA and its clients is to be developed and defined.

Why have I been chosen?

You as XXX at XXX have been chosen to take part in this study because your experiences of and ideas for HRDD and the consideration of human rights as such in Germany's export credit guarantee scheme seems to be extremely valuable and necessary. Moreover, I think it is imperative to involve all stakeholders of the German ECA in my research project, as I believe that this is the best way to achieve a common understanding for how HRDD should and could look like in the ECA context.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason.

What will I do if I take part?

You will attend one interview session which will cover topics including: how HRDD could and should look like in the ECA context, the scope of HRDD, the involvement of stakeholders, and prioritisation.

The interview will take place in your organisational setting or online via Zoom or MS Teams, depending on how it suits you best, between March-July 2023. The interview will last approximately one hour and will be recorded on a Dictaphone. Additionally, handwritten notes will be taken. After the interviews, a short debriefing about the interview is being offered.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

Apart from taking up your valuable time, there are no disadvantages and risks during the research. Your privacy and confidentiality will be protected and all information pertaining to you as an individual and to your institution will be anonymised and kept confidential.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

By taking part in the research, you can contribute to a common understanding of HRDD in the ECA context and identify opportunities, but also challenges and limitations, regarding the implementation of the UNGPs and the consideration of human rights in export finance.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Emma Cuckow and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

All information received will be stored securely in password protected electronic files. All references to individuals and organisations will be anonymised. I am the only one having access to the data collected. It will be stored in my personal HAW Hamburg cloud and therefore will be kept confidential. Nevertheless, I will share some of the findings and transcripts with my supervisors so that they can support me in the analysis. For this, I only use the data transfer from the HAW Hamburg to the UWS or the University of West London. All data will be destroyed on submission and successful completion of my PhD.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

After I have successfully completed my dissertation, I would like to make it available to the public - either in the form of one or more papers or articles, in blogs on sustainability or Business and Human rights in specific, as well as a book or via an online format (open access). I am currently also assuming that I will be able to make the findings of my research known at events in Germany or at the OECD level as well as in lectures (at the HAW Hamburg and through my international network).

Who has reviewed the study?

ESS Ethics Committee

Contact for further information

If you require any further information please contact:

Researcher:

Johanna Imiela

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Research Supervisor:

Colin Clark

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Thank you for considering my invitation to take part in my research!

Information zum Promotionsvorhaben von Johanna Imiela

Ich bin Promotionsstudentin an der University of the West of Scotland (UWS) sowie Wissenschaftliche Mitarbeiterin an der HAW Hamburg. Mein Promotionsprojekt mit dem Titel *„Implementing the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights: The Challenge of Operationalising UN Guiding Principle No. 4 in the Context of State Export Credit Agencies“* untersucht die VN-Leitprinzipien für Wirtschaft und Menschenrechte (UNLP) im Hinblick auf Exportförderung/Exportkreditgarantien, die von staatlichen Exportkreditagenturen (ECAs) bereitgestellt werden. Konkret geht es um die Operationalisierung der menschenrechtlichen Sorgfaltspflicht (Human Rights Due Diligence, HRDD) in diesem Kontext, die in den UNLP sowohl für ECAs als auch für deren Kunden bzw. Projekte als wichtig hervorgehoben und identifiziert wird (Leitprinzip 4).

Die übergeordnete Forschungsfrage ist, wie Menschenrechte im Kontext staatlicher Exportkreditgarantien berücksichtigt werden können und sollten, um die Vorgaben der UNLP zu erfüllen. Da es weder eine einheitliche Definition von HRDD noch klar definierte Anforderungen an HRDD und deren Elemente im Rahmen der Außenwirtschaftsförderung gibt, liegt mein Forschungsschwerpunkt auf der spezifischen Bedeutung von und Erwartungen an HRDD, und zwar bezogen auf projektbezogene Menschenrechtsrisiken. Entsprechend ist mein Ziel, konkrete Vorschläge für die Umsetzung von HRDD im ECA-Kontext zu erarbeiten.

Durch den explorativen Ansatz auf der Basis von Experteninterviews (die Teilnehmenden sind Vertreter der verschiedenen Stakeholdergruppen der deutschen ECA, d. h. Bundesregierung/IMA-Ressorts, Mitarbeitende bei Euler Hermes, Exportunternehmen und Banken, Forschungs- und Wissenschaftsinstitutionen sowie NROs) sowie einer anschließenden Fokusgruppendifkussion sollen die Schwierigkeiten bei der Umsetzung der UNLP besser verstanden und die notwendige HRDD einer ECA bzw. deren Kunden entwickelt und definiert werden. Um ein gemeinsames Verständnis von HRDD zu erreichen, halte ich es für unabdingbar, alle Stakeholder der deutschen ECA in mein Forschungsprojekt einzubeziehen.

Bisher habe ich eine Literaturrecherche zur Berücksichtigung von Menschenrechten bei staatlich geförderter Exportfinanzierung durchgeführt und Berichte über negative Auswirkungen auf Menschenrechte bei Projekten, die im Zusammenhang mit Exportkreditgarantien stehen, recherchiert. Dabei kamen viele Vorwürfe zum Vorschein, DASS Menschenrechte unzureichend berücksichtigt werden, weniger jedoch konkrete Vorschläge, WIE dies geschehen kann. Genau hier soll meine weitere Forschung ansetzen. Die anstehenden Interviews werden sich mit der konkreten Bedeutung und dem Umfang von HRDD im ECA-Kontext befassen, mit der Einbeziehung von Interessengruppen sowie der aus den UNLP stammenden Priorisierung von Maßnahmen.

Die Privatsphäre und Vertraulichkeit aller zu interviewenden Expert:innen werden geschützt und alle Informationen, die eine Person sowie deren Institution/Einrichtung betreffen, anonymisiert und vertraulich behandelt. Bei einer etwaigen Veröffentlichung meiner Arbeit werden weder die Expert:innen noch Institutionen persönlich identifiziert.

Durch die Teilnahme an meiner Studie können die Expert:innen zu einem gemeinsamen Verständnis von Menschenrechten im ECA-Kontext beitragen und Chancen, aber auch Herausforderungen und Grenzen, bei der Umsetzung der UNLP und der Berücksichtigung von Menschenrechten in der Exportfinanzierung aufzeigen.

Appendix G: Consent Form

School of Education and Social Science

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: *Implementing the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights: The Challenge of Operationalizing UN Guiding Principle No. 4 in the Context of State Export Credit Agencies*

Ethics Application Number 17501, Submission Reference 14925 (approved 28/02/2022)

Investigators names: Johanna Imiela

Researcher [REDACTED]

You have been invited to take part in a study on how Human Rights Due Diligence (HRDD), one of the key concepts of the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Right (UNGPs), could and should look like in the ECA context. By completing this form and agreeing to give your full consent, you agree that you have read and understood the participant information sheet and understand what is being asked of you in this study.

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm your agreement:

	Initial below:
I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet and instruction sheet for the study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and I need not answer any questions, and that I am free to withdraw at any time up to one month after taking part without giving any reason.	
I understand that the information I give is confidential and any publication resulting from this work will not identify me personally.	
I agree to have my voice/likeness digitally recorded.	
I freely agree to participate in this study.	

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals):

Name of researcher (block capitals):

Date:

Date:

Signature:

Signature:

If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the ESS Ethics Committee by email at: ess.ethics@uws.ac.uk. Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Education and Social Science, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

Appendix H: Categories for Analysis of Cases

Project Name	Country	Exporter with ECA support	Bank with ECA support	Sector/Indus	Export/Guarant/Insurinq Value	Project Value	HR Allegedly Violated	Affects Person	Severity Impa	ECA involvem	Form of ECA Co	Client involvem	Author Caze	Literat/ Sourc	Year	Ta	If not	ECA involved/Expor Country	Criticis/ Lackinq	Comments	
Hydropower plant Hidroegomoso	COL	Andritz Hydro	Banco Santander	Energy (Water)	US\$ 13 mm	?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Right to adequate standard of living - Right to effective remedies (some of the replacement land much smaller than promised, now worsened conditions of life -> insufficient or no compensation, fish stocks diminished) - Right to health (environmental impacts) - Right to adequate standard of living, Right to effective remedies (r) - Recognition of (indirectly) affected people - Right to participate in public life (information, consultation) - Right to freedom of opinion and speech, Right to life (protestors threatened or killed) 	Community	30,000 people affected community, 180 families resettled	linked to (indirect)	para cover		Pezava	grey/NGO	2016	y		ENHGER	project does not comply w/ Intl. Standards	nothing new though	
		Andritz	Santander				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Right to participate in public life (information, consultation) - Right to adequate standard of living (environmental impacts preventing income generation/fishing) - Right to effective remedies (Compensation) - Right to freedom of opinion and speech, Right to life (protestors killed) 		30,000 people	linked to (indirect)	para cover	linked to (indirect)	Keenan, Hamilton (eds.)	grey/NGO	2015	y		ENHGER	Failure to recognize real threats to the affected population's human rights and to establish effective measures to safeguard against human rights violations		
		Andritz					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Right to adequate standard of living, Right to effective remedies (resettlement: now worsened conditions of life -> insufficient or no compensation, fish stocks diminished) - Recognition of (indirectly) affected people - Right to participate in public life (information, consultation) - Right to health (environmental impacts) - Right to freedom of opinion and speech, Right to life (protestors threatened or killed) 		30,000 people affected community, 180 families resettled	linked to (indirect)	para cover		Kim et al.	grey/NGO	2015	y		ENHGER	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Should - HRRIA undertaken by DN and ECA before (i) signing the contract - verification of the adequacy and completeness of the consultations and reqs requirements - verification of human rights-based project assessment in case undertaken by third party - directives only made and enforcement cover only applies if conditions are fully met and a complaints mechanism is demonstrably functioning - verification of implementation of provision incl. involvement of the affected population by ECA and other financiers - companies have to have a human rights policy which covers its issues in hydropower plant projects and compliance with UNGPs and VCD recommendations - sector initiatives by ECAs etc: hr expectations, jointly press for solutions - Commissioning of independent human rights experts 		
Power station Medupi	ZAF	Mitsubishi Hitachi Power Systems Europe (former Hitachi Power Europe)		Energy (Coal)		?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk to Right to water (groundwater and river water contamination) - Risk to Right to health (environmental impacts: groundwater and river water contamination, emissions (soot/dioxin)) - Right to food - Right to participate in public life (information, consultation, incl. recognition of affected people) - Right to culture (groveyards destroyed) 	community	?	linked to (indirect)	para cover	contribute/linked to (indirect)	Germanswath, Misseron	grey/NGO	2017	y		ENHGER	associated facilities inadequately taken into account; HRRIA	possible, in absence (article) not take into account; not fully completed by	
		?					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Right to an adequate standard of living (resettlement) 	community	> 1mm people	linked to (indirect)	para cover		Germanswath, Misseron	grey/NGO	2017	y		ENHGER		only shortly mentioned	
							<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Right to adequate standard of living (resettlement; improper compensation, local food 														

Appendix I: ECAs Referenced in Cases

Appendix J: Themes from Expert Interviews

- Benchmark Standards
 - Support hr compliance, the IFC Performance Standards which will (finally!) become the prime benchmark standard in GER
- Biggest Challenge
 - HRDD elements
 - Knowing and improving hr at project level
- Closer look necessary
 - Explaining hr in the ECA context
 - Generating Transparency
 - Especially beyond CA
- ECA business_techniques
 - Complex BHR setting
 - Incl. wholistic approach vs. transactions
 - Economic interests meet human rights
 - Hr risks are inherent in ECA system
 - Politically desirable but dubious
 - Tied hands – the L-word
- Exclusion list
 - Alternative view: tackle the disadvantages
- Granular hr aspects
 - Avoiding tick box exercise
 - Definition of focus are helpful internally and externally
 - Not needed
 - OECD embedding
- Interaction of evolving HRDD legislation in the ECA context
 - GER LkSG helps for addressing hr also in the ECA context
 - Pragmatic link of ECA and LkSG
 - Risk of bureaucratic burden
- Leverage
 - Disagreeing with Ruggie
 - Influenced by various factors
 - Not to be used as an excuse
 - Prio risks
- Meaning of HRDD
 - Addressing hr in ECA context
 - Important in ECA finance
 - Something for companies only
 - Something seen too incomplete
 - Something vague
 - Something with hr
 - Something with leverage
- Mixed
 - Environmental and hr aspects are not sufficiently considered together
 - Hr guidance is lacking at all levels
 - Hr in export finance need to be addressed in a joint approach
 - Risk-based approach needed
 - SMEs vs. TNCs
- Overview for enhanced HRDD
 - No need

- Would be helpful for external stakeholders
- To publish or not to publish
- Prioritisation
 - According to predefined and verifiable criteria
 - Depending on certain hr risks
 - Lack of leverage can pose a risk
 - Risks will always exist
- HRDD framework
 - All interviewees (but one) agree to my suggestion
 - HRDD already takes place, esp. Risk I&A, but not sufficiently and despite a lacking common understanding of HRDD
 - Big topics:
 - Stakeholder engagement
 - Transparency and Reporting
 - HR Policy
 - German NCP as grievance mechanism for export credit context
- Scope of ECA HRDD
 - AND is the only possibility
 - DN should have hr policy to be eligible for ECG
 - If an OR is sufficient cannot be said in general
 - Sometimes, it could be the DN's HRDD only
 - The ECA's HRDD should focus on the project only

Appendix K: Headings and Themes from Interviews

Human Rights in the ECA context

- Hr are already addressed
 - Standards
 - IFC Performance Standards to become main reference standard in GER → deficiencies though (see Lit.Review-chapter), but good start (ibid.)?
 - Exclusion lists
- Meaning of hr
 - Diverse and lacking knowledge of all players involved (incl. SMEs)
 - mainstreaming and promotion needed
 - granular hr aspects could help mainstreaming and reduce resistance
- Complex BHR setting
 - Many players involved incl. role of politics
 - Streamlining processes asked for by all
 - Scale and scope of hr risks as a trade intermediary vs. company-own supply chain (incl. transaction approach vs. general one)
 - Economic interests meet hr
 - Original aim
 - Role of \$
 - Hr risks are inherent in state export finance

HRDD in the ECA context

- Diverse understanding of HRDD
- Important elements of HRDD in the ECA context
 - Some elements are already existing – HRDD is not new!
 - What is most important? (s. xls)
 - Some elements need to be further looked at
 - Stakeholder Engagement
 - Transparency and Reporting
 - HR Policy
 - German NCP as grievance mechanism for export credit context
 - Agreement to my proposal (pictorial presentation)
- What about...
 - Beyond CA
 - enhanced HRDD
 - Prioritisation
- Operationalising GP 4: Scope of ECA HRDD

What remains to be discussed

- Transparency
- The L-word (leverage)
 - Access to information
 - Ability to change
 - ➔ Knowing and improving hr at project level
- Hr guidance needed
- SMEs vs. large TNCs
- Practitioners' discussions and CA application re; human rights needed
 - No German solo run
 - Risk-based approach called for
 - Peer learning and exchange with all stakeholder groups
- Can pragmatism and a risk-based approach serve a common understanding?